

Safety Interactions of NPP & H2 cogeneration

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
DiD	Defence in Depth
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
HTSE	High Temperature Steam Electrolysis
HV	High Voltage
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
LTE	Low Temperature Electrolysis
LV	Low Voltage
MAPP	Major Accident Prevention Plan
MSR	Moisture Steam Reheater
MV	Medium Voltage
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
SAR	Safety Assessment Report
SR	Safety Report
SI	Safety Injection
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis
PIE	Postulated Initiating Event

Preface

This work was produced in a combined effort by various partners, each being responsible for the veracity and quality of their work. The distribution of work was the following:

- Ansaldo: Subtask 5
- ES Group: Subtask 2
- GRS: Subtask 5, Summary, Review tasks.
- NRG: Subtask 3, Review tasks.
- Tecnatom: Subtask 1
- TU Dresden: Subtask 4

Summary

This document is focused on determining the issues that may arise from applying the different regulatory frameworks to an integrated NPP-HPP facility. Based on the outcome of task 4.1, the impact of the different levels of integration on the license, licensing process and license documentation for both facilities is determined. For this purpose, 5 subtasks were carried out:

Subtask 1 (performed by Tecnatom) identifies and describes the available technologies to produce hydrogen using heat and electricity from an NPP. Their main characteristics are compared, and context information required for the licensing analysis is provided. The different interfaces between the NPP and the HPP are described for the different levels of integration.

Subtask 2 (performed by ES Group) focuses on the description of necessary technical modifications of NPP systems for the integration of an HPP, depending on the integration scenarios. This is illustrated using the example of the NPP Rivne in Ukraine.

Subtask 3 (performed by NRG) concerns a generic Safety Case Approach for the various integration scenarios, evaluating the safety impact of modifications to a nuclear installation or activity, followed by a specific safety case addressing the possible Rivne NPP-HPP integration scenarios.

Subtask 4 (performed by TU Dresden) presents the main outcomes from the impact assessment applied to the integration of a 40 MW hydrogen facility into the Rivne power station in Ukraine. This includes a definition of the worst case scenarios, a frequency assessment for these scenarios and a consequence estimation for the identified scenarios. The consequence estimations are based on deterministic safety calculations by means of selected semi-empirical methods from the process safety.

Subtask 5 (performed by GRS and Ansaldo) consists of the analysis of the impact of the NPP-HPP integration scenarios on the licensing process. Based on the outcomes of task 4.1, the requirements of the regulations applicable to the HPP and the NPP were considered and the approval procedures and safety analyses required for successful integration were assessed on a qualitative level. The impact of individual key aspects was evaluated and scored (high, medium, low) depending on the integration scenario, and the results were presented in tabular form.

1 Introduction

In addition to technical and economic issues, which are discussed in Work Packages 2 and 3 of the NPHyCo project, licensing aspects are of great importance when integrating an HPP into an existing NPP. It must be clarified which approval procedures are required to enable such integration in accordance with the regulations, and what effort is required for this.

Depending on the integration scenario chosen, the HPP can be regarded as a conventional industrial plant to be built largely independently of the NPP or as a modification of the NPP itself. Relevant topics to be considered include conventional plant safety, nuclear safety, environmental protection, building law, and land use law.

In order to discuss the advantages and disadvantages from a licensing perspective of the individual integration scenarios defined in D1.2, this document first identifies the potential interfaces between HPP and NPP and the system modifications required for the integration scenarios. These modifications are then evaluated in terms of safety. Risks that can arise are fires, explosions and projectiles damaging the adjacent facilities. Finally, a qualitative evaluation is carried out and overview tables are used to show the estimated impact for each sub-aspect of licensing law as a result of the integration scenario. This is done using a scoring system with three levels (high, medium, low)

2 Subtask 1: Identification and Description of Facility Types (NPP/HPP) and Operating Conditions

2.1 Integration Scenarios

Firstly, the available technologies to produce hydrogen using heat and electricity from an NPP are identified and described. Their main characteristics are compared, and context information required for the licensing analysis is provided. The different interfaces between the NPP and the HPP are described for different levels of integration.

In the full integration level, the HPP is on-site the NPP and all supply needs of the HPP are served from the NPP infrastructure (electricity, steam, water, nitrogen, wastewater treatment, etc). In the partial integration level, only some supply needs of the HPP are served from NPP infrastructure and the HPP can be located on-site or off-site the NPP. When no needs of the HPP are served from the NPP it is called zero integration level. For the licensing analysis eight scenarios with different levels of integration are considered:

Onsite Solutions

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
8. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)

2.2 Modes of Operation

Apart from the technical level of integration, there are as well different modes of operation possible that have impact on design and licensing of the NPP.

Continuous production strategy is the case in which the HPP is producing hydrogen at the designed capacity in a continuous way, and it is a constant additional consumer of the NPP. In this case, the HPP starts and stops with the NPP, or it requires external sources of supply when the NPP produces less electricity than the amount required by the HPP.

Production based on opportunity prices strategy, the production of hydrogen varies between no production and full capacity. This mode of operation involves frequent starts and stops of the HPP that may have an impact on the NPP, depending on the level of integration.

Production based on grid balancing services strategy, the operator provides balancing services to the grid. In this case the electricity supplied to the grid should change with a required ramp to follow the demand curve. For this reason, the HPP as a load of the NPP should be working at around 50% of its capacity to be able to increase or decrease its electricity consumption when required by the electricity market.

The different operating conditions cases considering the level of integration, the hydrogen production strategy and the HPP technology are summarized in tables in the document.

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Figure 1: HPP Process Flow Diagram based on the AEL technology.

Figure 2: HPP Process Flow Diagram based on the PEM technology.

Figure 3: HPP Process Flow Diagram based on the HTSE/SOEC technology.

3 Subtask 2: Identification and Description of Interaction Areas between NPP and HPP and necessary System Modifications and their Effects on the Safety of the NPP

3.1 Basic Characteristics of Rivne NPP

For the purpose of the deliverable 4.2 and the possibilities for sharing, first the basic characteristics of Rivne NPP are described.

The Rivne NPP consists of 2 VVER-440 units , commissioned in 1980-1981 and 2 VVER-1000 units – commissioned in in 1986 and 2004.. In 2010, the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate decided to extend the service life of Units 1 and 2 for twenty years.

VVER-440 is a 440 MW pressurized water reactor designed in the Soviet Union (2 K-220-44 KhtGZ turbines of 220 MW each).

- | | |
|-------------------------|--|
| 1.Confinement; | 9. Generator; |
| 2.Control Rods motor; | 10.Transformer; |
| 3.Fuel; | 11.Grid; |
| 4.Reactor Vessel; | 12.Feedwater Pump; |
| 5.Reactor Coolant Pump; | 13.Condenser; |
| 6.Steam Generator; | 14.Condenser Cooling (Circulation) Water Pump; |
| 7.Steam; | 15.Cooling Pond. |
| 8.Turbine; | |

Pressurized Water Reactor (VVER-1000) is a nuclear reactor of the VVER reactor series with nominal electric power of 1000 MW and thermal power of 3000 MW. This type of reactor is the most widespread in its series and accounts for 7.5% of the total number of power reactors of all types operating in the world. The most common modification is the serial reactor unit B-320.

Figure 4: Conceptual scheme of a power unit with a water-water reactor.

- | | |
|-------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1.Reactor Vessel, | 11.Generator exciter, |
| 2.Fuel, | 12.Condenser, |
| 3.Control Rods, | 13.Condenser cooling system, |
| 4.Control Rods motor, | 14.Feedwater heater, |
| 5.Pressurizer, | 15.Turbine-driven feedwater Pump, |
| 6.Steam Generator tubes, | 16.Cooling water circulation Pump, |
| 7.Feedwater to SG, | 17.Reactor Coolant Pump, |
| 8.Turbine-High Pressure part, | 18.Alternator-Grid lines, |
| 9.Turbine-Low Pressure part, | 19.Steam pipe to Turbine, |
| 10.Generator, | 20.Containment |

Characteristics of VVERs

Parameters	VVER-440	VVER-1000
Reactor thermal power, MW	1375	3000
Efficiency, (net)	29,7	31,7
Pressure, kgf/cm ²		
before Turbine	44,0	60,0
in Primary side	125	160,0
Water Temperature, °C:		
Reactor inlet	269	289
Reactor outlet	300	319
Core Diameter, m	2,88	3,12

Core Height, m	2,50	3,50
Fuel element diameter, mm	9,1	9,1
Number of Fuel rods in Assembly	126	312
Number of Assembly	(312+ARC 37)	163
Uranium mass, t	42	66
Average uranium enrichment, %	3,5	4,26
Average fuel burn-up, MW-day/kg	28,6	48,4

3.2 Selection of possible HPP Locations at the Rivne NPP

Since placing an HPP near power units, hydraulic structures and other important objects entails risks, it was decided to consider two locations:

1. on the territory of the NPP site,
2. outside the territory of the NPP in the sanitary protection zone, but with the possibility of using the necessary resources (electricity, water, staff, etc.).

Near all locations there are highways and access railway tracks. See the images below (Figure 5), based on free, unbanned Google Maps.

Figure 5: Locations of HPP scenarios onsite the Rivne NPP (site #1) and in the sanitary protection zone (site #2).

The buildings and structures of the units 1 & 2 (VVER-400) are designed for the impact of an air shock wave with a compression pressure along the front of 10 kPa. The units 3 & 4 (VVER-1000) are designed to withstand a shock wave pressure of 30 kPa. According to national and international regulations there were no requirements for anti-missile construction at the time of construction and therefore, calculations of this coefficient were not carried out for the Rivne units.

Table 1 gives a more detailed description of the two possible sites.

Table 1: Requirements and Solutions for locations

Requirements	Onsite location place	Offsite location place (the site is in the sanitary protection zone)
<p>Above ground performance.</p> <p>The size of the plot: 30*40 m</p>	<p>The site is located in the area of cooling towers No. 3, 4, 5 (diagonally between cooling tower No. 3 and No. 5). The maximum dimensions of the site are approximately 110*92 m, for development approximately 86*80 m. Nearby there is a 45 m common-units Diesel-generator station. The approximate minimum distance to the cooling towers is: to the cooling tower No. 3 – 138 m, to the cooling tower No. 4 – 159 m, to the cooling tower No. 5 – 177 m. Near the site there is an overpass, highways and approach railway tracks.</p> <p>This option is located closer to water supply network, a substantial justification of safety and location is required.</p>	<p>The site is located at a distance of 2900 m (open switchgear-330 kV) and 2750 m from the town's industrial structures. The dimensions of the site are 182.1*151.4 m. Distance 10-15 m to the mains water supply network. There are highways and access railway tracks near the site.</p> <p>This option has such a disadvantage as the laying of communications, but the site is located in a potentially safer place for the NPP.</p>

The report of subtask 2 (annex 2) describes in detail the current situation of the following Rivne systems:

- Electric system
- System of preparation of demineralized water
- System of domestic water supply of the NPP
- System of Turbine Hall service water
- Chilled Water
- The NPP household sewage system
- NPP Site's compressed (repair) air system
- Nitrogen-oxygen station in the nitrogen section

For these systems, the functionality during operation has also been described as well as the impact on operation.

Finally the subtask 2 report describes proposals for technical solutions how coupling of the NPP systems with the HPP can be realized, including a judgement of the regulatory feasibility.

From this initial analysis it appears that only coupling of the electric power supplysystem, the demineralized water system and/or the cooling water system are seen as feasible options.

3.3 Required Modifications of the Systems for Coupling

For the electric power supply system, demineralized water system and cooling water system the basic schemes and basic designs of the modifications were prepared and shown below

3.3.1 Electric Power Supply System

The organization of the HPP's electric power supply system will be organized from the existing open switchgear 110 kV (cubicle 8, which was in reserve according to the original design).

Approximate placement and length of the 110kV overhead line from cubicle №8 to the site of HPP substation:

- for the option of accommodation on the site - 2800 m;
- for the accommodation option in sanitary protection zone - 2000 m.

Figure 6: Schematic diagram of the HPP's electric power supply substation.

3.3.2 Demineralized Water System

As usual the NPPs produce demineralized water with sufficient capacity. However, the water parameters do not correspond to the quality required for the HPP.

System modification is required - additional-treatment water system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for additional-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h - (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). It is preferable to place such an installation near the NPP's system to produce DW.

Figure 7: Schematic diagram of the options for modification of the Demineralized Water System.

3.3.3 Cooling Water System

It is possible to use the service water of Turbine Dept. unit #3 and #4 RNPP for onsite HPP scenarios. But intervention in the heat balance of the cooling water of the nuclear power plant will lead to changes, so significant justifications are required. For offsite scenarios, service water supply is complicated by the need to long communications, so additional research is needed.

In addition, the issue of the possibility of selecting "raw" water from the RNPP service feed water pipeline (from the river to before entering the additional water purification system) was discussed. But then there is a problem with the return of heated water, due to the high temperature (up to 60°C), so there is a need for cooling before discharging.

Based on the above, two cooling options are currently being considered:

1. From the Turbine service water system.
2. Autonomous closed cooling system of the HPP

Figure 8: Schematic diagram of the modifications to the cooling water system (new pipes and equipment are shown in red).

3.4 Conclusions

Conclusion 1: Under the terms of NPP systems modification, there are no significant problems for the use of resources for an HPP. Licensing conditions allow to make the necessary changes to the NPP design.

Conclusion 2: To select the optimal deployment scenario, it should be considered that it is advisable to use only some of the resources for the needs of the HPP. These resources are Electricity, Cooling

Water and Demineralized Water. It is advisable to provide the other part of the resources as autonomous for the HPP project - Nitrogen, Compressed Air, Chilled Water. The use of the third group of resources is very dependent on the placement conditions. This group can be used both from NPPs and autonomously – Tap Water and Wastewater.

Conclusion 3: When choosing an NPP as a supplier of resources for an HPP, an important factor is the multi-unit of NPPs. Multi-unit NPPs are the first priority choice due to the reliability of the uninterrupted supply of resources for an HPP. The more NPP resources are used for an HPP, the more impact the reliability of the resources has. Multi-unit NPPs have a greater possibility of reserving resources.

4 Subtask 3: Development and detailed description of incident/accident scenarios at the HPP and their impact on the safety of the NPP

This part of Task 4.2 concerns the generic modification processes for NPPs and a generic Safety Case Approach for the various integration scenarios, followed by a specific example of a Rivne NPP-HPP integration scenario.

4.1 Modification processes for NPPs

Each NPP is obliged to have a program to manage modifications. Such a modification program, often referred to as Management of Change (MoC) program, should ensure a proper design, safety assessment, review, implementation and testing of each modification. Depending on their safety significance, modifications shall be subject to approval by the regulator. Also, the consequences of the modifications for procedures, human tasks and performance needs to be analyzed.

Modifications need to be categorized based on their safety significance, according to IAEA SSG-71:

- Category 1: Modifications with significant impact on safety
- Category 2: Modifications with impact on safety
- Category 3: Modifications with no impact on safety

According to IAEA SSG-71 (referring to GSR Part 4 (Rev. 1)) the safety assessment of a nuclear power plant is required to be updated as necessary so as to take into account modifications to the design or operation of the plant. An initial safety assessment should be carried out before starting a modification. Depending on the results of the initial safety assessment, a more detailed and comprehensive safety assessment might be needed. A comprehensive safety assessment should include an evaluation of the effect of the modification on radiological hazards during its implementation and during subsequent commissioning, testing, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the modified plant. This evaluation should include the effect of the modified plant item and its associated system on physically adjacent systems and plant items, and on interconnected systems or support systems such as electrical power supplies.

Proposals for modifications submitted for independent review should be in accordance with the management system of the operating organization.

4.2 Generic Safety Case Approach

The fundamental part of the comprehensive Safety Assessment will be the Safety Case Report. This report for the safety demonstration does not stick to a strict format or lay-out as long as the relevant and required safety topics are addressed.

An example of a format of a Safety Case for the NPP-HPP sharing is given:

1. Introduction.
 - a. General description and presentation of characteristics and relevant (safety related) topics.
2. Current situation
 - a. Extensive descriptions of the systems to be modified addressing the several functions, properties, conditions, qualifications etc.
3. Shared situation
 - a. Modified system description: addressing realization aspects, choices, design, quality, impact to other systems etc.
4. Impact on operation and plant conditions
 - a. Current situation. What (operational) functions are attributed to the current system in the various situations: normal operation, accident conditions, emergencies, training, maintenance, etc.?
 - b. Modified (shared) situation. What is the impact of the modifications to the subjects mentioned above? What procedures, maintenance protocols, check-out procedures, training and work instructions, etc. need to be changed?
5. Impact on Safety
 - a. Impact on Safety Functions. Evaluation of the fundamental safety functions in the original and in the modified situation should be performed. SSCs performing specific safety functions are to be determined for impact analyses on the fundamental safety functions as a result of modification(s).
 - b. Impact on Defence in Depth. In the nuclear industry the Defence in Depth (DiD) approach is applied. DiD means that multiple safety measures are in place in layers to guarantee safety. If the first level is compromised, additional layers exist to prevent incidents from developing into (severe) accidents.
 - c. Impact on Risks. By changing SSCs new risks can be introduced or also reduced. Evaluation of risk aspects concerns for example radiation for workers, conventional risks, SSCs linked to or responsible for nuclear safety.
 - d. Impact on Safety Analyses and Safety (Analysis) Report. Impact-evaluation of existing deterministic and probabilistic safety analyses. E.g. evaluation of the list of Postulated Initiating Events (PIEs) for which thermo-hydraulic (transients) and radiological calculations (dose consequences) are performed, which are applicable on the modified systems. It also needs to be checked what sections of the existing Safety Assessment Report (SAR) are impacted by the modification and what the implications are for that.
6. Safety Case conclusion.
 - a. Summarizing the different safety aspects and qualifying the safety impact of the modification.

A Safety Case evaluates the safety impact of modifications to a nuclear installation or activity. When an HPP is (partly) integrated with an NPP, the impact on safety of the NPP needs to be investigated and shown (in a Safety Case) that it still complies with existing regulations. The Management of Change procedure provides guidance on the level of detail of the required safety evaluation, depending on the safety category of the systems to be modified. The Safety Case Report is one of the necessary documents to be submitted for a license update/renewal.

Chapter 2 of the report describes the generic Management of Change (MoC) procedure, the safety classification of systems and the requirements for a safety case.

Chapter 3 is a generic safety case describing the various integration scenarios. This generic safety case describes all aspects that need to be addressed in the safety case and the documentation that need to be modified due to the integration. This is still in general terms since a specific safety case can only be based on detailed design and technical information from the installations involved. This is not available for theoretical integration scenarios.

Chapter 4 describes the specific safety case for an integration scenario for an HPP at Rivne NPP site (Ukraine) after evaluating several NPP systems having the possibility to be shared. The scenario taken into account is possible and realistic for the pilot hydrogen production plant at or near Rivne NPP. The safety impact of the integration scenario is evaluated and the impact on safety documentation is identified.

Another subtask, WP4.2 subtask 4 'Detailed assessment of the incident/accident scenarios' (by TU Dresden) will deal with the modelling of the physical impact of the HPP on the NPP and the calculation of the safety distances.

4.3 General conclusions for coupling a HPP to a NPP

4.3.1 Safety related systems

For modifications on safety related SSCs the impact can be (very) large, depending on the type of involved safety functions. The large amount of work and additional costs is caused by:

- The modifications and their (possible) impact on safety need to be justified by an extensive safety case and -analysis. Additional measures have to be taken to prevent any significant impact on safety.
- The modified systems have to fulfil strict requirements and nuclear qualifications, leading to high cost.
- Modifications to safety related systems have impact on operating-, abnormal-, accident-, emergency-, maintenance-, inspection- and test procedures. They all need to be adapted to the modified situation, for all plant states (start-up, operation, hot-shutdown, cold-shutdown etc.).
- The above-mentioned change in procedures requires training of personnel to assure that the new procedures will be followed correctly in all situations and for all plant states.
- Besides the mentioned changes/additions, also related documentation (like specifications, services contracts, management system) might need to be updated.

- Additionally, the HPP-part of the shared system will have to follow a stricter (nuclear) regime with respect to modifications, maintenance, accident procedures etc. which might also increase the operating costs of these systems.

This means that sharing safety related systems of the NPP with the HPP is unlikely unless the benefits of sharing are very high. Referring to WP 3 “Economical aspects of coupling” this might be relevant for sharing high temperature steam.

4.3.2 Non-safety related systems

Modifications on non-safety related SSCs will have no/limited safety impact and will require no or limited additional work to justify and implement the modification due to safety and license restrictions. The following topics still have to be addressed:

- Modifications will have (in principle) no impact on the described safety aspects. Nevertheless, an initial safety check has to be performed in which the mentioned safety aspects (DiD, Risks, FSF etc.) are addressed to show they are not impacted. No further activities have to be carried out with respect to safety analyses and the SAR.
- Modifications will probably have some impact on operation. This impact is mainly related to adapting/extending maintenance and operating procedures, possibly combined with some training for staff to operate and maintain the modified systems. Non-safety related systems have no function in abnormal situations and accident conditions, so in general no impact on arrangements to manage these abnormal and accident conditions will occur.

For a modification of a non-safety related system, the additional costs from a safety / regulations point of view are limited. This means that sharing of non-safety related systems is mainly a financial trade-off between the investment costs of separate systems compared to the investment costs of shared (non-safety) systems.

4.3.3 General findings

- Sharing of systems will not improve safety so there should be other drivers for sharing of systems between a NPP and a HPP like: operations, costs, strategy
- Safety related shared systems will have to comply with the nuclear requirements, the nuclear license and the related administrative and inspection regime by the nuclear regulator. Therefore only significant benefits due to sharing will outweigh the additional effort to be made for sharing nuclear safety related systems.
- In practice, sharing of systems will be focused on sharing of non-safety systems to minimize the additional effort of the modifications.
- For high temperature electrolysis, sharing safety related systems like high-temperature steam might be beneficial. In such cases the modifications to the NPP system should be designed in such a way that safe NPP operation is minimally compromised in all plant situations (normal operation, accident conditions, emergency response) and in all plant states (start-up, cold shut-down, hot shut-down,).

5 Subtask 4: Detailed Assessment of the Incident/Accident Scenarios

This section of the deliverable report presents the main outcomes from the impact assessment applied to the integration of a 40 MW hydrogen facility into the Rivne power station in Ukraine. Rivne nuclear power plant (NPP) comprises four VVER units with an overall electrical power output of 2880 MW. The reference hydrogen production plant (HPP) is based on a container solution, which hosts the electrolyser stacks and balance of plant. Gaseous hydrogen is generated at 3.5 MPa via low-temperature electrolysis through proton exchange membrane (PEM) technology. PEM has been selected in the study over alkaline electrolysis (AEL) due to its higher compactness and lower stack footprint. However, both technologies are analogous with few differences in balance of stack, and therefore the methodology and outcomes from this study can be likewise applied to AEL.

The HPP comprises two separated areas: the electrolyser facility meant for the production of hydrogen, which in this study is assumed integrated onsite of the NPP protected area, and the high-pressure storage area with a capacity of 5 tonnes, which is located outside of the NPP perimeter due to the large amount of hydrogen. The latter can be placed flexibly at a safe distance according to the stored hydrogen mass. The operation regime of the compressor in the high-pressure storage is decoupled from the electrolyser facility via a 30 kg storage (buffer) tank.

The worst-case accident scenario is identified through HAZID (HAZard IDentification) technique applied to the electrolyser system and assisted by system reliability analysis through the evaluation of component failure rates and implementation of event tree analysis (ETA). For this purpose, the impact assessment uses generic component reliability data available in several sources from the literature. Hazardous points for unintended hydrogen releases, with subsequent escalation into fires and chemical explosions after ignition of the hydrogen-air mixture, are identified at various locations within the electrolyser system. In addition, a physical explosion in the hydrogen buffer tank with subsequent fragment generation is addressed in the impact assessment. Based on the guidelines provided in selected IAEA official reports, those external events applied to NPP impact assessment comprise:

- (a) external release of hazardous material,
- (b) external fire,
- (c) external explosion, and
- (d) generation of projectiles.

The schematic representation of the adopted methodology is displayed in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Applied methodology in the sub-task report.

The impact assessment addresses loading characterization against structural criteria for three different scenarios: (1) hydrogen VCE, (2) pressure vessel burst (PVB), and (3) projectile impact.

A hydrogen explosion is deemed as the worst-case scenario due to the destructive potential over long-range distances by the shock wave propagation. Contrarily, the main impact load of a fire is the thermal radiation at short-range distances, namely over HPP structures and plant personnel. The source term, thermal loading, blast loading, and mechanical impact by projectiles strongly depend on the HPP features, namely hydrogen inventory and distances to critical NPP structures. The loading characterization is performed through deterministic safety calculations by semi-empirical models in the process safety, which are implemented in the simulation software MATLAB. The ultimate goal of the study is to establish minimum safety distances and determine whether and which means of protection are needed to comply with nuclear safety regulations.

5.1 Frequency estimation for the identified accident scenarios

5.1.1 Worst-case scenario at the electrolyser facility

In this work, the postulated initiating event in the electrolyser facility is an undetected overpressure, which eventually leads to mechanical failure (fracture and hydrogen leakage) in the hydrogen collector and separator vessel flange. Pressure build-up is assumed after fault operation of a check valve along the gaseous hydrogen flow path. This constitutes one of the common hazards in PEM systems [1]. In the sub-task report, only the most credible initiating events are reported, which are based on generic hydrogen-system leak frequencies developed by [2, 3]. Mean leak frequencies are used in the release calculations presented in this section. In addition, equipment reliability data specific to PEM systems have been obtained from [4]. The schematic representation of the gaseous leakage in the electrolyser is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of hazardous events in the electrolyser facility

The leakage in the hydrogen collector is assumed in one of the valves downstream of the 8 PEM stacks, so that all hydrogen produced in the 10 MW module leaks into the container volume. Hydrogen leakage in the separator vessel is assumed in the upstream piping flange, and tank blowdown is assumed in the gas processing unit. The impact assessment foresees a range of leak sizes of interest comprising small (1%), medium (10%), and large breaks (100%). Very small leakages (< 1%) are omitted in this study due to the rather negligible contribution to the worst-case scenario or hydrogen explosion. The slow concentration build-up will hardly reach the LFL before the leak can be detected and isolated.

The unintended hydrogen release is set as the initiating event inside the electrolyser, and through ETA it has been expanded towards all potential hazard events. The leak size influences frequencies of the outcome events, as it affects not only leak frequencies, but also probabilities of intermediate events (e.g., cloud dispersion). The initiating event can lead to three different outcomes: (a) Safe condition, (b) jet fire, and (c) hydrogen explosion. Safe condition refers to no ignition of the hydrogen-air mixture and thus no risk-significant consequences, whereas jet fire implies immediate ignition at the leak. Hydrogen explosion requires delayed ignition of the hydrogen gas mixture.

The frequencies of occurrence of all identified outcome events for a confined and unconfined hydrogen release are summarized in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Table 2: Frequencies of occurrence for confined hydrogen release

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	1% (/yr)	10% (/yr)	100% (/yr)
Outcome VCE-01	Safe Condition	$6.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-02	Safe Condition	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.78 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Outcome VCE-03	Safe Condition	$3.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.57 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.23 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-04	Jet Fire	$6.47 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$9.70 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3.88 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome VCE-05	Chemical Explosion	$3.21 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$4.81 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome VCE-06	Safe Condition	$7.99 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.79 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome VCE-07	Safe Condition	$9.77 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-08	Safe Condition	$1.80 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$6.75 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$2.70 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Outcome VCE-09	Jet Fire	$3.60 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$5.40 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.16 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Outcome VCE-10	Chemical Explosion	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.68 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Outcome VCE-11	Safe Condition	$4.45 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$6.67 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.67 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Table 3: Frequencies of occurrence for unconfined hydrogen release

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	1% (/yr)	10% (/yr)	100% (/yr)
Outcome UVCE-01	Safe Condition	$1.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-02	Safe Condition	$3.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-03	Jet Fire	$7.23 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$4.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome UVCE-04	Chemical Explosion	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$6.28 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome UVCE-05	Safe Condition	$8.93 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome UVCE-06	Safe Condition	$1.95 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.42 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-07	Safe Condition	$3.60 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.30 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.16 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Outcome UVCE-08	Jet Fire	$7.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$4.32 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Outcome UVCE-09	Chemical Explosion	$3.57 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$6.25 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Outcome UVCE-10	Safe Condition	$8.89 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$5.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$

The highest frequency for a hydrogen VCE under confined release lies in the range of 10^{-9} per year. This low value is explained by the low frequency of the leak as well as the flow and pressure transmitters. On the other hand, the highest frequency of occurrence for a hydrogen VCE under unconfined release is on the order of 10^{-7} to 10^{-9} per year for mid and large breaks. Main differences between confined and unconfined release scenarios lie on the leak frequencies and atmospheric dispersion instead of forced ventilation.

5.1.2 Worst-case scenario at the buffer tank

In the buffer tank, the initiating event is an external fire originated by an arc fault in the electrical cabinet within the container electrical unit that extends to the buffer tank area. The fire may likewise be assumed in one of the three transformers. The calculated frequencies are gathered in Table 4.

Table 4: Frequencies of occurrence at the buffer tank

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	Frequency (1/yr)
Outcome PVB-01	Safe Condition	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Outcome PVB-02	Safe Condition	$3.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Outcome PVB-03	Jet Fire	$4.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-04	Chemical Explosion	$2.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-05	Safe Condition	$8.23 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Outcome PVB-06	Safe Condition	$2.70 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-07	Jet Fire	$3.58 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome PVB-08	Chemical Explosion	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome PVB-09	Safe Condition	$6.22 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome PVB-10	Physical Explosion	$3.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$

To sum up, an external fire nearby the buffer tank is the major risk contribution within the HPP site.

According to the USNRC Regulatory Guide 1.91, the applicant or licensee may show that the risk is acceptably low on the basis of low probability of explosions and fires. A demonstration that the rate of exposure to a calculated peak positive incident overpressure of 6.9 kPa is less than 10⁻⁶ per year when based on conservative assumptions, or 10⁻⁷ per year when based on realistic assumptions, is deemed as acceptable. The calculated frequencies in this section are based on conservative conditions in terms of high hydrogen inventory and multiple failure of detection and safety systems. In this regard, a chemical explosion in the buffer tank exceeds the threshold of 10⁻⁶ per year.

In many states, a target frequency of exceedance of 10⁻⁴ per year or less is used for design basis external events for natural hazards. In addition, a probability of 10⁻⁷ per reactor-year is used in the design of new facilities as one acceptable limit on the probability value for interacting events with serious radiological consequences, and this is considered a conservative value for the screening probability level if applied to all events of the same type (e.g., explosions). Therefore, probabilistic safety assessment (PSA) of external hazards has to be performed unless it can be shown that the design basis of the plant ensures that the plant can withstand the loads induced by a hazard with

10⁻⁷ per year frequency. The results from the loading characterization should demonstrate that those outcome events do not pose a risk to the NPP structures based on the fragility criterion of 10 kPa set by the NPP operator JSC Energoatom.

5.2 Consequence estimation for the identified accident scenarios

5.2.1 Worst-case scenario at the electrolyser facility

5.2.1.1 Confined hydrogen explosion

The key figure of merit in the safety analyses is the peak overpressure. In order to obtain the normal reflected peak overpressures with the TNT-Equivalency model for spherical charge detonations, the correlations of Mills and Kinney are applied as an upper- and lower-bound, respectively. These two correlations are widely used in structural design studies. Furthermore, two different container volumes, and therefore hydrogen masses, are imposed in the calculations. This approach allows to obtain the most conservative value of the peak overpressure against distance. Figure 11 shows the decay of the peak overpressure with increasing distance to the blast source. The approximate distances needed to comply with the structural design criterion of 10 kPa are gathered in Table 5.

Figure 11: TNT-Equivalency results for confined VCE

The most conservative value obtained with the TNT-Equivalency model by means of the Mills correlation and the upper-bound container volume (102.65 m³), points out to a required distance of 65 m to comply with the fragility criterion of 10 kPa. Note that these results are also conservative in terms of the hydrogen mass involved in the vapour cloud and do not take into account the blast energy absorbed by the container walls and surrounding structures during the shock wave propagation. Those two factors will significantly reduce the required safety distances. In any case, the calculation results comply with the structural criterion in the nearest NPP structure, i.e., the standby diesel generators.

Table 5: Minimum separation distances for the confined VCE scenario

Applied model	Correlation	Container volume	Safe distance (m)
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	Cont-1	57
		Cont-2	65
	Kinney	Cont-1	47
		Cont-2	53
Baker-Strehlow-Tang	M = 0.35	Cont-2	28
	M = 1.00	Cont-2	80

Besides the TNT-Equivalency method, the impact assessment also considers the BST model to evaluate peak overpressure based on several flame front Mach numbers. In this regard, the calculations have considered all flame speeds from the original curves. The peak overpressure against distance is plotted in Figure 12, and the Mach numbers corresponding to deflagrations are labelled as black, whereas those corresponding to detonations are labelled in blue. All BST curves with Mach number above 0.35, which is a value that can be regarded as a slow deflagration (115.5 m/s) and are coinciding at distances above 20 m from the ignition point. The hydrogen mass available for combustion accounts for 2.48 kg (upper-bound). The calculation results show that for a slow deflagration, a distance of 28 m would be

required to comply with the 10 kPa safety limit, whereas for fast deflagrations and detonations a distance of 80 m would be required to comply with structural design criteria.

Figure 12: BST results for confined VCE

To sum up, the minimum separation distances necessary to comply with the 10 kPa limit account for 65 m with the TNT-Equivalency, whereas 80 m would be required with the BST model for the upper-bound hydrogen mass involved in the chemical explosion. A comparison between both models shows higher peak overpressure at the point of ignition with the TNT-Equivalency, and a slower pressure decay with distance based on the BST model. Both models foresee catastrophic failure near the hydrogen facility. The positive impulse is likewise a relevant parameter in structural analysis. The incident impulse at 80 m computed with the BST model accounts for $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kPa.ms. These results stress the need for detailed structural analysis once plant-specific data is available.

5.2.1.2 Unconfined hydrogen explosion

The unconfined VCE is assumed in the gas processing area located above the container process unit. In particular, mechanical failure occurs in the flange upstream of the vessel, and gaseous hydrogen is released during vessel blowdown. The separator vessel contains approximately 38 kg of hydrogen. The calculation results show that the vessel is completely depressurized at 5 s, 50 s, and 500 s approximately for full-bore, mid, and small breaks, respectively. The rapid depressurization and hydrogen release during full-bore rupture and mid break size increases the probability of a VCE. The available hydrogen mass at explosion accounts for 2.48 kg. This quantity corresponds to the gas processing unit neglecting balance of plant (upper-bound). The TNT-Equivalency and Wiekema models are implemented to determine the peak overpressure against distance.

The TNT-Equivalency model considers three different yield factors (lower-bound, average, and upper-bound) based on empirical evidence. The calculation results are plotted in Figure 13 and summarized in Table 6. The most conservative conditions show that a minimum separation distance of 48 m would be required to comply with the safety limit of 10 kPa. The differences with respect to the results obtained in the confined VCE arise from the explosion yield. The results obtained with the Wiekema model for a fast deflagration and a detonation are depicted in Figure 14. The most conservative results for a hydrogen detonation point out to minimum separation distance of 40 m. The obtained results

do not take into account effects of atmospheric dispersion, which would significantly reduce the risk of a delayed ignition, and amount of gaseous hydrogen available for combustion.

Figure 13: TNT-Equivalency results for unconfined VCE

Table 6: Summary of minimum separation distances for the unconfined VCE

Applied model	Correlation	Yield (-)	Safe distance (m)
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	0.01	17
		0.04	30
		0.10	48
	Kinney	0.01	16
		0.04	25
		0.10	33
Wiekema	Deflagration	-	31
	Detonation	-	40

Figure 14: Wiekema model results for unconfined VCE

5.2.2 Worst-case scenario at the buffer tank

The calculation results for the physical explosion after an overpressure in the buffer tank are gathered in Table 7. As it is common practice in the process safety, a safety factor is applied over the maximum allowable working pressure of the hydrogen tank. In this work, a safety factor of 1.25 is implemented to account for the set-point of the relief-safety valve plus the factor of 1.21. An additional factor of 2 is applied in the Brode’s model to account for ground reflection. Based on the calculation results gathered in Table 7, the most conservative explosion condition would not exceed the design criterion in the nearby NPP structure.

Table 7: Minimal separation distance for single pressure vessels

Applied Model	Correlation	Hydrogen mass	Pressure	Safe Distance
Brode and TNT-Eq.	Mills	30 kg	35 bar	85 m
	Kinney			70 m

Projectiles and missiles are identified as secondary hazards after an explosion. A PVB may lead to fragmentation and projectile ejection. The range of the flying fragments is strongly determined by the angle of departure, mass, and shape of the fragment. The flying range of the fragment is strongly affected by dynamic forces acting upon the fragment during the flight, namely drag, lift, and gravity.

The fragmentation patterns of cylindrical vessels have been extensively investigated numerically and experimentally. The most common number of fragments after a cylindrical pressure burst due to overpressure falls in between two to three pieces. In order to characterize the mechanical load upon impact, the Moore’s method has been implemented in this work. This method allows to determine the fragment initial velocity and maximum flying range. Two different fragmentation patterns are considered for the calculations:

- Two different pieces: tube end (336 kg) plus flattened plate (914 kg).
- Three pieces: two end caps (143.5 kg) plus the cylindrical plate (963 kg).

Hazard assessment is based on the maximum flying range of the fragments. Missiles or projectiles causing mechanical impacts are classified into two categories: (i) hard missiles; and (ii) soft missiles. The categorization is based on the missile's deformability with respect to the deformability of the impacted object. The fragments originated from the pressure burst can be assumed as soft missiles when impacting continuous reinforced concrete walls, whereas it may be assumed as hard missiles when impacting other NPP structures such as the standby diesel generators.

The results from Moore's model are gathered in Table 8, which provides initial fragment velocity and maximum flying range based on fragment shape and fraction of released energy transferred to kinetic energy of fragments. The fragment masses are 143 kg for the hemispherical caps and 963 kg for the cylinder body. The initial velocity of the fragments is the same regardless of the fragment shape and mass. It is simply calculated according to the released energy after vessel burst and a geometric factor relation based on the stored mass of hydrogen and the total mass of the empty vessel.

Table 8: Fragment velocity and maximum range with Moore's model

Fragment shape	Explosion energy to fragments			
	20%		10%	
	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)
Hemispherical cap (tumbling)	145	431	103	323
Hemispherical cap (no tumbling)	145	564	103	324
Cylinder body (edge on)	145	326	103	37

Based on the results summarized in Table 8, the flying fragments upon the most conservative calculations have the potential to reach the standby diesel generators, cooling towers, as well as turbine building. The structural response of those buildings and structures needs to be analyzed with specific NPP data. Some points need to be highlighted: (1) the flying fragments are deemed as soft missiles due to the high deformability upon impact, and therefore they will present a limited damage potential upon impact, (2) the departure angle of the fragments, set as 45° for the maximum flying range, can be reduced significantly by the design of the vessel, and (3) the buffer tank may be located either underground or outside the NPP perimeter for a higher assurance.

To conclude, the frequency estimation showed that the delayed ignition of a hydrogen gas mixture after the actuation of the safety-relief valve in the buffer tank had a frequency in the order of 10⁻⁵ per year. Under the most conservative conditions, assuming that all 30 kg of hydrogen are available for ignition, and a 10% efficiency for unconfined explosion, 3 kg of hydrogen would be involved in the combustion process. Based on the results displayed in Section 5.2.1.2 (respectively Section 28.3 in the full report of subtask 4) with the upper-bound hydrogen mass, the generated shock wave by the hydrogen VCE is not expected to exceed the fragility criterion at the nearby standby diesel generators.

5.3 Conclusions

This section has reported the main outcomes from the impact assessment of the integration of a hydrogen cogeneration facility into Rivne NPP in Ukraine. The NPP site features have been provided by the state operator JSC Energoatom in the framework of the Euratom NPHyCo project. The risk of damage at the NPP site by the worst-case scenario at the HPP, which was identified as a hydrogen explosion, was evaluated by means of frequency estimation obtained through HAZID and ETA

methodologies, and deterministic safety calculations by means of selected semi-empirical methods from the process safety.

The external hazard impact assessment has identified three different accident scenarios:

1. Confined hydrogen explosion within the electrolyser container
2. Unconfined hydrogen explosion within the gas processing area
3. Physical explosion in the buffer tank and fragment generation

The highest frequency obtained for a hydrogen VCE within the electrolyser facility lies at around 10^{-7} per year for a small leak. According to the calculation results, the small leak size (1%) is not expected to exceed the LFL before detection and isolation by the multiple detectors onsite the HPP. Therefore, the mid-size break (10%) is assumed as the most likely event leading to an explosion with a frequency of 10^{-9} per year. On the other hand, the calculation results applied to a hydrogen VCE in the buffer tank show a frequency of 10^{-5} per year. Note that this result is conservative, since the authors have not been able to quantify the thermal effect of the fire nearby on the delayed ignition probability of the hydrogen vapour cloud. The obtained value lies above the threshold of 10^{-6} per year based on conservative assumptions adopted by the USNRC, and also above the value of 10^{-7} per year that would justify an external event PSA. The load characterization by semi-empirical methods shows that the shock wave would not exceed the fragility criterion of the nearby NPP structure.

The deterministic calculations are performed with conservative conditions in terms of available hydrogen mass at combustion. The calculation results show that both confined and unconfined VCEs comply with the available safe distances at Rivne NPP on the proposed location by the NPP operator, and do not exceed the fragility criterion of the nearby NPP structure. A physical explosion in the buffer tank may lead to the generation of fragments with the potential to reach the cooling towers and turbine building. The energy stored in the hydrogen pressure vessel and the relatively low fragment mass, together with a 45° departure angle are major contributors to the maximum flying range. Nevertheless, the frequency of occurrence of the physical explosion lies in the range of 10^{-9} per year, mostly by the high reliability of the passive pressure-relief devices on the pressure vessel.

In order to reduce the uncertainties arising from the worst-case scenario at the buffer tank, the authors of the study propose either to place the pressure vessel outside of the NPP perimeter, or to perform an external event PSA to analyse its contribution to core damage frequency. Furthermore, in order to reduce the risk of domino effects within the HPP site, the deployment of physical barriers, i.e., blast walls, between the 10 MW electrolyser containers is highly advised by the authors of this study.

6 Subtask 5: Analysis of the impact of integration on the licensing and license documentation

6.1 Aspects to be considered for the licensing of an HPP

In this subtask of Deliverable 4.2, the impact of the NPP-HPP integration scenarios on the licensing process are analyzed. For this purpose, the key documents which define relevant requirements for industrial and nuclear installations are first collected. These mainly include:

- IAEA Safety Standards and Recommendations
- WENRA Safety Reference Levels for Existing Reactors
- Directives and other regulations of the European Union

The information contained in these documents is utilized to gain a general overview of the safety standards to be met and the activities required to demonstrate compliance with these standards as part of approval processes. In addition to the documents mentioned, national regulations and standards must always be taken into account in individual cases.

The main subject areas that must be taken into account are then described in detail. This is done first from the perspective of the necessary approvals for the construction and operation of the HPP and then from the perspective of the necessary reviews and updates for the approval of the NPP, which is mainly covered by the Safety Analysis Report (SAR).

The HPP is essentially to be regarded as a chemical facility and, due to the hydrogen produced, harbors the possibility of fire and explosion risks. For both onsite and offsite scenarios, possible effects on the environment (during construction, commissioning and operation) must be examined and, if necessary, remedial measures must be planned. The fundamentally important aspects of licensing law that were considered with regard to the construction and operation of an HPP are as follows:

- Environmental Impact:** An environmental impact assessment (EIA) must be carried out to minimize potential impacts on local protected plant and animal species as well as on the soil and groundwater. This must include both the construction measures and the operation of the HPP. One possible impact that may result from the construction of the HPP is the impairment of the habitat and possibly the breeding activities of protected plant and animal species. This may mean that construction work is only permitted at certain times of the year. Care must also be taken to ensure that no substances hazardous to the soil or groundwater (e.g., ion exchange resins used for water treatment, acids and alkalis, cooling fluids in the cooling circuits, hydraulic oils, the oils used in transformers, wastewater (concentrated solution)) escape during construction work or during operation of the HPP. To avoid this, the application of the best available techniques for preventive measures is mandatory. The effort required for offsite scenarios may be expected to be significantly greater, as a completely new EIA may have to be prepared depending on the location of the HPP. Onsite scenarios can be based on the EIA prepared for the construction and operation of the NPP and the preventive measures already taken.
- External Hazards and Risks/ Emergency Provisions and Response Organization:** According to the Seveso III Directive, depending on the maximum amount of hydrogen that can be present in the HPP (including storage tanks and all pipes and containers) the facility can be classified in one of two categories: as a lower-tier establishment (hydrogen quantities between 5 and 50 tons), or as an upper-tier establishment (hydrogen quantities of 50 tons or more). Depending on the category, certain safety analyses and reports as well as internal and external emergency plans are required. Possible interactions with other plants and/or the NPP must be included in these analyses, and necessary measures taken to avoid negative effects. In onsite scenarios, the analyses and emergency plans must be harmonized and coordinated with those of the NPP.
- Product Safety:** The components and systems used in the HPP must meet the basic requirements of product safety in order to minimize the risk of malfunctions and accidents. This is primarily the responsibility of the manufacturer but should be verified by the operator.
- Occupational Health and Safety:** In principle, the usual occupational health and safety measures for workers in industrial plants must be implemented. In addition to the use of

protective equipment and procedures that are appropriate to the hazard potential of individual activities, explosion protection measures (avoiding the formation of flammable mixtures of hydrogen and air, avoiding ignition sources, minimizing the effects of ignition) and the marking of potentially explosive areas with warning notices must be implemented. For onsite scenarios, radiation protection measures must be taken into account where necessary and appropriate.

- Energy Transmission and Media Supply Lines:** Depending on the integration scenario, geography, and existing infrastructure at the selected location, it may be necessary to install electric power lines to connect the HPP to the public power grid or to the NPP. In addition, pipelines may be needed to supply the HPP with the required operating media (cooling water, demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) and to transport the hydrogen produced to the consumers. If this is the case, it may be necessary to acquire usage rights for surrounding land, which may involve extensive approval processes including public participation (local communities, associations and private individuals) and can significantly delay the overall project.
- Transport of Dangerous Goods:** If the hydrogen produced is transported away by trailer, train or ship, a loading terminal must be built. To do this, the necessary permits from the directive on the domestic transport of dangerous goods must be obtained. In addition, the terminal must be included in all safety-related analyses and possible negative effects must be excluded or minimized as much as possible. The latter aspect is particularly important for onsite scenarios.
- Building Permit:** A building permit is generally required for the construction of all types of buildings and structures. Plans of the facility to be constructed and the execution of the construction works must be submitted to the competent authority for approval. The authority will check the construction in regular inspections and carries out a final inspection when the work is completed. Other aspects described above (e.g., the performance of an EIA, the possible inclusion of energy transmission and/or media supply lines, and public participation processes) have a strong influence on both the time frame and the manner of the realization of the project.

These main aspects form the basis of the assessment of the eight integration scenarios with regard to the licensing process for the HPP. The aim of this analysis is to assess the potential expenditures (in terms of time and money) that are likely to arise from the individual constellations of the integration scenarios on a qualitative level. The key points are summarized in table form for each of the integration scenarios. Finally, **Table 10** gives an overview of the scores (High, Medium or Low) of the main aspects mentioned with regard to their impact, depending on the integration scenario.

6.2 Aspects to be considered for the renewal of the NPP license

Regarding the necessary adjustments to the existing NPP license, the focus is on the Safety Analysis Report (SAR). The SAR contains all key aspects of importance for the safe operation of the NPP. All direct and indirect changes to the technical systems of the NPP, the structure of the operating organization, the activities and procedures resulting from the integration of the HPP must therefore be described and documented in the SAR by the operator. The extent of the evaluation will strongly depend on the actual changes, firstly to structures, systems & components, and secondly to the operating organization, procedures and activities at the NPP site.

Based on the assessment of the necessity and safety significance of plant modifications resulting from the integration scenarios in subtask 2 of D4.2, a generic assessment was performed and discussed.

The SAR summarizes all relevant aspects which need to be analysed to effectively assess the safety of an NPP and the activities carried out at the NPP site. This includes the technical safety of structures, systems & components, the safe operation, accident & emergency procedures, and plant security. The content of the SAR may be divided or combined into different documents.

Recommendations regarding the content and structure of a generic SAR are given by the IAEA in the [Specific Safety Guide No. 12 “Licensing Process for Nuclear Installations”](#) [5] and [Specific Safety Guide No. 61 “Format and Content of the Safety Analysis Report for Nuclear Power Plants”](#) [6]. A comprehensive list of the main topics to be addressed in an SAR is presented in the table below.

Table 9: Main topics of a generic SAR and their general content, based on [5] and [6].

Main topic	
Overall planning of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A draft project plan • A site evaluation report • Reports on the use of cooling sources and discharges into the environment • Technical specifications, including all operational limits and conditions • References to and benchmarks against other relevant nuclear installations
Licensing process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The strategic plan for the licensing process • Public inquiry strategy plans and reports
Technical design and construction of the plant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A descriptive construction report • A report on the management and organization of the design and construction project • A report on the acquisition programme (list of SSCs and their origin, details of the manufacturing process for SSCs important to safety) • Technical design documents • Fire protection plans • Physical protection plans
Plant operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General operating rules • Modification rules (may be included in the general operating rules) • Plans relating to the operating organization and its management system for all licensing steps • Commissioning programmes and reports
Plant security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General site protection plans • Access rules
Management of nuclear material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans for accounting and control of nuclear material • Reports on radioactive waste and spent fuel management

Management of personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and qualification plans for operations personnel • Proof of trustworthiness of all staff who will be engaged in responsible or sensitive positions
Maintenance and ageing management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Details of the maintenance programme and the periodic testing programme • Ageing management plans
Continuous improvement of safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A plan for collecting and applying feedback on operating experience • Plans for evaluating and improving safety performance • Reports on periodic safety reviews or other safety reviews
Accident and emergency management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating procedures for accident management • Emergency preparedness and response plans
Radiation protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports and manuals on the radiation protection programme
Decommissioning of the plant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decommissioning plans and reports

Not all the listed aspects are affected by the integration of an HPP into an existing NPP. It is the licensee's task to evaluate, which aspects are affected and how.

For the assessment, the basic structure and content of a generic SAR as recommended by the IAEA is first described. Subsequently, for all chapters of the SAR for which it cannot be ruled out from the outset that they will be affected by the integration of the HPP, the potential impact of the integration scenarios is also assessed at a qualitative level. Other key topics that are not directly part of the SAR, but nevertheless play an important role in safe and successful integration, are also included in the assessment. These are as follows:

- Organizational Aspects
 - Operating Organization
 - Emergency Organization
 - Access and Security Rules
 - Management System
- Emergency Preparedness and Response
- Fire Protection Plans
- Operational Limits, Operating Procedures
- Periodic Safety Review Program

6.3 Overview of the results of the qualitative assessment

The results of the detailed qualitative analysis of the individual main topics regarding the NPP are presented in **Table 11** and **Table 12**.

Table 10: Qualitative overview of the impact of the integration scenarios on the licensing requirements for the HPP

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Environmental Impact	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
External Hazards and Risks	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency provisions and response organization	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Product Safety	No Specific Impact							
Occupational Health and Safety	LOW							
Energy transmission lines	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
Transport of dangerous goods	LOW							
Building Permit	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM

Table 11: Qualitative overview of the impact of the integration scenarios on the licensing requirements for the NPP

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Operating organization	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency organization	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Access and security rules	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Management system	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency preparedness and response	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Fire protection plans	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Operational limits, operating procedures	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Periodic safety review program	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

Table 12: Qualitative assessment of the impacts of the integration of HPP into a NPP on a typical Safety Assessment Report

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Chapter 1: introduction and general considerations	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 2: Site Characteristics	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 3: Safety objectives and design rules for structures, systems and components	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 6: Engineered safety features	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 7: Instrumentation and control	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW
Chapter 8: Electrical power	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 9: Auxiliary systems	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW
Chapter 12: Radiation Protection	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 13: Conduct of Operations	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 14: Plant Construction and Commissioning	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 15: Safety Analysis	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 16: Operational Limits and	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW

Conditions for Safe Operation								
Chapter 17: Management for Safety	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 18: Human Factor Engineering	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 19: Emergency Preparedness and Response	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 20: Environmental Aspects	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of Life Aspects	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

6.4 Conclusions

The main findings of subtask 5 are listed below:

HPP licensing

- The more independent the HPP is from the NPP, the more systems have to be set up and connected to supply points (e.g. for electric power supply, water for demineralization, cooling water, wastewater disposal).
- If the hydrogen produced is to be transported by pipeline, it will also be necessary to construct longer pipelines to the nearest connection to an existing hydrogen network or to the consumer(s)
- Depending on the local infrastructure and geographical conditions, it may be necessary to lay longer power lines and/or pipelines. In this case, approval procedures with public participation may have to be carried out for the authorization to use privately or publicly owned land.
- An onsite location of the HPP on the NPP's perimeter may offer the opportunity to simplify procedures such as the environmental impact assessment and habitat assessment, as these have already been carried out for the existing NPP.
- However, a closer integration of the HPP with NPP systems requires more extensive considerations regarding risks and possible effects of the HPP's operation on the safe operation of the NPP (e.g., in the MAPP and/or safety report for the HPP).
- When choosing an onsite integration scenario, certain existing assessments, reports and licenses for the NPP (protection of wild flora and fauna, environmental impact assessment, industrial emissions etc.) can serve as basis for procedures/documents needed for the licensing of the HPP. If the competent authorities agree to it, the HPP may even be integrated in existing licenses as a modification of the NPP.

NPP licensing

- A more independent offsite integration largely or completely eliminates the need for the NPP operator to carry out comprehensive analyses of the safety implications of system modifications.
- Close integration of the HPP into the infrastructure of the NPP (i.e. sharing of systems such as the Electric Power Distribution System, the Demineralized Water System, or the Feedwater System) requires consideration of possible safety-related effects (e.g. explosion, internal flooding) and, if necessary, the provision of measures to prevent them.
- Certain aspects, such as the integration of the HPP into operational processes (e.g. operating and maintenance procedures) as well as instrumentation & control technology required for a smooth joint operation of the two facilities, need to be addressed in any integration scenario.
- A closer integration of the HPP requires a revision of existing internal and external emergency procedures of the NPP.

Overall conclusions

- Both onsite and offsite integration scenarios offer advantages and disadvantages from a licensing perspective.

- The advantages and disadvantages are not exclusively dependent on the integration scenario, but also on individual conditions at the plant location, which are not foreseeable within the scope of this project.
- In principle, from a sole licensing point of view, there is a slight tendency for the advantages of onsite location of the HPP to outweigh the disadvantages more than is the case with offsite location. This is due to the possibility of avoiding certain approval procedures (e.g. land use) or making them less extensive (e.g. EIA, protection of wild flora & fauna).

The main determining factor for the choice of the integration scenario to be applied will therefore most likely be economic factors.

7 Overall Conclusions

1. Licensing conditions generally allow to make changes to NPP systems needed for the integration of an HPP. However, due to the potentially/likely large amount of work and additional costs (e.g. extended safety analysis to justify modifications with regard to their possible impacts on safety, adaptations of procedures, training of personnel, changes of documentation), sharing safety related systems of the NPP with the HPP is unlikely unless the benefits of sharing are very high. Referring to WP 3 “Economical aspects of coupling” this might be relevant for sharing high temperature steam. For a modification of a non-safety related system, the additional costs from a safety / regulations point of view are limited. This means that sharing of non-safety related systems is mainly a financial trade-off between the investment costs of separate systems compared to the investment costs of shared (non-safety) systems. In practice, sharing of systems will be focused on sharing of non-safety systems to minimize the additional effort of the modifications. A close integration of an HPP with an NPP and the high safety requirements to be complied with (with respect to modifications, maintenance, accident procedures etc.) may also increase the operating costs of the HPP’s systems.
2. The external hazard impact assessment has identified three different accident scenarios that can occur at the HPP:
 - a. Confined hydrogen explosion within the electrolyzer container.
 - b. Unconfined hydrogen explosion within the gas processing area.
 - c. Physical explosion in the buffer tank and fragment generation.

The calculation results for a 40 MW hydrogen facility show that both confined and unconfined Vapor Cloud Explosions (VCEs) comply with the available safe distances at Rivne NPP on the location proposed by the NPP operator, and do not exceed the fragility criterion of 10 kPa of the nearby NPP structures (see Table 13 and Table 14).

Table 13: Calculation results of minimum separation distances for the confined VCE scenario (fragility criterion of 10 kPa)

Applied model	Correlation	Container volume	Safe distance (m)
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	Cont-1	57
		Cont-2	65
	Kinney	Cont-1	47
		Cont-2	53

Baker-Strehlow-Tang	M = 0.35	Cont-2	28
	M = 1.00	Cont-2	80

Table 14: Calculation results of minimum separation distances for the unconfined VCE (fragility criterion of 10 kPa)

Applied model	Correlation	Yield (-)	Safe distance (m)
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	0.01	17
		0.04	30
		0.10	48
	Kinney	0.01	16
		0.04	25
		0.10	33
Wiekema	Deflagration	-	31
	Detonation	-	40

A physical explosion in the buffer tank may lead to the generation of fragments with the potential to reach the cooling towers and turbine building (calculation results for Table 15). The obtained results point out the need of mitigation measures deployed on the high-pressure storage area in order to prevent domino effects between storage vessels. The load impact and structural response of the NPP structures will much depend on their seismic category.

Table 15: Fragment velocity and maximum range with Moore's model

Fragment shape	Explosion energy to fragments			
	20%		10%	
	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)
Hemispherical cap (tumbling)	145	431	103	323
Hemispherical cap (no tumbling)	145	564	103	324
Cylinder body (edge on)	145	326	103	37

On a generic level, calculation results are highly dependent on the chosen assumptions (electrolyser and storage size, position and distance of the HPP in relation to the NPP's SSCs and stability of SSCs at the specific NPP). Potentially, protective measures such as the construction of shielding walls to absorb pressure waves and projectiles may be deemed necessary by the authority to provide acceptable safety margins. This would result in additional effort and costs that need to be justified by a significant benefit of placing the HPP near the NPP's SSCs.

3. Onsite location of the HPP offers the advantages that certain licensing and approval procedures can either be omitted or simplified, e.g. land use, EIA, protection of wild flora & fauna. This advantage depends also on individual conditions at the plant location such as existing transport infrastructure and geographical conditions in the surrounding area. From a sole licensing perspective there is a slight tendency that the advantages of onsite location of the HPP is favorable as compared to offsite location. As discussed above, additional effort and costs of an onsite integration may still lead to the result that an onsite integration is not economically favorable.

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Annex 1: Full Report of Subtask 1 – Identification and Description of Facility Types (NPP/HPP) and Operating Conditions

Deliverable 4.2 subtask 1

Identification and description of facility types
(NPP/HPP) and operating conditions

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Revisions

IND REV	RELEASE DATE	PARAGRAPH	SCOPE OF THE REVISION
1.A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue, reviewed by GRS

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEL	Alkaline Electrolysis
AGR	Advanced Gas-cooled Reactors
BWR	Boiling Water Reactor
CANDU	CANada Deuterium Uranium reactors
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
COMAH	Control of Major Accident Hazard
DOE	Department of Energy
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EU	European Union
ETC	Energy Transitions Commission
FOAK	First-of-a-Kind
Gen IV	Generation IV
GFR	Gas cooled Fast Reactor
GHG	Green House Gases
HAZID	Hazard Identification
HEEP	Hydrogen Economic Evaluation Programme
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
HTE	High Temperature Electrolysis
HTGR	High Temperature Gas Reactors
HTR	High Temperature Reactor
HTSE	High Temperature Steam Electrolysis
HV	Hydrogen Valley
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
LFR	Lead-cooled Fast Reactor
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LOHC	Liquid organic hydrogen carriers
LTE	Low Temperature Electrolysis
LTO	Long-Term Operation
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MSR	Molten Salt Reactor
NG	Natural Gas
NOAK	Nth-of-a-kind
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
NZE	Net Zero Emissions
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PEMEL	Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolyzer
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
R&D	Research and development
SCWR	Super Critical Water-cooled Reactor
SFR	Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor

Acronym	Description
SMR	Small Modular Reactor
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USD	Unites States Dollar
VHTR	Very High Temperature Reactor
VRE	Variable Renewable Electricity sources
WEO	World Energy Outlook
WP	Work Package

Summary

This document identifies and describes the available technologies to produce hydrogen using heat and electricity from an NPP, comparing its main characteristics, and providing the context information required for licensing analysis. The different interfaces between the NPP and the HPP are described with different levels of integration.

In the full integration level, the HPP is on-site the NPP and all needs of the HPP are served from NPP infrastructure (electricity, steam, water, nitrogen, wastewater treatment, etc). In the partial integration level, only some needs of the HPP are served from NPP infrastructure and the HPP can be located on-site or off-site the NPP. When no needs of the HPP are served from the NPP it is called zero integration level.

For the licensing analysis eight scenarios with different levels of integration are considered:

Onsite Solutions

9. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
10. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
11. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
12. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

13. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
14. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
15. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
16. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)

Apart from the technical level of integration, there are as well different modes of operation possible that have impact on design and licensing of the NPP.

The **continuous production strategy** is the case in which the HPP is producing hydrogen at the designed capacity in a continuous way, and it is a constant additional consumer of the NPP. In this case, the HPP starts and stops with the NPP, or it requires external sources of supply when the NPP produces less electricity than the amount required by the HPP.

In the **production based on opportunity prices strategy**, the production of hydrogen varies between no production and full capacity with respect to the achievable revenue. This mode of operation involves frequent starts and stops of the HPP that may have an impact on the NPP, depending on the level of integration.

In the **production based on grid balancing services strategy**, the operator provides balancing services to the grid. In this case the electricity supplied to the grid should change with a required ramp to follow the demand curve. For this reason, the HPP as a load of the NPP should be working at around 50% of its capacity to be able to increase or decrease its electricity consumption when required by the electricity market.

The different operating conditions cases considering the level of integration, the hydrogen production strategy and the HPP technology are summarized in tables in the document.

8 Identification and description of facility types

D1.1 establishes the frame of reference for the Nuclear-Powered Hydrogen Cogeneration (NPHyCo) project. In Section 5 of D1.1, qualitative and quantitative information on the available technologies to produce hydrogen has been compiled. There are 4 possible pathways for nuclear-powered hydrogen cogeneration (see

Figure 15: Pathways for hydrogen production from nuclear energy and selection for the project.

), namely low-temperature water electrolysis (LTE), high-temperature electrolysis (HTE), thermochemical water splitting and fossil fuels reforming. All these technologies need electricity and/or heat as a driving energy form. Both electricity and heat can be supplied by a nuclear power plant (NPP) without releasing direct Green Houses Gas (GHG) emissions.

Figure 15: Pathways for hydrogen production from nuclear energy and selection for the project.

Water electrolysis is a method of producing hydrogen directly from water. The decomposition of water is driven by electrical energy. The LTE hydrogen plant is suitable for coupling with nuclear power plants in several interface degrees. There are two commercially available LTE technologies: Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL) and Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolysis.

Steam electrolysis is a promising pathway for hydrogen production by utilizing nuclear electricity and heat. HTE enables reaching higher electrical efficiencies than LTE. The integration of HTE with an NPP is more challenging than LTE. HTE is a less developed technology than LTE. HTE can be achieved through solid oxide electrolyzers cells (SOEC).

The thermochemical process is a method that uses thermal energy to split water into hydrogen and oxygen. It requires high temperatures that cannot be satisfied by low-temperature reactors such as Light Water Reactors (LWR). Thermochemical cycles are still in an early developmental phase. This method is not considered in the project.

Hydrocarbon reforming technologies (Steam Methane Reforming) extract hydrogen from hydrocarbon fuel by employing high temperatures. Reforming fossil fuels is associated with significant Green Houses Gas (GHG) emissions. For this reason, this method is not considered in the project.

In relation to nuclear reactors, it is worth distinguishing the case of nuclear reactors currently in operation and the case of new advanced reactors, as indicated in section 8.3 below.

8.1 Water Electrolysis

As indicated in D1.1, water electrolysis involves an electrochemical process that splits water molecules into their constituent parts – hydrogen and oxygen. The decomposition of water is driven by electrical energy. The working principle is based on passing an electrical current between two electrodes immersed in an electrolyte. As a result, high purity gaseous hydrogen and oxygen are produced.

Electrolysis has many attributes that make it suitable for coupling with NPPs. A hydrogen production plant (HPP) based on low-temperature electrolysis (LTE) utilizes demineralized water as a feedstock and electricity as an energy source. There are other auxiliary inputs to the plant, such as cooling water, nitrogen, and instrumentation air supply. All these interfaces can potentially be shared with an NPP. The outputs of an LTE HPP are hydrogen, oxygen, heat (absorbed by cooling water) and wastewater. The nuclear powered LTE process does not emit CO₂.

Due to electricity being the only driving energy form needed for LTE, any nuclear reactor type is suitable for coupling with low-temperature electrolyzers. HPPs based on LTE may therefore be powered by existing NPPs as well as new, advanced nuclear reactors. The power supply for the LTE process is realized via electric transmission only. The absence of heat input makes LTE the simplest hydrogen production method to integrate at an NPP’s site. Unlike high-temperature electrolysis, thermochemical cycles and steam reforming processes, water electrolysis does not require an intervention into the turbine island or a connection of NPP and HPP via steam piping. LTE technology also offers the possibility of partial off-site integration, where the HPP is located outside of the NPP’s perimeter and connected to the NPP by power lines. This partial off-site integration scenario reduces safety concerns, helps to overcome regulatory limitations and minimizes the need for intervention into the NPP’s existing infrastructure.

The two commercially available LTE technologies are Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL) and Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolysis.

8.1.1 Alkaline electrolysis

Alkaline water electrolysis is the most developed electrolysis technology.

Alkaline electrolysis was the first hydrogen generation method that was coupled with an NPP. A 0,6-MW_{el} hydrogen plant has been producing hydrogen using nuclear power at Oskarshamn nuclear plant in Sweden since 1992 [7].

Alkaline electrolysis typically operates between 60 and 80 °C. Working pressure ranges from atmospheric to 30 bar. Electrical efficiency of alkaline electrolyzers reaches 63-70 % (based on Lower Heating Value) [8]. Due to stack degradation, electrical efficiency degrades over time. The efficiency loss of AEL is estimated at around 0,12 % per 1000 operating hours, but it strongly varies depending on the mode of operation and other factors [9]. Commercial alkaline electrolyzers have the longest operating lifetime among all electrolyzer technologies, ranging between 60.000 and 90.000 hours [8].

8.1.2 PEM electrolysis

Proton exchange membrane (PEM), also known as polymer electrolyte membrane, water electrolysis is a type of low-temperature electrolysis. A PEM electrolysis cell is based on a solid polymer electrolyte, as opposed to a liquid electrolyte used in alkaline electrolysis cells.

PEM electrolysis operates between 50 and 80 °C. Both LTE technologies yield high-purity gas, but the purity of hydrogen produced by PEM electrolysis is higher. PEM electrolyzers (PEMELs) have slightly lower efficiency than alkaline electrolyzers, i.e. around 56-60 % (based on LHV). One of the advantages of PEM electrolysis technology is the production of highly compressed hydrogen. The working pressure of PEMELs typically ranges from 30 to 80 bar [8]. This technology also offers flexible operation with a wide operating range, quick response, and short start-up times. These characteristics make PEMELs more suitable for fluctuating demand than AELs. Another attractive attribute of PEMELs is its smaller plant footprint (space requirements) than that of an AEL. On the downside, the lifetime of

commercial PEMELs is somewhat shorter compared to AELs. They provide between 30.000 and 90.000 operating hours [8].

In 2022, the US Department of Energy (DOE) approved the construction and installation of a PEMEL system at Nine Mile Point with a price of USD 5.8 million. Since March of 2023 the Nine Mile Point NPP has been producing 560 kilograms of hydrogen per day using a 1,25 megawatt PEMEL, which is enough to meet the on-site hydrogen demand for cooling purposes [10].

8.2 Steam Electrolysis

As indicated in D1.1, steam electrolysis is a promising pathway for hydrogen production by nuclear electricity and heat. Unlike LTE, which operates near ambient temperature, HTE employs higher temperatures (650 – 1000 °C) to split water. In the HTE process, the first step is the conversion of water to high-temperature steam by consuming heat. Steam is subsequently supplied to an electrolysis cell where it is dissociated to hydrogen and oxygen by using electricity.

HTE enables reaching higher electrical efficiencies than LTE, because part of the energy required for the decomposition of water is supplied in the form of heat. Furthermore, electrolysis reaction consumes less energy at higher temperatures. This results in specific electricity consumption decrease by approximately one-third compared to LTE. The heat input also improves economic viability since thermal energy is generally cheaper than electricity. These characteristics make steam electrolysis an attractive candidate for coupling with NPPs.

An HPP based on HTE utilizes demineralized water as a feedstock and requires electricity and heat as energy sources. Another auxiliary input is sweep gas (usually air), that flows produced oxygen out of the system. All these interfaces can potentially be shared with an NPP. The outputs of a HTE hydrogen production plant are hydrogen, oxygen, and wastewater. Heat recovered from exhaust gases is used to preheat the input media. The nuclear powered HTE process produces low-carbon hydrogen. Medium- and high-temperature nuclear reactors are more suitable for coupling with HTE due to the requirement of high-temperature steam input. Nonetheless, the use of lower temperatures is also possible. A preliminary analysis undertaken by EDF indicates that supplying the HTE process with low-temperature heat (c. 150- 200°C) from pressurized water reactors is technically feasible and provides benefits over water electrolysis.

The integration of an HTE based hydrogen plant to an NPP’s site is more complex compared to the LTE technology because the HTE process requires both heat and a power source. In addition to power lines, a heat connection between HPP and NPP via steam pipes is necessary. This makes potential partial off-site integration of an HTE hydrogen plant more complicated in comparison to LTE. Furthermore, an increase in the distance between HPP and NPP leads to a higher amount of heat loss. Another barrier to implementation is the low technology readiness level of HTE. This advanced electrolysis method is still in a developmental phase and has not yet been deployed at a commercial scale [8].

HTE can be achieved through solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOEC). This technology is described in the following section.

8.2.1 SOEC

SOEC is an emerging technology potentially offering high-efficiency operation, but it has yet to be demonstrated at a multi-MW scale.

To perform steam electrolysis, SOECs operate at high temperatures between 700 and 1000 °C. As a consequence, cold start times are much longer (typically 12 hours) compared to LTE technologies (1 hour for AEL, 30 seconds for PEMEL) [9]. SOECs achieve the highest electrical efficiency of all the

above-mentioned electrolyzer types. It ranges between 74-81 % (based on LHV) [8]. Due to stack degradation, electrical efficiency degrades over time. The efficiency loss of SOECs is estimated at around 2 % per 1000 operating hours, but it strongly varies depending on the mode of operation and other factors [9].

Unlike AEL or PEMEL, SOEC technology offers a unique possibility to be operated in reverse mode as a fuel cell. With the ability to convert electricity to hydrogen and hydrogen back to electricity, SOECs could provide balancing services to the grid.

Initiatives are currently underway to demonstrate nuclear-powered HTE. Prairie Island NPP (USA) is to pilot hydrogen production using steam and electricity from nuclear reactors. The SOEC electrolyzer system is scheduled to become operational in 2024 [11].

8.2.2 Summary and Comparison of Hydrogen production technologies.

The following tables summarize the different characteristics of water and steam electrolysis technologies to produce hydrogen.

Table 16: Pros and Cons of Water and Steam Electrolysis

Water Electrolysis	Steam Electrolysis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mature technology • Commercially available • High purity hydrogen • Modular • Flexible operation • Can be powered by all nuclear reactor types 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High efficiency than LTE • Potentially lower hydrogen production costs than LTE • Modular • SOECs can operate in reverse mode to produce electricity from hydrogen
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher hydrogen production costs than SMR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not commercial • In development phase • Higher CAPEX than LTE • Slow response time

Table 17: Overview of key parameters of electrolyzer technologies. Data sources: [8] [9] [12]

Parameter	Unit	Water electrolysis		Steam electrolysis
		Alkaline	PEM	SOEC
Electrical efficiency (LHV)	%	63-70	56-60	74-81
Operating temperature	°C	60-80	50-80	650-1 000
Operating pressure	bar	1-30	30-80	1
Lifetime/ Operating hours	Thous. hrs	60-90	30-90	10-30
Efficiency degradation rate	%/1000 hrs	0,12	0,19	1,9
Cold start up time	sec	3 600	30	12 (hrs)
Footprint/Space requirements	m ² /MW	100	50	150
Technology readiness level	scale 1-9	9	7-8	5-7

8.3 Nuclear power plants

Section 6 of D1.1 provides an assessment of nuclear power reactor suitability and advantageous factors.

It has been agreed in the meeting of September 2023 that the project will evaluate only reactors in operation. Advanced reactors and new designs are subject of other projects funded by the European Union.

8.3.1 Assessment of reactors in operation.

As of February 2023, 180 NPPs were in operation in Europe, with a total electrical capacity of 152 GW, and eight power reactors were under construction. As mentioned in D1.1, several types of NPPs have been deployed in the last decades; however, in Europe, power reactors in operation are generally categorized as Pressurized Water Reactors (PWR) and Boiling Water Reactors (BWR). (There are Advanced Gas-cooled Reactors (AGR) operating in the UK and 2 CANDU reactors in Romania.)

The coupling between an HPP and an NPP could significantly increase the system's flexibility by producing hydrogen during low-demanding periods. This would allow for maintaining the reactor's nominal power, resulting in high fuel burnup and lower maintenance costs and a more cost-efficient operation. However, power plants in operation were not designed to be coupled with an HPP; consequently, several challenges can be expected regarding regulatory barriers, safety, and other technical subjects. With the existing NPPs, Low-Temperature Electrolysis is one of the most promising hydrogen production technologies, as the electric transmission is sufficient to be the only connection between the two facilities. (Auxiliary resources can still be an option to be shared to reduce cost, but it is not a necessity.) In this way, the hydrogen plant could be sited more freely, even outside of the safety zone of the NPP, which could help to overcome regulatory or safety limitations, as stated in section 6.1 of D1.1. In an INL report issued in 2019 [13], a techno-economic analysis is done for the viability of retrofitting existing PWRs with High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE). Such a system would require a deeper integration, as heat needed to be transferred to the HPP, resulting in a more challenging coupling with significantly reduced hydrogen production costs.

8.3.2 Assessment of new advanced reactors

New generations of NPPs are being developed to address the challenges and limitations of current nuclear reactor technologies. These reactors are designed to be more efficient, expand the current nuclear fuel reserves, and increased safety margins compared to existing NPPs. In many cases, higher operation temperatures are planned with improved efficiency and with the direct utilization of the process heat for various applications, including water desalination, providing industrial steam, or hydrogen production. The coupling is planned during the design phase and will be realized as a closely connected system with the reactor and a thermochemical water-splitting process or a high-temperature steam electrolyzer.

The close coupling, the increased safety requirements, the limited experience with the new technologies, and the high operating temperatures present extensive logistical, regulatory and development challenges. Therefore, there is significant international interest in further developing advanced nuclear reactors to address these many challenges.

8.3.3 The flexibility of the Gen IV reactors

Generation IV reactors are expected to be more flexible compared to the currently available technologies. A position paper, Ref. [65], was created to investigate the effect of the increasing share of renewable energy sources on the deployment of Gen IV reactors. This paper summarizes the different kinds of flexibility potentials and development needs of the introduced six advanced reactor concepts. Developers are considering flexible operation during the design phase to reduce thermal fluctuations and optimize operating conditions. The fast neutron spectra will decrease the effect of xenon poisoning, which could increase the load-following capabilities of the power plant. Furthermore, Gen IV systems are more suitable for cogeneration as higher outlet temperatures are expected. The increased temperatures raise the possibilities of process heat applications, and it could also result in high efficiencies with new thermochemical hydrogen production technologies.

9 Definition of scenarios: Interfaces and levels of integration

In D2.1 the possible needs of the HPP that can be supplied by the NPP are defined. In D1.2 the different feasible scenarios **from a technical point of view**, that are considered in the NPHyCo project, are described. This section is based on both inputs to establish the basis for the licensing analysis.

9.1 Description of interfaces

There are several potential interfaces between the NPP and the HPP. The most feasible ones are electricity supply and steam supply (for steam electrolysis technologies). Nevertheless, all the potential interfaces are briefly described here.

9.1.1 Electricity supply

The HPP is considered to be connected to the NPP grid and its complete consumption is covered by the NPP production. The electrical supply can be divided into a DC supply necessary for electrolysis and AC supply necessary for equipment. It is approximately estimated 93% DC consumption and 7% AC consumption.

The electrolyzers usually present three states:

- **Production:** In this state, the input power to the water electrolysis system ranges from minimum partial operation (typically 10% of electrolyser’s rated power) to full load operation.

- Standby: In this state there is no hydrogen production, but electricity consumption is required to maintain a specific temperature and pressure within the electrolyser. Returning to a production state requires energy consumption but takes only a couple of seconds.
- Idle: In this state the electrolyser is turned off, that is, it is depressurized and cold. In this state, only low power consumption from control units and anti-freezing systems (if applicable given the location of the plant) is required; this consumption is much lower than needed to keep the system in standby.

During the NPP outages, it is expected to have the electrolyser in idle state and a small energy consumption is required. This energy must be provided from a non-interrupted source or from the external grid.

The power supply can be connected to the NPP side of the unit's transformer or to the high voltage side of the transformer. The decision will depend on the HPP size. The connection to the NPP transformer side will be limited to the availability and dimension of the internal network of each NPP. Some studies [14] consider an upper limit for supply from the NPP side of the transformer of around 6% of nominal power of the NPP. This criterion establishes a first determining factor on the size of the eventual HPP plant.

Electrolysis plants with a single digit capacity are usually connected to the mid-voltage grid (20-30kV), a 100MW plant would be usually connected to the high-voltage grid (110kV) and electrolysis plants with capacities of 1GW are connected to the transport grid (380kV) [TEC2]. Besides, hydrogen compressors will need a 6kV voltage level and the rest of the equipment will run on 400V.

In case there are not enough spare connection points in the LV and/or MV grid available, the electricity may come as well from the 110kV grid. Respectively needed additional transformers will be integrated in the planning accordingly.

FIG. 4. Electrical connections to two substations.

Figure 16: Electric grid reliability and interface with NPP [15]

9.1.2 Steam supply

In case high-temperature steam electrolysis (SOEC/HTE) is considered, the steam supply is diverted from the NPP to the HTE process.

HTE has an operating range of 600-850°C and uses electricity and heat to produce hydrogen. Electrolysis efficiency increases at higher operating temperatures, requiring less electrical energy. This increased efficiency can lower production costs because the thermal energy required is generally less expensive than electrical energy .

As a general description, thermal power is utilized to preheat feedstocks or de-ionized water for the HTE unit via intermediate heat exchangers. Some of the designs consider using steam from NPPs to evaporate (which is the largest energy expenditure) the demineralized water from hydrolysis through several heat exchangers, and then in a second stage to electrically superheat the steam to HTE conditions.

Various iterations of designs for thermal power extraction are being studied. Figure 17 includes heat removal from the main steam line and returning the condensate to the condenser. Other design options, as shown in Figure 18, include removing part of the steam after the high-pressure turbine and returning the condensate to the condenser. This configuration uses steam instead of hot oil to transfer heat from the NPP.

In case the design modification derived from heat removal is performed, it will lead the NPP to readjust the turbine control system and it will likely imply a readjustment also of the turbogenerator mechanical parameters. If the extraction is performed in the High Pressure (HP) turbine outlet, for the same flow at the HP turbine inlet, it would exist a lower flow at the low pressure (LP) turbine inlet.

Figure 17: Overview of HTSE integrated with an NPP. Main steam extraction and returning to condenser [TEC4]

Figure 18: Overview of HTSE integrated with an NPP. Heat removal from high pressure turbine outlet and returning to condenser.

The optimal configuration will be established depending on the NPP requirements and recommendations done by previous studies. Regarding integration level effects, if steam supply is provided by the NPP, both plants coupling is considered as full integration scenario.

9.1.3 Demineralized water supply

The water electrolysis is the process in which the water molecule is split into oxygen and hydrogen. This process requires a treated water supply.

NPP demineralized water system produces, stores and supplies high purity water to the nuclear plant for makeup to various systems. In order to obtain the demineralized water, the system has ionic exchanger sets (cationic, anionic and mixed) that transform the water obtained from the pre-treatment plant into demineralized water.

9.1.4 Chilled water supply

The NPP chilled water system supplies cold water (7°C) to the different cooling coils of the air conditioning and ventilation units' non-safety related during NPP normal operation. The evacuated thermal load is transferred to the final heat sink by means of the non-essential services water system.

In order to evaluate if this system is able to cover HPP demand, some aspects should be considered as: the amount of flow that could be available, the conditions of the water supply and if there is any tie-in point already available.

9.1.5 Cooling water supply

A supply of cooling water would be required for the removal of HPP process heat, which is mainly dissipated within the electrolyser stack and its process water circuit.

The NPP water circulating system's function is to supply the condenser with the amount of cooling water necessary to evacuate the maximum thermal load produced by the condensation of the main turbine exhaust steam and to maintain the vacuum on the steam side. The water circulating system acts as a heat sink of the secondary side of the plant and it transfers the heat to the cold sink .

In order to evaluate if the selected system is able to cover HPP demand, some aspects should be considered, such as: the amount of flow that could be available, the conditions of the water supply and if there is any tie-in point already available.

9.1.6 Nitrogen supply

In the NPP the nitrogen is required to pressurize tanks or other equipment, to provide inert atmosphere if necessary and to actuate as working fluid during gas entrainment.

The NPP's N₂ system keeps the pressure in the accumulators of the safety injection (SI) system within the specified values . Besides, the N₂ supply system provides a non-corrosive atmosphere to the tanks that contain demineralized water and to some equipment that requires it during a prolonged downtime. The N₂ supply system has no functions related to the safe plant shutdown, so this system is not considered as safety system.

In the full integration scenario, the NPP's N₂ supply system completely covers the N₂ requirements of the HPP plant.

On the other hand a separate gas-bottle station dedicated to the HPP may be a good choice. The cost of the piping connection to the existing bottle station may be unreasonably high depending on the location of the HPP.

9.1.7 Pressurized air supply

In the full integration scenario, the pressurized air supply required for the HPP may be completely covered by the pressurized air supply system of the NPP. The HPP pressurized air supply requirements are 5 to 10 bars.

In the NPP's pressurized air is required for performing the actuation of instrumentation, controls, and various pneumatic equipment drives. The pressurized air for the instrumentation must have certain properties to prevent corrosion and general degradation of the control elements.

The use of pressurized air in the HPP has the same purposes. So, it can be assumed that the quality of the available air is sufficient. Thus, to determine the level of integration in terms of pressurized air supply only the availability and storage capacity should be analysed.

9.1.8 Wastewater treatment

The electrolyser can generate effluents, for example filters unblocking or cooling towers purge. These effluents must be collected and treated or disposed of by another downstream system.

In the full integration scenario, it has been considered that the effluents generated by the HPP are completely treated by the NPP liquid waste system.

The main function of the NPP's liquid wastewater system is to collect the liquid waste from several building and areas of the NPP, to monitor the effluents radioactive level, to separate and store the oilseed products and to treat the non-radioactive effluents until environmentally acceptable limits are reached.

To evaluate if the HPP effluents can be integrated with the NPP liquid wastewater system, some aspects should be considered, such as: the characteristics of the NPP's liquid wastewater system (pH, conductivity, etc.) and the availability of a discharge point.

9.1.9 H₂ and O₂ internal consumption

After performing the water electrolysis process, oxygen and hydrogen are obtained as products.

The full integration scenario considers the NPP's internal consumption of these gases, however, a complete production consumption is not required. Depending on the NPP's strategy the amount of hydrogen or oxygen produced could be higher than the internal NPP necessities.

The demonstrative hydrogen projects as Nine Mile Point are covering the on-site hydrogen demand to help cool the power plant by means of a 1,25MW LTE. Some of the hydrogen applications in the NPPs are: supply to the tank of the volume control system, supply to the reactor coolant drain tank and supply to the gaseous waste treatment system.

The oxygen in the NPP is used in the following situations: in the catalytic recombinants of the gaseous waste treatment system and in the N₂ and O₂ water pre-treatment system.

9.2 Description of integration levels

The levels of integration are defined in NPHyCo Deliverable 1.2 and summarized in the following figures.

Figure 19: Full integration scenario

Figure 20: Partial integration scenario (on-site)

Figure 21: Partial integration scenario (off site)

Figure 22: Zero integration scenario (off site)

9.3 Description of scenarios

In D1.2, 9 scenarios are pre-selected to be analysed for any NPP site in discussion:

Onsite Solutions

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at normal price (grid)
2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at reduced price (home need)
3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only normal price
4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only reduced price

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at normal price (grid)

6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at reduced price (home need)
7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at normal price
8. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at reduced price
9. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark i.e. normal price (grid)

One of the variables of the scenarios is the electricity price, depending on whether the electricity is obtained from the grid (normal price) or as an internal consumption of the NPP (reduced price). For the licensing analysis it is better to present the scenarios considering the design modifications needed. Taking this into account, the scenarios number 7 and 9 are identical, and the definition of the scenarios is as follows:

Onsite Solutions

17. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
18. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
19. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
20. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

21. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
22. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
23. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
24. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)

10 Operating conditions based on hydrogen production strategy

Apart from the technical level of integration, there are as well different modes of operation possible that need to be analysed due to their impact on design, license and cost of installation and operation.

10.1 Continuous production

In this operational scenario the HPP is producing hydrogen at the designed capacity in a continuous way. This is possible in case the operator of the NPP is dedicating a certain amount of electricity and other resources permanently to the production of hydrogen. In this case the HPP is a constant additional consumer within the NPP surroundings and the production of hydrogen at a certain rate needs to be integrated in the operational licences of the NPP.

The HPP starts and stops with the NPP or it requires external sources of supply (electricity and other supplies depending on the integration level) when the NPP is in outage or produces less electricity than the amount required by the HPP.

10.2 Production based on opportunity prices

As market prices for electricity are constantly changing the operator may prefer an operational model in which the production of hydrogen varies between no production and full capacity with respect to the achievable revenue. This operational mode involves frequent starts and stops of the HPP, possibly several times a day. Frequent starts and stops result in higher fatigue effects and need to be considered in the design of the plant. Depending on the level of integration of the HPP into NPP systems, such frequent starts and stops may have an impact on the NPP as well.

10.3 Production based on grid balancing services.

Other strategy to be considered by the operator is to participate in electricity markets that provide balancing services to the grid. In this case the electricity supplied to the grid should change with a required ramp to follow the demand curve.

For this reason, the HPP as a load of the NPP should be working at around 50% of its capacity to be able to increase or decrease its electricity consumption when required by the electricity market.

10.4 Operating conditions cases

The following tables summarize the different operating conditions cases considering the level of integration, the hydrogen production strategy and the HPP technology.

10.4.1 Integration with electricity and additional systems (scenarios 1 to 6) and NPP at 100% nominal Power

Table 18: operating conditions cases for integration scenarios 1 to 6 with NPP at 100% nominal Power.

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
1aa	NPP > 100% HPP	100%	Continuous production for several days/weeks and predictable	<p>Note 1aa_a: In all H2 production methods, it implies new power transformers that can be upstream or downstream of the NPP Generator transformer, depending on the size of the HPP.</p> <p>Note 1aa_b: Any Integrated systems will be treated as a Design Modification of the NPP, as the original design of the NPP is modified to provide supplies (cold water, steam, etc.) to the HPP. The following situations may occur:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Changes in the operating conditions of the integrated system (for example cooling water return temperature due to the inclusion of new hot components) without requiring alignment changes. In this case, it must be verified that the new conditions comply with the Performance Technical Specification (PTS) of the NPP. b) Alignment changes (for example, starting an additional pump) to support the new consumption and flows. In this case, compliance with the PTS and required backup equipment must be verified. c) New components in the NPP system (new pumps, for example). 		<p>Note 1aa_c: In the case of SOEC technology a new operating point for turbines and its power control would be implied. This can affect also the maintenance plan and lifetime of the turbine. Steam extractions can influence primary circuit temperature and turbine control.</p>

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
1ab		0 OR 100%	Production based on opportunity prices. (> 1 hour predictable) Several start/stop cycles of HPP are possible in the same day.	See Note 1aa_a. See Note 1aa_b. Due to the variable demand of the HPP it would be required to: a) review the control loops of integrated systems b) update maintenance plans and expected lifetime of equipment affected		See Note 1aa_c. Lifetime of turbines could be affected by the frequent change of the operating point.
1ac		variable around 50%	Production based on Grid regulation. Not predictable, demand based.	See Note 1aa_a. See Note 1aa_b. Due to the variable demand of the HPP it would be required to: a) review the control loops of integrated systems b) update maintenance plans and expected lifetime of equipment affected		This option may not be possible since SOEC could not achieve the ramps required in regulation mode. See Note 1aa_c. Lifetime of turbines could be affected by the frequent change of the operating point.
1b		standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in a short time.	See Note 1aa_a. See Note 1aa_b. It is necessary to have preheated systems and to pressurize them. It requires some consumption of the NPP's integrated systems.	Not always necessary or with low impact. Ready to produce times are different for	Steam consumption is always necessary to preheat pipes and set level in process steam generator.

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
					PEM (quicker) and AEL.	
1c		idle	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the mid time.	See Note 1aa_a. See Note 1aa_b.		

10.4.2 Integration with electricity and additional systems (scenarios 1 to 6) and NPP at Power lower than HPP demand.

Table 19: operating conditions cases for integration scenarios 1 to 6 with NPP at Power lower than HPP demand.

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
2aa	NPP = 0% (refueling outage or any shutdown)	100%	Continuous production for several days/weeks and predictable	In this situation it is not possible for full integration to provide the consumptions for the HPP, unless there are alternative sources of supply available.		

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
2ab	operation mode) or < HPP.	0 OR 100%	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.			
2ac		variable around 50%	Production based on Grid regulation. Not predictable, demand based.			
2b		hot standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.			
2c		cold standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.		Cold standby operating mode of the HPP is required to maintain HPP integrity while waiting for NPP availability. Very reduced consumption.	

10.4.3 Integration with electricity only (scenario 7) and NPP at 100% nominal Power

Table 20: operating conditions cases for integration scenario 7 with NPP at 100% nominal Power.

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
3aa	NPP > 100% HPP	100%	Continuous production for several days/weeks and predictable	<p>Note 3aa_a: In all H2 production methods, it implies new power transformers that can be upstream or downstream of the NPP Generator transformer, depending on the size of the HPP (INL mentions that upstream would be limited to power around 6% of the NPP Unit).</p>		Note 3aa_b: Not possible without steam from other sources.
3ab		0 OR 100%	Production based on opportunity prices. (> 1 hour predictable) Several start/stop of HPP is possible in the same day.			See Note 3aa_b.
3ac		variable around 50%	Production based on Grid regulation. Not predictable, demand based.			See Note 3aa_b. This option may not be possible since SOEC could not achieve the ramps required in regulation mode.
3b		hot standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.			See Note 3aa_b.
3c		cold standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hours.			See Note 3aa_b.

10.4.4 Integration with electricity only (scenario 7) and NPP at Power lower than HPP demand.

Table 21: operating conditions cases for integration scenario 7 with NPP at Power lower than HPP demand.

Case	Operating condition NPP (% nominal power)	Operating condition HPP (% of nominal HPP)	Hydrogen production strategy	Generic comments	LTE specific comments	HTE specific comments
4aa	NPP = 0% (refueling outage or any shutdown operation mode) or < HPP.	100%	Continuous production for several days/weeks and predictable	In this situation it is not possible to provide the consumptions for the HPP, unless there are alternative sources of supply available.		
4ab		0 OR 100%	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.			
4ac		variable around 50%	Production based on Grid regulation. Not predictable, demand based.			
4b		hot standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hour.			
4c		cold standby	Opportunity production. Ready to produce in the next hours.		Cold standby operating mode of the HPP is required to maintain HPP integrity while waiting for NPP availability. Very reduced consumption.	

11 Transport and storage scenarios.

For the licensing analysis, it is also important to consider how the hydrogen will be delivered to the consumers. Hydrogen should be transported to the final consumer. This consumer, in general, will be far from the NPP facility and hydrogen should be delivered by gas pipelines or stored in tanks and transported in trucks.

The different cases are described in the table below.

Table 22: transport and storage scenarios

Case	Consumer proximity	Gas pipelines system in the proximity of the NPP	Transport media	comments
TS-1	Internal consumer (the NPP)	No transport required.		
TS-2	Far consumer	Yes	Gas pipelines	No big storage required
TS-3	Far consumer	No	Trucks	Risk associated with storage at high pressure for truck transport. The proximity of the HPP to the NPP (onsite or offsite) should be considered.

Annex 2: Full Report of Subtask 2 – Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP

Deliverable 4.2 subtask 2

Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP.

Consideration of Rivne NPP systems integration.

Licensing Impact due to NPP-system modifications for HPP-NPP integration

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ESG

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Revisions

IND REV	RELEASE DATE	PARAGRAPH	SCOPE OF THE REVISION
1.A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue, reviewed by GRS & NRG

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEM	Anion Exchange Membrane
ACS	Air Compressor Station
ARC	Reactor control assembly
DW	Demineralized water
EC	European Committee
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EN	European Norm
EU	European Union
GR	Group Risk
GRIP	Coordinated Regional Incident Response Procedures
HOR	Higher Education Reactor (Hoger Onderwijs Reactor)
HPC	High-pressure cylinder
HPH	High-pressure heaters
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICRP	International Committee on Radiological Protection
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IED	Industrial Emissions Directive
IPPC	Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
Kew	Nuclear Energy Act (Kernenergiewet)
LPC	Low-pressure cylinder
LPH	Low -pressure heaters
NAEK	National Atom Energy Company
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
RCP	Reactor coolant pumps
RNPP	Rivne NPP
SFP	Spent Fuel Pool
SG	Steam Generator
VVER	Water Power Reactor

12 Determination of approximate parameters of modifications.

Table 23 presents possible scenarios for the location of the HPP and the conditions for supplying it with NPP resources. The list of scenarios is defined earlier at the project conceptualization stage. The main division of the scenarios is the location of the HPP site relative to the NPP site. The HPP can be located inside the NPP perimeter or outside of it. Specific HPP site plans for two Ukrainian NPPs are analyzed at the conceptualization stage (task 1.2). In addition, the scenarios differ in the possibility of providing various resources from nuclear power plants, as well as in the possible economic conditions for the provision of these resources. The table defines unique numbers of possible conditions for the use of each resource for each accepted scenario. These numbers are used further to assess the applicability conditions and analyze the need for modifications to the relevant NPP systems.

Table 23: Conditions for the use of NPP for an HPP.

	Scenario #								
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
	Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at normal price (grid)	Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at reduced price (home need)	Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only normal price	Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only reduced price	Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at normal price (grid)	Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at reduced price (home need)	Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at normal price	Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at reduced price	Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark i.e. normal price (grid)

AL: N
ECCN: N

Resource									
Electrical Power (HV, MV, LV)	1.E	2.E	3.E	4.E	5.E	6.E	7.E	8.E	9.E
Demineralized Water Supply	1.D	2.D	3.D	4.D	5.D	6.D	7.D	8.D	9.D
Tap Water Supply	1.T	2.T	3.T	4.T	5.T	6.T	7.T	8.T	9.T
Steam	1.S	2.S	3.S	4.S	5.S	6.S	7.S	8.S	9.S
Cooling Water	1.C	2.C	3.C	4.C	5.C	6.C	7.C	8.C	9.C
Chilled Water Supply System	1.H	2.H	3.H	4.H	5.H	6.H	7.H	8.H	9.H
Waste Water System	1.W	2.W	3.W	4.W	5.W	6.W	7.W	8.W	9.W
Instrumentation Air Supply System	1.A	2.A	3.A	4.A	5.A	6.A	7.A	8.A	9.A
Nitrogen Supply System	1.N	2.N	3.N	4.N	5.N	6.N	7.N	8.N	9.N

ECCN: N

AL: N

Table 24 provides a description of the use of each resource for the needs of the HPP in each deployment scenario. It also provides an assessment of the need to modify the relevant NPP systems for each scenario. The numbers reflect the deployment scenario and resource, according to the encoding shown in Table 23.

Table 24: Estimation of the need to modify NPP systems depending on the scenario of the location of the HPP.

	Description of the use of NPP systems for HPP	The need to modify of NPP systems
Scenario 1 Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at normal price (grid)		
1.E	<p>The NPP does not have a transformer with an output voltage of 20 kV. The modification should include the installation of such a transformer with an output power of at least 40 MW, as well as a rectifier. However, a power line must be drawn to the NPP site to connect the HPP equipment.</p> <p>A power line with a voltage of 6 kV from the external network must also be fed to the HPP inside the NPP site. A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (normal buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load should be justified. It is advisable to install the rectifier inside the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (output voltage 0.4kV) to control the HPP equipment and valves.</p> <p>Modification is required - inside the NPP, a design for laying electrical cables through the territory of the NPP to the HPP site and a design for installing and connecting a rectifier. A design for installing an additional transformer (determination of locations and justification of the impact on NPP safety) and a design for connecting an additional load to the normal 6kV buses . Outside the NPP site the design of a substation with transformers connected to the grid is necessary.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
1.D	<p>NPPs produce demineralized water with sufficient capacity. However, the water parameters do not correspond to the quality required for the HPP.</p> <p>System modification is required - after-treatment water system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for post-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h - (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). It is preferable to place such an installation near the NPP's system to produce DW.</p> <p>For the needs of HPPs, it is expedient to use the power supply for own needs buses and other internal resources of nuclear power plants with the allocation of costs to the hydrogen production.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
1.T	<p>The NPP has a tap water distribution system. To supply such water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, a modification of the system is necessary.</p> <p>A modification of the NPP tap water supply system is required - a design to expand the pipeline network and equipment for supplying HPP</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>premises with tap water and a sewer system connected to similar existing NPP systems.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, the internal resources of the NPP should be used with attribution of costs to the cost of hydrogen production.</p>	
1.S	<p>During the operation of the nuclear power plant, steam is generated with maximum parameters of 280 °C and 64 kg/cm². For the NPP's own needs, there is a special manifold, where steam parameters are maintained at no more than 190 °C and 12 kg/cm². Steam extraction at the HPP is potentially possible only from the auxiliary collector. The auxiliary collector is distributed throughout the NPP site for different consumers. It is also possible to supply steam to the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required, if it is expedient to use steam - a design for supplying steam to the premises and equipment of the HPP, condensing steam and draining condensate. Technically, the problem can be solved for this scenario.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, only NPP resources are used with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production.</p>	In case of use - modification of NPP systems is required
1.C	<p>Nuclear power plants use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable VC20 system is the process water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the HPP pond and after the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. Maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, pressure is 44-54 bar.</p> <p>Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units.</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of a part of the water from the pressure part of the system. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the reservoir without cooling due to environmental restrictions. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the power supply for own needs and other internal resources of nuclear power plants with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, their power supply from an external substation providing the HPP can be used.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
1.H	<p>NPP air conditioners and chilled water cannot be used in the HPP cycle. Reasons for inexpediency of using NPP equipment for supplying HPP - insufficient chilled water parameters, lack of NPP chilled water capacity reserve, technically difficult to perform modification of this equipment, significant losses of parameters during transportation from the source to HPP.</p> <p>No modifications required.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
1.W	<p>The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Economic sewerage has a developed system at nuclear power plants. Liquid non-radioactive waste (except for oil products) can be discharged from the HPP into the NPP sewerage system. A waste disposal system containing</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N
ECCN: N

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>oil products is also available at the NPP. Solid waste disposal is carried out in containers.</p> <p>Modification is required - the design of pipelines for connecting the sewerage system of the HPP with a similar system of the NPP. A pump shall be provided to supply waste from ladders and drains to the system for disposal by the relevant NPP systems. If it is necessary to discharge oil products, an appropriate similar line can be made or their collection and removal in portable containers (barrels) can be organized. The solid waste disposal system should be integrated into the existing NPP system and does not require significant modifications.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the internal resources of the NPP with attribution of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. Alternatively, electricity for one or several additional waste water pumps can be used from an external substation providing the HPP.</p>	
1.A	<p>NPPs have several compressed air supply systems. One of them is a safety system that does not have significant reserves for permanent operation. The other is a regular station-wide compressed air system and is fed by a station-wide air compressor with a pressure of 5.5-6.0 kg/cm². However, especially during the repair of the power unit, the air pressure is significantly reduced. The system does not have enough reserve to maintain constant parameters to supply the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design for the installation of an additional air compressor station for the needs of the HPP on the territory of the HPP site. The use of pipelines of the existing NPP compressed air system is not applicable due to possible pressure changes in this network.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, power supply for own needs and other internal resources of the NPP can be used with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. Alternatively, electricity for one or several additional air compressors can be used from an external substation providing the HPP.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
1.N	<p>The NPP has a nitrogen-oxygen station for its own needs. The design capacity of the NPP nitrogen station is sufficient for the supply of the HPP with nitrogen. In principle, it is possible to use the nitrogen station of the NPP for the needs of the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design to install an additional nitrogen station with a separate pipeline to the HPP equipment. It is advisable to combine such a station with a compressor station in terms of ease of equipment maintenance. An alternative is to supply the HPP with nitrogen from cylinders.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, the power supply for own needs and other internal resources of the NPP can be used with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. Alternatively, electricity for a nitrogen station can be used from an external substation providing the HPP.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
Scenario 2 Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at reduced price (home need)		
2.E	<p>The NPP does not have a transformer with an output voltage of 20 kV. The modification should include the installation of such a transformer with an output power of at least 40 MW, as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (normal buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load should be justified. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (output voltage 0.4kV) to control the HPP equipment and valves.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determination of locations and justification of the impact on NPP safety) and a design for connecting an additional load to the normal 6kV buses .</p>	
2.D	<p>NPPs produce demineralized water with sufficient capacity. However, the water parameters do not correspond to the quality required for HPP.</p> <p>System modification is required - after-treatment water system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for post-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). It is preferable to place such an installation near the NPP's system to produce DW. It is expedient to use the internal resources of the NPP in the installation of additional water treatment for the needs of the HPP, with the allocation of costs to the hydrogen production cost.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
2.T	<p>The NPP has a tap water distribution system. To supply such water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, a modification of the system is necessary.</p> <p>A modification of the NPP tap water supply system is required - a design to expand the pipeline network and equipment for supplying HPP premises with tap water and a sewer system connected to similar existing NPP systems.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it should use the internal resources of the NPP with attribution of costs to the cost of hydrogen production.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
2.S	<p>During the operation of the NPP, steam is generated with maximum parameters of 280 °C and 64 kg/cm². For the NPP's own needs, there is a special manifold, where steam parameters are maintained at no more than 190 °C and 12 kg/cm². Steam extraction at the HPP is potentially possible only from the auxiliary collector. The auxiliary collector is distributed throughout the NPP site for different consumers. It is also possible to supply steam to the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required, if it is expedient to use steam - a design for supplying steam to the premises and equipment of the HPP, condensing steam and draining condensate. Technically, the problem can be solved for this scenario.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, only NPP resources are used with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production.</p>	In case of use - modification of NPP systems is required
2.C	<p>NPPs use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable system is the process water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the NPP pond and after the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. The maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, the pressure is 44-54 bar.</p> <p>Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N
ECCN: N

	<p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of a part of the water from the pressure part of the system. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the reservoir without cooling due to environmental restrictions. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the power supply for own needs and other internal resources of NPPs with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, their power supply from an external substation providing the HPP can be used.</p>	
2.H	<p>NPP air conditioners and chilled water cannot be used in the HPP cycle. Reasons for inexpediency of using NPP equipment for supplying HPP - insufficient chilled water parameters, lack of NPP chilled water capacity reserve, technically difficult to perform modification of this equipment, significant losses of parameters during transportation from the source to HPP.</p> <p>No modifications required.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
2.W	<p>The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Economic sewerage has a developed system at NPPs. Liquid non-radioactive waste (except for oil products) can be received from the HPP into the NPP sewerage system. A waste disposal system containing oil products is also available at the NPP. Solid waste disposal is carried out in containers.</p> <p>Modification is required - the design of pipelines for connecting the sewerage system of the HPP with a similar system of the NPP. A pump shall be provided to supply waste from ladders and drains to the system for disposal by the relevant NPP systems. If it is necessary to discharge oil products, an appropriate similar line can be made or their collection and removal in portable containers (barrels) can be organized. The solid waste disposal system should be integrated into the existing NPP system and does not require significant modifications.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the internal resources of the NPP with attribution of costs to the hydrogen production cost. Electricity for one or several additional waste water pumps is also used from the normal buses.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
2.A	<p>NPPs have several compressed air supply systems. One of them is a safety system that does not have significant reserves for permanent operation. The other is a regular station-wide compressed air system and is fed by a station-wide compressor. However, especially during the repair of the power unit, the air pressure is significantly reduced. The system does not have enough reserve to maintain constant parameters to supply the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design for the installation of an additional (separate) compressor station for the needs of the HPP on the territory of the HPP site. The use of pipelines of the existing NPP compressed air system is impractical due to possible pressure changes in this network.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

	For the needs of the HPP, electricity supply from the auxiliary buses of the NPP and other internal NPP resources can be used with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production.	
2.N	<p>The NPP has a nitrogen-oxygen station for its own needs. In principle, it is possible to use the nitrogen station of the NPP for the needs of the HPP.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design to install an additional nitrogen station with a separate pipeline to the HPP equipment. It is advisable to combine such a station with an air compressor station in terms of ease of equipment maintenance. An alternative is to supply the HPP with nitrogen from cylinders.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
Scenario 3 Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only normal price		
3.E	<p>The NPP does not have a transformer with an output voltage of 20 kV. The modification should include the installation of such a transformer with an output power of at least 40 MW, as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear.</p> <p>A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (common normal plant buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load should be justified. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (output voltage 0.4kV) to control the HPP equipment and valves.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determination of locations and justification of the impact on NPP safety) and a design for connecting an additional load to the buses of the general plant 6kV buses .</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
3.D	<p>Modification only in terms of the use of space at NPPs. Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the perimeter of the HPP (on the territory of the NPP site). It should be designed for DW purification to the quality required by HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment deployment at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system.</p> <p>The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Power supply of the installation from the common normal plant buses of the NPP, however, at a normal price. In this case, justification is required for connecting additional loads to the normal buses.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
3.T	<p>Modification only in terms of the use of space at NPPs. Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, valves, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment deployment at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair.</p> <p>The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Power supply of the installation from the plant common normal buses</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required

AL: N ECCN: N

AL: N ECCN: N

	of the NPP, however, at a normal price. In this case, it will be necessary to justify the connection of additional loads to the NPP normal buses.	
3.S	Using steam of parameters required at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source. Steam source not available.	Not available
3.C	NPPs use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable system is the service water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the NPP pond and after the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. The maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m ³ /h, the pressure is 44-54 bar. Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the plant's system of one of the units. Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of a part of the water from the system. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the cooling pond without cooling due to environmental restrictions. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective. For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the internal resources of NPPs with attribution of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, the power supply from the plant normal buses is also used.	Modification of NPP systems required
3.H	NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional load to the plant normal buses.	Modification of NPP systems not required
3.W	The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. A modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste. If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
3.A	Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. A modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the territory of the HPP or use compressed air cylinders. For the HPP air compressor, electricity supply from the NPP normal buses can be used, however, at the normal price of electricity. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional loads to the plant normal buses. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
3.N	Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. A modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the territory of the HPP or use nitrogen cylinders. For the HPP nitrogen station, power supply from the auxiliary normal buses of the nuclear power plant can be used, however, at the normal	Modification of NPP systems not required

	price of electricity. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional loads to the auxiliary normal buses. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	
Scenario 4 Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only reduced price		
4.E	<p>The NPP does not have a transformer with an output voltage of 20 kV. The modification should include the installation of such a transformer with an output power of at least 40 MW, as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear.</p> <p>A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (common normal plant buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load should be justified. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (output voltage 0.4kV) to control the HPP equipment and valves.</p> <p>Modification is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determination of locations and justification of the impact on NPP safety) and a design for connecting an additional load to the buses of general plant buses 6kV.</p>	Modification of NPP systems required
4.D	<p>Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the perimeter of the HPP (on the territory of the NPP site). It should be designed for DW purification to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment deployment at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system.</p> <p>The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Power supply of the installation from the common normal plant buses of the NPP, however, at a reduced price, with the costs attributed to the cost of hydrogen production. In this case, justification is required for connecting additional loads to the normal buses.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
4.T	<p>Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, valves, tanks), a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment deployment at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair.</p> <p>The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Electricity supply of the installation from the plant common normal buses of the NPP, however, at a reduced price, with the costs attributed to the cost of hydrogen production. In this case, it will be necessary to justify the connection of additional loads to the NPP normal buses.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
4.S	<p>Using steam of parameters required at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source.</p> <p>Steam source is not available for this scenario.</p>	Not available
4.C	Nuclear power plants use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable system is the service water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the NPP pond and after	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N ECCN: N

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. The maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, the pressure is 44-54 bar. Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the plant's system of one of the units.</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of a part of the water from the system. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the cooling pond without cooling due to environmental restrictions. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, it is expedient to use the internal resources of NPPs with attribution of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed to the cooling towers, the power supply from the plant normal buses is also used at reduced prices.</p>	
4.H	NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional load to the plant normal buses.	Modification of NPP systems not required
4.W	The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste. If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
4.A	Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the territory of the HPP or use compressed air cylinders. For the HPP air compressor, the electricity supply from the NPP normal buses can be used, at the reduced price of electricity with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional loads to the plant normal buses. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
4.N	Modification only in terms of the use of space at the NPP site. Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the territory of the HPP or use nitrogen cylinders. For the HPP nitrogen station, power supply from the auxiliary normal buses of the NPP can be used, at the reduced price of electricity with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. In this case, modification is required in terms of justifying the connection of additional loads to the auxiliary normal buses. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
Scenario 5 Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at normal price (grid)		
5.E	Transformers with output voltage of 20kV and 6kV must be installed. The modification must include the installation of transformers with an	Do not defined. Depends on

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>output power of at least 40 MW (20 kV), as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with laying the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) to control the equipment and valves.</p> <p>In case of installation of electrical equipment at the NPP outdoor switchgear, modification of the electrical part of the NPP is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determining the location and justifying the impact on the safety of the NPP).</p>	connection scheme decision.
5.D	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the HPP (outside the territory of the NPP). It should be designed to treat DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h. The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system.</p> <p>The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at normal price. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
5.T	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, valves, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair.</p> <p>The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at reduced price. Electricity supply for own needs of HPP is also from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
5.S	<p>Using steam of parameters required at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source.</p> <p>Steam source is not available for this scenario.</p>	Not available
5.C	<p>NPPs use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable system is the service water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the NPP pond and after the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. The maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, the pressure is 44-54 bar. Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the plant's system of one of the units.</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of a part of the water from the NPP system. In addition, it is necessary to develop a design for the water supply of the HPP from NPPs, considering the laying of long pipelines (both NPP onsite and offsite parts). The distance from the NPP pump (VC20 system) to the</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N ECCN: N

	<p>HPP is more than 1 km. The heated water return pipeline from the HPP must also run along the supply pipeline to the NPP discharge channel. Considering the distance and the required flow rate, a booster pumping unit is expected to be required. The NPP pump (VC20 system) with this scheme will work as a booster pump. In this case, additional electricity will be required. The return of heated water is discharged into the NPP circulating water cooling system. During transportation to NPPs, heated water can be partially cooled by air. However, thermal insulation should be provided for the cold season (and possibly thermal satellites).</p> <p>If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, power from transformers is also used, according to 5.E.</p>	
5.H	<p>NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
5.W	<p>The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste. If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
5.A	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the HPP site or use compressed air cylinders. For the HPP compressor, electricity supply from a transformer (see 5.1) can be used, at a normal price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
5.N	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the HPP site or use nitrogen cylinders. For the HPP nitrogen station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 5.1) can be used at a normal price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
<p>Scenario 6 Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at reduced price (home need)</p>		
6.E	<p>Transformers with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV must be installed. The modification must include the installation of transformers with an output power of at least 40 MW (20 kV), as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with laying the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) to control the equipment and valves.</p> <p>In case of the installation of electrical equipment at the NPP outdoor switchgear, a modification of the electrical part of the NPP is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determining the location and justifying the impact on the safety of the NPP).</p>	Do not defined. Depends on connection scheme decision.

AL: N
ECCN: N

6.D	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the HPP (outside the territory of the NPP). It should be designed to treat DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h. The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system.</p> <p>The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at reduced price. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
6.T	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, valves, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair.</p> <p>The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at reduced price. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
6.S	<p>Using steam of required parameters at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source.</p> <p>Steam source is not available for this scenario.</p>	Not available
6.C	<p>NPPs use several different cooling water systems. For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable system is the service water of non-compliant consumers. Water is taken from the NPP pond and after the consumers have cooled down, it is discharged back into the pond. The Maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, the pressure is 44-54 bar. Each system cools the consumers of one power unit. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the plant's system of one of the units.</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of part of the water from the NPP system. In addition, it is necessary to develop a design for the water supply of the HPP from the NPP, considering the laying of long pipelines (both NPP onsite and offsite parts). The distance from the NPP pump (VC20 system) to the HPP is more than 1 km. The heated water return pipeline from the HPP must also run along the supply pipeline to the NPP discharge channel. Considering the distance and the required flow rate, a booster pumping unit is expected to be required. The NPP pump (VC20 system) with this scheme will work as a booster pump. In this case, additional electricity will be required. The return of heated water is discharged into the NPP circulating water cooling system. During transportation to the NPP, heated water can be partially cooled by air. However, thermal insulation should be provided for the cold season (and possibly thermal satellites).</p>	Modification of NPP systems required

AL: N
ECCN: N

	If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, power from transformers is also used, according to 5.E, at a reduced cost of electricity.	
6.H	NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design.	Modification of NPP systems not required
6.W	The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste. If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
6.A	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the HPP site or use compressed air cylinders. For the HPP compressor, electricity supply from a transformer (see 6.1) can be used, at a reduced price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
6.N	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the HPP site or use nitrogen cylinders. For the HPP nitrogen station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 6.1) can be used at a reduced price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	Modification of NPP systems not required
Scenario 7 Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at normal price		
7.E	Transformers with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV must be installed. The modification must include the installation of transformers with an output power of at least 40 MW (20 kV), as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with laying the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) to control the equipment and valves. In case of installation of electrical equipment at the NPP outdoor switchgear, modification of the electrical part of the NPP is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determining the location and justifying the impact on the safety of the NPP).	Do not defined. Depends on connection scheme decision.
7.D	Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the HPP (outside the territory of the NPP). It should be designed to treat DW to the quality required by HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h. The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system. The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks	Modification of NPP systems not required

AL: N ECCN: N

	(from a 6 kV transformer), at normal price. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.	
7.T	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, valves, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair.</p> <p>The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at normal price. Electricity supply for own needs of HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
7.S	<p>Using steam of required parameters at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source.</p> <p>Steam source is not available for this scenario.</p>	Not available
7.C	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required. An HPP cooling water design is required. A closed circulation system on the territory of the HPP with water supply (up to 900 t/h) by a pump (reserved) is preferred. Heated water should be cooled down to cooling units (preferably a cooling tower). The design should provide for a system make-up line to compensate for water carryover during convection. An Equipment and water cleaning system should also be provided. Recharging with water from the river will require additional approvals from environmental services and funding. It is possible either to build a pumping station with an appropriate make-up pipeline to the HPP (the choice of such a station requires additional research), or to supply water for the needs of the HPP by ground transportation, or to use groundwater in nearby areas (an additional analysis is required).</p> <p>If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, electricity supply from transformers is also used, according to 7.E.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
7.H	NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design.	Modification of NPP systems not required
7.W	<p>The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal.</p> <p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste.</p> <p>If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
7.A	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the HPP site or use compressed air cylinders.</p> <p>For the HPP compressor, electricity supply from a transformer (see 7.E) can be used, at a normal price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
7.N	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the HPP site or use nitrogen cylinders.	Modification of NPP systems not required

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	For the HPP nitrogen station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 7.E) can be used at a normal price of electricity. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.	
Scenario 8 Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at reduced price		
8.E	Transformers with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV must be installed. The modification must include the installation of transformers with an output power of at least 40 MW (20 kV), as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with laying the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) to control the equipment and valves. In case of installation of electrical equipment at the NPP outdoor switchgear, modification of the electrical part of the NPP is required - a design for installing an additional transformer (determining the location and justifying the impact on the safety of the NPP).	Do not defined. Depends on connection scheme decision.
8.D	Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous water treatment plant can be located inside the HPP (outside the territory of the NPP). It should be designed to treat DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h. The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, maintenance and repair of the system. The HPP water treatment plant uses only external resources, including logistics. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at a reduced price, including the costs for the cost of hydrogen production. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.	Modification of NPP systems not required
8.T	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required. The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, fittings, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair. The system uses only external resources for the needs of the HPP. Electricity supply of the plant from the NPP electrical networks (from a 6 kV transformer), at a reduced price, including the costs for the cost of hydrogen production. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.	Modification of NPP systems not required
8.S	Using steam of required parameters at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source. Steam source is not available for this scenario.	Not available
8.C	Modification of NPP systems is not required. An HPP cooling water design is required. A closed circulation system on the territory of the HPP with water supply (up to 900 t/h) by a pump (reserved) should be considered. Heated water should be cooling down to cooling units (preferably a cooling tower). The design should provide for a system	Modification of NPP systems not required

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	<p>make-up line to compensate for water carryover during convection. Equipment and water cleaning system should also be provided. Recharging with water from the river will require additional approvals from environmental services and funding. It is possible either to build a pumping station with an appropriate make-up pipeline to the HPP (the choice of such a station requires additional research), or to supply water for the needs of the HPP by ground transportation, or to use groundwater in nearby areas (an additional analysis is required).</p> <p>If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, electricity from transformers is also used, according to 8.E at a reduced price of electricity.</p>	
8.H	<p>NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of chilled water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
8.W	<p>The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste.</p> <p>If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
8.A	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the HPP site or use compressed air cylinders.</p> <p>For the HPP compressor, electricity supply from a transformer (see 8.E) can be used, at a reduced price of electricity with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
8.N	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the HPP site or use nitrogen cylinders.</p> <p>For the HPP nitrogen station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 8.E) can be used at a reduced price of electricity with the allocation of costs to the cost of hydrogen production. In case of use of cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
Scenario 9 Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark i.e. normal price (grid)		
9.E	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - within the framework of the HPP design, transformers with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV should be installed. The design provides for the installation of transformers with an output power of at least 40 MW (20 kV), as well as a rectifier. The proposed installation site is at a separate HPP substation (inside the site or near the HPP). This scenario will also require an additional transformer (with 0.4kV output voltage) to control the equipment and valves.</p> <p>For this scenario, the HPP has an electricity supply like any other consumer. In this case, there is no need to limit the distance to the NPP. HPP can be located considering other important factors (water, transport, electrical resources, high temperature steam, hydrogen consumers, etc.). Licensing issues may not be related to NPPs (simplified).</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required

AL: N ECCN: N

9.D	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - an autonomous demineralized water installation can be located HPP onsite (outside the territory of an NPP). It should be designed for purification of DW to the quality required by the HPP with a flow rate of up to 6 t/h - (electrical conductivity - 0.1 mS/sm, also requirements for other water parameters). The design should also include a system for supplying source water to the treatment plant (pumps, pipelines, valves), a system for supplying reagents and removing waste, and tanks. An area should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, maintenance, and repair of the system. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.</p> <p>The HPP water treatment plant uses only its own resources, including logistics. Electricity supply of the installation from an external electrical network (from a 6kV transformer), at a normal price. Electricity supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.T	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the supply of tap water to the premises and for the needs of the HPP, an autonomous system design is required.</p> <p>The design should include a system for supplying and preparing source water for internal economic use (pumps, pipelines, fittings, tanks), and a domestic sewerage system. Space should be provided for equipment placement at the HPP site, logistics, maintenance and repair. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.</p> <p>Power supply of the installation from an external electrical network (from a 6kV transformer), at a normal price. Power supply for own needs of the HPP is also provided from an additional 0.4kV transformer.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.S	<p>Using steam of desired parameters at the HPP can only be done if it is generated by an external source.</p> <p>An external high temperature steam source may be available for this scenario. It depends on the location of the HPP. NPP modifications are not required.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.C	<p>Modification of NPP systems is not required. An HPP cooling water design is required. A closed circulation system on the territory of the HPP with water supply (up to 900 t/h) by a pump (reserved) is expedient. Heated water should be vented to cooling units (preferably a cooling tower). The design should provide for a system make-up line to compensate for water carryover during convection. Systems of equipment and water cleaning should also be provided. Feeding water from a water source will require additional approvals from environmental services and funding. It is possible either to build a pumping station with an appropriate make-up pipeline to the HPP (the choice of such a station requires additional research), or to supply of water for the needs of the HPP by ground transportation, or to use groundwater in nearby areas (additional research is required). Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the water supply system of an object located nearby.</p>	Modification of NPP systems not required

	If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, electricity supply from transformers is also used, according to 9.E.	
9.H	NPP modifications are not required. It is necessary to develop a design for the supply of cold water to the HPP within the framework of the HPP design. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.W	The HPP waste disposal system should include domestic sewerage, oily and hazardous waste disposal, and solid waste disposal. Modification of NPP systems is not required - a stand-alone system design is required for the disposal of HPP waste. If it is necessary to dump liquid, solid waste and oil products, their collection and disposal in portable containers (barrels, containers) can be organized. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.A	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous air compressor station on the HPP site or use air compressor cylinders. For the HPP air compressor station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 9.E) can be used, at the normal price of electricity. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.	Modification of NPP systems not required
9.N	Modification of NPP systems is not required - for the needs of the HPP, it is necessary to install an autonomous nitrogen station on the HPP site or use nitrogen cylinders. For the HPP nitrogen station, electricity supply from a transformer (see 9.E) can be used, at the normal price of electricity. When using cylinders, appropriate logistics must be organized. Also, depending on the location of the HPP site, it is possible to use the resources of an object located nearby.	Modification of NPP systems not required

AL: N
ECCN: N

This section presents an assessment of the possibility of using the resources of the Rivne and Khmelnytsky NPPs to produce hydrogen at the HPP. An analysis was made of the need for modifications to NPP systems for each of the selected scenarios for the location of HPP and the conditions for using resources.

13 Assessment of modifications impact to NPP safety

The current section provides a brief description of the technical features of possible modifications of NPP systems and an assessment of the impact of modifications on NPP safety. The safety impact assessment was conducted for those systems that were identified above as resources requiring modification for identified scenarios.

Table 25: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at normal price (grid)

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
1.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It's necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025-2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p> <p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p> <p>Cable connections with a voltage of 20 kV and 6 kV from the external grid must be laid inside the NPP to the HPP site.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
1.D	Demineralized Water Supply	<p>For the needs of the HPP, demineralized water from the NPP cycle can be used. But according to Energoatom's internal standard SOU NNEG 171, the requirements for its composition do not meet the HPP requirements, so there is a need to install a post-treatment system at the HPP. This water can also be used as cooling water for a rectifier.</p> <p>Requires modification of the desalination and demineralization system. The modification includes a design for the installation of a water purification system after the NPP DW installation on the NPP site. It must be connected to a NPP DW unit and designed for additional treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP. Part of the water from the plant DW system will be withdrawn from the NPP supply cycle and sent to the HPP.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the demineralized water system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

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		A purification system to the required parameters is necessary with a consumption of approximately 6 t/h.	
1.T	Tap Water Supply system	It is required to modify the NPP domestic and tap water supply system - a design to expand the pipeline network and equipment for supplying the HPP premises with domestic water and a sewerage system connected to similar existing NPP systems. The effect of additional consumption on the network parameters must be calculated. Development and justification of communication lines on the territory of the NPP and a binding design.	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Tap Water Supply system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.
1.C	Service water Turbine department system.	For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20, VC10, VB) of the turbine hall. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the NPP's system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented). Modification of these systems should include the development of a design for the diversion of part of the water for the HPP. At the same time, pipelines for supplying and returning water to the HPP must be installed and laid through the territory of the NPP. A calculation of the effect of withdrawing part of the water on the cooling of consumers effectiveness of the secondary circuit equipment and a calculation of heat redistribution in the circulating water cooling system should be performed. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the reservoir directly without cooling due to environmental restrictions.	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.
1.W	Waste Water system.	Modification is required - the design of pipelines for connecting the sewerage system of the HPP with a similar system of the NPP. A pump shall be provided to supply waste from ladders and drains to the system for disposal by the relevant NPP systems. If it is necessary to discharge oil products, an appropriate similar line can be made or their collection and removal in portable containers (barrels) can be organized. The solid waste disposal system should be integrated into the existing NPP system and does not require significant modifications.	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Waste Water system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.
1.A	Compressed air system	NPPs have several compressed air supply systems. One of them is a safety system and it cannot be used as an HPP resource. The other one is a regular	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the

AL: N ECCN: N

		<p>station compressed air system and is fed by a site's compressor with a pressure of 5.5-6 bar. However, especially during repairing work of the power unit, the air pressure is significantly reduced. The system does not have enough reserve to maintain constant parameters to supply the HPP. Since the compressed air of the NPP does not provide the required pressure and purity, it is necessary to consider the option of installing your own compressor.</p> <p>When using the existing NPP system, a modification is required - a design for installing an additional (separate) compressor station for the needs of the HPP on the territory of the NPP. The use of pipelines of the existing NPP compressed air system is impractical due to possible pressure changes in this network.</p>	<p>Compressed air system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
1.N	Nitrogen supply system.	<p>The design capacity of the NPP nitrogen station for nitrogen supply is 100 Nm³/h, which is sufficient to withdraw part of the nitrogen for HPP needs. The design purity of nitrogen is 99.6 - 99.9% of nitrogen at the RNPP, and 99.99% of nitrogen at the KhNPP.</p> <p>For the needs of an HPP, a minimum nitrogen purity of 99.95% is required.</p> <p>In principle, it is possible to use the nitrogen station of the KhNPP for the needs of the HPP.</p> <p>Modification required - for the RNPP, a design to install an additional nitrogen station with a separate pipeline to the HPP equipment. For KhNPP, a pipeline design from the nitrogen station of the NPP to the HPP is possible.</p> <p>An alternative for both NPPs is to supply the HPP with nitrogen from cylinders. This does not require any modification.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Nitrogen supply system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

Table 26: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity at reduced price (home need).

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
2.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier. A design is required for</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore,</p>

AL: N ECCN: N

		<p>connecting an additional load to the NPP 6kV normal common buses.</p> <p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p> <p>It's necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 -2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p> <p>Cable connections with a voltage of 20 kV and 6 kV from the external grid must be laid inside the NPP to the HPP site.</p>	<p>modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
2.D	Demineralized water system.	<p>For the needs of the HPP, demineralized water from the NPP cycle can be used. But according to Energoatom's internal standard SOU NAEK 171, the requirements for its composition do not meet the HPP requirements, so there is a need to install a post-treatment system at the HPP. This water can also be used as cooling water for a rectifier.</p> <p>Requires modification of the desalination and demineralization system. The modification includes a design for the installation of a water purification system after the NPP DW installation on the NPP site. It must be connected to a NPP DW unit and designed for additional treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP. Part of the water from the plant DW system will be withdrawn from the NPP supply cycle and sent to the HPP.</p> <p>A purification system to the required parameters is necessary with a consumption of approximately 6 t/h.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the demineralized water system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
2.T	Tap Water Supply system	<p>It is required to modify the NPP domestic and tap water supply system - a design to expand the pipeline network and equipment for supplying the HPP premises with domestic water and a sewerage system connected to similar existing NPP systems. The effect of additional consumption on the network parameters must be calculated. Development and justification of communication lines on the territory of the NPP and a binding design.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Tap Water Supply system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
2.C	Service water Turbine	<p>For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20,</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis</p>

AL: N ECCN: N

	department system.	VC10, VB) of the turbine hall. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the NPP's system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented). Modification of these systems should include the development of a design for the diversion of part of the water for the HPP. At the same time, pipelines for supplying and returning water to the HPP must be installed and laid through the territory of the NPP. A calculation of the effect of withdrawing part of the water on the cooling of consumers effectiveness of the secondary circuit equipment and a calculation of heat redistribution in the circulating water cooling system should be performed. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the pond directly without cooling due to environmental restrictions.	Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.
2.W	Waste water system	Modification is required - the design of pipelines for connecting the sewerage system of the HPP with a similar system of the NPP. A pump shall be provided to supply waste from ladders and drains to the system for disposal by the relevant NPP systems. If it is necessary to discharge oil products, an appropriate similar line can be made or their collection and removal in portable containers (barrels) can be organized. The solid waste disposal system should be integrated into the existing NPP system and does not require significant modifications.	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Waste Water system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.
2.A	Compressed air system	NPPs have several compressed air supply systems. One of them is a safety system and it cannot be used as an HPP resource. The other one is a regular station compressed air system and is fed by a site's compressor with a pressure of 5.5-6 bar. However, especially during repairing work of the power unit, the air pressure is significantly reduced. The system does not have enough reserve to maintain constant parameters to supply HPP. Since the compressed air of the NPP does not provide the required pressure and purity, it is necessary to consider the option of installing your own compressor. When using the existing NPP system, a modification is required - a design for installing an additional (separate) compressor station for the needs of the HPP on the territory of the NPP. The use of pipelines of the existing NPP compressed air system is impractical due to possible pressure changes in this network.	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Compressed air system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.

2.N	Nitrogen supply system.	<p>The design capacity of the NPP nitrogen station for nitrogen supply is 100 Nm³/h, which is sufficient to withdraw part of the nitrogen for HPP needs.</p> <p>The design purity of nitrogen is 99.6 - 99.9% of nitrogen at the RNPP, and 99.99% of nitrogen at the KhNPP.</p> <p>For the needs of the HPP, a minimum nitrogen purity of 99.95% is required.</p> <p>In principle, it is possible to use the nitrogen station of the KhNPP for the needs of the HPP.</p> <p>Modification required - for the RNPP, a design to install an additional nitrogen station with a separate pipeline to the HPP equipment. For KhNPP, a pipeline design from the nitrogen station of the NPP to the HPP is possible.</p> <p>An alternative for both NPPs is to supply HPP with nitrogen from cylinders. This does not require any modification.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Nitrogen supply system is not a safety related system.</p> <p>Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
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Table 27: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only normal price.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
3.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110 kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install a 330/110/35 kV autotransformer with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p> <p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4 kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p> <p>A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (common normal plant sections), but the possibility of their use for an additional load (HPP compressor and 400V consumers) should be justified. Cable connections</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems.</p> <p>Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

		with a voltage of 20 kV and 6 kV from the external grid must be laid inside the NPP to the HPP site.	
3.C	Service water Turbine department system.	<p>The most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20, VC10, VB) of the turbine hall for the needs of the HPP. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented).</p> <p>Modification of these systems should include the development of a design for the diversion of part of the water in the HPP. At the same time, pipelines for supplying and returning water to the HPP must be installed and laid through the territory of the NPP. A calculation of the effect of withdrawing part of the water on the cooling of consumers of the turbine equipment and a calculation of heat redistribution in the circulating water cooling system should be performed. It is necessary to develop a design to justify the reliability of NPPs when diverting part of the water from the system. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective. Additional booster pumps or water return pumps to the cooling towers are available.</p>	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.

ECCN: N

AL: N

Table 28: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only reduced price.

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
4.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install a 330/110/35 kV autotransformer with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p>	Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.

AL: N ECCN: N

		<p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p> <p>A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (common normal plant buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load (HPP compressor and 400V consumers) should be justified. Cable connections with a voltage of 20 kV and 6 kV from the external grid must be laid inside the NPP to the HPP site.</p>	
4.C	Service water Turbine department system.	<p>For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20, VC10, VB) of the turbine hall. The flow rate need for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the NPP's system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented).</p> <p>Modification of these systems should include the development of a design for the diversion of part of the water in the HPP. At the same time, pipelines for supplying and returning water to the HPP must be installed and laid through the territory of the NPP. A calculation of the effect of withdrawing part of the water from cooling of consumers of the turbine equipment and a calculation of heat redistribution in the circulating water cooling system should be performed. It is necessary to develop a design to justify the reliability of NPPs when diverting part of the water from the system. It is possible that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective. Additional booster pumps or water return pumps to the cooling towers are available.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

Table 29: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at normal price (grid).

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
5.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of</p>

		<p>from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p> <p>The proposed location of transformer installation is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation site. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with laying the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP. An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p>	<p>the system does not impact safety.</p>
5.C	Service water Turbine department system.	<p>For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20, VC10, VB) of the turbine hall. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented).</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of part of the water from the NPP system. In addition, it is necessary to develop a design for the water supply of the HPP from the NPP, considering the laying of long pipelines (both at the NPP onsite and offsite parts). The distance from the NPP pump (VC20/VB system) to the HPP is more than 1 km. The heated water return pipeline from the HPP must also run along the supply pipeline to the NPP's circulated water channel. Considering the distance and the required flow rate, a booster pumping unit is expected to be required. The NPP pump (VC20/VB system) with this scheme will work as a booster pump. In this case, additional electricity consumption will be required. The return of heated water is discharged into the NPP circulating water cooling system. During transportation to the NPP, heated water can be partially cooled by air. However, thermal insulation should be provided for the cold season (and possibly thermal satellites).</p> <p>If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, power supply from transformers is also used, according to 5.E.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

AL: N
ECCN: N

Table 30: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity at reduced price (home need).

The specifications for all modifications are the same as in Scenario 5.

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
6.E	Normal buses system.	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the HPP.</p> <p>The proposed location of transformer installation is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation site. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with deployment of the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP.</p> <p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>
6.C	Service water Turbine department system.	<p>For the needs of the HPP, the most suitable is the service water system of auxiliary consumers (VC20, VC10, VB) of the turbine hall. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units (or a scheme for sharing the systems of several power units has been implemented).</p> <p>Modification is required - the NPP safety justification design for the removal of part of the water from the NPP system. In addition, it is necessary to develop a design for the water supply of the HPP from the NPP, considering the laying of</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the Service water Turbine department system is not a safety related system. Therefore, modification of the system does</p>

AL: N ECCN: N

		<p>long pipelines (both at the NPP onsite and offsite parts). The distance from the NPP pump (VC20/VB system) to the HPP is more than 1 km. The heated water return pipeline from the HPP must also run along the supply pipeline to the NPP's circulated water channel. Considering the distance and the required flow rate, a booster pumping unit is expected to be required. The NPP pump (VC20/VB system) with this scheme will work as a booster pump. In this case, additional electricity consumption will be required. The return of heated water is discharged into the NPP circulating water cooling system. During transportation to the NPP, heated water can be partially cooled by air. However, thermal insulation should be provided for the cold season (and possibly thermal satellites). If additional booster pumps or water return pumps are installed on the cooling towers, power supply from transformers is also used, according to 6.E.</p>	<p>not impact safety.</p>
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Table 31: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at normal price.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
7.E	<p>Normal buses system.</p> <p><i>The specifications for the modification are the same as in Scenario 5.</i></p>	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the hydrogen generation station.</p> <p>The proposed location of transformer installation is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation site. Although there are 6kV normal power sections at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with deployment of the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

		An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.	
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Table 32: Safety impact of modifications - Scenario 8. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only at reduced price.

Scenario and Resource	NPP system to be modified	Brief description of the purpose of the modification	Impact on NPP safety
8.E	<p>Normal buses system.</p> <p><i>The specifications for the modification are the same as in Scenario 5.</i></p>	<p>The modification must include a design for the installation of a transformer with an output voltage of 20kV and 6kV with an output power of at least 40 MW. Connection of the new transformers to the main electrical circuit of the NPP or in-house buses. It is necessary to install a 110/20/6 kV transformer, and to install a rectifier.</p> <p>It is necessary to install a 110 kV switch and disconnectors. Also conducting are power lines from transformer 110/20/6 kV to the opened switchgear OS-110kV.</p> <p>KhNPP is planned to install an autotransformer 330/110/35 kV with a capacity of 125 MW at an opened switchgear (OS-330kV) in 2025 - 2027. It will be possible to allocate 45 MW of the declared capacity for the hydrogen generation station.</p> <p>The proposed location of transformer installation is the NPP switchgear, either at the HPP site or at a separate HPP substation site. Although there are 6kV normal power buses at the NPP, it is unlikely that a design to transfer power to the NPP site would be feasible given the problems with deployment of the communication cable from the NPP to the HPP.</p> <p>An additional transformer (with an output voltage of 0.4kV) will also be required to control equipment and HPP valves.</p>	<p>Based on NPP Safety Analysis Report the electrical normal buses are not safety related systems. Therefore, modification of the system does not impact safety.</p>

AL: N
ECCN: N

Scenario 9. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark i.e. normal price (grid)

NPP modifications are not required. As a result of the analysis, NPP systems and the main conditions of their modifications were determined. None of the proposed modifications to NPP systems is safety related. Table 33 presents the systems that need to be modified under various conditions of their use for the needs of the HPP. This assessment is preliminary, as it may not consider various options for the technical characteristics of new equipment, various connection schemes, features of equipment maintenance and management, and other factors. None of the scenarios required the steam distribution system and NPP chilled water system to be applied. This is due to the comparison of hydrogen production technology with the current available technologies, as well as the technical features of Ukrainian NPP

designs. Accordingly, these systems are not subject to modifications and can be excluded from further analysis.

ECCN: N

AL: N

Table 33: NPP systems subject to modifications in scenarios of their use for HPP.

Scenario No	NPP resources								
	E	D	T	S	C	H	W	A	N
	Electrical Power Supply system	Demineralized Water Supply system	Tap Water Supply system	NPP Steam Supply system	Turbine equipment Cooling Water System	Chiller Water Supply System	Waste Water Utilization System	NPP Repair Air Supply System	NPP Nitrogen Supply System
1.	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
2.	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES
3.	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
4.	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
5.	POSSIBLE	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
6.	POSSIBLE	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
7.	POSSIBLE	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
8.	POSSIBLE	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
9.	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

AL: N
ECCN: N

YES - modification is required.

NO - modification is not required.

Possible – modification possibly required, depends on connection scheme details.

14 Characteristics Rivne NPP

Rivne NPP is the first nuclear power plant in Ukraine with pressurized nuclear reactors, currently the only type of reactors in Ukraine, and the only one with power units based on the first reactors of this series VVER-440 (V-213).

Rivne NPP (RNPP) is located in Volyn Polesie, near the Styr River, four kilometers from the town of Varash. The plant's history dates back to 1971, when the design of the West-Ukrainian NPP began, which during construction was renamed Rivne NPP. The abbreviated name is SS RNPP, a separate subdivision of NAEK Energoatom.

The construction of the plant started in 1973. The first two power units with VVER-440 reactors were commissioned in 1980-1981, the 3rd power unit - VVER-1000 - in 1986. The 4th power unit - VVER-1000 - in 2004. Rivne NPP was the first nuclear power plant in the to pass IAEA inspection in early 1989. In 2010, the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate decided to extend the service life of Units 1 and 2 for twenty years.

14.1 Power units with VVER-440

VVER-440 is a 440 MW pressurized water reactor designed in the Soviet Union (2 K-220-44 KhTGZ turbines of 220 MW each).

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 23: Characteristics of the VVER-440 reactor

- | | |
|-------------------------|--|
| 1.Confinement; | 9. Generator; |
| 2.Control Rods motor; | 10.Transformer; |
| 3.Fuel; | 11.Grid; |
| 4.Reactor Vessel; | 12.Feedwater Pump; |
| 5.Reactor Coolant Pump; | 13.Condenser; |
| 6.Steam Generator; | 14.Condenser Cooling (Circulation) Water Pump; |
| 7.Steam; | 15.Cooling Pond. |
| 8.Turbine; | |

The VVER-440 core consists of 349 hexagonal fuel assemblies, some of which are used as working bodies of the VVER-440 control system. Inside the fuel assembly casing there are 126 rod fuel elements (fuel elements) with a diameter of 9.1 mm mounted in a triangular lattice. The core of the fuel rod (sintered uranium dioxide with 3.5% enrichment), 7.5 mm in diameter, is enclosed in a 0.6 mm thick cladding. The material of the fuel assembly casing and the fuel rods cladding is zirconium alloyed with niobium (1%).

VVER-440 operates in the mode of 4-6 partial fuel assembly refueling per campaign lasting about 3-6 years. Every 280-290 days 1/3-1/6 part of fuel assembly is replaced in VVER-440. First, fuel assemblies are removed from the central core area, and in their place fuel assemblies from the core periphery are moved. The vacated spaces on the core periphery are filled with fresh fuel assemblies. Fuel assemblies are reloaded under a 5-meter-thick protective water layer that reduces the radiation dose in the reactor hall below the maximum permissible dose.

At present, fuel with burn-up neutron absorber (gadolinium, erbium) has been developed for VVER reactors, which allows to enrich fresh fuel more and to have a larger reactivity reserve during the fuel campaign, which allows to use one fuel assembly with fuel not for 3-4 years, but for 5-6 years at practically equal cost, which allows to reduce fuel costs by about 40%.

Power reactivity coefficient of VVER is a negative value. At NPPs, it is used to increase the interval between refueling during maximum power consumption in the autumn and winter. Before partial refueling, the reactor is switched for some time into the self-regulation mode. The reactor power is slowly reduced, which frees up reactivity. This reactivity is used to compensate for additional fuel burnup.

The VVER-440 core is contained in a thick-walled steel vessel. It has an outer diameter of 3.8 m, height of 11.2 m and is designed for operation under pressure of 125 atm. The casing has two rows of nozzles for coolant inlet and outlet. From above the vessel is closed with a top cover.

The VVER-440 control system has two independent systems: the control assembly (ARC) and the boron control system. The first system of 37 ARCs provides reactor control in unsteady modes and reactor shutdown. The fuel assembly with fuel elements is the lower tier of the ARC. The upper tier of ARCs is filled with boride alloy elements. The ARCs are mounted on rods extending upward through the top cover of the vessel. They are moved vertically by electric motors and in emergency cases are dropped into the core. After dropping, the place of the ARC fuel tier in the core is taken by a boride alloy absorber.

Slow changes in reactivity are compensated for by the boron control system. Application of the boron control system simplified the reactor control system. The number of ARCs is 37.

The scheme of the power unit with VVER-440 reactor consists of two circuits, the first of which refers to the reactor part, and the second - to the steam turbine part. In the reactor side, water circulates at a pressure of 125 atm. Water with a temperature of 269 °C enters the annular slot between the vessel wall and the core and flows downward. It then moves upwards and, cooling the fuel elements, heats up to 300 °C. In the steam generators, the heat removed from the reactors is used to produce saturated steam (pressure 44 atm, temperature 257 °C) that turns the turbine generators.

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1. Nuclear reactor vessel, 2. Steam generator, 3. Refueling machine, 4. Spent nuclear fuel pool, 5. Isolation system, 6. Make-up system, 7. Protective cover, 8. Confinement system, 9. Barbotage system,

10. Safety valves, 11. Ventilation system, 12. Turbine, 13. Condenser, 14. Turbine unit, 15. Feed water tank with deaerator, 16. Heater, 17. Turbine hall crane, 18. Electrical equipment and control chambers

14.2 Power units with VVER-1000

Pressurized Water Reactor (VVER-1000) is a nuclear reactor of the VVER reactor series with nominal electric power of 1000 MW and thermal power of 3000 MW. This type of reactor is the most widespread in its series and accounts for 7.5% of the total number of power reactors of all types operating in the world. The most common modification is the serial reactor unit B-320.

The reactor is a water-water, heterogeneous, vessel, thermal neutron reactor with water as a coolant, moderator and neutron reflector.

Nuclear fuel - fuel assemblies consisting of fuel elements containing uranium dioxide pellets weakly enriched in uranium-235 isotope.

The reactor power is regulated by the control and protection system - by changing the position of clusters of rods with absorbing elements (tubes with boron carbide) in the core, as well as by changing the concentration of boric acid in the reactor coolant system water.

Most often in the layout plan of NPPs with VVER-1000 it is envisaged to locate several power units on one site, which is connected with the necessity to maintain services, equipment and infrastructure common for all units at the NPP site. Each main building is a monoblock and consists of a reactor compartment, a turbine room, a deaerator rack and an electrical equipment rack adjacent to the turbine room. The main vessel houses the following main equipment:

- VVER-1000 type reactor,
- turbine unit of K-1000-60/1500 type,
- generator of TVV-1000 type.

Figure 24: Conceptual scheme of a power unit with a water-water reactor.

1.Reactor Vessel,
2.Fuel,

11.Generator exciter,
12.Condenser,

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 3. Control Rods, | 13. Condenser cooling system, |
| 4. Control Rods motor, | 14. Feedwater heater, |
| 5. Pressurizer, | 15. Turbine-driven feedwater Pump, |
| 6. Steam Generator tubes, | 16. Cooling water circulation Pump, |
| 7. Feedwater to SG, | 17. Reactor Coolant Pump, |
| 8. Turbine-High Pressure part, | 18. Alternator-Grid lines, |
| 9. Turbine-Low Pressure part, | 19. Steam pipe to Turbine, |
| 10. Generator, | 20. Containment |

The technological scheme of each unit is two-circuit. The first circuit is radioactive; it includes a VVER-1000 reactor with a thermal capacity of 3,000 MW and four circulation loops that pump coolant - water at a pressure of 16 MPa (160 kgf/cm²) - through the core using the reactor coolant pumps. The water temperature at the reactor inlet is approximately 289 °C, and at the outlet - 322 °C. The circulation flow rate of water through the reactor is 84000 t/h. The water heated in the reactor is directed through four pipelines to the steam generators. The pressure and level of the coolant of the reactor coolant system are maintained by means of a steam pressurizer.

The secondary side is non-radioactive and consists of an evaporator and water supply unit, a desalting unit and a turbine unit with an electrical capacity of 1000 MW. The coolant of the primary side is cooled in the steam generators, while giving heat to the water of the secondary side. Saturated steam produced in the steam generators, with pressure of 6.4 MPa and temperature of 280 °C, is supplied to the steam header and directed to the turbine unit driving the electric generator. The steam flow rate from 4 steam generators per turbine is approximately 6,000 t/h. The secondary side also includes first and second stage condensate pumps, high- and low-pressure heaters, deaerator, and turbo driven feed pumps.

Turbine section

In the Secondary side steam with humidity of 0,5 % from four steam generators is supplied through steam pipelines through stop and control valves to the middle of two-flow symmetrical high-pressure cylinder (HPC) of the turbine, where, after expansion, with pressure of 1,2 MPa and humidity of 12 % is directed to four steam superheater separators. There, after drying of steam (condensate for utilization of its heat is discharged to the deaerator), it is superheated in two stages, in the first stage by the first extraction steam with pressure of 3 MPa and temperature of 234 °C, in the second stage - by fresh steam. Condensate of heating steam is directed to high-pressure heaters to transfer its heat to feed water. The main superheated steam at the parameters of 1.13 MPa and 250 °C enters two receiver pipes, and from them - through stop valves - into three similar two-flow low-pressure cylinders (LPC). Further, from each LPC the steam enters its condenser. The regenerative system of the unit consists of four low-pressure heaters (LPH), a deaerator and two groups of HPHs. The feed water to the HPHs is supplied by two turbo feed pumps of about 12 MW each. Their drive turbine is fed with superheated steam and has its own condenser. The turbo feed pumps (two per unit) supply feed water from the deaerator to the steam generators. The capacity of each pump is about 3800 m³/h, pressure 7.33 MPa. For units with VVER-1000 there are no reserve pumps, because is the necessity to warm up the turbine drive before switching on, so in case of failure of one of them the power unit capacity is reduced by 50%. Auxiliary electric feedwater pumps are provided for emergency, start-up to cooling modes.

Three-phase synchronous generator sets TVV-1000 are designed for power generation in direct connection with steam turbines. Active power - 1000 MW, voltage 24 kV, rotor speed 1500 rpm. The

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generator consists of stator, end shields, rotor, leads with zero current transformers and flexible junctions, gas coolers, support bearing, shaft seals and base plates. Many auxiliary systems support the operation of the generator. Two three-phase step-up transformers with a capacity of 630 MW-A each are connected to each generator via generator circuit breakers, which, connected in parallel, make it possible to supply the unit's rated power to the grid.

Reactor units with VVER-1000 operate according to the two-circuit circulation scheme. In terms of safety, they are almost similar to European and American units with PWRs. A separate main building is constructed for each power unit. All reactor plant equipment and special technological systems (safety and auxiliary systems) are located in the reactor compartment of the power unit, which is a special structure.

The reactor compartment consists of a pressurized and a non-pressurized part. The pressurized part, called the containment, houses the primary side equipment and the reactor. The containment vessel is made in the form of a cylinder of prestressed reinforced concrete with a thickness of 1.2 meters, an inner diameter of 45 meters and a height of 52 meters, with an elevation of 13.2 meters above ground level. There is its flat bottom, up to the 66.35 meter mark, where the top of its dome-shaped top is located. The total volume is 67,000 m³. All the large main equipment in the containment is serviced by a circular full-turn crane.

The non-tight part asymmetrically surrounds the containment and is a square in plan with a side of 66 meters. The building goes 6.6 m underground and rises 41.4 m, inside it there is a railroad entrance for delivery of cargoes under the containment, in the bottom of which there is a large transport hatch. There is a 3 m diameter ventilation stack for blowing off from the production facilities, with a relative top elevation of 100 meters.

All large devices and pipelines are equipped with hydraulic shock absorbers, a complex system of supports, hangers, stops and other equipment to protect against earthquakes, the impact of reactive forces and flying objects during the destruction of equipment, as well as to reduce the vibration of process equipment and the reactor vessel. In addition to the large equipment described below, all systems include pipelines, a variety of shutoff, control, protection and safety valves, various sensors, thermocouples and other equipment.

VVER-1000 Reactor coolant system

Figure 25: Spatial diagram of the primary side of the VVER-1000 reactor.

CP-1,2,3,4 - Reactor coolant pumps; SG-1,2,3,4 - Steam Generators; NR - Reactor vessel; P – Pressurizer

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The primary side circulates the coolant - non-boiling water at a pressure of about 16 MPa (160 kgf/cm²). The coolant enters the reactor at a temperature of about 289 °C, heats up to 322 °C and is directed through 4 circulation loops to the steam generators ("hot" legs), where it transfers its heat to the coolant of the Secondary side. From the steam generators, the water is returned to the reactor by the reactor coolant pumps ("cold" legs). A pressurizer (volume compensator) connected to one of the "hot" legs is used to maintain pressure stability and to compensate for changes in the volume of the coolant during its heating up or cooling down. The total volume of the primary side is 370 m³.

Steam generator PGV-1000

The main circulation pipelines with an internal diameter of 850 mm connect the equipment of the primary side. They are located in pairs, in opposite sides from the reactor with an angle between the paired loops of 55°. The design of pipelines and methods of their fixing are designed to bear the load in case of an earthquake of 9 points on the MSK-64 scale with simultaneous impact of loads from guillotine breaks of one of the circulation loops. For various purposes, the main circulation pipelines are connected with a variety of auxiliary and emergency systems by means of welded-in branches, fittings and hermetic covers. Flow restrictors (leak restrictors) are installed at the tie-in points to minimize leaks when auxiliary system piping ruptures. Control and measurement piping is tapped through shutoffs to prevent leaks in the event of rupture. Temperature expansions of the main pipelines are compensated by moving steam generators and Reactor coolant pumps on roller supports. Large equipment is also equipped with powerful hydraulic shock absorbers.

The steam generator is designed to transfer the energy produced in the reactor core to the Secondary side. VVER-1000 uses PGV-1000 steam generators, horizontal, with a tubular heat exchange surface. The primary side coolant passes through 11,500 heat transfer tubes inside the steam generator vessel, heating the Secondary side water. The boiling Secondary side water is converted to steam and flows through collection steam lines to the turbine. Steam is produced saturated, with a temperature of 280 °C, pressure of 6.4 MPa and humidity of 0.2 % at a feed water temperature of 220 °C. Thermal capacity of each steam generator is 750 MW, steam production capacity is 1470 t/h.

Reactor coolant pumps (RCP) provide forced circulation of the coolant through the primary side. It is a vertical centrifugal single-stage pump with a mechanical shaft seal unit. Capacity - 20 000 m³/h, head - 6.75 kgf/cm², power 7000-5300 kW (on cold and hot water), weight - 140 tons. The pump has its own oil system, with a total oil flow of about 28 m³/h. In case of shutdown of one RCP, the reactor power is reduced by 36 %, two - by 60 %, more - the reactor is stopped by the action of emergency protection. At the same time, even in the absence of operating pumps, natural circulation of the coolant is maintained in the primary side, which provides the necessary heat removal from the fuel to cool down the plant.

The pressurizer is used to create and maintain the pressure in the primary side. The pressurizer is a vertical vessel with an elliptical bottom, in the lower part of which 28 blocks of electric heaters with a total capacity of 2520 kW are located. To increase the pressure in the primary side, the coolant in the pressurizer is heated by electric heaters. For lowering - the steam space is injected from the "cold" leg of the first loop, which leads to condensation of a part of steam and pressure reduction. For emergency pressure reduction there are 3 safety valves, discharging steam with flow rate up to 150 kg/s into the bubble tank, the main purpose of which is to receive and cool leaking safety valves.

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Service water supply

Service water supply at NPPs with VVER-1000 is recycled, i.e. service water circulates in a closed circle. Three types of coolers are used in the circulating systems: cooling ponds, splash pools and cooling towers. Combinations of these types are used in various projects, as autonomous service water supply systems are usually three: cooling system for turbine condensers, cooling system for turbine consumers and cooling system for critical components (equipment, including emergency equipment, the interruption of water supply to which is not allowed in any operating mode). The last system combines the functions of the safety and normal operation system, and splash pools are most often used in it.

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- | | | |
|----------------------------|-----------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1.Reactor; | 12.Emergency core cooling system; | 23.Heat exchanger; |
| 2.Reactor coolant system; | 13.Diesel-Generator Station; | 24.Cooling water inlet and outlet; |
| 3.Reactor coolant pump; | 14.Turbine Hall; | 25.Cooling water pumps station; |
| 4.Pressurizer; | 15.Steam auxiliary header; | 26.Cooling water pump; |
| 5.Steam Generator; | 16.Main steam pipes; | 27.Cooling tower; |
| 6.Containment polar crane; | 17.Turbine - High pressure part; | 28. Generator electrical lines; |
| 7.Spent fuel pool; | 18.Turbine - Low pressure part; | 29.Transformer; |
| 8.Refueling machine; | 19. Generator; | 30.Grid connection lines; |
| 9.Hydro accumulators; | 20. Generator exciter; | 31.Distillate tanks. |
| 10.Containment; | 21.Steam Separator; | |
| 11.Ventilation stack; | 22.Condenser; | |

Safety systems

Safety systems are designed to perform so-called critical safety functions during accidents, these functions include:

- control of chain reaction, i.e. shutdown of the reactor and control of its subcriticality after shutdown;
- removal of residual reactor power;
- limiting the spread of radioactive products.

The set of *safety systems* is determined by the design depending on the need to fulfill these functions. When creating the VVER-1000 safety systems, the following principles were used: physical separation of channels, diversity of principles of operation of the equipment used, independence of operation of different systems from each other. The single failure principle was applied to all safety systems, according to which safety functions are performed in case of any failure in safety systems independent of the initial event that caused the accident. This leads to the necessity of redundancy of safety systems. In NPP with VVER-1000 the redundancy ratio is accepted as 3-100 % (in many American and European projects this value is only 3-50 %), i.e. each safety system consists of three independent channels, each independently capable of ensuring fulfillment of design functions.

The emergency protection system transfers the reactor to a subcritical state in case of accidents and maintains it in this state.

The emergency boron injection system supplies boric acid solution to the first circuit at a pressure of 160-180 kgf/cm². This is necessary in accidents with the release of positive reactivity in the core while maintaining high pressure in the primary side. Solution concentration is 40 g/kg, flow rate of one channel of the system is 6 m³/h, solution supply is provided not more than 5 minutes after the emergency alarm. The system includes boron concentrate emergency stock tanks and pumps.

The emergency boron injection system supplies solution with concentration of 40 g/kg with a flow rate of at least 100 m³/h at a pressure of 100 kgf/cm² in the primary side, at a pressure of 15-90 kgf/cm² - with a flow rate of at least 130 m³/h. These flow rates are provided by one channel. The solution supply starts no later than 35-40 seconds after the required pressure is established in the primary side. The system includes emergency stock tanks of boron concentrate and pumps.

The system of emergency and planned cooling is designed both for emergency core cooling and removal of residual heat generation, and for planned cooling of the plant during shutdown and removal of residual heat generation during refueling. The system provides supply of boric acid solution with concentration 16 g/kg with flow rate 250-300 m³/h at pressure in the primary side 21 kgf/cm² and 700-750 m³/h at pressure 1 kgf/cm². It starts supplying no later than 35-40 seconds after the required pressure is established in the primary side. The system consists of pumps, a 500 m³ borated water tank in a containment (the emergency boron injection system and the sprinkler system can also be operated from it) and heat exchangers for emergency and scheduled defrosting.

The spray system is designed to localize accidents with rupture of primary and secondary side pipelines within the containment. In such an accident, the pressure in the Containment increases, and the Containment t is designed for a pressure not exceeding 5 kgf/cm². To prevent its collapse, as well as to bind radioactive iodine isotopes and to provide emergency filling of the fuel pool, the sprinkler system delivers boric acid solution to a number of nozzles under the containment dome. The system consists of centrifugal and water jet pumps, sprinkler tanks and spray nozzles.

The passive part of the emergency core cooling system (hydro accumulator system) is designed for operation in accidents with large leaks. This system is passive, i.e. it does not require commands for switching on and energy supply to fulfil its functions. It consists of four hydraulic accumulators, vertical cylindrical vessels containing 50 m³ of boric acid solution with a concentration of 16 g/kg each. The

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tanks are containment, directly connected to the reactor and isolated from it by check valves. The pressure in the tanks is 60 kgf/cm² (created by nitrogen), so at normal pressure in the primary side the check valves are closed. When the pressure in the primary side drops below 60 kgf/cm², the check valves open on their own and the solution from the tanks starts to flood the reactor. After emptying them, quick-acting gate valves cut off the accumulators from the circuit to prevent nitrogen from entering the reactor.

The emergency gas removal system is designed to remove the gas mixture from the Primary side equipment: reactor top points, pressurizer, steam generator headers along the primary side. Such necessity may arise in case of accidents with coolant boiling, level drop in the core, occurrence of zirconium steam reaction in the fuel and appearance of steam-gas bubbles in the upper points of the plant equipment as a result of these events. The introduction of this system was the designers' response to the 1979 accident at Three Mile Island NPP.

The emergency feedwater system for the steam generators is designed to operate in the event of a secondary side feedwater system failure, which is necessary to create a cool-down condition for the reactor plant. Each channel is capable of supplying desalinated water with a flow rate of 150 m³/h at normal steam generator pressure (64 kgf/cm²), 125 m³/h at 70 kgf/cm² pressure, 80 m³/h at 86 kgf/cm² pressure. The system includes pumps and chemically desalinated water tanks of 500 m³ each.

Containment. System of filtering emergency ventilation of the containment.

System of passive hydrogen removal from the containment (recombiners).

Mobile equipment. For each unit - 3 mobile pumping units for water supply to SFP, SGs and service water system. Flow rates - more than 100 tonnes/hour to the SG, and more than 400 tonnes/hour to the SFP and the service water system.

For each unit - mobile diesel generator (air-cooled). Voltage - 0.4 kV, Power - 800 kW.

The service water supply system for Group "A" equipment combines the functions of the safety system (cooling of the heat exchanger of the emergency cooling system, cooling of the pumps of the safety systems) and the normal operation system (heat removal from the crucial equipment: Spent fuel pool, heat exchangers of the intermediate circuit, a number of ventilation systems, etc.). The system operates on a closed circulating principle, water is cooled by splash pools on the territory of the plant site. The system includes service water pumps.

For emergency power supply, autonomous power supply sources are provided: automated diesel generators and an uninterruptible power supply unit based on accumulator batteries. There are 3 diesel generator sets of 5600 kW capacity each and 6 kV voltage for each power unit, they are deployed within 15 seconds and are capable of operating for 240 hours in maintenance-free mode. The batteries are operated in constant recharge mode.

Characteristics of VVERs

Parameters	VVER-440	VVER-1000
Reactor thermal power, MW	1375	3000
Efficiency, (net)	29,7	31,7
Pressure, kgf/cm ²		
before Turbine	44,0	60,0

in Primary side	125	160,0
Water Temperature, °C:		
Reactor inlet	269	289
Reactor outlet	300	319
Core Diameter, m	2,88	3,12
Core Height, m	2,50	3,50
Fuel element diameter, mm	9,1	9,1
Number of Fuel rods in Assembly	126	312
Number of Assembly	(312+ARC 37)	163
Uranium mass, t	42	66
Average uranium enrichment, %	3,5	4,26
Average fuel burn-up, MW-day/kg	28,6	48,4

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Figure 26: Location of Rivne NPP near Varash town.

14.3 HPP location selection

Table 34: Requirements and Solutions for locations

Requirements	Onsite location place	Offsite location place (the site is in the sanitary protection zone)
Above ground performance. The size of the plot: 30*40 m	The site is located in the area of cooling towers No. 3, 4, 5 (diagonally between cooling tower No. 3 and No. 5). The maximum dimensions of the site are approximately 110*92 m, for development approximately 86*80 m. Nearby there is a 45 m common-units Diesel-generator station. The approximate minimum	The site is located at a distance of 2900 m (open switchgear-330 kV) and 2750 m from the town's industrial structures. The dimensions of the site are 182.1*151.4 m. Distance 10-15 m to the mains water supply network. There are highways and access railway tracks near the site.

Requirements	Onsite location place	Offsite location place (the site is in the sanitary protection zone)
	<p>distance to the cooling towers is: to the cooling tower No. 3 – 138 m, to the cooling tower No. 4 – 159 m, to the cooling tower No. 5 – 177 m. Near the site there is an overpass, highways and approach railway tracks.</p> <p>This option is located closer to water supply network, a substantial justification of safety and location is required.</p>	<p>This option has such a disadvantage as the laying of communications, but the site is located in a potentially safer place for the NPP.</p>

Locations at the industrial site and in the sanitary and protective zone were analyzed for the RNPP. Since there is a risk of placing HPP near power units, hydraulic structures and other important objects, it was decided to consider two places: the first - on the territory of the industrial site, and the second - outside the territory of the industrial site in the sanitary protection zone, but with the possibility of using the necessary resources (electricity, water, staff, etc.). After discussions and detours, such locations were found. Near all locations there are highways and access railway tracks. See the images below, based on free, unbanned Google Maps.

The buildings and structures of the NPP are designed for the impact of an air shock wave with a compression pressure along the front of 10 kPa for the structures of power units #1, 2 of the Rivne NPP, 30 kPa for power units #3, 4 of the Rivne NPP. According to national and international regulatory documents, there are no requirements for anti-missile construction. Therefore, calculations of this coefficient were not carried out in NPP projects.

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Figure 27: Locations of HPP scenarios onsite the Rivne NPP (site #1) and in the sanitary protection zone (site #2).

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Figure 28: Location of site #1 (approximate minimum distance to: cooling tower #3 - 138 m, cooling tower #4 - 159 m, cooling tower #5 - 177 m, common standby diesel generators - 45 m, open switchgear - 1500 m, turbine department - 450 m)

Figure 29: Location of site #2 (approximate distance to: the town - 1100 m, to the NPP - 1200 m).

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System description will be about multi-unit Rivne NPP. Relevant systems shared among the NPP units will be mentioned and also the relevant systems who are not shared with other NPP units.

14.4 Electric system

The main electric scheme of the NPP.

Power units №1 and №2 each consist of one VVER-440 reactor with an electrical capacity of 420 MW, and two turbine units with an electrical capacity of 220 MW each. The generators are connected to the 330 kV switchgear via step-up transformers. In the scheme of paired power units No. 1 and 2, two 330 kV generator-transformer monoblocks are combined. The connection between generators and block transformers is made by current conduits, on which connectors are provided for operating (11T, 12T, 2 1T, 22T) and reserve(backup) (1RT, 6RT) transformers of own needs, which are working power sources of consumers of own needs.

Power units №3 and (№4) each consist of one VVER-1000 reactor, one generator with an electrical capacity of 1000 MW, consisting of a K-1000/3000-2 turbine. Two operating transformers with a voltage of 24/6.3 kV each are installed to power all consumers of power unit №3's own needs. Operating transformers of own needs are connected between the generator switch and the step-up transformer. Backup of power for own needs of power unit №3 is provided by a group of reserve transformers. A group of reserve transformers is installed near power unit №3 and connected to the 330 kV substation.

The transformers have a voltage of 6.3 kV on the low side. The reserve transformers of own needs are connected to unit's buses by 6 kV reserve power supply busbars.

To produce power at a voltage of 330 kV, power units №1, №2 and №3 are connected to the 330 kV switchgear according to the "one-and-a-half" scheme (three switches for two connections). Overhead lines run from the 330 kV open switchgear to the system-forming grid of the Western region of Ukraine at 4 substations.

The 330 kV substation is connected to the 110 kV networks of the adjacent district by a 330/110 kV autotransformer connection. The output of power in the 110 kV network of the surrounding area is carried out by overhead lines at 5 substations. The 110 kV switchgear is designed according to the scheme with two main and a third bypass bus system with one switch per connection.

To produce the power of the RNPP at a voltage of 750 kV and connect power unit №4 to the grid, the 750 kV open switchgear is provided according to the "quadrilateral" scheme, to the "corners" of which are attached:

- communication autotransformer 750/330 kV;
- power unit №4;
- overhead line to substation "X1";
- overhead line to substation "X2".

The 750 kV open switchgear and the 330 kV open switchgear are interconnected by a 750/330 kV autotransformer.

Station own needs supply description.

N
ECCN: N The station's own needs supply of power units № 3 and №4 consists of four 6kV switchgears: 3BE, 3BF, 4BE, 4BF and lower-level switchgear, which is fed from these 6kV buses through step-down transformers 6/0.4kV.

N
AL: N Buses 3BE, 3BF receive power from unit's normal buses 3BA, 3BD, respectively, and have 6kV redundancy of power unit 3 – 3BM, 3BN, respectively. To unit buses of own needs 3BA, 3BD, buses 3BE, 3BF are connected through two sectional switches. To 6kV unit №3 – 3BM, 3BN buses 3BE, 3BF are connected through one circuit breaker.

Buses 4BE, 4BF receive power from unit's normal buses 4BD, 4BB, respectively, and have a backup of 6kV of unit №4 – 4BN, 4BM, respectively. To the unit buses of own needs 4BD, 4BB, buses 4BE, 4BF are connected through two sectional switches. To 6kV unit №4 – 4BN, 4BM buses 4BE, 4BF are connected through one circuit breaker.

Own needs of power units №1 (PU1) and №2 (PU2) consist of four 6kV switchgears 1RA, 1RB, 2RA, 2RB for PU 1 and 3RA, 3RB, 4RA, 4RB for PU 2. Reserve power supply getting from reserve busbar systems 6kV (RBS-1RT-A, RBS-1RT-B, RBS-6RT-A, RBS-6RT-B).

14.5 System of preparation of demineralized water (DW)

The demineralized water plant with a capacity of 265 m³/h is designed to produce chemically demineralized water (DW) to replenish steam and condensate losses in the primary and secondary circuits. The technological scheme of demineralization includes five "chains" of desalination, two mixed action filters with a regenerator filter. Parameters of the quality of chemically desalinated water and the removal of filters for regeneration upon reaching one of the indicators:

- SiO₂ ≥ 20 µg/dm³;

- Na $\geq 5.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$;
- $\rho \geq 0.3 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$;
- Fe $\geq 20 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$;
- Total organic carbon $\geq 300 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$;
- Hydrogen pH indicator from 5.6 to 7.5;
- Mass concentration of sulfate ions $\geq 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$;
- Mass concentration of chloride ions $\geq 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$.

Filter loading: cationite Amberlight HPR 650 H, anionite Amberlight HPR 550 OH (ratio 1:1). Consumption of DW when operating power units at a capacity of 85-100 m³/h, maximum consumption of DW is 270-285 m³/h. There is no reserve of productivity at the maximum consumption of DW.

14.6 System of domestic water supply of the NPP

The domestic tap (drinking) water supply system, external water supply and distribution systems are designed for uninterrupted and reliable supply of tap water to meet drinking, sanitary and hygienic and production needs. Water quality meets sanitary standards and requirements. The technological line of water production and transportation looks as follows: Pump station of the 1st rise (artesian wells - 9 units - source of tap water) - water pipes - pure water tank (2 units) - Pump station of the 2nd rise - water pipes - distribution networks of water supply - the final consumer (including the own needs of the RNPP). External water supply and distribution systems provide consumers in the city of Varash, Zabolottya village and RNPP with tap water. Centralized water supply networks include:

- main water supply networks from the pump station-1 to the pump station-2;
- main water supply networks from pump station-2 to the consumer;
- from pump station-2 to the Zabolottya village;
- water supply distribution networks of the industrial site and external facilities of the RNPP;
- distribution networks of water supply of construction bases;
- water supply distribution networks of the Zabolottya village.

14.7 System of Turbine Hall service water (VC20, VB)

To provide cooling service water to consumers of group "B" of power units №3 and №4, a reversible separate scheme of service water supply with water cooling in spray pools has been adopted. The circulating service water supply system for Turbine Hall consumers with water cooling in the spray basins of the Rivne NPP is designed to provide cooling service water to group "B" consumers of the turbine and reactor department of power units № 3 and № 4, special housing of the Chemical Department and unit transformers T-5, T-6.

Water supply to Turbine Hall consumers of power unit № 3 and for cooling in the spray pool is carried out by two pumps VC20D01 (D02) of the pumping station № 3.

Pump of irresponsible consumers 3VC20D01 (D02):

- Flow rate, m³/h - 4000
- Pressure, m - 95

Water supply to Turbine Hall consumers of power unit № 4 is the same as of power unit №3.

The technological scheme of the system of Turbine Hall consumers of group "B" of power units №3 and №4 provides for the unification of the spray pool of unit №3 and the spray pool of unit № 4, in which the joint work of the spray pools is carried out. In the same way, the technological scheme of the system of Turbine Hall consumers of group "B" of units №3 and №4 provides for the unification of these systems and their joint operation both through the pressure pipelines of water supply from pump stations № 3 and № 4 to the turbine halls of units №3 and №4, and along the drain line from the consumers of the reactor and turbine sections of units №3 and №4 to the spray pool.

Purified water from pump stations is used to replenish water losses from the system of Turbine Hall consumers.

14.8 Chilled Water

Four steam-ejector refrigerating machines (hereinafter SERMs) are operated at power units № 1 and № 2 of the RNPP.

For the operation of the four SERMs of units №1 and №2, it is necessary to supply heating steam from the collector of own needs with a flow rate of 10,000 kg/h and a dryness at least 0.94, as well as cooling water with a flow rate of 1680 m³/h and a temperature of no higher than 28°C.

There is no provision for a backup source of cooling in the event of a malfunction or maintenance of the SERM. In the warm period of the year, the installed SERMs are not sufficient to ensure the regulated temperature regime in production premises. Considering the above, the SERM of units №1 and №2 are economically inefficient, non-autonomous equipment.

In the case of joint use with a hydrogen production plant, additional load must be considered, and redundancy should be provided during the replacement of SERMs.

Steam-ejector refrigerating machines are part of the refrigeration system and are designed for cooling working (chilled) water with supply to irrigation chambers and air coolers of air conditioning systems. The operational period of refrigerating machines is set from April to October.

Technical characteristics of refrigerating machines:

- Cooling capacity: 300,000 kcal/h (348.9 kW), (under the following conditions)
- T working water: +7 °C at the outlet of the evaporator;
- T technical (cooling) water: +28 °C at the entrance to the condenser;
- Consumption of working water through the evaporator: 100 m³/h
- Technical (cooling) water pressure: ≤ 2.5 kgf/cm²
- Consumption of technical (cooling) water through the condenser: 420 m³/h
- Working steam pressure: 10.11 kgf/cm²
- Temperature of working steam: ≤ +250 °C
- The degree of dryness of the working steam: 0.94%
- Consumption of working steam: 2500 kg/h

At present, 4 steam chillers (hereinafter referred to as SECMs) have been in operation at RNPP units №3 and №4.

The data are given for Unit №3. The data for Unit №4 is similar.

 AL: N
 ECCN: N

The chilled system with a steam ejection machine 3UX11H01 (type 17-EP) is designed for cooling of air coolers of recirculation ventilation systems serving controlled rooms of the sealed area of the part of the reactor compartment, autonomous air conditioners serving the premises of the deaerator compartment (boiler room, sampling preparing equipment room). There is no reserve.

Refrigeration system with a steam ejection machine 3UX31H01 designed for cooling of the air conditioning system irrigation chambers, which serves the production facilities of electrical devices, the turbine department, and a some of premises. There is no reserve.

Technical characteristics of the 3UX11H01

- Set temperature of "cold" water at the evaporator outlet: 13.5 °C;
- Amount of "cold" water circulating through the evaporator: 400 m³/h;
- Cooling water flow rate to condensers: 1350 m³/h;
- Operating steam consumption: 7500 kg/h;
- Working steam temperature: no more than 260 °C;
- Degree of dryness of working steam: not less than 0.94 %;
- Working steam pressure: 7 kgf/cm².

3UX31H01

- Set temperature of "cold" water at the evaporator outlet: 13.0 °C;
- Amount of "cold" water circulating through the evaporator: 175 m³/h;
- Cooling water flow rate to condensers: 700 m³/h;
- Operating steam consumption: 3800 kg/h;
- Working steam temperature: no more than 260 °C;
- Degree of dryness of working steam: not less than 0.94 %;
- Working steam pressure: 7 kgf/cm².

AL: N
ECCN: N

14.9 The NPP household sewage system

Domestic wastewater from sanitary equipment (washbasins, sinks, ladders, drains, bathtubs, toilets, etc.) of the Rivne NPP facilities is collected by self-flowing pipelines and diverted to sewage pumping stations. From the pumping stations, wastewater is pumped through pressurized pipelines for treatment at treatment facilities: the biological treatment station of unit No. 3 and the wastewater treatment facilities of the industrial RNPP site.

Through a pressure pipeline, wastewater from the industrial treatment facilities of the RNPP is pumped to the city treatment facilities of Varash town for treatment and disinfection. The productivity of industrial treatment facilities is 730 m³/day. The volume of wastewater treated in 2022 is 157,403 m³ (average 431 m³/day).

Water drainage at the RNPP is carried out considering discharge regimes, quantitative and qualitative composition of wastewater coming from RNPP units and consumers. Acceptance of site wastewater into the water drainage system of the town of Varash is carried out on contractual terms.

14.10 Site's compressed (repair) air system

Compressor units are located on Air Compressor Station (ACS-2) and Nitrogen-oxygen station ACS-1. These units work in joint system as the systems of normal operation and are intended for maintaining the pressure in the general plant network ($6.0 \div 8.0 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$), for carrying out works performed with compressed air in the site's departments. The compressed air system is atmospheric air compressed to a pressure of $6.0 \div 8.0 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$.

The ACS-2 Air compressor station includes 4 compressors with a capacity of $50 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$ each.

The ACS-1 Nitrogen-oxygen station includes:

- compressors with a capacity of $13.5/27 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$;
- compressors with a capacity of $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$ each.

The quality of compressed air produced by piston compressors ACS-2 and ACS-1 for the general station system of compressed air for own needs corresponds to the 8-th pollution class and meets the following requirements: the size of solid particles, no more than 80 microns.

The content of extraneous impurities:

- solid particles, no more than 12.5 mg/m^3 ;
- water in liquid form, 0.5 to 5 g/m^3

14.11 Nitrogen-oxygen station in the nitrogen section

The system for obtaining cryogenic air separation products is designed to provide the NPP with liquid and gaseous nitrogen with a pressure of up to 200 kgf/cm^2 and consists of 2 air distribution units. The system also includes compressor units ACS-1 and -2 and compressor unit ACS-3, which provide nitrogen distribution units with a pressure of up to 200 kgf/cm^2 .

- Productivity - gaseous nitrogen $70 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
- Productivity - liquid nitrogen 70 kg/h
- nitrogen purity 99.6% to 99.9%

15 Current situation: system description

15.1 Switch gear/Transformers/E-cabinets (sharing: Electricity)

Electric power supply system of HPP will be powered from the Open Switchgear 110 kV.

15.1.1 Description of existing scheme

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear is designed to supply power of local district consumers, and to provide power supply to the reserve(backup) transformers of power units 1 and 2 (1RT and 6RT) with installed capacity 40MVA 110kV/6kV. 1RT and 6RT connecting to the reserve busbar system of PU1 and PU2

The 110 kV and 330 kV outdoor switchgears will be interconnected by two autotransformers 7AT and 8AT with installed capacity $2 \times 125 \text{ MVA}$ 330kV/110kV.

AL: N
ECCN: N

The 330/110 kV outdoor switchgear is an integral part of the power system of the Western region of Ukraine. The 330/110 kV outdoor switchgears is a complex of individual devices, switchgear, instrumentation and equipment for measurement, automation, protection, control and signaling.

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear uses a circuit with two operating busbars (BS-I, BS-II) and bypass busbar systems (BBS).

Busbar systems I (BS-I) and II (BS-II) can be interconnected by a busbar disconnection circuit breaker (BCS).

The bypass busbar system (BBS) together with the bypass circuit breaker (BS) allows the breaker to be removed for repair at any switchgear connection.

110 kV outdoor switchgear consists of 12 cubicles (CP):

- CP 1 – circuit breaker for connection of 110/330 kV communication autotransformer 7AT (S-7AT);

- CP 2 – circuit breaker for connection of the 110/330kV communication autotransformer 8AT (S-8AT);

- CP 3 – circuit breaker for connection of the reserve auxiliary transformer VP 1TR (S-1RT);

- CP 4 – circuit breaker for connecting the bypass circuit breaker (BS) and connecting voltage measuring transformers.

- CP 5 – is a circuit breaker for connecting the reserve auxiliary transformer 6TR (S-6RT);

- CP 6 – circuit breaker of the RNPP-Volodymyrets switchgear (S-6PL);

- CP 7 – connection circuit breaker of RNPP-Hinochi (S-7PL);

- CP 8 – reserve (there will be connection of HPP to the Rivne NPP).

- CP 9 – circuit breaker for connection of RNPP-Varash GIS (S-9PL);

- CP 10 – busbar disconnecter with circuit breaker (BCS);

- CP 11 – connection circuit breaker of the RNPP-Manevychi GIS (S-11PL);

- CP 12 – circuit breaker for connection of RNPP-Komarovo GIS (S-12PL).

At 110 kV outdoor switchgear, circuit breakers of LTB-145 D1/B type, disconnectors of RDN-3.2, RDN-3.1a, SGF-123n type are used.

In normal operation, the circuit breakers of 110 kV outdoor switchgear connections are connected:

- to the busbar (BS-I): S-7AT; S-1RT; S-6PL; V-11PL;
- to busbar (BS-II): S-8AT; S-7PL; S-9PL; S-12PL; S-6RT.

Instrumental current transformers (CT) of IMB-123 type are installed in all cubicles.

Voltage transformers (VT) are installed at 110 kV outdoor switchgear at BS-I, BS-II, BBS busbars.

For protection against switching or atmospheric overvoltages of electrical equipment overvoltage arresters of OPN-110 type of various modifications are used.

Auxiliary reserve (backup) transformers (1RT, 6RT), which are redundant power supplies, are assigned to normal operation systems not affecting safety, class 4.

(Scheme of Open switchgear 110 kV illustrated in Figure 30)

(Scheme of Reserve busbars 6 kV illustrated in Figure 31)

Figure 30: Open switch gear 110 kV (before the modification)

ECCN: N
AL: N

Figure 31: Reserve busbars 6kV and auxiliary switchgears 6kV of PU1 and PU2.

15.1.2 Normal functioning of the system (for PU 1 and PU 2)

In normal operation mode, auxiliary consumers are supplied with power from two operating transformers of 25 MVA each, 15.75/6.3-6.3 kV, connected to generator current lines by blind taps between unit transformers and generator circuit breakers.

Consumers connected to 0.4 kV sections are supplied from 6/0.4 kV operating transformers, which are connected to 6 kV sections of the power unit.

A separate 6/0.4 kV transformer connected to the 6 kV section supplies power to the rectifier of the unit-wide DC installation, which provides DC power to consumers, including power to inverters, as well as recharging of the unit-wide accumulator battery.

In normal operation mode, the battery of the CSP (control and protection system) is recharged from a separate rectifier connected to the 0.4 kV section. Inverters connected to the DC panel busbars convert DC voltage into three-phase AC 0.4 kV voltage of 50 Hz frequency.

When the AC voltage at the 6 kV section disappears, the rectifier is switched off and the accumulator battery enters the discharge mode, continuing to supply the DC load and inverters. In this case the operation mode of consumers of the first reliability group is not interrupted.

When AC voltage is restored at the 6 kV section, the rectifier is automatically switched on (in 50-90 seconds), charging the accumulator battery to the voltage determined by the rectifier stabilization voltage setpoint.

15.1.3 System functioning in case of failures

Possible consequences of accidents in the electrical part, as well as accidents with the main equipment of the power unit are considered below:

(a) Short circuit on the communication line of the coupled power unit with the 330 kV switchgear. Protection of the unit busbar disconnects both generator circuit breakers (S-TG-1, S-TG-2 for PU1), 330 kV circuit breakers, circuit breakers of working power supply of 6 kV sections, affects the generator field extinguishing circuit breaker and sends a signal to the turbine stop valves landing. Full load shedding takes place. The reactor power regulator brings the power of the nuclear steam generating unit in accordance with the turbine power, i.e. it brings the reactor to no-load running.

Power unit auxiliary power supply is automatically transferred to the reserve(backup) transformer (1RT for PU1). The decision on further operation of the power unit is made by personnel depending on the size of the line damage;

(b) Damage of the power unit transformer (T-1, T-2 for PU1).

Transformer diff protection or transformer gas protection is operating. Further according to point (a), and in case of gas protection operation, automatic start of fire extinguishing is carried out.

After disconnection of the 330 kV disconnecter in the circuit of the damaged transformer by the operator from the control room, the power unit can continue to operate with one turbine generator at 50% capacity;

(c) Damage of the auxiliary operating transformer (11T, 12T for PU1).

AL: N
ECCN: N

In the event of damage to the auxiliary operating transformer, the diff protection or gas protection of the transformers is operated. Further according to point (a);

(d) short circuit on one section of auxiliary needs 6 kV (1RA, 1RB, 2RA, 2RB for PU1).

There is a start-up of redundant mechanisms of similar purpose connected to the operable 6 kV sections.

The damage may result the loss of one or two RCP (reactor coolant pump).

The power regulator sets the reactor to a power level corresponding to the number of remaining RCPs in operation;

(e) Disappearance of voltage on the section of normal operation (auxiliary switchgear 6kV 1RA, 1RB, 2RA, 2RB for PU1) as a result of disconnection of the working input (false tripping of automatics or erroneous action of the operator). Tripping of the working input circuit breaker causes operation of ALT (automatic load transfer) S without time delay. Technological process of the power unit is not interrupted;

(f) damage of any 0.4 kV section or damage of 6/0.4 kV transformers causes activation of redundant mechanisms on the remaining "healthy" sections, power supply of gate assemblies is transferred by the ALT (automatic load transfer) unit of the assembly to the remaining 0.4 kV sections in operation;

(g) damage to the unit-wide DC panel or battery causes the necessity to shut down the power unit;

(h) Generator damage tripped by the generator switch does not lead to changes in the auxiliary power supply scheme. The power of the reactor power unit is reduced to 50%, and the power unit operates with auxiliary loads supplied from operating transformers;

(i) turbine damage causes tripping of the generator switch (with a time delay or instantaneously, depending on the nature of the turbine damage and the protection in place).

The consequences are similar to those discussed in (h);

(j) in the event of a fault in the operating rectifier supplying the DC panel, an emergency signal of rectifier malfunction shall be issued and the power shall be manually transferred to the standby rectifier, with no disturbance in the operation of the technological systems.

(k) failures in the lighting system do not cause disturbances in the technological process of the power unit.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

15.2 Water purification system (sharing: Demiwater/Feedwater)

Desalination plant

Objective:

1). The water pre-treatment plant with liming and flocculation (coagulation) is designed for pretreatment of RNPP power units water before its chemical desalination. When liming with the use of flocculant (coagulant), a decrease in water alkalinity (and, as a rule, a corresponding decrease in water hardness and dry residue) is achieved.

water hardness and dry residue, removal of suspended solids and clarification, and reduction of iron, silicic acid and organic compounds. For the deep removal of large and small particles from the water treated after the clarifier, mechanical filter treatment is used.

2). The desalination plant is designed to produce chemical desalinated water to replenish steam and condensate losses in the Primary and Secondary sides. The technological scheme of the desalination plant includes five desalination "chains", two mixed-type filters with a filter regenerator.

The stand-alone desalination unit is designed to clean the "dirty" condensate from turbine shops #1 and #2 from chemical contamination.

The capacity of the mixed-type filter is 265 m3/h.

The capacity of one "chain" is 145 m3/h.

The capacity of the desalination plant is 125 m3/hour.

15.2.1 System functions

Operational functions

The operational functions of the system are to:

- regeneration operations of the unit's desalting unit, electromagnetic filter washing, mixed-type filter washing before and during operation, hydro-testing and pumping of pipelines in cold season.

- regeneration operations of water treatment systems;

- acid-alkali washing of evaporators;

- acid washing of condenser-degassers;

- cleaning and decontamination of premises.

- decontamination of overalls, special footwear and PPE in special laundries, washing of overalls and decontamination of equipment.

- decontamination of the removable part of the RCP and decontamination of the Reactor Department equipment

- decontamination of metal RW, decontamination of the SFP

- for own needs of Reactor Department systems and facilities in distillate storage tanks and emergency feed water tanks.

- performing process operations for equipment maintenance and routine maintenance, namely:

- regenerations, hydro-removals and filter washings;

- preparation of boric acid solutions;

- preparation of decontamination solution

- consumption of HWC for technological needs of maintenance systems and equipment is performed by consumers: condensers of TG, FWP-1,2; steam-ejector machines; maintenance systems, as well as for return of steam generator blowdown.

- During the period of maintenance and repair by the turbine department of the power unit, DWC is consumed for pressure testing and washing of the equipment of the Secondary side of the unit.

15.2.2 System description

The water pretreatment system includes:

- Unit for liming and flocculation (coagulation) of raw water

- Clarification unit for lime-flocculated (coagulated) water

- Unit of loosening washing of mechanical filters

- Compressed air supply unit

- Unit for pumping out drainage water from the DW pit.

The unit for liming and flocculation (coagulation) of raw water includes:

- Clarifier - designed for liming and flocculation (coagulation) of raw of raw water.
- Saturator tank - designed to produce a saturated lime solution.
- Saturated lime solution tanks - designed to pump the solution to the clarifier.
- Flocculant and coagulant solution tank - designed to prepare a solution of coagulant and flocculant, respectively, with subsequent dosing of solutions into the clarifier.
- Flocculant and coagulant solution dosing pumps are designed to dose the reagents into the clarifier.
- Saturated lime solution pumps - designed to dose the solution into the clarifier.
- Flocculant and coagulant solution filters - for filtering reagents before dosing.

The lime-flocculated (coagulated) water clarification unit includes:

- Mechanical filters - for capturing fine contaminants.
- Intermediate tanks - designed to collect clarified water and supply it to mechanical filters.
- Clarified water pumps - for supplying clarified water to the mechanical filters.

The feed water, heated in the turbine shop's raw water heater to $T=30\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, is supplied at a flow rate of 150-350 m³/h to the clarifier through the air separator distribution system, where excess air is separated from it.

Dosing of the coagulant and flocculant solution into the clarifier can be performed in three modes:

- N
ECCN:
- Dosing of the flocculant solution only.
 - Dosing of the coagulant solution only.
 - Joint dosing of both coagulant and flocculant.

N
AL:

With any method of dosing the coagulant and flocculant solution, the saturated lime solution is continuously supplied to the clarifier. The coagulant and lime solutions are injected into the clarifier cone. The coagulant solution can be dosed into the raw water supply pipeline to the clarifier. The interaction of these reagents with substances dissolved in water begins at the outlet of the clarifier mixer. To enlarge the flakes formed, a flocculant solution is injected 1 m above the injection point of the lime and coagulant solution. The products of this interaction fall out in the form of flakes. The outflow of clarified water is controlled by a throttle valve from the DW panel.

The clarified water from the distribution device enters the intermediate tanks and is then fed to the mechanical filters by pumps. In an emergency situation, when for any reason the supply of raw water from the Turbine Dept. #1 to the clarifier is not ensured or the clarifiers are out of service, artesian water is supplied to the pumps.

During liming and coagulation (flocculation) of water in the clarifier, sludge is formed. To remove the sludge from the clarifier, continuous and periodic blowing of sludge water into the sludge pit is organized, from where the clarifier blowdown water is sent to the sludge pit for natural evaporation. The water treated in the clarifier, even during normal operation, contains a certain amount of mechanical contaminants, which are in the form of suspended particles of fine dispersion. Their number increases significantly in the event of a violation of the clarifier's operation due to the removal of sludge. Two-chamber mechanical filters are used to capture contaminants.

Mechanical filters clarify the water treated in the clarifier, usually containing CaCO₃ and Mg(OH)₂ in the form of a fine suspension. The clarified water after the mechanical filters is supplied to the desalination system and to the splash pools of units 1 and 2.

During normal operation of the units, one clarifier, two intermediate tanks, two or three mechanical filters are in operation (depending on the consumption of DW and clarified water). The water pretreatment system must include a desalination system, reagent warehouses, and a compressed air system.

The purified water after the "chains" enters the desalinated water tanks. Then it is supplied by pumps to mixed-type filters for cleaning residual ion concentrations, and then goes to fill clean condensate tanks, condensate storage tanks (Turbine Dept.-1,2), condensate storage tanks (Turbine Dept.-3,4), the start-up backup boiler facility and the diesel generator set. The NPP's electrolysis installation is filled with water from the desalinated water tanks. The "dirty" condensate from Turbine Units 1,2 or 3,4 is cleaned and it is technically possible to further process it on the "chains". The steam condensate from the Startup Backup Boiler Station can be accepted simultaneously with the "dirty" condensate from the dirty condensate tanks of the Turbine Dept.

During normal operation of the units, one (two) "chains" and one mixed-type filters are in operation, with the consumption of DW: "80÷145 m³/h for the chains and 80÷265 m³/h for the mixed-type filters, in accordance with the regulations.

The "dirty" condensate from the Turbine Dept.#1 or #2 is taken to the common collector in turn to prevent the transfer of counterflows in case of simultaneous intake from the Turbine Dept #1 and #2.

- N
ECCN:
N
AL:
- The full cycle of the "chain" consists of the following operations:
- pre-start-up cleaning;
 - putting the "chain" into operation;
 - sequential filtration of clarified water through the filters of the "chain" to obtain desalinated water;
 - shutting down the chain for regeneration;
 - loosening of ions in each individual filter;
 - step-countercurrent regeneration of H-cationic and anionic filters;
 - washing ionites from regeneration products and excess regeneration solutions;
 - putting the "chain" into reserve.

15.2.3 Operation of mixed-type filters

The third stage of ionization (filters with a mixed layer of cationite and anionite) is designed for deep, almost complete desalination of water after the DW "chains". The optimal filtering speed is 30 ÷ 50 m/h. Water after mixed-type filters is supplied by desalinated water pumps to consumers.

The full cycle of the charge operation in mixed-action filters consists of the following stages:

- operating cycle;
- shutdown for regeneration;
- transportation of the depleted charge to the filter regenerator;
- loosening and separation of the ion-exchange charge;
- compaction of ionites;
- establishing opposite water flows through the anionics and cationics;
- simultaneous regeneration of anionite and cationite;
- separate washing of anionite and cationite;
- transportation of the regenerated charge to mixed-action filters;

- creation of an air cushion in the mixed-type filters;
- mixing of ions with compressed air;
- filling the mixed-type filters with water;
- final washing of the charge in the mixed-type filters.

The mixed-type filter is taken out of operation for regeneration when the content of sodium in the filtrate exceeds 5.0 µg/dm³, the specific electrical conductivity exceeds 0.3 µS/cm, the concentration of silicic acid exceeds 18 µg/dm³, the mass concentration of chloride ions exceeds 10 µg/dm³, the concentration of iron exceeds 20 µg/dm³, and the concentration of total organic carbon exceeds 300 µg/dm³.

Also, the mass concentration of oils and heavy oil products is monitored for no more than 100 µg/dm³.

The "chain" is sent for regeneration based on the following water indicators:

- the appearance (increase) of alkalinity by phenolphthalein behind the stage A2 filter of more than 100 µg-e/dm³;
- increase in water hardness of more than 3 µg-e/dm³ after the stage H2 filter;
- with an increase in chloride content after the stage A1 filter of more than 3 mg/dm³ at low acidity of the filtrate;
- increase of silicon content in the filtrate after the stage A2 filter by more than 200 µg/dm³.

Figure 32: DW system. Basic scheme

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 33: DW system. Detailed scheme

15.3 Service water system (sharing: Cooling water)

Pool cooling system

Objective:

Rivne NPP is multi-unit with separate cooling water supply systems for Units 1-2 and 3-4. The cooling water system of units No. 1 and No. 2 (VVER-440) is much less powerful than the system for units No. 3 and No. 4 (VVER-1000). Due to the low design capacity of the system for VVER-440 units, when it is used for the needs of HPP, a significant deficit of both water balance and cooling capacity is possible. This may lead to reduction of cooling conditions of equipment of units No.1 and No.2 below design conditions. Therefore, it was decided to use modified cooling systems of units No.3 and No.4 as more powerful ones for HPP needs. Further description concerns only cooling systems of units No. 3 and No. 4 of Rivne NPP. The systems of cooling of service water of "B" group are almost similar for units No. 3 and No. 4. Therefore, the operation of the system for one of these units is described below. Circulating system of service water supply to the equipment of the Turbine Department with cooling water in the splash pool No. 9 of Rivne NPP Unit 4 is designed to provide with cooled service water for consumers of group "B" turbine, reactor compartment of power unit No. 4, unit transformer T-6 and also used to lubricate the bearings of the Turbine circulation water pumps.

15.3.1 System functions

Safety functions

The system of service water supply of the turbine compartment is not included in the list of systems important for safety. However, in case of abnormal situations and accidents the system can be used for:

1. cooling of turbine compartment consumers.
2. cooling of RCP electric motors.
3. heat removal from the process condenser.
4. cooling of the unit transformer.

Operational functions

The operational functions of the pool cooling system are to:

1. supplying cooling process water to consumers of group B of the turbine compartment (steam ejector machine, bearings of the circulation pumps, ventilation systems, oil coolers and heat exchangers).
2. ensuring the efficiency of the circulation pumps.
3. supplying cooling process water to consumers of Group B of the reactor compartment
4. cooling of the unit transformer.

15.3.2 System description

The pool cooling system is schematically depicted in Figure 34 and Figure 35.

The service water supply system of Group B of power unit No. 4 includes:

- 4VB12D01 (D02) pumps designed to supply cooling water to the turbine hall of Unit 4 to consumers of the turbine, reactor compartments, special chemical compartment, as well as to cool the T-6 unit transformer
- splash pool No. 9, which has the following geometric dimensions and characteristics:
 - 68.5 x 132.0m;
 - pool depth - 4.0 m;
 - productivity - 6000 m³/hour;
 - irrigated area - 6000 m²;
 - number of installed nozzles of B-50 type - 100 pcs;
 - distance between distribution pipelines - 5000 mm;
 - distance between nozzles on distribution pipelines - 5000 mm;
 - diameter of distribution pipelines 200 - 600 mm.
 - pressure and drain pipelines with valves.

Process water of group "B" of unit No. 4 from the splash basin No. 9 is supplied to the suction line of pumps 4VB12D01 (D02) through pipelines Dy1600 mm. One pump is in operation, the other is in automatic standby. Further, the service water is supplied through Du800mm pressure pipelines to the heat exchangers of the special chemical compartment, turbine room and reactor compartment of Unit

ECCN: N

AL: N

4. After heating in the heat exchangers, the service water is supplied through the outlet pipelines of Du1000 mm to the splash pool No. 9 for cooling, and this cycle is repeated constantly.

During normal operation of the system, one half of the splash pool No. 9 is in operation and the other half is in standby.

To replenish the losses in the system, there is a make-up line from the chemical department water lines.

Additional water from the chemical department's water lines is supplied through a 200 mm pipeline to the service water supply pipeline from the splash pool No. 9 to the pumping station.

The "winter discharge" valve 4VB12S03 opens or closes depending on the service water temperature. The technological scheme of the system of consumers of group "B" of unit No. 4 provides for the unification of splash pool No. 9 of unit No. 4 and splash pool No. 8 of unit No. 3, in which the splash pools operate together, the valve 4VB10S01 on the water supply line from splash pool No. 8 to the suction line of pumps 30VC20D01, 30VC20D02 of unit No. 3 is open.

In addition, the technological scheme of the Group B system of Unit 4 provides for the combination with the Group B system of Unit 3 and their joint operation both through the pressure pipelines for water supply from the pumping station of Unit 4 to the turbine rooms of Units 3 and 4, and through the discharge line from the consumers of the reactor and turbine compartments of Units 3 and 4 to the splash pool No. 9.

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ECCN: For the period of cleaning of splash pool No. 9 of unit No. 4 from silt deposits, it is planned to withdraw it for repair, water to the suction line of pumps 4VB12D01(D02) is supplied from splash pool No. 8 of unit No. 3, the system of consumers of group "B" of unit No. 4 remains in operation together with the system of consumers of group "B" of unit No. 3. The heated water from the consumers of unit No. 4 is discharged into the splash pool No. 8 of unit No. 3.

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AL: The pump of the group "B" system 4VB12D01 (D02) type D4000-95 is a centrifugal, horizontal, single-stage spiral type pump with a two-sided water supply to the impeller. The pump is connected to the motor by means of an elastic coupling.

Control and measuring instruments.

To control the operation of the pumping station equipment, light and sound alarms in case of deviation of parameters from the set values, to prevent damage to the main and auxiliary process equipment, the following control devices are provided:

- water measuring rulers designed to measure water levels;
- Differential pressure gauges for measurement and control of pressure of water on site (at the pump head and suction);
- resistance thermometers are designed to measure the temperature of the motor bearings.

Pump control keys 4VB12D01(D02) are located at the Main Control Room-4 and the Local Control Panel of Pumping Station-4.

In order to increase the reliability of the equipment, automatic switching on of the backup in case of shutdown of the operating unit and technological interlocks are provided for the 4VB12D01(D02) pumps.

The list of equipment with process protections, interlocks and alarms, as well as the parameters of their operation are given below:

1. Activation of the automatic relay pump 4VB12D01(2) when the pressure drops at the head of the operating pump 4VB12D02(1) $\leq 4.8 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$
2. Switching on the backup pump 4VB12D01(2) in case of emergency motor shutdown of the operating pump 4VB12D02(1)
3. Switching on the backup pump 4VB12D01 (2) when the water pressure decreases at the head of the operating pump 4VB12D02 (1) $\leq 4.0 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$
4. Switching off the operating pump 4VB12D01 (D02) when the relay protection of the pump motor 4VB12D01 (D02) is activated
5. Switching off the operating pump 4VB12D01 (2) when the water pressure at the head of the operating pump decreases to $\leq 3.5 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$. Switching off the pump with a time delay of 30 seconds.
6. Switching off the operating pump 4VB12D01 (2) when the temperature of the pump motor bearings rises to $\geq 70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Switch off the pump with a time delay of 60 seconds.

Figure 34: Basic scheme of cooling water system.

Figure 35: Basic scheme of cooling water system.

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AL: N

16 Shared situation: modified systems

16.1 Description new situation - Electric power supply system

16.1.1 Electric power supply system of HPP (Description)

Table 35: Requirements and Solutions for electricity

Requirements	The plot near the power unit	The site is in the sanitary protection zone
<p>The capacity of the hydrogen station is assumed to be 45 MW (of which the capacity of the electrolyzer is 30 MW).</p> <p>Power supply can be divided into:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - source of direct current, necessary for electrolysis; - source of alternating current, necessary for the equipment. <p>This is approximately 93% DC consumption and 7% AC consumption. Electrolysis plants are usually connected to the medium voltage network (20-30</p>	<p>For all locations, the possibility of connecting HPP with a capacity of 45 MW to the electricity of the NPP was analyzed. At the Rivne NPP there is a free cell (number 8) on the 110 kW substation, from which it can be powered.</p> <p>To organize the electrical supply of each HPP, you will need:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 110kV circuit breaker and 110kV disconnector on VRP-110kV, - power transmission line with a voltage of 110 kV with a length of 2200m to 2800m, - 63MVA step-down transformer (110kV/20kV/6kV), - complete distribution devices for the voltage of 20, 6, and 0.4 kV for powering consumers of HPP 	

Requirements	The plot near the power unit	The site is in the sanitary protection zone
kV). In addition, compressors will need a voltage level of 6 kV, and other equipment will work from 400 V	The transformer can be placed both in the area of the open switchgear and in the area of the HPP site. It is also necessary to take into account the reservation of the HPP power supply line. The expediency of the choice will be determined by pre-project studies.	

The presence of a free cell of 110 kV allows to implement the following connection scheme:

Figure 36: Electrical schematic diagram of HPP substation (approx.)

For the organization of this scheme, according to preliminary estimates, the equipment listed in the table below is required.

Table 36: Proposed electrical part composition

No	Element	Comment
1	Free cell (feeder) connection of three phases of power transmission of 45 MW to an open switchgear of 110 kV	At the Rivne NPP there is a free cell (number 8) on the RU of 110 kW, from which PVV can be powered. Missing - switch and disconnectors.
2	The 110/20/6kV transformer power supply line, which stretches from the cell of the 110 kV open switchgear to the power supply transformer of the HPP's own needs	It can be implemented in the form of: 1) overhead (or underground) cable line consisting of three single-phase cables with a voltage of 110 kV (section 240 mm ² , aluminum); 2) Air current conduit (parameters not defined); 3) By an overhead power line (if there is a place to install supports).
3	Power supply transformer for the needs of the HPP. TDTN 45(50) MW 110/20/6kV	It is possible that the power of the transformer will be higher than 45 MW. 110kV upper voltage to take power from 110kV open switchgear. An average voltage of 20 kV for powering the rectifier that feeds the electrolysis plant with a capacity of 41 MW. The lower voltage for powering the compressor and transformer of own needs is 6/0.4 kV
4	Complete switchgear with a voltage of 6 kV (up to 10 kV)	1) Input cabinet for 1200 A with switch and TT, TN. 2) Compressor connection cabinet with switch and TT. 3) Protection cabinet (may not be required). 4) Supply cabinet of transformer of own needs 6/0.4 kV with switch, TT.
5	Dry transformer for own needs, voltage 6/0.4 kV	Power from 1 to 2 MW
6	Complete distribution device with a voltage of 0.4 kV	Quantity depending on the number of consumers 0.4 kV
7	Complete distribution device with a voltage of 20 kV	Probably 2 cabinets, input and distribution, for a current of 2500 A.
Note: Elements numbered 1-2 are placed on the NPP site, numbered 3-7 are part of the NPP.		

AL: N
ECCN: N

Approximate placement and length of the 110kV overhead line from cubicle №8 to the site of HPP substation:

- for the option of accommodation on the site - 2800 m;
- for the accommodation option in sanitary protection zone - 2000 m.

16.1.2 Electric power supply system of HPP (Integration in new situation)

The organization of the HPP power supply system will be organized from the existing open switchgear 110 kV (cubicle 8, which was in reserve according to the original design). Thus, no new facilities or systems not planned in the original NPP design will be constructed on the plant site.

After the installation of a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers in the reserve cubicle №8, the final scheme of the 110 kV switchgear will look as follows (see Figure 37).

The planned power consumption of HPP (40 - 45MVA) is within the allowable load on the autotransformers feeding the 110kV switchgear (7AT and 8AT see Figure 37) with a capacity of

125MVA each but requires additional study considering the actual load from consumers connected to the power lines (12PL, 11PL, 9PL, 7PL, 6PL see Figure 37).

ECCN: N

AL: N

Figure 37: Open switch gear 110 kV with connection of HPP

ECCN: N
AL: N

16.2 Description new situation - Water purification system

16.2.1 Shared System description

The requirements for the hydrogen station defined in Tasks 1.2 and 2.1 are given below.

Requirements.

Consumption - approximately 5.7 t/h.

Preferred requirements (final requirements depend on the requirements of the electrolyser manufacturer):

- maximum electrical conductivity of 0.056 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$,
- specific electrical resistance min. 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$,
- maximum total organic carbon content of 10 $\mu\text{g/l}$,
- the maximum sodium content is 1 $\mu\text{g/l}$,
- the maximum content of silicon dioxide is 3 $\mu\text{g/l}$,
- the maximum chlorine content is 1 $\mu\text{g/l}$

The NPP project envisages a chemical water purification system with a capacity of 265 m^3/h . Part of the water can be used for a HPP. But there are modes when this productivity is not enough even for the needs of the RNPP, therefore, during such peaks, the water cannot be used for the needs of the HPP (the availability of these modes depends on the water level in the Styr River, from which it is taken).

AL: N
ECCN: N
Chemically desalinated water from the NPP cycle can be used for HPP needs. But according to the internal standard of NAEC "Energoatom" SOU NAEC 171, the requirements for its composition do not meet the requirements of HPP, therefore, it is necessary to install a post-purification system on HPP. According to the standard, the requirements for the quality of chemically desalinated water are as follows:

- maximum electrical conductivity – 0.3 $\mu\text{S/cm}$;
- hydrogen pH indicator - 5.6-7.5;
- maximum mass concentration of chloride ions – 10 $\mu\text{g/l}$;
- maximum mass concentration of sulfate ions – 10 $\mu\text{g/l}$;
- maximum sodium content - 5 $\mu\text{g/l}$;
- the maximum content of silicic acid - 20 $\mu\text{g/l}$;
- maximum mass concentration of iron - 20 $\mu\text{g/l}$;
- maximum concentration of total organic carbon - 300 $\mu\text{g/l}$.

A purification system to the required parameters is necessary with a consumption of approximately 6 t/h

As usual the NPPs produce demineralized water with sufficient capacity. However, the water parameters do not correspond to the quality required for the HPP.

System modification is required - additional-treatment water system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for additional-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h - (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). It is preferable to place such an installation near the NPP's system to produce DW.

An approximate schematic diagram is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 38: Demineralized water system options for modification diagram.

Figure 39: Demineralized water system modification schematic diagram.

ECCN: N

AL: N

Figure 40: Demineralized water system modification plan.

16.2.2 Integration in new situation

The figures below show the approximate placement and length of demineralized water pipelines (diagrams below) depends on HPP location scenario:

- for the option of onsite scenario - 1200 m.
- for the offsite scenario (in sanitary protection zone) – 2,800 m.

Figure 41: Scheme of placement of demineralized water pipelines modification on the industrial site (scenario No. 1)

Figure 42: Scheme of placement of demineralized water pipelines modification in the sanitary protection zone (scenario No. 2)

The places of connecting the pipelines from the HPP to the demineralized water pipeline are shown in the diagrams above (point on the technological diagram):

- Connection point after fittings TO-11A, TO-010 (in both demineralized water supply lines).
- NPP Treatment water Dept. - approx. 5/X row G2-D axis 14-15.

Several options for using the existing pumping equipment for supplying demineralized water to the HPP were considered:

Scenario 1 – RNPP site, area of cooling towers No. 3, 4 of pumping equipment (Q-216 t/h), DW will be enough;

Scenario 2 - the sanitary protection zone area - may also have enough capacity (1-3 NOV Q-216 t/h) of the DW, the diameter and length of the pipeline must be taken into account during the design.

It is also necessary to install flow rate sensors (2 pcs. for two pipelines) for measuring the flow rate of DW from Water treatment Dept. to HPP.

An additional water purification system is planned as part of the HPP, which will ensure the minimum distance for transporting purified water.

In some modes of NPP operation, the consumption of power unit needs may exclude the possibility of supplying demineralized water to the NPP. In view of the demineralized water production system

of the NPP load, a demineralized water storage tank for HPP should be installed and a water supply pump (consumption up to 10 t/h, pressure - to be specified from the technology) from this tank to HPP equipment. The tank is filled with DW after the NPP treatment system and is stored with the possibility of direct selection of demineralized water from the NPP for the treatment system of HPP. Taking into account the technological cycles of a multi-unit nuclear power plant, it is advisable to have a two-day supply of purified water (the useful volume of the tank is 280 m³).

Modification of the system consists in connection of a 50-70 mm diameter pipeline (depending on the adopted scenario of HPP location) to the pressure header of demineralized water supply pumps. A manual shut-off valve is installed on the new pipeline. After it, instrumentation (pressure and water flow rate control) is installed with readings on the water treatment operator's panel. Connection is performed in the premises of the NPP Water Treatment Department, where a unified water treatment system for all NPP units is installed. The new pipeline is laid along the existing trestles or partially underground to the HPP site.

The NPP operation does not require constant supply of DW to consumers. The DW flow rate to the NPP consumers can be changed or switched off. Therefore, for constant supply of DW to electrolyzers it is required to install a DW storage tank and booster pumps at the HPP site. At the HPP site, the pipeline is connected to the additional treatment module and further to the HPP DW tank and the HPP DW pump to the electrolyzers. Appropriate shut-off and control valves, instrumentation and automation are installed at the HPP site according to the design and are not considered as a modification of the NPP.

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16.3 Description new situation - Water cooling system

16.3.1 Shared System description

The requirements for the hydrogen station defined are given below.

To cool the stacks of the electrolyzer, a flow rate of 750-900 t/h is required, the optimal temperature of the cooling water supply is 30° C, and heating in the heat exchanger is 10° C. There is a requirement for the temperature of the water at the inlet, which should be no more than 50° C, then at output will be at least 60° C.

The quality of the cooling water of the electrolyzer: water or 50% propylene glycol, there are no special requirements.

On the contrary, add the found solutions that are discussed and proposed for implementation.

It is possible to use the service water of Turbine Dept. unit #3 and #4 for onsite HPP scenarios.

But intervention in the heat balance of the cooling water of the nuclear power plant will lead to changes, so significant justifications are required. For offsite scenarios, service water supply is complicated by the need to long communications, so additional research is needed.

In addition, the issue of the possibility of selecting "raw" water from the RNPP service feed water pipeline (from the river to before entering the additional water purification system) was discussed. But then there is a problem with the return of heated water, due to the high temperature (up to 60° C), so there is a need for cooling before discharging.

Based on the above, two cooling options are currently being considered:

1. From the Turbine service water system.

2. Autonomous closed cooling system of the HPP

Depending on technical and economic indicators, the most optimal option will be chosen, but both options should be considered.

Option 1 - From the Turbine service water system (previous scheme below).

There is a possibility of engaging the Turbine service water system, but this leads to a thermal imbalance of the NPP and interferes with the cooling mode of the power units.

Replenishment of water losses during evaporation is carried out from the Styr River. Water from the river is purified in the additional water purification system before replenishing the NPP reserves. The scheme for compensation of splash pool water losses from natural sources already exists at NPPs and does not require modification. This option requires modification of the Turbine service water system in terms of supplying water to the HPP and diverting it back for cooling.

Option 2 - Autonomous closed cooling system of the HPP.

A reversible closed system using a dry cooling tower consisting of 3 modules with a capacity of 4000 kW each is considered in advance. The cooling tower is used to remove heat to the final absorber (atmospheric air). A cooling water circulation system should be provided, including pump(s) with a capacity of at least 1,000 t/h, appropriate pipelines, fittings, control and control systems, power supply, redundancy, and a scheme for feeding the system if necessary.

For this option, the modification only includes an additional makeup line for the HPP autonomous cooling system. Since the autonomous cooling system is closed, with heat removal in a dry cooling tower, water losses will be minimized. Therefore, it is assumed to use the DW from the HPP DW system to make up the cooling circuit. This scheme does not require modification of NPP systems, therefore it is not considered in this report.

An approximate schematic diagram of modification is shown in the figure below.

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 43: Modification Cooling water diagram.

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ECCN: N

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AL:

AL: N
ECCN: N

Figure 44: Modification Cooling water schematic diagram (Red are new pipes and equipment).

The modification consists in connecting the pressure headers of the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of Unit 3 (3VC20D01,02) and the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of Unit 4 (4VB12D01,02). From these pumps, a pipeline should be extended to the HPP site. Such scheme will allow to supply cooling water from the pumps of any of the units, as well as simultaneously from both systems. This will increase the reliability of resource supply to the HPP and reduce the

negative impact of each system on NPP equipment cooling. Under equal conditions, water withdrawal for the needs of HPP can be reduced to 380-450 t/h from each system.

In addition, 2 additional pumps should be installed with the possibility to connect the suction pipe to each of the splash basins (Units No.3 and No.4). The parameters of each additional pump shall provide 100% of the cooling water demand of the HPP. This flow rate is not less than 900 t/h, the pressure is specified depending on the conditions of water transportation to the HPP. The outlet of the additional pumps is connected to the supply pipeline to the HPP site. Such a scheme will allow to supply cooling water to the CPP without reducing the flow rate for cooling of the NPP turbine department equipment. This is especially important in the summer period of NPP operation when units No. 3 and No. 4 are operating at maximum power. Reservation of additional pumps solves the problem of maintenance, repair and emergency shutdown of one of the pumps without loss of reliability of HPP cooling. Additional pumps are installed in the area of ordinary NPP cooling pumps, equipped with valves, drainage and air removal lines, instrumentation, automation. Power supply of additional pumps from the in-house supply buses of one of the units or general in-house load buses. Additional control of temperature, pressure and flow rate - on the supply and discharge pipelines at the HPP site. Preferred location of additional pumps - existing rooms of pumping stations of turbine department service water.

The heated water return pipeline from the HPP should be installed to the location of the respective service water pools of units No. 3 and No. 4. It is possible to return water to any of these pools. Pipes with valves are connected to water return collectors to the pools from turbine departments.

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17 Impact on operation/situations

17.1 Electric power supply system of HPP (Description)

Since in the initial design of 110kV switchgear only 1 redundant auxiliary transformer (1RT) with installed capacity of 40 MVA was installed, considering the connection of a second redundant transformer (6RT) with installed capacity of 40 MVA, it is necessary to analyze the operating mode of the 110 kV switchgear with simultaneous connection of all existing consumers via power lines (12PL, 11PL, 9PL, 7PL, 6PL see Pic.3-1) and simultaneous activation of two redundant transformers (1RT and 6RT) and taking into account the HPP load.

17.2 Demineralized water treatment system

17.2.1 Original Situation

The system is plant-wide and provides preparation, treatment and demineralization of water for the needs of all four NPP units. The equipment is located in the chemical water treatment building of the NPP Chemical Department. The system is maintained by the personnel of the chemical department. Parameter monitoring and control is performed at the chemical water treatment control room, at the local control rooms and at the equipment locations. Operational maintenance is performed by the NPP operating personnel. Control of water consumption is performed by the operating personnel from the chemical water treatment control room Control of the nozzle device is performed by the operating personnel when changing the pressure on the clarifier according to the instructions. During the operation of the "chain" it is necessary to control the operation of each filter for chemical indicators

of water (acidity, pH, hardness, chloride and silicic acid content) with the corresponding record in the additional information about the operation of the demineralization system.

Repairs and maintenance are performed by NPP repair and engineering personnel.

Normal operation is performed by the operating personnel according to procedures, normal operation instructions and programs. In case of abnormal cases and emergencies, the personnel use the procedures for elimination of accidents at the equipment. If necessary, 24-hour engineering support is provided by highly qualified NPP specialists.

For the operation of the demineralization system, the following systems must be in place in accordance with to the instructions:

- "Operating Instructions. Water treatment plant. Water treatment. System of normal operation. Unit No.1,2,3,4" 171-1-E-HC;
- "Instruction for operation. Water treatment. Chemicals storage system. System of normal operation Unit No. 1,2,3,4 " 171-1/2-E-HC;
- "Instruction for operation. Compressed air system. System of normal operation. Unit No.1,2" 171-26/1-E-HC.

Training and education of personnel are performed at different levels at the NPP and at the training center. Periodically the knowledge of instructions of the personnel who operate the system is checked.

Taking into account the multi-unit structure of NPP, the system usually operates continuously for water treatment and its return to power units and other NPP facilities. Demineralized water consumption by consumers is changeable. The highest water consumption from the system is required during power unit start-up after repair. Priorities of water distribution within the NPP are set by the NPP shift supervisor.

17.2.2 Modified (Shared) Situation

There is a minor modification to the existing system. An additional pipeline with a shut-off valve is installed in the room where the system is located. A pressure gauge and a flow meter are also installed for monitoring. All modifications are carried out in the demineralized water pump header room. The pipe laying to the HPP is performed in the NPP site and does not require operational control. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valve) is performed by the regular operating personnel who operate the NPP DW system. The schemes and operating instructions of the DW system should be modified. The personnel should be trained and given the necessary instruction on control and management of the modified system. Possible additional malfunctions (leaks, valve or instrumentation failures) should be analyzed. Personnel actions must be included in the instructions. All necessary measures before performing the modification are included in the technical decision document.

AL: N
ECCN: N

17.3 Cooling water system

17.3.1 Original Situation

The system consists of an extensive system of ducts, pools, pipelines and cooling towers. The system is a non safety related system. The systems are divided according to power units. The systems to serve Units 3 and 4 are similar but physically separated. However, the schemes have the possibility of their mutual redundancy. Usually, one pump out of two is in operation, the second pump is in automatic standby. The system cools the equipment of the turbine department and is a booster system for cooling the electric motors of the RCPs. The highest load of the system is usually in the summer period at high temperatures and when the units are operating at rated capacity. Heat removal to the air is controlled by varying the height of the water sprinkler over the pool. The system is managed by the hydraulic structures shop and the turbine shop. The pumps are in pumping station buildings separated from the turbine building on the NPP territory. Parameter monitoring and control is performed at the Main Control Room, at the local panels and at the equipment locations. Operation is performed by NPP operational personnel. Repair and maintenance are performed by NPP repair and engineering personnel. Normal operation is performed by the operating personnel according to procedures, normal operation instructions and programs. In abnormal cases and accidents, the personnel use the procedures for accident management on the turbine shop equipment. If necessary, 24-hour engineering support is provided by highly qualified NPP specialists. Operational personnel also monitor the system operation during routine walkarounds of the equipment.

ECCN: N Training and education of personnel are performed at different levels at NPP and at the training center. The knowledge of instructions of the personnel operating the system is periodically checked.

17.3.2 Modified (Shared) Situation

AL: N Modification of the existing system is not related to NPP safety. Additional pipelines with shut-off valves are installed within the location of the existing pipelines of the system. The new pipelines connect the existing pipelines of service water of units No. 3 and No. 4 with the HPP site. In addition, 2 new HPP water supply pumps are being installed. Where possible, existing advance chambers and existing suction pipes of existing systems (VC20, VB12) are used. Suitable valves and check valves are installed on the pipelines to allow for different switching and maintenance arrangements for the modified system.

A gauges and a flow meter also have to be installed. All changes are made at the location of the existing system. The laying of pipes to the HPP and water return is carried out on the territory of the NPP and does not require operational control. Control of water flow at the HPP is carried out on the territory of the HPP and is not required with NPP personnel. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valves, pumps) are performed by operating personnel who operate the existing NPP system. Changes must be made to the diagrams and operating instructions for VB, VC systems. The power supply equipment for the house needs of the corresponding Unit will also be modified and power supply cables will be extended to the new pump motors. New automation equipment for pumps and electric motors was modified and installed. Therefore, the diagrams and instructions of the Electrical Dept. and the Automation and Measurement Dept. must also be changed. The operational, technical and engineering personnel of the technological departments, the Electrical Dept. and the Automation and Measurement Dept. must be trained and given the necessary instructions on checking and managing the modified system. Possible additional faults (leaks, failures of valves, pumps or instruments) must be analyzed. Personnel actions must be included in the

instructions. The training programs and training materials for the staff of the Education and Training Center must also be changed. All necessary measures before carrying out the modification are included in the technical solution document.

18 Proposals of technical solutions for the identified issues and judgement of the regulatory feasibility.

Modifications of NPP systems and equipment are carried out based on the document "Requirements for modifications of nuclear installations and their safety assessment procedure". This document has been developed based on the Law of Ukraine and General provisions of NPP safety, considering the IAEA safety standard "Modifications to nuclear power plants" No. NS-G-2.3 .

By impact on NPP safety, modifications are divided into the following:

- modifications important for safety,
- modifications that do not affect safety.

Modifications important for safety include:

a. Modifications related with changes to NPP configurations, namely:

- changes in the design of buildings and structures of the NPP, construction of systems important for safety or their characteristics, technological process;
- changes of NPP Technical Specification, Emergency procedures, Radiation control regulations and others operational documents which should be agreed by the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine.

b. Modifications of NPP management systems - changes to organizational structures and resources of the NPP operator.

Modifications that do not affect the safety of the NPP means that they cannot result in impacts on safety even with their incorrect implementation.

The operator of the NPP must assess modifications based on the safety impact. For modifications related to the configuration of the NPP, the assessment is carried out taking into account the classifications of systems important for safety established by the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine. The State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine examines the assessment carried out by the NPP operator for its appropriateness in terms of the modifications' impact on safety and can demand changes.

Any modification important to safety cannot be implemented by the NPP operator without agreement of the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine. The NPP operator should coordinate all changes with the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine if the documents have been previously agreed.

Carrying out modifications of NPPs, which do not affect safety, do not need to be approved by the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine. However, the NPP operator must provide information to State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine about modifications and their impact on the safety of the NPP before the start of the implementation process.

The NPP operator is responsible for the safety of the NPP during the modification process, for the timely coordination of modifications important to safety with the State Nuclear Regulatory

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Inspectorate of Ukraine, and for the reliability of the information justifying the safety of modifications provided.

Any modification of the NPP carried out by the NPP operator must not reduce the level of safety of the NPP. To justify this, the NPP operator assesses the safety of the NPP considering the modification and the new operating conditions of the NPP.

This subsection shows that all possible modifications have no impact on the safety of the considered NPPs. Thus, the proposed modifications must be carried out in accordance with the requirements of the document "Requirements for modifications of nuclear installations and their safety assessment procedure". At the same time, coordination with the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine is required only at the first stage - assessment of the impact of the modification on the safety of the NPP. Further stages do not require coordination with the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine.

A Technical decision of modifications must be tested before implementation at the NPP. Testing of new equipment is provided during implementation modifications:

- previous tests at the manufacturer's site;
- previous complex tests at the NPP site;
- tests during the trial operation;
- admissions tests.

N
ECCN: The NPP operator develops a modification quality management procedure. Such a procedure includes development of a documentation process, coordination, control of the implementation of modifications etc. Also, the organizational structure, resources, and responsible persons should be indicated in the procedure. The procedure should include measures that make unauthorized modifications impossible.

AL: N The NPP operator must provide corresponding training and testing qualifications of personnel who are involved in the modification's implementation process. The staff responsible for using the modified equipment must be prepared for the beginning of modification trial operation at the NPP.

In case of changes of design systems or their characteristics, NPP buildings, structures, and systems, the NPP operator should develop the technical decision of modification, namely:

- Conceptual Decision on the modification;
- Technical Decision on the installation of the modification;
- Technical Decision on the start of trial operation;
- Technical Decision on the start of commercial operation.

The NPP operator must assess the necessary changes resulting from modifications, to:

- NPP Technical Specification,
- operating and maintenance instructions,
- emergency procedures and other operational documentation,
- Safety Analysis Report.

The NPP operator should ensure that these changes are reviewed and, if necessary, implemented before the start of the commercial operation mode. For the period of trial operation, temporary changes to the operational documentation, that are necessary for the implementation of modifications, are being developed. To each Technical Decision documents, which justify that the modifications meet the safety requirements, must be added. Technical Decisions should be approved

by the NPP operator, agreed with the project organization (if necessary), and other supervisory authorities (if necessary).

The State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine has the right to demand additional documents and information from the NPP operator. Such documents can consist of explanatory notes to the design, drawings, an act and protocols of previous tests of object modifications and others.

Conceptual decision on the modification

The Conceptual Decision on modifications is developed by the NPP operator and agreed upon by the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine before any work on NPP modification begins.

The conceptual decision should contain the following information:

- definition of the object of modification;
- the purpose of the modification, justification of its necessity with the determination of safety deficiencies or deviations from the requirements of the safety rules, which are eliminated by the proposed modification;
- a brief description of the modification;
- assessment of the impact of the implementation of the modification on safety, NPP personnel and the natural environment;
- proposals for establishing the safety class and classification designation of the object of modification;
- the possibility and expediency of storing elements of the object being modified, considered their technical condition;
- other (except for the impact on safety) expected technical and economic results of the modification;
- list of modification participants (designers, suppliers of equipment and services, etc.);
- Information about the results of the operation of similar objects of modifications abroad (if available);
- a schedule of works on the modification implementation.

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If necessary, based on the results of the review of the conceptual technical solution, the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine develops an appropriate safety assessment plan for the modification project. Expert organizations may be involved in the development of the safety assessment plan of the modification.

Technical Decision on installation of the object of modification

The Technical Decision on the installation of the modification object is developed by the NPP operator. The following works should be described in the Technical Decision: dismantling (if necessary) of old equipment, installation of new equipment, commissioning works, preliminary (autonomous and integrated as part of the NPP) tests of the modification object.

To justify the possibility of performing these works, the NPP operator adds the following documents to the Technical Decision on the installation of the modification object:

- technical task or technical requirements for the object of modification;
- technical conditions for technical means and equipment of the object of modification. For products of single production, it is allowed to be limited to the provision of a technical task. In case of equipment supply by foreign manufacturers, other documents (technical specifications, supply contracts, etc.) may be considered instead of technical conditions;
- Safety Analysis Report (SAR) of the (preliminary) design of the modification of the NPP;

- the program and methodology of preliminary tests of the object of modification (autonomous and complex as part of the NPP);
- the program for ensuring the quality of the modification;
- verification plan and software verification report;
- results of validation of the software and software technical complex (if software is modified);
- documents for verification of algorithms changed during the implementation of modifications.

In the case of modifications of the control and management systems, the following are additionally added:

- design assessment (analysis) of the reliability of technical and software tools and the system as a whole;
- analysis of the system's reaction to possible failures;
- stability analysis of control and regulation circuits.

These documents can be presented as a separate document in the SAR.

Technical Decision on the introduction of the object of modification into trial operation

The NPP operator develops a technical decision on the introduction of the modification object into trial operation for conducting and coordinating the introduction.

The following documents are attached to the technical decision to substantiate the possibility of safely introducing the object of modification into trial operation:

- report or other documents (act, protocols) on the results of installation and commissioning works;
- a report on the results of preliminary complex tests of the object of modification as part of the NPP with the provision of protocols and the act of conducting tests;
- information on the results of metrological verification of measurement channels (if necessary);
- information on the training of personnel involved in the operation of the modification object;
- information on making temporary changes to design and operational documentation;
- the program of trial operation of the object of modification;
- the program and methodology of acceptance tests of the object of modification.

Technical Decision on the introduction of the object of modification into commercial operation

The NPP operator develops a Technical Decision on the introduction of the modification object into commercial operation for the implementation and approval of the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate of Ukraine.

To substantiate the possibility of safe commercial operation of the modification object, the NPP operator adds the following documents to the Technical Decision:

- a report or other documents (act, protocols) on the results of trial operation;
- the act and protocol of admission tests and other admission materials;
- the final SAR, revised based on the results of trial operation;

- information on making changes to design and operational documentation;
- information on the results of metrological certification of measuring instruments (if necessary).

Special requirements for documents justifying safety during modifications related to changes in the NPP configuration.

The SAR must show that the implementation of the modification will not reduce (increase) the level of safety of the NPP, namely:

- preservation of the principle of defense in depth,
- no increase in the probability of severe damage to the reactor core,
- protection against personnel errors, equipment failures,
- preserving the principle of single failure,
- protection from internal and external impacts;
- the absence of such an effect of the modification on the NPP as a whole, as well as on other NPP systems, which could cause malfunctions and/or changes in the characteristics of these systems under any operating conditions;
- absence of increased dose loads on personnel or the population, emergency consequences and negative impact on the environment;
- absence of dangerous consequences in case of single failures of the modified system;
- ensuring fire and technical safety;
- the absence of dangerous consequences as a result of erroneous actions of personnel during the implementation and operation of the modified system, including during testing and maintenance;
- preservation of functioning and regulatory characteristics of the modified system in the event of failures in adjacent equipment.

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The need to make temporary changes to the NPP Technical Specification during the implementation of the modification and their cancellation after its implementation must be assessed. The analysis must include an assessment of the impact of the proposed modification on safety and the surrounding natural environment during all stages of its implementation.

The SAR is specified based on the results of trial operation of the object of modification. A conservative approach should be used when performing a security analysis. The influence of the implementation of the modified system on the results of the SAR of the entire NPP should be considered.

Programs of commissioning works, preliminary and acceptance tests, trial operation of objects of modifications

Programs and methods should be developed for planning and carrying out works and tests of the object of modification. The purpose is to check the performance of the specified functions, determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics and assess their compliance with the requirements of the technical conditions and the technical specification for the modification. These programs are approved by the NPP operator.

The need to conduct the tests and the types of tests are established in the Conceptual Decision on the modification of the NPP. During the stages of implementation of the modification, it is possible to specify the types of necessary tests.

19 Findings and Conclusions

Finding 1: All modifications of NPP systems that can be used as resources for HPPs are not important for NPP safety. None of the scenarios require modifications that affect security.

Finding 2: The key NPP systems to use as a resource for HPP are the electricity distribution system and the cooling water system. The most difficult can be the application of an autonomous HPP cooling water system, including the conditions for maintaining the inventory balance. The NPP demineralized water system can also be applied with an additional treatment facility.

Finding 3: The other of the NPP resources can be used for HPP under appropriate conditions. However, such resources may also be used from different sources. Some resources (for example, nitrogen, compressed air) are even advisable to use as autonomous ones.

Finding 4: NPP chilled water and steam systems cannot be used, for the selected conditions, as resources for HPP under any scenario.

Finding 5: The Systems that provide key resources for HPPs are available at KhNPP and RNPP and they can be modified to obtain the required parameters. As a rule, the development and justification of the design for each modification is required.

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ECCN: **Finding 6:** All systems of Ukrainian NPPs are universal for other VVER-type NPPs. Considerations and conclusions on the conditions of modifications can also be applied to other European NPPs with VVER reactors (with VVER-1000 reactors above all).

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AL: **Finding 7:** The list of documents for modifications and requirements for modifications are defined in the regulatory framework of Ukraine.

Conclusion 1: Under the terms of NPP systems modification, there are no significant problems for the use of resources for an HPP. Licensing conditions allow to make the necessary changes to the NPP design.

Conclusion 2: To select the optimal deployment scenario, it should be considered that it is advisable to use only some of the resources for the needs of the HPP. These resources are Electricity, Cooling Water and Demineralized Water. It is advisable to provide the other part of the resources as autonomous for the HPP project - Nitrogen, Compressed Air, Chilled Water. The use of the third group of resources is very dependent on the placement conditions. This group can be used both from NPPs and autonomously – Tap Water and Waste Water.

Conclusion 3: When choosing an NPP as a supplier of resources for an HPP, an important factor is the multi-unit of NPPs. Multi-unit NPPs are the first priority choice due to the reliability of the uninterrupted supply of resources for an HPP. The more NPP resources are used for an HPP, the more impact the reliability of the resources has. Multi-unit NPPs have a greater possibility of reserving resources.

**Annex 3: Full Report of Subtask 3 – Safety Case approach NPP-HPP
integration and Example for Rivne NPP**

Deliverable 4.2 *subtask 3*

*Safety Case approach NPP-HPP integration
and Example for Rivne NPP*

NRG

Revision 1.A

July 2024

Revisions

IND REV	RELEASE DATE	PARAGRAPH	SCOPE OF THE REVISION
1.A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue, reviewed by ESG

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AOP(s)	Abnormal Operation Procedure(s)
ARC	Control Assembly (VVER-440)
DBA	Design Base Accident
DiD	Defence in Depth
DW(S)	Demineralized Water (System)
EOP(s)	Emergency Operation Procedure(s)
EPDS	Electric Power Distribution System
FSF	Fundamental Safety Functions
GSR	General Safety Requirements
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
HTSE	High Temperature Steam Electrolyzer
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
INSAG	International Nuclear Safety Advisory Group
MoC	Management of Change
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PIE	Postulated Initiating Event
PSA	Probabilistic Safety Analysis
RCP(s)	Reactor Cooling Pump(s)
RCS	Reactor Control System
RNPP	Rivne NPP
SAMG	Severe Accident Management Guidelines
SAR	Safety Analysis Report
SG	Steam Generator
SRS	Safety Report Series
SSC or SSCs	System(s) Structure(s) and Component(s)
SSG	Specific Safety Guide
SSR	Specific Safety Requirements
SW(S)	Service Water (System)
VVER	Water-Water Power Reactor (type NPP)

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20 Introduction

This report is part of Task 4.2 -subtask 3- and concerns the generic Safety Case Approach for the various integration scenarios, followed by a specific example of a Rivne NPP-HPP integration scenario.

A Safety Case evaluates the safety impact of modifications to a nuclear installation or activity. When an HPP is (partly) integrated with an NPP, the impact on safety of the NPP needs to be investigated and shown (in a Safety Case) that it still complies with existing regulations. The Management of Change procedure provides guidance on the level of detail of the required safety evaluation, depending on the safety category of the systems to be modified. The Safety Case Report is one of the necessary documents to be submitted for a license update /renewal.

Chapter 2 of this report describes the generic Management of Change (MoC) procedure, the safety classification of systems and the requirements for a safety case.

Chapter 3 is a generic safety case describing the various integration scenarios (see **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**). This generic safety case describes all aspects that need to be addressed in the safety case and the documentation that need to be modified due to the integration. This is still in general terms since a specific safety case can only be based on detailed design - and technical information from the installations involved. This is not available for theoretical integration scenarios.

Chapter 4 describes the specific safety case for an integration scenario for an HPP at Rivne NPP site (Ukraine) after evaluating several NPP systems having the possibility to be shared. The scenario taken into account is possible and realistic for the pilot hydrogen production plant at or near Rivne NPP. The safety impact of the integration scenario is evaluated and the impact on safety documentation is identified.

Another subtask, WP4.2 subtask 4 'Detailed assessment of the incident/accident scenarios' (by TU Dresden) will deal with the modelling of the physical impact of the HPP on the NPP and the calculation of the safety distances.

Other aspects that could also impact the license, for instance grid, environmental and site-specific issues will be dealt with in WP4.2 subtask 5 'Analysis of impact of integration on the licensing' (by GRS, Ansaldo).

The NPP-HPP integration scenarios to be investigated within the NPHyCo project are described in Task 1.2 (D1.2). The technical scenarios are given in Table 37.

Table 37: Summary of plant coupling scenarios.

Onsite Solutions	Offsite Solutions
1. Full integration, except chilled water, with electricity from the grid	5. Integration of cooling water and electricity from the grid
2. Full integration, except chilled water, with electricity as a load of the NPP	6. Integration of cooling water and electricity as a load of the NPP
3. Integration of cooling water and electricity from the grid	7. Integration of electricity as a load of the NPP.

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4. Integration of cooling water and electricity as a load of the NPP	8. Zero integration (benchmark), with electricity from the grid
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Other scenarios

Other hydrogen production technics and integration scenarios are also possible but technically not further developed in this project (as described in Work package 1.2). For instance, an economically attractive HPP-NPP configuration is the sharing/production of high temperature steam in combination with high-temperature steam electrolysis (HTSE). In this case the steam supply is diverted from the NPP to the HTSE process. HTSE has an operating range of 600-850°C and uses electricity and heat to produce hydrogen. Electrolysis efficiency increases at higher operating temperatures, requiring less electrical energy. An example of such a process is given in Figure 45.

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Figure 45: HTSE integrated with NPP. Main steam extraction and returning to condenser.

In Work package 4.3 the (safety/licensing) impact of these type of scenarios are further evaluated within the scope of the defined tasks.

Economics

In Work package 3 of the NPHyCo project the economic evaluation of the HPP-NPP is performed. Also in this report economic drivers play an important role but are not further evaluated. However, a rough cost estimation is given in Appendix 3 to get insight in the order of magnitude of the costs for modifications and license update.

21 Modification processes for NPPs

Each NPP is obliged to have a program to manage modifications. Modifications shall cover adaptations to: structures, systems, components, operational limits and conditions, procedures, documentation and the operating organization, including safety assessment tools and -processes.

Such a modification program, often referred to as Management of Change (MoC) program, should ensure a proper design, safety assessment, review, implementation and testing of each modification. Depending on their safety significance, modifications shall be subject to approval by the regulator. Also, the consequences of the modifications for procedures, human tasks and performance needs to be analyzed. In addition, all plans, drawings, documents and computer programs need to be revised in line with the modification.

21.1 Categorization

Modifications need to be categorized based on their safety significance, according to IAEA SSG-71:

Category 1: Modifications with significant impact on safety

Modifications in Category 1 are capable of having a significant effect on safety or involve an alteration of the principles and conclusions on which the design and the licensing of the plant were based. Such modifications might involve changes in the set of design basis accidents, they might alter the technical solutions adopted for meeting the safety goals or they might lead to changes in the operating rules.

Modifications in Category 1 will involve a comprehensive safety assessment and might also necessitate prior approval, an amendment to the operating license or even the issuing of a new license by the regulatory body.

Category 2: Modifications with impact on safety

Modifications in Category 2 include changes in items important to safety and in associated operational approaches and/or procedures, and usually necessitate an update of the safety analysis report or other licensing documents. Modifications in Category 2 are characterized by a minor influence on safety and no significant alteration to the principles on which the licensing of the plant has been based. For such modifications, there should be no changes to the conclusions in the licensing documents. In the design stage for modifications in Category 2, it should be determined whether there are negative side effects, such as degradation of safety features or an expectation of causing significant radiation exposure from implementing the modification.

For modifications in Category 2, the operating organization should inform the regulatory body, in accordance with established procedures.

Category 3: Modifications with no impact on safety

Modifications in Category 3 are minor modifications that can be characterized in one of the following ways:

- (a) The modification has no consequences for safety.
- (b) The items to be modified are classified as items not important to safety and are not mentioned in the licensing documents.

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- (c) The modification, even if designed or implemented incorrectly, could not affect safety.

21.2 Safety Assessment

21.2.1 Initial safety assessment

According to IAEA SSG-71 (referring to GSR Part 4 (Rev. 1)) the safety assessment of a nuclear power plant is required to be updated as necessary so as to take into account modifications to the design or operation of the plant. An initial safety assessment should be carried out before starting a modification to determine whether the proposed modification has any consequences for safety. The implementation phase for the modification as well as the plant operation after the modification should be considered in the initial safety assessment. The result of the initial safety assessment should lead to a decision on the categorization of the proposed modifications.

Depending on the results of the initial safety assessment, a more detailed and comprehensive safety assessment might be needed. If the initial assessment has clearly demonstrated that the modification will have no adverse consequences for safety during its implementation nor after the modification is made, then further safety assessment might not be necessary.

21.2.2 Comprehensive safety assessment

A comprehensive safety assessment should include an evaluation of the effect of the modification on radiological hazards during its implementation and during subsequent commissioning, testing, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the modified plant. This evaluation should include the effect of the modified plant item and its associated system on physically adjacent systems and plant items, and on interconnected systems or support systems such as electrical power supplies.

21.2.2.1 Topics for demonstration

The comprehensive safety assessment should demonstrate that the modified plant can be operated safely and that it complies with the system specifications and relevant safety requirements. Special consideration should be given to demonstrating the following:

- (a) The modification complies with all relevant requirements related to design, commissioning and operation of nuclear power plants (IAEA SSR-2/1 and SSR-2/2, Rev. 1).
- (b) Interfaces with nuclear security have been taken into account.
- (c) New or modified systems will not adversely affect the safety of other items important to safety under all plant states.
- (d) Due account has been taken of the potential consequences of the modification being inadequately implemented.
- (e) The occupational and public exposures (during implementation, operation and during accidents) as a result of the modification are below approved limits and as low as reasonably achievable.

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- (f) The modification can be performed without adversely affecting the safety of the plant and will not introduce new hazards.
- (g) The technical or operational effect of the modified system on each of the accident sequences considered in the safety analysis report has been adequately assessed.
- (h) Each identified failure mode of the modified system has been assessed by appropriate evaluation methods. In addition to the direct effects on the plant, the effects on items important to safety should also be considered in the assessment.
- (i) The impact of potential external events and the consequences of inadequate qualification of the structures, systems and components to withstand them has been assessed and/or analyzed.
- (j) The environmental impact has been evaluated and considered.
- (k) The safety consequences of implementing the modifications (and of any temporary equipment used), and the ability to withstand anticipated operational occurrences and accident conditions during the implementation, have been considered.
- (l) The potential interaction with other design changes has been reviewed to ensure control of the plant configuration after implementation of the modification (e.g. because a later change might depend on whether an earlier proposed change has already been made).
- (m) The scope of commissioning testing meets system specifications.
- (n) The radioactive waste arising from the plant modification will be properly managed.
- (o) The need to temporarily disable any safety related plant interlocks, or to suspend any operating restrictions, has been fully assessed before implementation, and steps are in place to ensure the prompt reversal and reinstatement of such measures.
- (p) In a case where a modification has already been implemented in a similar plant, any differences between the plants have been properly assessed before design documentation, implementation procedures or test procedures have been duplicated.

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21.2.2.2 Submissions

Proposals for modifications submitted for independent review should be in accordance with the management system of the operating organization. The proposals should specify the functional requirements and safety requirements for the proposed modifications and should show how these are to be met. The amount of information needed will depend on the extent and complexity of the modification; however, at a minimum, submissions should include the following:

- a) Design documents or amendments to initial design documents.
- b) A description of the design and justification of the proposed modification.
- c) Sketches, drawings and a list of materials.
- d) Specifications for parts and materials.
- e) Applicable codes and standards and relevant safety analyses.

- f) A safety assessment and, if applicable, proposed modifications to the operating limits and conditions, if any.
- g) An analysis of adverse environmental conditions or operating conditions, including any implications in terms of radioactive waste, contamination, radioactive releases and exposure to radiation.
- h) A description of the methods of fabrication, installation and testing, including the methods of validation and verification of software.
- i) Specification of the operating conditions of the plant, or parts thereof, necessary to implement the modification.
- j) Statement of requirements for the assurance of quality in the management system.
- k) A description of the equipment qualification (see Requirement 13 of SSR-2/2 (Rev. 1)) and the testing and commissioning to be performed after implementation.
- l) A description of changes to the safety related plant maintenance and ageing management arrangements.
- m) A description of how to determine the effectiveness of the achievement of the objectives of the modification.

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The above list of topics that have to be checked and demonstrated and documents that have to be submitted for modifications impacting the NPP safety, shows that these types of modifications require a lot of work. This implies that sharing of safety systems between the NPP and the HPP is only likely to be profitable if it leads to significant cost savings, either capital or operational costs.

21.3 Overview of steps

Figure 46 presents an example of the steps to be followed when developing the overall modification process for safety related modifications.

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Figure 46: Example of steps in the modification process (IAEA SSG-71)

22 Safety Case approach

The “Safety Assessment“, point f) in the list of documents that have to be submitted to the regulator (section 21.2.2.2), will result in a Safety Case Report. This important report for the safety demonstration does not stick to a strict format or lay-out as long as the safety topics mentioned in section 21.2.2.2 are addressed.

In this chapter an example of a format of a Safety Case is given, but other formats can be chosen depending on the type of modifications. It is meant to present an overview of the activities that might have to be performed when modifying a nuclear installation. It will not be necessary to address all topics in every modification, but in case of serious modification to safety systems and/or design principles more or less all topics will have to be addressed.

22.1 Safety Case set-up

The following paragraphs describe each a chapter of typical safety case report.

22.1.1 Introduction

In this section the installation (nuclear power plant) is described and characteristics i.e. performance numbers, properties, dedicated functions etc. are briefly described. Relevant topics related to safety, like location and site/environmental situation, are also described (if applicable).

22.1.2 Current situation: system descriptions

To be able to evaluate the safety impact, the systems to be modified need to be explained, for instance based on the following topics:

- 1) System functions (safety, operational)
- 2) System description (working principle)
- 3) Schematic representation of system or drawing (no P&ID, too detailed)
- 4) Conditions (if applicable: p, T, V, flow, purity, conductivity, pH, mineral content, etc.)
- 5) Layout & properties (size, location, interfaces with other systems)
- 6) Description of operational states (configurations) and functions
- 7) Relation to safety (safety class? Function in emergency conditions? Proximity to safety equipment? Etc.)
- 8) Equipment qualification (codes & standards)

22.1.3 Shared situation: modified systems

In this section the modifications on the above-described systems are presented.

All topics mentioned in section 22.1.2 need to be addressed. Attention should be given to:

- Integration in the new situation
 - How can it be realized and built in in the current situation?
 - What choices/options are there? What is the rationale for the chosen option?
- Design and quality aspects
 - Does the coupling have design implications for the nuclear installations?
 - What are the (additional) requirements laid upon the modification and the HPP related installation parts due to the coupling to the nuclear installation?

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- Are there any operational restrictions for the HPP due to the coupling to the nuclear installation (training, procedures to follow, qualifications of personnel,)?

22.1.4 Impact on operation and plant conditions

22.1.4.1 Current situation

What (operational) functions are attributed to the current system in the various situations: normal operation, accident conditions, emergencies, training, maintenance, etc.?

So a short description should be presented of the situations where the system plays a role (and in what procedures/instructions this is described).

The following topics of concern can be relevant and need to be addressed (list is not exhaustive):

- Operations
 - Start/stop conditions (set-points, alarms etc.)
 - Functions per operational state (e.g. start-up, shutdown)
 - Alarms during operation or abnormal situations
 - Accident procedures
 -
- Services and maintenance
 - Procedures
 - Tests
 - Inspections
 - ...
- Long term operation
 - Asset management
 - Ageing management
 - Obsolescence

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22.1.4.2 Modified (Shared) Situation

What is the impact of the modifications to the subjects mentioned above?

What procedures, maintenance protocols, check-outs procedures, training and work instructions, ... etc. need to be changed?

22.1.4.3 Conclusion on impact on operation and plant conditions

The overall impact on the described operational topics and plant conditions should be listed and a qualitative statement on the safety implication should be made, indicating the magnitude of the impact on the safety of the nuclear installation.

22.1.5 Impact on Safety

22.1.5.1 Impact on Safety Functions

Evaluation of the fundamental safety functions in the original and in the modified situation should be performed. SSCs performing specific safety functions are to be determined for impact analyses on the fundamental safety functions as a result of modification(s).

The outcome of the impact assessment on the safety functions should be that there will be no impact on the Fundamental Safety Functions or that appropriate measures are taken to prevent (any significant) impact on the Fundamental Safety Functions.

22.1.5.1.1 Requirements/regulation

Relevant requirements and guidelines with respect to Fundamental safety functions are provided the IAEA SSR-2/1 **requirement 4 Fundamental safety functions**:

Fulfilment of the following fundamental safety functions for a nuclear power plant shall be ensured for all plant states: (i) control of reactivity; (ii) removal of heat from the reactor and from the fuel store; and (iii) confinement of radioactive material, shielding against radiation and control of planned radioactive releases, as well as limitation of accidental radioactive releases.

In Table 38 an example is given of detailing of the fundamental safety function Control of Reactivity into several specific safety functions [IAEA-TECDOC-1787, 2016].

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Table 38: Detailing of fundamental safety function in specific safety functions.

Control of Reactivity	R1 - Maintain core criticality control	R-1.1: Control of RCS boric acid concentration
		R-1.2: Control rod position
		R-1.3: Control reactor power distribution
		R-1.4: Control reactor thermal power
		R-1.5: Control linear power density
		R-1.6: Control pellet-clad interaction risk
		R-1.7: Control departure from nucleate boiling risk
		R-1.8: Limit reactor thermal power
		R-1.9: Limit linear power density
		R-1.10: Limit pellet-clad interaction risk
		R-1.11: Limit departure from nucleate boiling risk
		R-1.12: Reduce reactor power
Control of Reactivity	R2 - Shutdown and maintain core sub-criticality	R-2-1: Fast negative reactivity insertion into reactor core (reactor trip)
		R-2-2: Injection of high borated water into RCS at high pressure (e.g. in case of anticipated transients without scram)
		R-2-3: Injection of high borated water into RCS at medium and low pressure in case of DBA
		R-2-4: Compensate for reactivity increase during plant cooldown to the safe shutdown state by increasing the boric acid concentration in the RCS
Control of Reactivity	R3 - Prevention of uncontrolled positive reactivity insertion into the core	R-3.1: Restrict feedwater flow to steam generator (SGs) after reactor trip
		R-3.2: Isolation of feedwater supply to a damaged SG
		R-3.3: Prevent SG draining to RCS in case of SG tube rupture
		R-3.4: Prevent uncontrolled SG depressurization - Stop steam flow to turbine
		R-3.5: Prevent uncontrolled SG depressurization - Stop steam flow to atmosphere
		R-3.6: Prevent uncontrolled SG depressurization - Stop steam flow to main steam system
		R-3.7: Stop RCS forced flow to limit heat exchange in the SG
		R-3.8: Prevent component cooling water flow to RCS through leakage on heat exchanger (at low RCS pressure)
		R-3.9: Stop demineralized water make-up to RCS
Control of Reactivity	R4 - Maintain sufficient sub-criticality of fuel stored outside the RCS but within the site	R-4.1: Control of spent fuel pool water boric acid concentration

ECCN: N

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In the Safety Report of the NPP the implemented (active) systems are described which secures the three fundamental safety functions (FSF). A reference or citation can be made to the sections of the Safety Report where events are evaluated and safety is secured by these systems.

22.1.5.2 Impact on Defence in Depth

In the nuclear industry the Defence in Depth approach is applied. Defence in Depth (DiD) means that multiple safety measures are in place in layers to guarantee safety. If the first level is compromised, additional layers exist to protect incidents developing into (severe) accidents.

A general description of the various levels is provided in the following table.

Table 39: Levels of Defence in Depth.

DiD Level	Objective	The way to achieve this
1	Prevention of abnormal operation and failures	Conservative design, high quality in construction and operation.
2	Control of abnormal operations and detection of failures	Control-, limiting-, protection- and surveillance systems.
3	Control of accidents within the design base	Engineered safety features and accident procedures
4	Control of severe plant conditions, prevention of accident progression and mitigation of consequences	Complementary measures and accident management
5	Mitigation of radiological consequences of radiological emissions	Off-site emergency planning and response.

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It has to be evaluated in what way the -to be modified- SSCs will impact DiD. Topics to be evaluated are margins and conservatisms, radiation shielding, adequate procedures etc. (see Table 40Fout!
Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.)

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AL: N
The outcome should be that the DiD levels are not affected by the modifications or that appropriate measures are taken to prevent (significant) impact on DiD levels.

22.1.5.2.1 Requirements/regulation

Relevant requirements and guidelines with respect to Defence in Depth are provided in the IAEA SSR-2/1 **requirement 7 Application of defence in depth:**

The design of a nuclear power plant shall incorporate defence in depth. The levels of defence in depth shall be independent as far as is practicable.

Req. 7 (Art. 4.11). The design

(a) Shall provide for multiple physical barriers to the release of radioactive material to the environment;

(b) Shall be conservative, and the construction shall be of high quality, so as to provide assurance that failures and deviations from normal operation are minimized, that accidents are prevented as far as is practicable and that a small deviation in a plant parameter does not lead to a cliff edge effect;

(c) Shall provide for the control of plant behavior by means of inherent and engineered features, such that failures and deviations from normal operation requiring actuation of safety systems are minimized or excluded by design, to the extent possible;

(d) Shall provide for supplementing the control of the plant by means of automatic actuation of safety systems, such that failures and deviations from normal operation that exceed the capability of control systems can be controlled with a high level of confidence, and the need for operator actions in the early phase of these failures or deviations from normal operation is minimized;

(e) Shall provide for systems, structures and components and procedures to control the course of and, as far as practicable, to limit the consequences of failures and deviations from normal operation that exceed the capability of safety systems;

(f) Shall provide multiple means for ensuring that each of the fundamental safety functions is performed, thereby ensuring the effectiveness of the barriers and mitigating the consequences of any failure or deviation from normal operation.

In general, the DiD layers can be described as follows (see also Figure 47):

Level 1: Prevention of deviations through the application of conservative design, quality assurance and proper operation. This includes operating the reactor within limits, which in turn include margins from the conservative design.

Level 2: Detection and correction of deviations and malfunctions. This involves making corrections before safety limits are reached. The occurrence of design accidents as well as their consequences are reduced in this way.

Level 3: Accident control and intervention of safety systems to control design accidents. Safety limits are reached in this case.

Level 4: Reduction of the consequences of accidents for the environment by taking measures that prevent or limit the release of radioactive substances.

Level 5: Mitigation of radiological consequences of significant releases of radioactive materials (off-site emergency response).

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Figure 47: Defence Layers and Barriers [SRS No.46, IAEA,2005].

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In Table 40 [Safety Report Series No.46, IAEA, 2005] Safety Principles described in ‘Basis Safety Principles for NPPs’ [75-INSAG-3 Rev. 1, INSAG-12, IAEA, Vienna 1999] are coupled to the different levels of DiD and for the different stages in plant life. This table can be used as a check list to determine the (safety) SSCs that are incorporated in -or related to- the defence layers, and the accompanying safety principles/topics.

22.1.5.3 Impact on Risks

By changing SSCs new risks can be introduced or also reduced. Evaluation of risk aspects concerns for example radiation for workers, conventional risks, SSCs linked to or responsible for nuclear safety. For instance, extra pipework can result in added flooding risk (increase of leakage/break frequency) or increase of radiation in specific areas. Therefore, the existing risk evaluation of the NPP should be checked if modifications have impact on the different process parts causing changes in the final PSA result, see Figure 48.

Figure 48: Level 1 PSA process parts for internal flooding [IAEA SSG-3 rev.1]

The conclusion should be that the different existing risk levels for the different areas are not (significantly) affected by the modifications by taking appropriate measures (if applicable).

22.1.5.4 Requirements/regulation

Relevant requirements and guidelines are provided in:

IAEA GSR Part 3 for Radiation Protection (Requirement 21): Responsibilities of employers, registrants and licensees for the protection of workers.

Employers, registrants and licensees shall be responsible for the protection of workers against occupational exposure. Employers, registrants and licensees shall ensure that protection and safety is optimized and that the dose limits for occupational exposure are not exceeded.

IAEA SSR-2/1 for Nuclear Risks (art. 5.76):

The design shall take due account of the probabilistic safety analysis of the plant for all modes of operation and for all plant states, including shutdown, with particular reference to:

(a) Establishing that a balanced design has been achieved such that no particular feature or postulated initiating event makes a disproportionately large or significantly uncertain contribution to the overall risks, and that, to the extent practicable, the levels of defence in depth are independent.

(b) Providing assurance that situations in which small deviations in plant parameters could give rise to large variations in plant conditions (cliff edge effects) will be prevented.

(c) Comparing the results of the analysis with the acceptance criteria for risk where these have been specified.

EU-OSH Directive on Occupational Safety & Health and Safety

These requirements and regulation are described in more detail Work Package 4.1.

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22.1.5.5 Impact on Safety Analyses and Safety (Analysis) Report

Impact-evaluation of existing deterministic and probabilistic safety analyses. E.g. evaluation of the list of Potential Initiating Events (PIEs) for which thermo-hydraulic (transients) and radiological calculations (dose consequences) are performed, which are applicable on the modified systems. Are the relevant PIEs still enveloping for the modified situation or are new PIEs to be developed? What contributions due to the modification are impacting on existing PIEs?

Examples of possible applicable PIEs are:

- Loss of electrical power supplies:
 - Loss of normal electrical power
- Steam line break, in case of sharing steam from Steam Generator (SG)
- Secondary loop instabilities, in case of sharing steam from SG
- Special internal events (e.g. due to increase of frequencies of occurrence):
 - Internal fires or explosions.
 - Internal flooding.
 - Loss of support systems.
- External events: to be checked on event sequences/developments, e.g. consequences of earthquake on HPP SSCs and/or modified/new SSCs in the NPP à possible resulting in extra events for the NPP to be taken into account.

It also needs to be checked what sections of the existing Safety Analysis Report (SAR) are impacted by the modification and what the implications are for that. The SAR's content is given in the following list, the bold chapters are possibly affected by the modifications:

- Chapter 1: Introduction and general considerations.

- **Chapter 2: Site characteristics.**
- Chapter 3: Safety objectives and design rules for structures, systems and components.
- Chapter 4: Reactor.
- Chapter 5: Reactor coolant system and associated systems.
- Chapter 6: Engineered safety features.
- **Chapter 7: Instrumentation and control.**
- **Chapter 8: Electrical power.**
- **Chapter 9: Auxiliary systems and civil structures.**
- **Chapter 10: Steam and power conversion systems.**
- Chapter 11: Management of radioactive waste.
- **Chapter 12: Radiation protection.**
- **Chapter 13: Conduct of operations.**
- Chapter 14: Plant construction and commissioning.
- **Chapter 15: Safety analysis.**
- **Chapter 16: Operational limits and conditions for safe operation.**
- Chapter 17: Management for safety.
- Chapter 18: Human factors engineering.
- **Chapter 19: Emergency preparedness and response.**
- Chapter 20: Environmental aspects.
- Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of life aspects.

The conclusion should be that measures are taken (if applicable) to fulfill the existing safety requirements and authorized limits, followed by updating and/or extending the current NPP Safety Analyses and the Safety (Analysis) Report.

22.1.5.5.1 Requirements/regulation

IAEA SSR-2/1 (req.42, Art.5.71-5.76): **Safety analysis of the plant design**

A safety analysis of the design for the nuclear power plant shall be conducted in which methods of both deterministic analysis and probabilistic analysis shall be applied to enable the challenges to safety in the various categories of plant states to be evaluated and assessed.

IAEA GSR Part 4 -Rev.1 (req.20, Art 4.62-4.64): **Documentation of the safety assessment**

The results and findings of the safety assessment shall be documented.

22.1.6 Safety Case conclusion

In the conclusion of the Safety Case report the impact on safety is summarized for the different safety aspects. The relations and interactions between the different safety aspects need to be described and indications need to be given on the relevance of the various safety aspects that are impacted.

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23 Example: Rivne NPP

This chapter presents an example of a Safety Case Report for the Rivne NPP with the modifications to the systems that might be shared with the HPP pilot plant. The actual systems to be shared will be defined in NPHyCo work package 5 ‘Pilot Plant’.

The set-up of this safety case is quite comprehensive although most of the proposed shared systems have little safety impact. This is to give an ‘as good as possible’ indication of what needs to be addressed in case the shared systems do have impact on the safety of the NPP.

23.1 Characteristics

23.1.1 Rivne NPP

Rivne NPP is the first nuclear power plant in Ukraine with pressurized nuclear reactors, currently the only type of reactors in Ukraine, and the only one with power units based on the first reactors of this series VVER-440 (V-213).

Rivne NPP (RNPP) is located in Volyn Polesie, near the Styr River, four kilometers from the town of Varash. The plant's history dates back to 1971, when the design of the West-Ukrainian NPP began, which during construction was renamed Rivne NPP. The abbreviated name is SS RNPP, a separate subdivision of NAEK Energoatom.

The construction of the plant started in 1973. The first two power units with VVER-440 reactors were commissioned in 1980-19⁸¹, the 3rd power unit - VVER-1000 - in 19⁸⁶. The 4th power unit - VVER-1000 - in 2004. Rivne NPP was the first nuclear power plant in the Ukraine to pass IAEA inspection in early 1989. In 2010, the State Nuclear Regulatory Inspectorate decided to extend the service life of Units 1 and 2 for twenty years.

Table 41: Characteristics of VVERs.

Parameters	VVER-440	VVER-1000
Reactor thermal power, MW	1375	3030
Efficiency, (net)	29,7	31,7
Pressure, kgf/cm ²		
before Turbine	44,0	60,0
in Primary side	125	160,0
Water Temperature, °C:		
Reactor inlet	269	289
Reactor outlet	300	319
Core Diameter, m	2,88	3,12
Core Height, m	2,50	3,50
Fuel element diameter, mm	9,1	9,1
Number of Fuel rods in Assembly	126	312
Number of Assemblies	(312+ARC 37)	163
Uranium mass, t	42	66

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Average uranium enrichment, %	3,5	4,26
Average fuel burn-up, MW-day/kg	28,6	48,4

Figure 49: Location of Rivne NPP near Varash town.

An extensive description of the Rivne NPP is further given in Appendix 1.

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23.1.2 HPP Integration options

The needs of an HPP may be covered with already existing infrastructure and systems of an NPP. A good level of integration depends on the availability of the respective sources on the NPP site, the induced impacts of such coupling and finally of the commercial benefit it creates.

The level of integration is NPP dependent and reaches from full integration (see Figure 50) to no integration (see Figure 52).

For Rivne NPP the following provisions are considered for sharing with an HPP:

1. Electricity
2. Demineralized Water
3. Domestic water supply
4. Service water for cooling (non-safety components)
5. Chilled water
6. Household sewage
7. Pressurized air
8. Nitrogen

The systems delivering these provisions are described and a selection for sharing is made.

Due to the relatively low steam temperatures, the possible sharing of steam will not be considered for Rivne NPP.

Figure 50: Full integration scenario.

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Figure 51: Partial integration scenario (on-site).

Figure 52: Zero integration scenario (off-site).

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23.1.3 HPP location possibilities

In Table 42 two location options of the HPP facility are introduced.

Table 42: HPP dimensions and Solutions for locations.

HPP dimensions	Onsite location place	Offsite location place (in the sanitary protection zone)
<p>Above ground performance.</p> <p>Size of the HPP-area: 30x40 m</p>	<p>The site is located in the area of cooling towers No. 3, 4, 5 (diagonally between cooling tower No. 3 and No. 5). The maximum dimensions of the site are approximately 110*92 m, usage approximately 86*80 m. Nearby (45m) there is a Diesel-generator station (standby). The minimum distance to the cooling towers is approx. 138 m to tower No. 3, to No. 4 – 159 m, to No. 5 – 177 m. Near the site there is an overpass, highways and approach railway tracks.</p> <p>This option is located closer to water supply network; a substantial</p>	<p>The site is located at a distance of 2900 m from the open switchgear-330 kV and 2750 m from the town’s industrial structures. The dimensions of the site are 182*151 m. A distance of 10-15 m to the main water supply network. There are highways and access railway tracks near the site.</p> <p>This option has the disadvantage with respect to communication (line) possibilities; the site is located in a potentially safer place for the NPP.</p>

HPP dimensions	Onsite location place	Offsite location place (in the sanitary protection zone)
	justification of safety and location is required.	

Locations at the industrial site and in the sanitary protection zone were analyzed for the RNPP. Due to the potential risk of placing an HPP near power units, hydraulic structures and other important objects, two places were considered: the first - on the territory of the industrial site, and the second - outside the territory of the industrial site in the sanitary protection zone, but with the possibility of using/sharing the necessary resources (electricity, water, staff, etc.). Near all locations there are highways and access railway tracks (see Figure 53, Figure 54 and Figure 55).

The buildings and structures of the NPP are designed for the impact of an air shock wave with a compression pressure along the front of 10 kPa for the structures of power units #1, 2 and 30 kPa for power units #3, 4. According to national and international regulatory documents, there are no requirements for anti-missile construction. Therefore, calculations of this coefficient were not carried out in NPP projects.

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ECCN: N

Figure 53: Locations of HPP scenarios onsite the Rivne NPP (site #1) and in the sanitary protection zone (site #2).

Figure 54: Location of site #1 (approximate minimum distance to: cooling tower #3 - 138 m, cooling tower #4 - 159 m, cooling tower #5 - 177 m, common standby diesel generators - 45 m, open switchgear - 1500 m, turbine department - 450 m).

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Figure 55: Location of site #2 (approximate distance to: the town - 1100 m, to the NPP - 1200 m).

23.1.4 HPP needs

Figure 56 **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** gives a general plant design presented by a block flow diagram. It shows on the left side the auxiliary systems that provide the inputs for hydrogen production via electrolysis. These are electricity and demineralized water as main consumables; pressurized air for pneumatically activated valves and nitrogen for flushing of the equipment; furthermore, cooling water is needed to remove the dissipated heat and a wastewater connection to take wastewater from the feed water purification.

The core components of hydrogen production are shown in the middle: the feedwater make-up unit, the electrolysis-stack itself and the gas separation and purification units.

Finally, there are the subsystems for compression and (intermediate) storage of the produced hydrogen.

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Figure 56: General Block Flow Diagram.

Figure 57: Process Flow Diagram (PEM).

Figure 57 gives quantitative information for a 30MW electrolyzer HPP with Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (PEM) technology.

For Rivne NPP integration with an LTE (PEM or AEL) HPP with a total capacity of 40-45MW (30-40 MW 20kV load of electrolyzer) is foreseen to produce about 0.5-0.6 t/h of hydrogen.

23.2 Potential Systems for Sharing; Selection for safety case

In this section a brief description is given of the systems having the potential for sharing with the HPP given the needs of the HPP. The system selection for safety evaluation in this report is based on potential economic benefits and a (possible) relation to safety of the given system.

More specific information about the systems and HPP needs is given in Task 5.3 of this project.

23.2.1 Electric Power Distribution System

General

Power units №1 and №2 each consist of one VVER-440 reactor with an electrical capacity of 420 MW, and two turbine units with an electrical capacity of 220 MW each. Power units №3 and №4 each consist of one VVER-1000 reactor and one generator with an electrical capacity of 1000 MW. To produce power at a voltage of 330 kV, power units №1, №2 and №3 are connected to the 330 kV switchgear. The 330 kV substation is connected to the 110 kV networks by a 330/110 kV autotransformer connection. To produce power at a voltage of 750 kV, power Unit 4 is connected to the 750 kV switchgear, the 750 kV open switchgear is connected to 330 kV switchgear by a 750/330 kV autotransformer.

Specific system for sharing

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear is needed to supply power to the HPP. For this transformation a lower voltage is needed.

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear is designed to supply power of local district consumers, and to provide power supply to the reserve(backup) transformers of power units 1 and 2 with installed capacity 40MVA 110kV/6kV.

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear consists of 12 cubicles (CP), where CP8 is designated as a reserve position. This reserve position creates the possibility to make a E-connection with the HPP possible. The 110 kV outdoor switchgear is presented in the next figure (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**).

In Appendix 2 the system is further described with respect to normal functioning and functioning in case of failures.

Figure 58: Open Switch Gear 110 kV. The reserve position CP8 is indicated by the blue dotted circle.

Needs of the HPP

The capacity of the hydrogen station is assumed to be 45 MWe (of which the capacity of the electrolyzer is 30 MW).

Power supply can be divided into:

- source of direct current, necessary for electrolysis.
- source of alternating current, necessary for the equipment.

This is approximately 93% DC consumption and 7% AC consumption. Electrolysis plants are usually connected to the medium voltage network (20-30 kV). In addition, compressors will need a voltage level of 6 kV, and other equipment will work from 400 V.

Selection for sharing

For this example, the EPDS is selected for evaluation of sharing with the HPP due to potential economic benefits in combination with possible impact on safety related SSCs.

Implication for the selected system

The NPP does not have a transformer with an output voltage of 20 kV. The modification should include the installation of such a transformer with an output power of at least 40 MW, as well as a rectifier. However, a power line must be drawn to the NPP site to connect the HPP equipment.

A power line with a voltage of 6 kV from the external network must also be fed to the HPP inside the NPP site. A transformer with an output voltage of 6 kV is available at the NPP site (normal buses), but the possibility of their use for an additional load should be justified. It is advisable to install the rectifier inside the HPP. This scenario may also require an additional transformer (output voltage 0.4kV) to control the HPP equipment and valves.

Modification is required - inside the NPP, a design for laying electrical cables through the territory of the NPP to the HPP site and a design for installing and connecting a rectifier. A design for installing an additional transformer (determination of locations and justification of the impact on NPP safety) and a design for connecting an additional load to the normal 6kV buses. Outside the NPP site the design of a substation with transformers connected to the grid is necessary.

23.2.2 Demineralized Water System

The NPP's demineralized water plant with a capacity of 265 m³/h is designed to produce chemically demineralized water (DW) to replenish steam and condensate losses in the primary and secondary circuits. The technological scheme of demineralization includes five "chains" of desalination including several filtration steps. The quality of chemically desalinated water is represented by the following parameters, for which the exact values are not exactly known due to setpoint values for the removal of filters for regeneration:

- SiO₂ ≥ 20 µg/dm³;
- Na ≥ 5.0 µg/dm³;
- Æ (conductivity) ≥ 0.3 µS/cm;
- Fe ≥ 20 µg/dm³;
- Total organic carbon ≥ 300 µg/dm³;
- Hydrogen pH indicator from 5.6 to 7.5;

- h. Mass concentration of sulfate ions $\geq 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$;
- i. Mass concentration of chloride ions $\geq 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dm}^3$

Consumption of DW by the operating power units amounts to a rate of 85-100 m³/h, with a maximum consumption of 270-285 m³/h. When the maximum production is reached, no reserve production takes place (in buffer tanks for example).

In Appendix 2 the system is further described with respect to safety functions and operational functions.

Needs of the HPP

HPP with a capacity of 40-45 MWe to produce about 0.5-0.6 t/h of hydrogen.

Electrolyzers need demineralized water of high purity. Usually, the conductivity shall be lower than 0.1 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. In addition, the total organic contents (TOC) and the amount of dissolved trace minerals or elements, e.g., Sodium, Iron, Silica, Chloride, Oxygen or CO₂ need to be limited.

The requirements of the DW for the HPP are listed below:

1. Flow rate (approx.): up to 6 t/h;
2. Electric conductivity max.: 0.056-0.1 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 25 °C)
3. Electrical resistivity min.: 18.2 ($\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ at 25 °C)
4. TOC: max. 10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$)
5. Sodium: max. 3 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$)
6. Chlorine: max. 1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$)

Selection for sharing

For this example, the DWS is selected for evaluation of sharing with the HPP due to potential economic benefits in combination with possible impact on safety related SSCs.

Implication for the selected system

The NPP production of demineralized water has sufficient capacity for both facilities. However, the water parameters do not correspond to the quality required for the HPP.

System modification is required - after-treatment water system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for post-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h.

23.2.3 System of domestic water supply of the NPP

The domestic tap (drinking) water supply system, external water supply and distribution systems are designed for uninterrupted and reliable supply of tap water to meet drinking, sanitary and hygienic and production needs. Water quality meets sanitary standards.

The centralized water supply networks include:

- main water supply networks from the pump station-1 to the pump station-2.
- main water supply networks from pump station-2 to the consumers.
- from pump station-2 to the Zabolottya village.
- water supply distribution networks of the industrial site and external facilities of the RNPP.

- distribution networks of water supply of construction bases.
- water supply distribution networks of the Zabolottya village.

Needs of the HPP

To be used for household needs of the HPP, in accordance with general industrial sanitary and hygienic standards.

Selection for sharing

Sharing of domestic water supply is an economic decision which has no license or safety implications and therefore will not be further evaluated in this report.

23.2.4 Service Water System

Service water is amongst others used for cooling of components of the turbine compartment. The service water is cooled in spray pools. The pumps of the spray pools have the following specifications:

- Flow rate: 4000 m³/h
- Pressure head: 95 m

N Purified water from pump stations is used to replenish water losses.

ECCN: In Appendix 2 the system is further described with respect to safety functions and operational functions.

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Needs of the HPP

Reference HPP: a low temperature electrolyzer of 40-45 MWe

Supply of cooling water would be required for the removal of the HPP process heat, which is mainly dissipated within the electrolyzer stack and its process water circuit. The following requirements are applicable:

- Consumption for HPP: 750-900 t/h
- T_{in} : < 50°C.
- Heating: dT < 30°C.
- Removed thermal power: 6000-12000 kW.
- Water quality is not regulated.

The water circulating system is part of the heat removal of the secondary side of the plant, from which the heat is transferred to the ultimate heat sink (river).

Selection for sharing

For this example, the SWS is selected for evaluation of sharing with the HPP due to potential economic benefits in combination with possible impact on safety related SSCs.

Implication for the selected system

Water is taken from the NPP pond and after the cooling it is discharged back into the pond. Maximum pump flow rate is 5040 m³/h, pressure is 44-54 bar. Each system cools the users of one power unit. The flow rate for the HPP (up to 900 t/h) can be ensured by a diverting part of the water from the standard system of one of the units.

Modification is required for the removal of a part of the water from the pressure part of the system. The return of heated water from the HPP cannot be discharged into the reservoir without cooling due to environmental restrictions. It is likely that a cooling tower cooling scheme, combined with circulating water, can be effective.

23.2.5 Chilled Water System

The RNPP power units № 1 and № 2 have four steam-ejector refrigerating machines. Steam-ejector refrigerating machines (hereinafter SERMs) are part of the refrigeration system and are designed for cooling the supply water to irrigation chambers and air coolers from air conditioning systems.

The four SERMs need to be supplied with heating steam (flow rate of 10,000 kg/h and a dryness of at least 0.94) as well as cooling water (flow rate of 1680 m³/h, temperature < 28°C). The installed capacity of the SERMs at RNPP are not sufficient in summer to ensure the regulated temperature regime in production buildings.

In the case of joint use with an HPP, additional load must be considered, and redundancy should be provided during the replacement of the SERMs.

RNPP units №3 and №4 have four steam chillers (hereinafter referred to as SECMs) in operation. The 4 chillers consist of 2 types with different capacity.

Needs of the HPP

Taking as a reference a low temperature electrolyzer of 40-45 MWe, the following inlet and outlet temperatures are required for cooling in the gas separation -and purification process: $T_{in} < 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T_{out} < 8^{\circ}\text{C}$. The thermal load that would be evacuated would be 350kWth.

Selection for sharing

Sharing of Chilled Water Supply is an economic decision which has no license or safety implications and therefore will not be further evaluated in this report.

23.2.6 The NPP household sewage system

Domestic wastewater from sanitary equipment (washbasins, sinks, ladders, drains, bathtubs, toilets, etc.) of the Rivne NPP facilities is collected by self-flowing pipelines and diverted to sewage pumping stations. From the pumping stations, wastewater is pumped through pressurized pipelines for treatment at treatment facilities: the biological treatment station of unit No. 3 and the wastewater treatment facilities of the industrial RNPP site.

Through a pressure pipeline, wastewater from the industrial treatment facilities of the RNPP is pumped to the city treatment facilities of Varash town for treatment and disinfection. The productivity

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of industrial treatment facilities is 730 m³/day. The volume of wastewater treated in 2022 is 157,403 m³ (average 431 m³/day).

Water drainage at the RNPP is carried out considering discharge regimes, quantitative and qualitative composition of wastewater coming from RNPP units and consumers. Acceptance of site wastewater into the water drainage system of the town of Varash is carried out on contractual terms.

Needs of the HPP

The electrolyzer can generate effluents, for example filters unblocking or cooling towers purge. These effluents must be collected and treated or eliminated by other system downstream.

Selection for sharing

Sharing of the household sewage is an economic decision which has no license or safety implications and therefore will not be further evaluated in this report.

23.2.7 Site's compressed (repair) air system

Compressor units are located on Air Compressor Station (ACS-2) and Nitrogen-oxygen station ACS-1. These units work in joint system as the systems of normal operation and are intended for maintaining the pressure in the general plant network (6-8 kgf/cm²), for carrying out works performed with compressed air in the site's departments. The compressed air system is atmospheric air compressed to a pressure of 6-8 kgf/cm².

The ACS-2 Air compressor station includes 4 compressors with a capacity of 50 m³/min each.

The ACS-1 Nitrogen-oxygen station includes:

- compressors with a capacity of 13.5/27 m³/min;
- compressors with a capacity of 30 m³/min each.

The quality of compressed air produced by piston compressors ACS-2 and ACS-1 for the general station system of compressed air for own needs corresponds to the 8-th pollution class and meets the following requirements: the size of solid particles, no more than 80 microns.

The content of extraneous impurities:

- solid particles, no more than 12.5 mg/m³;
- water in liquid form, 0.5 to 5 g/m³

Needs of the HPP

The HPP pressurized air supply requirements are 5 to 10 bar. The pressurized air is used for actuation of instrumentation, controls, and several equipment pneumatic drives. The pressurized air for the instrumentation must present specific characteristics in order to prevent corrosion and in general, degradation of the control elements.

For the use of pressurized air in the HPP it can be assumed that the quality of the available air of the NPP could be sufficient. Thus, to determine the level of integration in terms of pressurized air supply only the availability and storage capacity are to be analyzed.

Selection for sharing

Sharing of compressed air supply is an economic decision which has no license or safety implications and therefore will not be further evaluated in this report.

23.2.8 Nitrogen-oxygen station in the nitrogen section

The system for obtaining cryogenic air separation products is designed to provide the NPP with liquid and gaseous nitrogen with a pressure of up to 200 kgf/cm² and consists of 2 air distribution units. The system also includes compressor units ACS-1 and -2 and compressor unit ACS-3, which provide nitrogen distribution units with a pressure of up to 200 kgf/cm².

- Productivity - gaseous nitrogen 70 m³/h
- Productivity - liquid nitrogen 70 kg/h
- nitrogen purity 99.6% to 99.9%

Needs of the HPP

Nitrogen is needed for flushing and purging of the equipment, i.e. to remove hydrogen and oxygen from the system in emergency cases or for maintenance.

Selection for sharing

Sharing of nitrogen supply is an economic decision which has no license or safety implications and therefore will not be further evaluated in this report.

23.3 Modifications of the selected shared systems

23.3.1 Electric Power Distribution System

To organize the electrical supply of the HPP (on- or off-site), you will need:

- 110kV circuit breaker and 110kV disconnector on VRP-110kV,
- power transmission line with a voltage of 110 kV with a length of 2200m to 2800m,
- 63MVA step-down transformer (110kV/20kV/6kV),
- complete distribution devices for the voltage of 20, 6, and 0.4 kV for powering consumers of the HPP

The transformer can be placed both in the area of the open switchgear and in the area of the HPP site. It is also necessary to take into account the reservation of the HPP power supply line. The expediency of the choice will be determined by pre-project studies.

The presence of a free cell of 110 kV allows to implement the following connection scheme:

AL: N
ECCN: N

ECCN: N
AL: N

Figure 59: Electrical schematic diagram of a HPP substation.

For the organization of this scheme, according to preliminary estimates, the equipment listed in the table below is required.

Table 43: Proposed electrical part composition.

No.	Element	Remarks
1	Free cell (feeder) connection of three phases of power transmission of 45 MW to an open switchgear of 110 kV.	At the Rivne NPP there is a free cell (number 8) on the RU of 110 kV, from which the PVV can be powered. Missing - switch and disconnectors.
2	The 110/20/6kV transformer power supply line, which stretches from the cell of the 110 kV open switchgear to the power supply transformer of the HPP's own needs.	It can be implemented in the form of: 1) overhead (or underground) cable line consisting of three single-phase cables with a voltage of 110 kV (section 240 mm ² , aluminum); 2) Air current conduit (parameters not defined); 3) By an overhead power line (if there is a place to install supports).

No.	Element	Remarks
3	Power supply transformer for the needs of the HPP. TDTN 45(50) MW 110/20/6kV	It is possible that the power of the transformer will be higher than 45 MW. 110kV upper voltage to take power from 110kV open switchgear. An average voltage of 20 kV for powering the rectifier that feeds the electrolysis plant with a capacity of 41 MW. The lower voltage for powering the compressor and transformer of own needs is 6/0.4 kV
4	Complete switchgear with a voltage of 6 kV (up to 10 kV)	1) Input cabinet for 1200 A with switch and TT, TN. 2) Compressor connection cabinet with switch and TT. 3) Protection cabinet (may not be required). 4) Supply cabinet of transformer of own needs 6/0.4 kV with switch, TT.
5	Dry transformer for own needs, voltage 6/0.4 kV	Power from 1 to 2 MW
6	Complete distribution device with a voltage of 0.4 kV	Quantity depending on the number of consumers 0.4 kV
7	Complete distribution device with a voltage of 20 kV	Probably 2 cabinets, input and distribution, for a current of 2500 A.
Note: Elements numbered 1-2 are placed on the NPP site, numbered 3-7 are part of the HPP.		

AL: N
ECCN: N

Approximate placement and length of the 110kV overhead line from cubicle № 8 to the site of HPP substation:

- for the option of accommodation on the site - 2800 m;
- for the accommodation option in sanitary protection zone - 2000 m.

After the installation of a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers in the reserve cubicle №8, the final scheme of the 110 kV switchgear will look as presented in Figure 60.

The planned power consumption of HPP (40 - 45MVA) is within the allowable load on the autotransformers feeding the 110kV switchgear (7AT and 8AT see) with a capacity of 125MVA each but requires additional study considering the actual load from consumers connected to the power lines (12PL, 11PL, 9PL, 7PL, 6PL).

Figure 60: Open switch gear 110 kV with connection of HPP.

23.3.2 Demineralized Water System

The NPP project envisages a chemical water purification system with a capacity of 265 m³/h. Part of the water can be used for an HPP. But there are modes when this productivity is not enough even for the needs of the RNPP, therefore, during such peaks, the water cannot be used for the needs of the HPP (the availability of these modes depends on the water level in the Styr River, from which it is taken). Chemically desalinated water from the NPP cycle can be used for HPP needs. But according to the internal standard of NAEC "Energoatom" SOU NAEC 171, the requirements for its composition do not meet the requirements of the HPP, therefore, it is necessary to install a post-purification system at the HPP.

A purification system to the required parameters is necessary with a consumption of approximately 6 t/h.

System modification is required - additional water treatment system after a site's DW installation can be located near the site's system or inside the HPP (on the territory of the NPP). It should be designed for additional-treatment of DW to the quality required by the HPP at a flow rate of up to 6 t/h - (electrical conductivity: 0.1 mS/sm). It is preferable to place such an installation near the NPP's system to produce DW.

An approximate schematic diagram is shown in the figure below.

Figure 61: Demineralized water system options modification diagram.

The figures below show the approximate placement and length of demineralized water pipelines (diagrams below) depending on the HPP location scenario:

- for the option of onsite scenario - 1200 m.
- for the offsite scenario (in sanitary protection zone) – 2,800 m.

Figure 62: Scheme of placement of demineralized water pipelines (on site scenario).

Figure 63: Scheme of placement of demineralized water pipelines in the sanitary protection zone (off-site scenario).

Several options for using the existing pumping equipment for supplying demineralized water to the HPP are considered; it is also necessary to install flow rate sensors (2 pcs. for two pipelines) for measuring the flow rate of DW from Water treatment Dept. to HPP.

In some modes of NPP operation, the consumption of power unit needs may exclude the possibility of supplying demineralized water to the HPP, therefore a demineralized water storage tank for the HPP is to be installed and a water supply pump (consumption up to 10 t/h) from this tank to HPP equipment. The tank is filled with DW after the NPP treatment system and is stored with the possibility of direct selection of demineralized water from the NPP for the treatment system of the HPP. Taking into account the operation cycles of a multi-unit NPP, it is advisable to have a two-day supply of purified water (the useful volume of the tank is 280 m³).

Modification of the system consists in connection of a 50-70 mm diameter pipeline (depending on the adopted scenario of HPP location) to the pressure header of demineralized water supply pumps. A manual shut-off valve is installed on the new pipeline. After this, instrumentation (pressure and water flow rate control) is installed with readings on the water treatment operator's panel. Connection is performed in the premises of the NPP Water Treatment Department, where a unified water treatment

system for all NPP units is installed. The new pipeline is laid along the existing trestles or partially underground to the HPP site.

The NPP operation does not require constant supply of DW to consumers. The DW flow rate to the NPP consumers can be changed or switched off. Therefore, for constant supply of DW to electrolyzers it is required to install a DW storage tank and booster pumps at the HPP site. At the HPP site, the pipeline is connected to the additional treatment module and further to the HPP DW tank and the HPP DW pump to the electrolyzers. Appropriate shut-off and control valves, instrumentation and automation are installed at the HPP site according to the design and are not considered as a modification of the NPP.

23.3.3 Service Water System

The specifications for cooling the stacks of the electrolyzer at the HPP are given below.

Parameter	Value
Flow rate	750-900m ³ /h
Cooling water inlet temperature	30° C (optimal) 50° C (maximum)
Cooling water outlet temperature	Inlet temperature + 10° C
Water quality	No special requirements 50% propylene glycol can also be used.

AL: N ECCN: N

For the supply of cooling water to the HPP, the following options are available:

1. Using the service water of the Turbine Department unit #3 and #4 from RNPP for onsite HPP scenarios. However, this causes a change in the heat balance of the cooling water NPP that will need modifications. For these modifications a technical and safety justification is required. Using the service water supply from the Turbine Dept. for offsite HPP scenarios is complicated due to the need for long connections.
2. Using "raw" water from the RNPP service feed water pipeline from the river, before entering the additional water purification system, is also possible for an offsite HPP. Still there is a problem with the return flow of heated water that need to be cooled before discharging, due to the high temperature (up to 60°C).
3. Using an autonomous cooling system for the HPP (not considered in this report).

Option 1 (and 3) is considered as feasible.

Option 1 - The Turbine service water system (Figure 64). There is a possibility of using the Turbine service water system, but this leads to a thermal imbalance of the NPP and interferes with the cooling mode of the power units. Replenishment of water losses during evaporation is carried out from the Styr River. Water from the river is purified in the additional water purification system before replenishing the NPP reserves. The scheme for compensation of splash pool water losses from natural sources already exists at NPPs and does not require modification. This option requires modification of the Turbine service water system in terms of supplying water to the HPP and diverting it back for cooling.

Figure 64: Schematic diagram modification service cooling water.

N
ECCN:
N
AL:

The modification consists in connecting the pressure headers of the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of Unit 3 and the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of Unit 4. From these pumps, a pipeline should be extended to the HPP site. Such scheme will allow to supply cooling water from the pumps of any of the units, as well as simultaneously from both systems. This will increase the reliability of resource supply to the HPP and reduce the negative impact of each system on NPP equipment cooling. Under equal conditions, water withdrawal for the needs of the HPP can be reduced to 380-450 t/h from each system.

Two additional pumps should be installed with the possibility to connect the suction pipe to each of the splash basins (Units No.3 and No.4). The parameters of each additional pump shall provide 100% of the cooling water demand of the HPP. This flow rate is not less than 900 t/h, the pressure is specified depending on the conditions of water transportation to the HPP. The outlet of the additional pumps is connected to the supply pipeline to the HPP site. Such a scheme will allow to supply cooling water to the HPP without reducing the flow rate for cooling of the NPP turbine department equipment. This is especially important in the summer period of NPP operation when units No. 3 and No. 4 are operating at maximum power. Reservation of additional pumps solves the problem of maintenance, repair and emergency shutdown of one of the pumps without loss of reliability of HPP cooling. Additional pumps are installed in the area of the existing NPP cooling pumps, equipped with valves, drainage and air removal lines, instrumentation, and automation. Power supply of additional pumps comes from the in-house supply buses of one of the units or general in-house load buses; the additional load shall be justified. Additional control of temperature, pressure and flow rate is implemented on the supply and discharge pipelines at the HPP site. Preferred location of additional pumps are existing rooms of pumping stations of turbine department service water.

The heated water return pipeline from the HPP should be installed to the location of the respective service water pools of units No. 3 and No. 4. It is possible to return water to any of these pools. Pipes with valves are connected to water return collectors to the pools from turbine departments.

23.4 Impact on operation or plant conditions

In this section the impact on NPP operation or possible occurring situations due to the modifications of the selected shared systems are described.

23.4.1 Electric Power Distribution System

In the initial design of the 110kV switchgear only 1 redundant auxiliary transformer (1RT, see Appendix 2) with installed capacity of 40 MVA was installed. After connection of an (additional) second redundant transformer (6RT) with installed capacity of 40 MVA full load of in-house consumers of PU1 and PU2 from redundant transformers may reach 80 MVA. When we are considering the operating mode of the 110 kV switchgear in case when simultaneous connection of all existing consumers via power lines (12PL, 11PL, 9PL, 7PL, 6PL) and simultaneous activation of two redundant transformers (1RT and 6RT) plus load of the HPP (35-40 MVA), then in this case it may be necessary to cut off some loads, focusing on the priority in supplying of NPP in-house consumers. The maximum capacity of the 110 kV switchgear is 250MVA.

N
ECCN: All electrical connections are not related to equipment used in accident conditions, so they are not considered in the emergency documentation of the NPP. This refers to accidents at the reactor or Spent Fuel Pool. Consequently, there is no impact of HPP operation to EOPs, SAMG, Flex-procedures, and other emergency documents. There is also no impact on the AOPs.

AL: N Modification will have impact on Relay protection automatic algorithms, they will be updated with new parameters and setpoints. Maintenance instructions of 110 kV Switchgears will also be changed. The modification will not result in any changes in Safety Technical Specifications.

In Ageing management documentation data will be added with respect to new SSC's. Start-Up and Shut-down procedures of the 110kV switchgear will be updated as a result of the new connection.

23.4.2 Demineralized Water System

Normal operation is performed by the operating personnel according to procedures, normal operation instructions and programs. In case of abnormal events and emergencies, the personnel use accident procedures. If necessary, 24-hour engineering support is provided by highly qualified NPP specialists.

Repairs and maintenance are performed by NPP repair and engineering personnel.

Training and education of personnel are performed at different levels at the NPP and at the training center. Periodically the knowledge of instructions of the personnel who operate the system is verified.

Taking into account the multi-unit structure of the NPP, the system usually operates continuously for water treatment and its return to power units and other NPP facilities. Demineralized water consumption by consumers is changeable. The highest water consumption from the system is required during power unit start-up after outage. Priorities of water distribution within the NPP are set by the NPP shift supervisor.

For the HPP connection a minor modification to the existing system is needed. An additional pipeline with a shut-off valve is installed in the room where the system is located. A pressure gauge and a flow

meter are also installed for monitoring. All modifications are carried out in the demineralized water pump header room. The pipe laying to the HPP is performed at the NPP site and does not require operational control. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valve) is performed by the regular operating personnel who operate the NPP DW system. The schemes and operating instructions of the DW system will be modified. The personnel will be trained and given the necessary instruction on control and management of the modified system. Possible additional malfunctions (leaks, valve or instrumentation failures) will be analyzed, and personnel actions will be included in the instructions. All necessary measures before performing the modification are included in a dedicated technical decision document. The technical decision document includes amongst other the following topics of concern:

- Conditions for restrictions and limitations of operation.
- impact to related systems.
- changes to related documents, operating and maintenance procedures.
- terms and responsibilities.
- testing of systems.
- emergency documentation.
- needs and terms of personal training.

In case of shortage of DW for NPP needs (possibly during start-up operations at the power unit), it is possible that DW supply to the HPP will be temporarily stopped. This condition may remain in effect for several hours. Although the flow rate of DW to the HPP is insignificant compared to the NPP flow rate, its shutdown may be required. In order to avoid an HPP shutdown it is necessary to have a storage tank for DW (water prepared for the HPP) at the HPP site. Such a stock of DW can ensure autonomous operation of HPP for 1 or 2 days. The DW reserve in this tank is replenished during normal operation of the NPP.

In case of leakage of the modified DW pipeline in the non-isolation part (part of the system that cannot be disconnected from the main DW equipment of the NPP), (a part of the, or in the most conservative case the whole) NPP DW system should be shut down for emergency repair. However, the NPP DW system has DW storage tanks and, if necessary, make-up of the NPP DW system can be performed from these tanks. The NPP DW system has two lines of DW supply to the power units, so such an event does not affect the safety of the NPP and does not have a significant impact on the reliability of the NPP. According to preliminary estimates, the pipeline repair time may be up to 3 hours. If it is necessary to completely shut down the DW of the NPP for a time longer than 1 day, conditions may arise under which some NPP equipment must be shut down or NPP capacity must be reduced. In this case, the modification impacts NPP reliability (and does not impact safety).

The DWS is not a safety related system. All connections are not related to equipment used in accident conditions and are not considered in the emergency documentation of the NPP. Consequently, due to modification of the DWS there is no impact on EOPs, SAMGs, Flex-procedures and other emergency documents. There is also no impact on the AOPs.

Modification of the DWS shall include changes to DW operating procedures, DW schematics, DW monitoring procedures, Chemical Department training programs, ageing management programs, and pipeline testing programs.

 N
 ECCN:
 N
 AL:

23.4.3 Service Water System

The system consists of an extensive system of ducts, pools, pipelines and cooling towers. Heat removal to the air is controlled by varying the height of the water sprinkler over the pool. The pumps are in pumping station buildings and separated from the turbine building on the NPP territory. Parameter monitoring and control is performed at the Main Control Room, at the local panels and at the equipment locations. Operation is performed by NPP operational personnel. Repair and maintenance are performed by NPP repair and engineering personnel. Normal operation is performed by the operating personnel according to procedures, normal operation instructions and programs. In abnormal cases and accidents, the personnel use the procedures for accident management. If necessary, 24-hour engineering support is provided by highly qualified NPP specialists. Operational personnel also monitor the system operation during routine walkarounds of the equipment.

Training and education of personnel are performed at different levels at the NPP and at the training center. The knowledge of instructions of the personnel operating the system is periodically checked.

Modification of the existing system is not related to NPP safety. Additional pipelines with shut-off valves are installed within the location of the existing pipelines of the system. In addition, 2 new HPP water supply pumps are being installed. Where possible, existing plenum chambers and existing suction pipes of existing systems are used. Suitable valves and check valves are installed on the pipelines to allow for different switching and maintenance arrangements for the modified system.

A gauge and a flow meter also have to be installed. All changes are made at the location of the existing system. The laying of pipes to the HPP and water return is carried out on the territory of the NPP and does not require operational control. Control of water flow at the HPP is carried out on the territory of the HPP and is not required with NPP personnel. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valves, pumps) are performed by operating personnel who operate the existing NPP system. Changes must be made to the diagrams and operating instructions. The power supply equipment for the house needs of the corresponding Unit will also be modified and power supply cables will be extended to the new pump motors. New automation equipment for pumps and electric motors was modified and installed. Therefore, the diagrams and instructions of the Electrical Dept. and the Automation and Measurement Dept. must also be changed. The operational, technical and engineering personnel of the technological departments, the Electrical Dept. and the Automation and Measurement Dept. must be trained and given the necessary instructions on checking and managing the modified system. Possible additional faults (leaks, failures of valves, pumps or instruments) must be analyzed. Personnel actions must be included in the instructions. The training programs and training materials for the staff of the Education and Training Center must also be changed. All necessary measures before carrying out the modification are included in the technical solution document.

The system is designed to cool the equipment of the Turbine Department and, in case of abnormal situations or accidents, the cooling of electric motors of the RCPs. In case a large volume of water is withdrawn from the system for HPP needs or in case of pipeline rupture, the equipment of the Turbine Department will have insufficient cooling. This may lead to the need to reduce the power unit capacity or to its shutdown. In this case, the reliability of NPP operation (of one power unit) will be reduced. There is no impact on safety in this case.

In case of loss of water consumption for cooling of electric motors of the RCPs by the service water of the Turbine Department, the cooling will be restored by other service water systems. In the most conservative case, in the case of complete loss of cooling of the RCPs, the unit will be shut down, but

AL: N
ECCN: N

the core cooling function will not be lost. This incident is addressed as a design event and is covered in appropriate (emergency) procedures. The event is referred to as 'loss of Turbine Department service water pumps'. Due to modification of the SW there is no impact on EOPs, SAMGs, Flex-procedures and other emergency documents. There is also no impact on the AOPs.

However, modifications shall include some changes to SW operation procedures, SW schematics, SW monitoring procedures, Turbine Department training programs, ageing management programs, and pipeline testing programs.

23.5 Impact on Safety

23.5.1 Impact on Safety Functions

23.5.1.1 Electric Power Distribution System

The 110 kV outdoor switchgear is designed to supply power to local district consumers, and to provide power supply to the reserve(backup) transformers of power units 1 and 2 (1RT and 6RT) with an installed capacity of 40MVA 110kV/6kV.

The 110kV outdoor switchgear does not supply power to nuclear safety systems or systems having a (basic) safety function. It is not designed to have a safety function in accident conditions.

The modification has resulted in addition of a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers at a reserve position (cubicle No8) of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear with the functionality to supply electricity to the HPP. The present, other functionalities of the 110kV outdoor switchgear does not change due to the modification. The reliability of the modified system needs to be tested, but dysfunction of the system does not impact safety functions of the NPP SSCs.

A possible loss of electric power at the NPP caused by malfunctioning of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear (if possible) does not threaten the basic safety functions. The reactor is able to shut down (scram) and the core can be cooled by emergency powered systems; confinement functions (e.g. reactor cooling system, containment system) are maintained. Loss of power is an event for which the plant is designed.

Conclusion

The modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear has no impact on, and is not related to, the(basic) safety functions of the Rivne NPP.

23.5.1.2 Demineralized Water System

The demineralized water plant is designed to produce chemically demineralized water having the function to replenish steam and condensate losses in the primary and secondary circuits. The DWS has no cooling function.

Modification of the system consists in the connection of a pipeline to the pressure header of demineralized water supply pumps. A manual shut-off valve is installed on the new pipeline. After this, instrumentation (pressure and water flow rate control) is installed with readings on the water treatment operator's panel. The new pipeline is laid along the existing trestles or partially underground to the HPP site. This modification on the NPP site is an extension of the DWS, not changing or interfering with its function. For constant supply of DW to electrolyzers it is required to install a DW storage tank and booster pumps at the HPP site.

ECCN: N
AL: N

Conclusion

The modified DWS has no impact on the (basic) safety functions of the Rivne NPP.

23.5.1.3 Service Water System

Cooling is suggested by making use of the service water of the turbine department of unit 3 and 4. The modification consists in connecting the pressure headers of the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 3 and the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 4. From these pumps, a pipeline is to be extended to the HPP site.

The turbine equipment is part of the secondary water loop of the NPP. Heat of the NPP in the primary loop is cooled by the secondary loop in the Steam Generator. The heat of the secondary loop is also absorbed by turbine equipment which needs to be cooled. However, the turbine department service water system has no dedicated safety function with respect to the cooling of the core. Due to the extra heat take-up as a result of the HPP presence, the modification causes a change in the heat balance of the cooling water heat removal capacity of the NPP. Due to connection to the HPP the service water system needs to remove more heat than it was designed for, so for this modification technical and safety justification is required (meeting required margins to operating and safety limits, but also procedures for preferred users).

The service water system has not relation to other basic safety functions, i.e. reactivity control of the core and confinement of radioactive material.

Conclusion

The heat balance of the NPP needs to be adjusted and needs further analysis. However, the modification has no impact on dedicated nuclear safety functions with respect to cooling of the core, reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

23.5.2 Impact on Defence in Depth

General

The systems to be modified (supply of electricity for measurement and correction systems, contribution to replenishment of primary and secondary system inventory, cooling of secondary system components) are related/connected to SSCs in the first level of DiD. These systems have no role in other layers of defence. The requirements for these level 1 systems (see **Fout!**

Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.-2) are that the design, construction and operation is of high quality. This can be achieved by

- sufficient margins and conservatism in design,
- high reliability of systems and components,
- adequate training and qualification of personnel, and
- quality assurance system.

It is therefore expected that the modifications will not largely impact the DiD levels. This will be described in the following sections.

23.5.2.1 Electric power distribution system

The modification is an expansion of the electric power distribution system. The function and configuration of electric systems of the NPP does not change. The supply capacity to and infrastructure of electricity (safety) systems involved in the different Defence in Depth layers, are not changed.

AL: N
 ECCN: N

23.5.2.2 Demineralized Water System

The modification has no impact on the DiD layers. A possible advantage for the deepest defence layers can be the extra DW storage tank (for the continuous supply of the HPP). During (severe) accident conditions the extra water inventory could be used as emergency cooling water. This is a small benefit for the 4th level of DiD. This benefit is however so small that it best can be treated as a non-credited emergency means, for which no documentation updates would be required.

23.5.2.3 Service Water System

The modification has no impact on the DiD layers. A possible advantage for the deepest defence layers can be the extra piping in the NPP area. During (severe) accident conditions extra possibilities of using service water as emergency cooling water due to extra connection points, are in principle available. This could also be seen as an extra, non-credited, emergency means.

23.5.3 Impact on Risks

Due to the modifications extra risks could be introduced due to failure or interference with other systems.

23.5.3.1 Electric power Distribution system

Increase in Initiating Events or Probability numbers:

- slight (/negligible) increase of fire probability (e.g. ignition frequency): due to extra heat and number of the extra electronic components or due to extra interferences among electronic systems.
- slight (/negligible) increase of Loss of power probability: due to interference with other electric power systems and/or failure of the implemented 110 kV switchgear in cell 8 and the connected electronic components of the HPP.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels in the different plant states.

23.5.3.2 Demineralized Water System

Increase in Initiating Events or Probability numbers:

- slight (/negligible) increase of flooding probability: due to extra water inventory structures flooding due to leakage/break of water containing structures is possible.
- slight (/negligible) increase of failure probability of the replenish system to the primary and secondary circuit due to extension of the existing system with components and structures.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels in the different plant states.

23.5.3.3 Service Water System

Increase in Initiating Events or Probability numbers:

- slight (/negligible) increase of flooding probability: due to extra water inventory structures flooding due to leakage/break of water containing structures is possible.
- slight (/negligible) increase of failure probability of turbine equipment cooling system due to extension of the existing system with components and structures.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels in the different plant states.

AL: N
ECCN: N

23.5.4 Impact on Safety Analyses

The modifications may impact the existing Postulated Initiating Event analysis and need to be checked for possible influence (e.g. assumptions made in the analysis). The following PIEs could be influenced:

23.5.4.1 Electric power Distribution system

Loss of electrical power supplies:

- Loss of normal electrical power

Internal events:

- Internal fires (ignition frequency)
- Electro-Magnetic Interference (EMI) from equipment on site

23.5.4.2 Demineralized Water System

Internal events:

- Internal flooding;

23.5.4.3 Service Water System

Internal events:

- Internal flooding.

23.6 Conclusion RIVNE safety case

Selection

For HPP coupling with the RIVNE NPP eight provisions for sharing were described in terms of needs, specifications and implications. Three systems were selected based on potential economic benefit. This resulted in the coupling scenario 'partial integration' for an on-site or off-site situation.

The selected systems for sharing concern:

- Electric Power Distribution System (EPDS)
- Demineralized Water System (DWS)
- Service Water System (SWS)

All systems are non-safety systems.

Impact on operation

For the three selected systems little impact on operation was determined. The impact concerns operational changes like changing/extending procedures, some training activities and updating of related documentation and systems.

No impact on safety measures (e.g. accident procedures) or related safety systems was identified.

Impact on safety

The four safety aspects were evaluated with respect to the three systems:

- Safety Functions:

AL: N
ECCN: N

- the modifications of the three systems have no impact on nuclear (basic) safety functions.
- Comment related to the SWS: the heat balance of the NPP needs to be adjusted.
- Defence in Depth:
 - the three systems are related/connected to SSCs in the first level and have no role in other layers. By application of high-quality design/implementation standards, modified systems will not contribute to extra system failures.
 - Comment related to the DWS and SWS: the access to extra emergency cooling water in level 4 conditions is a minor (not credited) benefit of these modified systems.
- Risks:
 - the modifications give rise to slight/negligible risk increase with respect to fire and loss of normal power (EPDS), flooding and failure of replenishment systems (DWS), and flooding and failure of turbine cooling systems (SWS).
 - The modifications do not result in increase of radiation levels in the different plant states.
- Safety Analyses:
 - The following PIEs could be negatively influenced (but likely negligible in practice):
 - Loss of normal electric power
 - Internal fires
 - Electro-magnetic interference
 - Internal flooding

ECCN: N

Qualitative statement

It can be concluded that the modifications foreseen on the -non safety- systems of Rivne NPP selected to be shared with the HPP, have a negligible impact on safety related SSCs of Rivne NPP. Although some checks on operation and safety have to be done (e.g. heat balance, assumptions for PIE analysis), it is expected that a limited Safety Case Report has to be composed and less/no changes or extensions have to be made to safety analyses, procedures and technical documents. Also, other related activities, like training for staff, will be limited.

AL: N

Costs

The costs for the modifications for Rivne NPP with respect to the license update can be estimated by use of Appendix 3. For Rivne NPP “situation 1” (non-safety related systems) can be applied resulting in roughly 500 k€ for the cost level in The Netherlands. The costs are dominated by labor costs, so for Ukraine the costs are estimated much lower, resulting in an order of magnitude of 100-200 k€.

24 Overall Conclusion Safety Impact NPP-HPP Integration

24.1 Assessment process of the safety impact

- For changing NPP systems a formal modification process (MoC process in the Management System) has to be followed in which the impact on safety is assessed based on the safety category of the modification.
- An initial screening on safety impact has to be performed to determine the safety category of the modification. When there is no /hardly safety impact, the modification work will mainly consist of the technical design and implementation of the modification with no / limited additional safety or license related work.
- A comprehensive safety assessment needs to be performed in case the modification concerns safety categories 1 and 2. The described 'safety case' (see chapter 22) constitutes the most important part of the comprehensive assessment.
- In the safety case, safety impact is addressed with the following main topics:
 - Operation and plant conditions
 - Safety Functions
 - Defence in Depth
 - Risks
 - Safety Analyses

Appropriate IAEA documents can/must be used for evaluation of these topics, depending on the coupling of the license requirements with IAEA standards.

24.2 General conclusion for coupling HPP to NPP

24.2.1.1 Safety related systems

For modifications on safety related SSCs the impact can be (very) large, depending on the type of involved safety functions. The large amount of work and additional costs are caused by:

- The modifications and their (possible) impact on safety need to be justified by an extensive safety case and -analysis. Additional measures have to be taken to prevent any significant impact on safety.
- The modified systems have to fulfil strict requirements and nuclear qualifications, leading to high cost;
- Modifications to safety related systems have impact on operating-, abnormal-, accident-, emergency-, maintenance-, inspection- and test procedures. They all need to be adapted to the modified situation, for all plant states (start-up, operation, hot-shutdown, cold-shutdown etc.).
- The above-mentioned change in procedures requires training of personnel to assure that the new procedures will be followed correctly in all situations and for all plant states.
- Besides the mentioned changes/additions, also related documentation (like specifications, services contracts, management system) might need to be updated.

AL: N
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- Additionally, the HPP-part of the shared system will have to follow a more strict (nuclear) regime with respect to modifications, maintenance, accident procedures etc. which might also increase the operating costs of these systems.

This means that sharing safety related systems of the NPP with the HPP is unlikely unless the benefits of sharing are very high. Referring to WP 3 “Economical aspects of coupling” this might be relevant for sharing high temperature steam.

24.2.1.2 Non-safety related systems

Modifications on non-safety related SSCs will have no/limited safety impact and will require no or limited additional work to justify and implement the modification due to safety and license restrictions. The following topics still have to be addressed:

- Modifications will have (in principal) no impact on the described safety aspects. Nevertheless, an initial safety check has to be performed in which the mentioned safety aspects (DiD, Risks, FSF etc.) are addressed to show they are not impacted. No further activities have to be carried out with respect to safety analyses and the SAR.
- Modifications will probably have some impact on operation. This impact is mainly related to adapting/extending maintenance and operating procedures, possibly combined with some training for staff to operate and maintain the modified systems. Non-safety related systems have no function in abnormal situations and accident conditions, so in general no impact on arrangements to manage these abnormal and accident conditions will occur.

For a modification of a non-safety related system, the additional costs from a safety / regulations point of view are limited. This means that sharing of non-safety systems is mainly a financial trade-off between the investment costs of separate systems compared to the investment costs of shared (non-safety) systems.

24.2.1.3 General findings

- Sharing of systems can only have a net zero or negative effect on safety. There should therefore be other drivers for sharing of systems between an NPP and an HPP like: operations, costs, strategic, political, ...
- Safety related shared systems will have to comply with the nuclear requirements, the nuclear license and the related administrative and inspection regime by the nuclear regulator. Therefore only significant benefits due to sharing will outweigh the additional effort to be made for sharing nuclear safety related systems.
- In practice, sharing of systems will be focused on sharing of non-safety systems to minimize the additional effort of the modifications.
- For high temperature electrolysis, sharing safety related systems like high-temperature steam might be beneficial. In such cases the modifications to the NPP system should be designed in such a way that NPP operation is minimally compromised in all plant situations (normal operation, accident conditions, emergency response) and in all plant states (start-up, cold shut-down, hot shut-down, ...).

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1

RIVNE NPP

Power units with VVER-440

VVER-440 is a 440 MW pressurized water reactor designed in the Soviet Union (2 K-220-44 KhTGZ turbines of 220 MW each).

The VVER-440 core consists of 349 hexagonal fuel assemblies, some of which are used as working bodies of the VVER-440 control system. Inside the fuel assembly casing there are 126 rod fuel elements (fuel elements) with a diameter of 9.1 mm mounted in a triangular lattice. The core of the fuel rod (sintered uranium dioxide with 3.5% enrichment), 7.5 mm in diameter, is enclosed in a 0.6 mm thick cladding. The material of the fuel assembly casing and the fuel rods cladding is zirconium alloyed with niobium (1%).

VVER-440 operates in the mode of 4-6 partial fuel assembly refueling per campaign lasting about 3-6 years. Every 280-290 days 1/3-1/6 part of fuel assembly is replaced in VVER-440. First, fuel assemblies are removed from the central core area, and in their place fuel assemblies from the core periphery are moved. The vacated spaces on the core periphery are filled with fresh fuel assemblies. Fuel assemblies are reloaded under a 5-meter-thick protective water layer that reduces the radiation dose in the reactor hall below the maximum permissible dose.

At present, fuel with burn-up neutron absorber (gadolinium, erbium) has been developed for VVER reactors, which allows to enrich fresh fuel more and to have a larger reactivity reserve during the fuel campaign, which allows to use one fuel assembly with fuel not for 3-4 years, but for 5-6 years at practically equal cost, which allows to reduce fuel costs by about 40%.

Power reactivity coefficient of VVER is a negative value. At NPPs, it is used to increase the interval between refueling during maximum power consumption in the autumn and winter. Before partial refueling, the reactor is switched for some time into the self-regulation mode. The reactor power is slowly reduced, which frees up reactivity. This reactivity is used to compensate for additional fuel burnup.

The VVER-440 core is contained in a thick-walled steel vessel. It has an outer diameter of 3.8 m, height of 11.2 m and is designed for operation under pressure of 125 atm. The casing has two rows of nozzles for coolant inlet and outlet. From above the vessel is closed with a top cover.

The VVER-440 control system has two independent systems: the control assembly (ARC) and the boron control system. The first system of 37 ARCs provides reactor control in unsteady modes and reactor shutdown. The fuel assembly with fuel elements is the lower tier of the ARC. The upper tier of ARCs is filled with boride alloy elements. The ARCs are mounted on rods extending upward through the top cover of the vessel. They are moved vertically by electric motors and in emergency cases are dropped into the core. After dropping, the place of the ARC fuel tier in the core is taken by a boride alloy absorber.

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Slow changes in reactivity are compensated for by the boron control system. Application of the boron control system simplified the reactor control system. The number of ARCs is 37.

The scheme of the power unit with VVER-440 reactor consists of two circuits, the first of which refers to the reactor part, and the second - to the steam turbine part. In the reactor side, water circulates at a pressure of 125 atm. Water with a temperature of 269 °C enters the annular slot between the vessel wall and the core and flows downward. It then moves upwards and, cooling the fuel elements, heats up to 300 °C. In the steam generators, the heat removed from the reactors is used to produce saturated steam (pressure 44 atm, temperature 257 °C) that turns the turbine generators.

1. Nuclear reactor vessel, 2. Steam generator, 3. Refueling machine, 4. Spent nuclear fuel pool, 5. Isolation system, 6. Make-up system, 7. Protective cover, 8. Confinement system, 9. Barbotage system, 10. Safety valves, 11. Ventilation system, 12. Turbine, 13. Condenser, 14. Turbine unit, 15. Feed water tank with deaerator, 16. Heater, 17. Turbine hall crane, 18. Electrical equipment and control chambers

Power units with VVER-1000

Pressurized Water Reactor (VVER-1000) is a nuclear reactor of the VVER reactor series with nominal electric power of 1000 MW and thermal power of 3030 MW. This type of reactor is the most widespread in its series and accounts for 7.5% of the total number of power reactors of all types operating in the world. The most common modification is the serial reactor unit B-320.

The reactor is a water-water, heterogeneous, vessel, thermal neutron reactor with water as a coolant, moderator and neutron reflector.

Nuclear fuel - fuel assemblies consisting of fuel elements containing uranium dioxide pellets weakly enriched in uranium-235 isotope.

The reactor power is regulated by the control and protection system - by changing the position of clusters of rods with absorbing elements (tubes with boron carbide) in the core, as well as by changing the concentration of boric acid in the reactor coolant system water.

Most often in the layout plan of NPPs with VVER-1000 it is envisaged to locate several power units on one site, which is connected with the necessity to maintain services, equipment and infrastructure common for all units at the NPP site. Each main building is a monobloc and consists of a reactor compartment, a turbine room, a deaerator rack and an electrical equipment rack adjacent to the turbine room. The main vessel houses the following main equipment:

- VVER-1000 type reactor,
- turbine unit of K-1000-60/1500 type,
- generator of TVV-1000 type.

The technological scheme of each unit is two-circuit. The first circuit is radioactive; it includes a VVER-1000 reactor with a thermal capacity of 3,000 MW and four circulation loops that pump coolant - water at a pressure of 16 MPa (160 kgf/cm²) - through the core using the reactor coolant pumps. The water temperature at the reactor inlet is approximately 289 °C, and at the outlet - 322 °C. The circulation flow rate of water through the reactor is 84000 t/h. The water heated in the reactor is directed through four pipelines to the steam generators. The pressure and level of the coolant of the reactor coolant system are maintained by means of a steam pressurizer.

The secondary side is non-radioactive and consists of an evaporator and water supply unit, a desalting unit and a turbine unit with an electrical capacity of 1000 MW. The coolant of the primary side is cooled in the steam generators, while giving heat to the water of the secondary side. Saturated steam produced in the steam generators, with pressure of 6.4 MPa and temperature of 280 °C, is supplied to the steam header and directed to the turbine unit driving the electric generator. The steam flow rate from 4 steam generators per turbine is approximately 6,000 t/h. The secondary side also includes first and second stage condensate pumps, high- and low-pressure heaters, deaerator, and turbo driven feed pumps.

Turbine section

In the Secondary side steam with humidity of 0,5 % from four steam generators is supplied through steam pipelines through stop and control valves to the middle of two-flow symmetrical high-pressure cylinder (HPC) of the turbine, where, after expansion, with pressure of 1,2 MPa and humidity of 12 % is directed to four steam superheater separators. There, after drying of steam (condensate for utilization of its heat is discharged to the deaerator), it is superheated in two stages, in the first stage by the first extraction steam with pressure of 3 MPa and temperature of 234 °C, in the second stage - by fresh steam. Condensate of heating steam is directed to high-pressure heaters to transfer its heat to feed water. The main superheated steam at the parameters of 1.13 MPa and 250 °C enters two receiver pipes, and from them - through stop valves - into three similar two-flow low-pressure cylinders (LPC). Further, from each LPC the steam enters its condenser. The regenerative system of the unit consists of four low-pressure heaters (LPH), a deaerator and two groups of HPHs. The feed water to the HPHs is supplied by two turbo feed pumps of about 12 MW each. Their drive turbine is fed with superheated steam and has its own condenser. The turbo feed pumps (two per unit) supply feed water from the deaerator to the steam generators. The capacity of each pump is about 3800 m³/h, pressure 7.33 MPa. For units with VVER-1000 there are no reserve pumps, because is the necessity to warm up the turbine drive before switching on, so in case of failure of one of them the power unit capacity is reduced by 50%. Auxiliary electric feedwater pumps are provided for emergency, start-up to cooling modes.

Three-phase synchronous generator sets TVV-1000 are designed for power generation in direct connection with steam turbines. Active power - 1000 MW, voltage 24 kV, rotor speed 1500 rpm. The generator consists of stator, end shields, rotor, leads with zero current transformers and flexible junctions, gas coolers, support bearing, shaft seals and base plates. Many auxiliary systems support the operation of the generator. Two three-phase step-up transformers with a capacity of 630 MW-A each are connected to each generator via generator circuit breakers, which, connected in parallel, make it possible to supply the unit's rated power to the grid.

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Reactor units with VVER-1000 operate according to the two-circuit circulation scheme. In terms of safety, they are almost similar to European and American units with PWRs. A separate main building is constructed for each power unit. All reactor plant equipment and special technological systems (safety and auxiliary systems) are located in the reactor compartment of the power unit, which is a special structure.

The reactor compartment consists of a pressurized and a non-pressurized part. The pressurized part, called the containment, houses the primary side equipment and the reactor. The containment vessel is made in the form of a cylinder of prestressed reinforced concrete with a thickness of 1.2 meters, an inner diameter of 45 meters and a height of 52 meters, with an elevation of 13.2 meters above ground level. There is its flat bottom, up to the 66.35 meter mark, where the top of its dome-shaped top is located. The total volume is 67,000 m³. All the large main equipment in the containment is serviced by a circular full-turn crane.

The non-tight part asymmetrically surrounds the containment and is a square in plan with a side of 66 meters. The building goes 6.6 m underground and rises 41.4 m, inside it there is a railroad entrance for delivery of cargoes under the containment, in the bottom of which there is a large transport hatch. There is a 3 m diameter ventilation stack for blowing off from the production facilities, with a relative top elevation of 100 meters.

All large devices and pipelines are equipped with hydraulic shock absorbers, a complex system of supports, hangers, stops and other equipment to protect against earthquakes, the impact of reactive forces and flying objects during the destruction of equipment, as well as to reduce the vibration of process equipment and the reactor vessel. In addition to the large equipment described below, all systems include pipelines, a variety of shutoff, control, protection and safety valves, various sensors, thermocouples and other equipment.

VVER-1000 Reactor coolant system

Spatial diagram of the primary side of the VVER-1000 reactor.

CP-1,2,3,4 - Reactor coolant pumps; SG-1,2,3,4 - Steam Generators; NR - Reactor vessel; P – Pressurizer

The primary side circulates the coolant - non-boiling water at a pressure of about 16 MPa (160 kgf/cm²). The coolant enters the reactor at a temperature of about 289 °C, heats up to 322 °C and is directed through 4 circulation loops to the steam generators ("hot" legs), where it transfers its heat to the coolant of the Secondary side. From the steam generators, the water is returned to the reactor by the reactor coolant pumps ("cold" legs). A pressurizer (volume compensator) connected to one of the "hot" legs is used to maintain pressure stability and to compensate for changes in the volume of the coolant during its heating up or cooling down. The total volume of the primary side is 370 m³.

Steam generator PGV-1000

The main circulation pipelines with an internal diameter of 850 mm connect the equipment of the primary side. They are located in pairs, in opposite sides from the reactor with an angle between the paired loops of 55°. The design of pipelines and methods of their fixing are designed to bear the load in case of an earthquake of 9 points on the MSK-64 scale with simultaneous impact of loads from guillotine breaks of one of the circulation loops. For various purposes, the main circulation pipelines are connected with a variety of auxiliary and emergency systems by means of welded-in branches, fittings and hermetic covers. Flow restrictors (leak restrictors) are installed at the tie-in points to minimize leaks when auxiliary system piping ruptures. Control and measurement piping is tapped through shutoffs to prevent leaks in the event of rupture. Temperature expansions of the main pipelines are compensated by moving steam generators and Reactor coolant pumps on roller supports. Large equipment is also equipped with powerful hydraulic shock absorbers.

The steam generator is designed to transfer the energy produced in the reactor core to the Secondary side. VVER-1000 uses PGV-1000 steam generators, horizontal, with a tubular heat exchange surface. The primary side coolant passes through 11,500 heat transfer tubes inside the steam generator vessel, heating the Secondary side water. The boiling Secondary side water is converted to steam and flows through collection steam lines to the turbine. Steam is produced saturated, with a temperature of 280 °C, pressure of 6.4 MPa and humidity of 0.2 % at a feed water temperature of 220 °C. Thermal capacity of each steam generator is 750 MW, steam production capacity is 1470 t/h.

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Reactor coolant pumps (RCP) provide forced circulation of the coolant through the primary side. It is a vertical centrifugal single-stage pump with a mechanical shaft seal unit. Capacity - 20 000 m³/h, head - 6.75 kgf/cm², power 7000-5300 kW (on cold and hot water), weight - 140 tons. The pump has its own oil system, with a total oil flow of about 28 m³/h. In case of shutdown of one RCP, the reactor power is reduced by 36 %, two - by 60 %, more - the reactor is stopped by the action of emergency protection. At the same time, even in the absence of operating pumps, natural circulation of the coolant is maintained in the primary side, which provides the necessary heat removal from the fuel to cool down the plant.

The pressurizer is used to create and maintain the pressure in the primary side. The pressurizer is a vertical vessel with an elliptical bottom, in the lower part of which 28 blocks of electric heaters with a total capacity of 2520 kW are located. To increase the pressure in the primary side, the coolant in the pressurizer is heated by electric heaters. For lowering - the steam space is injected from the "cold" leg of the first loop, which leads to condensation of a part of steam and pressure reduction. For emergency pressure reduction there are 3 safety valves, discharging steam with flow rate up to 150 kg/s into the bubble tank, the main purpose of which is to receive and cool leaking safety valves.

Service water supply

Service water supply at NPPs with VVER-1000 is recycled, i.e. service water circulates in a closed circle. Three types of coolers are used in the circulating systems: cooling ponds, splash pools and cooling towers. Combinations of these types are used in various projects, as autonomous service water supply systems are usually three: cooling system for turbine condensers, cooling system for turbine consumers and cooling system for critical components (equipment, including emergency equipment, the interruption of water supply to which is not allowed in any operating mode). The last system combines the functions of the safety and normal operation system, and splash pools are most often used in it.

Safety systems

Safety systems are designed to perform so-called critical safety functions during accidents, these functions include:

- control of chain reaction, i.e. shutdown of the reactor and control of its subcriticality after shutdown;
- removal of residual reactor power;
- limiting the spread of radioactive products.

The set of *safety systems* is determined by the design depending on the need to fulfill these functions. When creating the VVER-1000 safety systems, the following principles were used: physical separation of channels, diversity of principles of operation of the equipment used, independence of operation of different systems from each other. The single failure principle was applied to all safety systems, according to which safety functions are performed in case of any failure in safety systems independent of the initial event that caused the accident. This leads to the necessity of redundancy of safety systems. In NPP with VVER-1000 the redundancy ratio is accepted as 3-100 % (in many American and European projects this value is only 3-50 %), i.e. each safety system consists of three independent channels, each independently capable of ensuring fulfillment of design functions.

The emergency protection system transfers the reactor to a subcritical state in case of accidents and maintains it in this state.

The emergency boron injection system supplies boric acid solution to the first circuit at a pressure of 160-180 kgf/cm². This is necessary in accidents with the release of positive reactivity in the core while maintaining high pressure in the primary side. Solution concentration is 40 g/kg, flow rate of one channel of the system is 6 m³/h, solution supply is provided not more than 5 minutes after the emergency alarm. The system includes boron concentrate emergency stock tanks and pumps.

The emergency boron injection system supplies solution with concentration of 40 g/kg with a flow rate of at least 100 m³/h at a pressure of 100 kgf/cm² in the primary side, at a pressure of 15-90 kgf/cm² - with a flow rate of at least 130 m³/h. These flow rates are provided by one channel. The solution supply starts no later than 35-40 seconds after the required pressure is established in the primary side. The system includes emergency stock tanks of boron concentrate and pumps.

The system of emergency and planned cooling is designed both for emergency core cooling and removal of residual heat generation, and for planned cooling of the plant during shutdown and removal of residual heat generation during refueling. The system provides supply of boric acid solution with concentration 16 g/kg with flow rate 250-300 m³/h at pressure in the primary side 21 kgf/cm² and 700-750 m³/h at pressure 1 kgf/cm². It starts supplying no later than 35-40 seconds after the required pressure is established in the primary side. The system consists of pumps, a 500 m³ borated water tank in a containment (the emergency boron injection system and the sprinkler system can also be operated from it) and heat exchangers for emergency and scheduled defrosting.

The spray system is designed to localize accidents with rupture of primary and secondary side pipelines within the containment. In such an accident, the pressure in the Containment increases, and the Containment is designed for a pressure not exceeding 5 kgf/cm². To prevent its collapse, as well as to

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bind radioactive iodine isotopes and to provide emergency filling of the fuel pool, the sprinkler system delivers boric acid solution to a number of nozzles under the containment dome. The system consists of centrifugal and water jet pumps, sprinkler tanks and spray nozzles.

The passive part of the emergency core cooling system (hydro accumulator system) is designed for operation in accidents with large leaks. This system is passive, i.e. it does not require commands for switching on and energy supply to fulfil its functions. It consists of four hydraulic accumulators, vertical cylindrical vessels containing 50 m³ of boric acid solution with a concentration of 16 g/kg each. The tanks are containment, directly connected to the reactor and isolated from it by check valves. The pressure in the tanks is 60 kgf/cm² (created by nitrogen), so at normal pressure in the primary side the check valves are closed. When the pressure in the primary side drops below 60 kgf/cm², the check valves open on their own and the solution from the tanks starts to flood the reactor. After emptying them, quick-acting gate valves cut off the accumulators from the circuit to prevent nitrogen from entering the reactor.

The emergency gas removal system is designed to remove the gas mixture from the Primary side equipment: reactor top points, pressurizer, steam generator headers along the primary side. Such necessity may arise in case of accidents with coolant boiling, level drop in the core, occurrence of zirconium steam reaction in the fuel and appearance of steam-gas bubbles in the upper points of the plant equipment as a result of these events. The introduction of this system was the designers' response to the 1979 accident at Three Mile Island NPP.

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ECCN: *The emergency feedwater system* for the steam generators is designed to operate in the event of a secondary side feedwater system failure, which is necessary to create a cool-down condition for the reactor plant. Each channel is capable of supplying desalinated water with a flow rate of 150 m³/h at normal steam generator pressure (64 kgf/cm²), 125 m³/h at 70 kgf/cm² pressure, 80 m³/h at 86 kgf/cm² pressure. The system includes pumps and chemically desalinated water tanks of 500 m³ each.

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AL: *Containment.* System of filtering emergency ventilation of the containment.

System of passive hydrogen removal from the containment (recombiners).

Mobile equipment. For each unit - 3 mobile pumping units for water supply to SFP, SGs and service water system. Flow rates - more than 100 tonnes/hour to the SG, and more than 400 tonnes/hour to the SFP and the service water system.

For each unit - mobile diesel generator (air-cooled). Voltage - 0.4 kV, Power - 800 kW.

The service water supply system for Group "A" equipment combines the functions of the safety system (cooling of the heat exchanger of the emergency cooling system, cooling of the pumps of the safety systems) and the normal operation system (heat removal from the crucial equipment: Spent fuel pool, heat exchangers of the intermediate circuit, a number of ventilation systems, etc.). The system operates on a closed circulating principle, water is cooled by splash pools on the territory of the plant site. The system includes service water pumps.

For emergency power supply, autonomous power supply sources are provided: automated diesel generators and an uninterruptible power supply unit based on accumulator batteries. There are 3 diesel generator sets of 5600 kW capacity each and 6 kV voltage for each power unit, they are deployed within 15 seconds and are capable of operating for 240 hours in maintenance-free mode. The batteries are operated in constant recharge mode.

Appendix 2

Selected systems for sharing

Electric Power Distribution System

Normal functioning of the system (for PU 1 and PU 2)

In normal operation mode, auxiliary consumers are supplied with power from two operating transformers of 25 MVA each, 15.75/6.3-6.3 kV, connected to generator current lines by blind taps between unit transformers and generator circuit breakers.

Consumers connected to 0.4 kV sections are supplied from 6/0.4 kV operating transformers, which are connected to 6 kV sections of the power unit.

A separate 6/0.4 kV transformer connected to the 6 kV section supplies power to the rectifier of the unit-wide DC installation, which provides DC power to consumers, including power to inverters, as well as recharging of the unit-wide accumulator battery.

In normal operation mode, the battery of the CSP (control and protection system) is recharged from a separate rectifier connected to the 0.4 kV section. Inverters connected to the DC panel busbars convert DC voltage into three-phase AC 0.4 kV voltage of 50 Hz frequency.

When the AC voltage at the 6 kV section disappears, the rectifier is switched off and the accumulator battery enters the discharge mode, continuing to supply the DC load and inverters. In this case the operation mode of consumers of the first reliability group is not interrupted.

When AC voltage is restored at the 6 kV section, the rectifier is automatically switched on (in 50-90 seconds), charging the accumulator battery to the voltage determined by the rectifier stabilization voltage setpoint.

System functioning in case of failures

Possible consequences of accidents in the electrical part, as well as accidents with the main equipment of the power unit are considered below:

(a) Short circuit on the communication line of the coupled power unit with the 330 kV switchgear. Protection of the unit busbar disconnects both generator circuit breakers (S-TG-1, S-TG-2 for PU1), 330 kV circuit breakers, circuit breakers of working power supply of 6 kV sections, affects the generator field extinguishing circuit breaker and sends a signal to the turbine stop valves landing. Full load shedding takes place. The reactor power regulator brings the power of the nuclear steam generating unit in accordance with the turbine power, i.e. it brings the reactor to no-load running.

Power unit auxiliary power supply is automatically transferred to the reserve(backup) transformer (1RT for PU1). The decision on further operation of the power unit is made by personnel depending on the size of the line damage;

(b) Damage of the power unit transformer (T-1, T-2 for PU1).

Transformer diff protection or transformer gas protection is operating. Further according to point a), and in case of gas protection operation, automatic start of fire extinguishing is carried out.

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ECCN: N

After disconnection of the 330 kV disconnecter in the circuit of the damaged transformer by the operator from the control room, the power unit can continue to operate with one turbine generator at 50% capacity;

(c) Damage of the auxiliary operating transformer (11T, 12T for PU1).

In the event of damage to the auxiliary operating transformer, the diff protection or gas protection of the transformers is operated. Further according to point (a);

(d) short circuit on one section of auxiliary needs 6 kV (1RA, 1RB, 2RA, 2RB for PU1).

There is a start-up of redundant mechanisms of similar purpose connected to the operable 6 kV sections.

The damage may result in the loss of one or two RCPs (reactor coolant pumps).

The power regulator sets the reactor to a power level corresponding to the number of remaining RCPs in operation;

(e) Disappearance of voltage on the section of normal operation (auxiliary switchgear 6kV 1RA, 1RB, 2RA, 2RB for PU1) as a result of disconnection of the working input (false tripping of automatics or erroneous action of the operator). Tripping of the working input circuit breaker causes operation of ALT (automatic load transfer) S without time delay. Technological process of the power unit is not interrupted;

(f) damage of any 0.4 kV section or damage of 6/0.4 kV transformers causes activation of redundant mechanisms on the remaining "healthy" sections, power supply of gate assemblies is transferred by the ALT (automatic load transfer) unit of the assembly to the remaining 0.4 kV sections in operation;

(g) damage to the unit-wide DC panel or battery causes the necessity to shut down the power unit;

(h) Generator damage tripped by the generator switch does not lead to changes in the auxiliary power supply scheme. The power of the reactor power unit is reduced to 50%, and the power unit operates with auxiliary loads supplied from operating transformers;

(i) turbine damage causes tripping of the generator switch (with a time delay or instantaneously, depending on the nature of the turbine damage and the protection in place).

The consequences are similar to those discussed in (h);

(j) in the event of a fault in the operating rectifier supplying the DC panel, an emergency signal of rectifier malfunction shall be issued and the power shall be manually transferred to the standby rectifier, with no disturbance in the operation of the technological systems.

(k) failures in the lighting system do not cause disturbances in the technological process of the power unit.

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Demineralized Water System

Safety functions

The demineralized water preparation system is not included in the list of safety-related systems. However, in the event of abnormal operations and accidents, the system can be used for:

1. Replenishment of losses and maintenance of balance of water of the secondary side, turbine room systems.
2. Replenishment of losses and maintenance of water reserves in the emergency feed water tanks of the SG.

Operational functions

The operational functions of the system are:

- regeneration operations of the unit's desalting unit, electromagnetic filter washing, mixed-type filter washing before and during operation, hydro-testing and pumping of pipelines in cold season.
- regeneration operations of water treatment systems;
- acid-alkali washing of evaporators;
- acid washing of condenser-degassers;
- cleaning and decontamination of premises.
- decontamination of the removable part of the RCP and decontamination of the Reactor

Department equipment

- decontamination of metal RW, decontamination of the SFP
- for own needs of Reactor Department systems and facilities in distillate storage tanks and emergency feed water tanks.
- performing process operations for equipment maintenance and routine maintenance, namely:
 - regenerations, hydro-removals and filter washings;
 - preparation of boric acid solutions;
 - preparation of decontamination solution
- technological needs of maintenance systems and equipment is performed by the turbine department equipment
- During the period of maintenance and repair by the turbine department of the power unit, DW is consumed for pressure testing and washing of the equipment of the Secondary side of the unit.

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Service Water System

Safety functions

The system of service water supply of the turbine compartment is not included in the list of systems important for safety. However, in case of abnormal situations and accidents the system can be used for:

1. cooling of turbine compartment consumers.
2. cooling of RCP electric motors.
3. heat removal from the process condenser.
4. cooling of the unit transformer.

Operational functions

The operational functions of the pool cooling system are:

1. supplying cooling process water to consumers of Group B of the turbine compartment (steam ejector machine, bearings of the circulation pumps, ventilation systems, oil coolers and heat exchangers).
2. ensuring the efficiency of the circulation pumps.
3. supplying cooling process water to consumers of Group B of the reactor compartment
4. cooling of the unit transformer.

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Appendix 3

Cost estimation modifications/license update

(Cost level: The Netherlands)

Realisation of a new NPP license, incorporating a coupled HPP activity on site, will bring costs for the activities to be performed. After/during modifying and coupling of NPP systems and adapting site facilities, changes have to be made to reports, procedures, management systems etc. to comply with the applicable requirements for the new NPP licence. Therefore several activities have to be performed for which time, and so cost, is consumed.

The following activities can be listed for the situation of full integration including the modification of a safety related system (e.g. main steam line):

1. Meetings with the Nuclear Regulator and other involved (local) parties/authorities
 - a. Intention, plans, constraints, conditions etc.
2. Rewriting checks, tests, inspections and procedures like
 - a. Start and stop procedures/checks
 - b. Maintenance (test, inspection) procedures
 - c. Ageing management
 - d. Procedures for AOO, DBA
 - e. Emergency procedures DEC/SA (e.g. function recovery)
3. Modify the Management system like
 - a. IT tools
 - b. Incorporated documents and drawings
4. Perform/modify/check safety analyses
 - a. Check existing PIE evaluations: are the specific plant DBAs still enveloping?
 - b. Perform or change safety analyses.
5. Modify the Safety Assessment Report, like
 - a. Sections with general descriptions
 - b. Sections with operation descriptions
 - c. Sections with accident/emergency descriptions
 - d. Sections with safety analyses
6. Modify documents/permit concerning other licensing impacts
 - a. Environment
 - b. Land use plan
 - c. Grid
 - d. Other Permit restrictions
7. License documentation
 - a. Filling in application documents requested by the Nuclear Regulator

Cost related to licensing of the NPP-HPP coupling (change of the NPP license) are made by man-hours (external experts, NPP-employees) and application fees from governments. For the following parts an order of magnitude is given:

AL: N
ECCN: N

• Safety analysis neighbourhood HPP (explosion)	100 k€
• Safety Analysis safety related system (enveloping check or new)	100k€ -1M€
• Modification non-safety systems:	100 k€
○ safety demonstrations and	
○ document modifications	
• Estimated other services (e.g. fees)	100 k€
• New/change Land-Use plan + environmental license + other permits (e.g. environment effect reporting can add up to 500 k€)	100 k€-1M€
<hr/>	
	+
	Total: 0.5-2.5 M€

ECCN: N

- ❖ Situation 1: modifying a few non safety related systems: order of magnitude 500 k€
- ❖ Situation 2: safety related system modifications: order of magnitude 2.5 M€.

AL: N

Annex 4: Full Report of Subtask 4 – Detailed Assessment of the various Incident / Accident Scenarios

Deliverable 4.2 subtask 4

DETAILED ASSESSMENT OF THE VARIOUS INCIDENT / ACCIDENT SCENARIOS

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Revisions

IND REV	RELEASE DATE	PARAGRAPH	SCOPE OF THE REVISION
1.A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue, reviewed by GRS & NRG

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
BST	Baker-Strehlow-Tang
DDT	Deflagration-to-Detonation Transition
ETA	Event Tree Analysis
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
LEL	Lower Explosive Limit
LFL	Lower Flammability Limit
LTE	Low-Temperature Electrolysis
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PSA	Probabilistic Safety Assessment
PVB	Pressure Vessel Burst
TNT	Trinitrotoluene
VCE	Vapour Cloud Explosion
VVER	Water-Water Energy Reactor

25 Introduction

The excess thermal and electrical energy produced by a nuclear power plant (NPP) can be used to produce low-carbon hydrogen through a cogeneration facility. Plant integration into an NPP site is expected to bring financial and technical benefits to the NPP. The impact assessment needs to demonstrate that the operation of the hybrid {NPP+HPP} system does not represent a significant risk to critical NPP structures based on their structural design criteria. The benefits of plant integration are expected to increase with smaller distances by sharing auxiliaries or balance of plant. The benefits for the NPP are twofold: first it generates an additional revenue source by the sale of hydrogen in periods of high renewable energy penetration into the electrical grid, whereas it reduces the negative impact over plant components due to flexible-load operation.

This report presents the main outcomes from the impact assessment applied to the integration of a 40 MW hydrogen facility into the Rivne power station in Ukraine. Rivne NPP comprises four VVER units with an overall electrical power output of 2880 MW. The reference hydrogen production plant (HPP) is based on a container solution, which hosts the electrolyser stacks and balance of plant. Gaseous hydrogen is generated at 35 bar via low-temperature electrolysis through Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) technology. The HPP site comprises two separated areas: an electrolyser facility for the production of hydrogen, and a high-pressure storage area with a capacity of 5 tonnes. The operation regime of the compressor in the high-pressure storage is decoupled from the electrolyser facility via a 30 kg buffer tank. The impact assessment is performed for the onsite HPP integration scenario into the NPP protected area.

In the presented study, the worst-case accident scenario is identified through HAZID technique applied to the electrolyser system and assisted by system reliability analysis through the evaluation of component failure rates and implementation of event tree analysis (ETA). For this purpose, the study uses generic component reliability data from the literature. Hazardous points for unintended hydrogen releases with subsequent escalation into fires and chemical explosions after ignition of the hydrogen-air mixture are identified at various locations within the electrolyser system. On the surroundings of the HPP, a physical explosion in the hydrogen buffer tank with subsequent fragment generation is addressed in the impact assessment. Based on the guidelines provided in [16, 17], those external events applied to our impact assessment comprise: (a) external release of hazardous material, (b) external fire, (c) external explosion, and (d) generation of projectiles.

The impact assessment addresses loading characterization against structural criteria for three different scenarios: (1) vapour cloud explosion (VCE), (2) pressure vessel burst (PVB), and (3) projectile impact. A hydrogen explosion is deemed as the worst-case scenario due to the destructive potential over long-range distances by the shock wave propagation. Contrarily, the main impact load of a fire is the thermal radiation at short-range distances, namely over HPP structures and plant personnel. The source term, thermal loading, blast loading, and mechanical impact by projectiles strongly depend on the HPP features, namely hydrogen inventory, and distances to critical NPP structures. The loading characterization is performed through deterministic safety calculations by semi-empirical models in the process safety [18, 19], which are implemented in the simulation software MATLAB. The ultimate goal is to establish minimum safety distances and determine whether and which means of protection are needed. The schematic representation of the adopted methodology is displayed in Figure 9.

The report is structured as follows: besides the introduction, Section 26 provides a description of the hydrogen and nuclear facilities from the impact assessment point of view, Section 27 reports the hazard identification process within the hydrogen plant, and Section 28 and Section 29 report the

main outcomes of the deterministic safety calculations applied to a confined release, unconfined release, and PVB with fragment generation and ejection. Finally, Section 30 provides the main conclusions of the study.

Figure 65: Applied methodology in the sub-task report

26 Description of the Involved Facilities

The HPP comprises two different areas: the electrolyser facility, and the high-pressure storage area. The first can be deployed onsite or offsite of the NPP perimeter based on the outcomes of the impact assessment, whereas the storage area will be in any case located outside of the NPP perimeter due to the large amount of energy stored and associated risks to critical NPP structures. Since detailed information about the HPP has not yet been defined in the project, a generic configuration with layouts and distances provided by one of the project industrial partners is adopted as a reference facility in this report. The use of the figures of this facility is restricted to the presented calculations.

The Ukrainian state operator JSC Energoatom through the project partner ESG has provided numerous data and technical discussions regarding Rivne and Khmelnytskyi NPP sites, which include aerial views, information about interface systems and components, proposed HPP locations (onsite and offsite), and relative distances to critical NPP structures. In order to be consistent with the techno-economic study performed in Work Package 3, the detailed assessment of incident/accident scenarios resulting from the coupling of both facilities is exclusively based on the features of the Rivne NPP site.

26.1 Nuclear Power Station

Rivne NPP is the reference nuclear facility in this study. It is located in the Rivne Oblast in Ukraine and comprises an overall turbine-generator output of 2800 MW. The NPP site hosts two reactor units powered by VVER-440/V-213 (440 MW), and two units powered by VVER-1000/V-320 (1000 MW). The NPP is run by the state enterprise JSC Energoatom. Buildings and structures are designed to withstand an airborne shock wave with a frontal compression pressure of approximately 10 kPa for Units 1 and 2, and 30 kPa for Units 3 and 4. Likewise, country-specific standards set the limit value of heat flux on the human body as 4.2 kW/m² and 12.5 kW/m² for equipment and materials. The presented impact assessment sets the structural design limit of 10 kPa as the conservative fragility criterion.

In the framework of the Euratom NPHyCo project, free locations were analysed at the industrial site (Place-1), and within the sanitary protection zone (Place-2). After discussions and walkdowns, two different locations were found suitable and proposed for further investigation of a potential HPP integration. An aerial view of the NPP site obtained with Google Maps is displayed in Figure 66, which highlights the two proposed sites for the plant integration. Both locations have access roads and railway tracks. A free cell on a 110 kV open switchgear can be the connection to power the cogeneration facility through a step-down transformer in the hydrogen island.

Figure 66: Location of building sites in the two selected locations at Rivne NPP

Approximate distances to critical structures and components at both proposed integration locations are gathered in Table 44. The default distances refer to the outer boundaries of both proposed plant integration sites. The available surface area in the site within the protected area (Place-1) accounts for approximately 110 m x 90 m, whereas the hydrogen facility footprint accounts for 40 m x 40 m without sharing balance of plant with the NPP. That is, if the HPP deployment over the available NPP site is optimized, an additional distance of 50 m is available to those structures (see column 4 in Table 44). These distances are used as the reference values in the reported calculations.

The nearest NPP structure to the proposed integration site is the standby diesel generator. From the list of structures gathered in Table 44, the most critical buildings and structures are the cooling towers, turbine building, and open switchgear. Those are relevant to provide the ultimate heat sink to ensure core cooling. Loss of switchyard components would mean a loss of offsite power event, which may challenge the NPP to shutdown safely. This is one of the main contributors to core damage frequency.

Table 44: HPP distances to critical NPP structures

Integration Site	NPP Structure	Distance (default)	Distance (optimal)
Onsite (Place-1)	Standby Diesel Generator	45 m	95 m
	Cooling Tower #3	138 m	188 m
	Cooling Tower #4	159 m	209 m

	Cooling Tower #5	177 m	227 m
	Turbine Building	450 m	500 m
	Open Switchgear	1500 m	1550 m
Offsite (Place-2)	Nearest Village	1100 m	-
	Nuclear Station	1200 m	-

26.2 Hydrogen Cogeneration Facility

The schematic representation of the reference electrolyser system in this work is displayed in Figure 67. It consists of PEM technology (it shares many similarities with AEL technology and results may be extrapolated), where feed water is supplied in the oxygen gas-liquid separator, which vents the oxygen generated in the anode (via oxidation). The H_2 generated in the cathode (via reduction) flows through the gas-liquid separator, drying and purification unit, which enhances purity up to 99.999 vol %. Gaseous H_2 is delivered to the buffer tank at 35 bar and 40 °C. The electrolyser facility comprises a 30 kg cylindrical buffer tank to decouple the electrolyser and compressor operating regimes.

Figure 67: Process flow diagram of the PEM electrolyser system [20]

26.2.1 Electrolyser facility description

The technical specifications of the HPP are taken from D2.1 “Analysis of viable interfaces within NPP environment for H₂ co-generation” and D2.2 “Impact Assessment Report”. In this regard, Figure 68 provides a detailed block flow diagram for PEM technology. The auxiliary systems that provide the inputs for hydrogen production via electrolysis are electricity and demineralized water as main consumables; pressurized air for pneumatically activated valves and nitrogen for flushing of the equipment; furthermore, cooling water is needed to remove the dissipated heat and a wastewater connection to take wastewater from the feed water purification. The core components for hydrogen production are the feedwater make-up unit, the electrolyser stacks and the gas separation and purification units. There are the subsystems for compression and intermediate storage of hydrogen.

Figure 68: Block flow diagram of a generic PEM electrolyser system [21]

The agreed list of the electrolyser technical parameters is gathered in Table 45.

Table 45: List of HPP technical parameters

Property	Unit	Value
Operating temperature	degC	80
Operating pressure	bar	30
DeltaT in/out stacks	degK	5
Electricity PEM	kWh/kgH2	50
Feedwater	kg/kgH2	11
Cooling water	degK	10 (Tin 50°C & Tout 60°C)
Chilled water	degK	5 (Tin 3°C & Tout 8°C)
Oxygen	kg/h	4350-4800
Hydrogen	kg/h	450-600
Wastewater	kg/h	8650

The reference HPP is based on a container solution, whose overall power needs account for 40 MW. The HPP comprises three 10 MW modules, each with its own balance of stack and balance of plant. The reference HPP configuration in this work is based on the layouts depicted in Figure 69 and Figure 70. The figure is representative of a 20 MW container solution. Based on the specifications from D2.2, this work has added an additional 10 MW module to reach the foreseen electrolyser capacity. Each 10 MW module comprises its own medium voltage transformer and three different containers: (1) container process unit, (2) container electrical unit, and (3) container demineralized water unit, with corresponding cooling systems (air ventilators) and maintenance areas. Above the adjacent container

process and electrical units stands the gas processing unit, an unconfined area with a metallic roof to protect against adverse weather conditions.

The 10 MW container process unit hosts 8 PEM stacks. Each electrolyser stack is assumed to deliver at full load 23 kg/h of gaseous hydrogen at 35 bar. Therefore, each 10 MW module has a nominal production rate of 184 kg/h, and the HPP as a whole of 552 kg/h. At full load, production accounts for 13.25 tonnes per day. Based on the hydrogen production rate per container, the authors have estimated a hydrogen collector diameter of 50 mm. The HPP is fully automated and operated from the NPP control room. The impact assessment assumes electrical energy from the NPP as a feedstock to the electrolyser facility. Sharing of balance of plant between facilities is outside of the scope of this work. In the report, the HPP is assumed operated at full capacity with a fixed NPP allocated power.

The balance of stack and balance of plant of the electrolyser facility are summarized below:

Container process unit (ground floor)

- Electrolyser cell stacks
- Gas collectors (H_2/O_2)
- Water supply tanks
- Water pumps
- Water cooler (heat exchanger)
- Deionized water polishing module
- Hydrogen/oxygen vents

Container process unit (first floor)

- Hydrogen gas separator
- Oxygen gas separator
- Hydrogen cooler
- Hydrogen water separator
- Hydrogen purification and dryer

Container electrical unit (ground floor)

- Rectifiers
- Control unit

Container electrical unit (first floor)

- Rectifier cooling supply (air inlet)
- Electrolyser cooling supply (ventilator)
- Air inlet (relative air humidity)

Container water purification (ground floor)

- Water purification system for demineralized water

Container water purification (first floor)

- Gas chilled cooling supply (ventilator)

The container process unit includes vents, gas leak and flame detectors, and fire detectors and water sprinkles. It is likewise equipped with bottom and ceiling openings to force a minimum natural ventilation flow rate under normal operation, and an additional electric motor driving an air fan to provide forced ventilation upon leak detection or abnormal operation. The ventilation rates should be sufficient to dilute hydrogen leaks to less than 25 % of the lower flammability limit (LFL), which is about 1 % by volume in air. Based on natural ventilation specifications from 29 CFR 1910.106 and TRBS 3151/TRGS 751, natural ventilation openings would be able to provide an air exchange rate of 5.

The amount of hydrogen contained in the HPP process equipment is summarized in Table 46. The safety margin accounts for 10% of the gas separator volume. The process equipment contains approximately 165 kg of hydrogen (55 kg per 10 MW module).

Table 46: Hydrogen inventory in the HPP

HPP Component	Inventory H ₂ (Nm ³)	Inventory H ₂ (kg)
Electrolyser stacks	Negligible	Negligible
Gas separator	48	116
Gas drying and purification	10	-
Piping	5	-
Safety margin	5	12
Total	68	164

The dimensions of the electrolyser stack and process container are gathered in Table 47. The table comprises two different container configurations: Cont-1 represents the free volume in the stack compartment (referred as lower-bound in the calculations), whereas Cont-2 represents the volume of the empty container (referred as upper-bound in the calculations). The latter includes the container compartment for balance-of-stack such as water tanks, water pumps, and heat exchangers (among others). Cont-1 configuration consists of Cont-2 configuration considering the volume occupied by the 8 PEM stacks. Balance-of-stack such as water tanks, pumps, heat exchangers, and so on are not accounted in that volume due to lack of specific data. Nevertheless, the addition of those parameters is not expected to change the results significantly on the applied calculation methodologies.

Table 47: Dimensions of stack container

Dimensions	Unit	PEM Stack	Cont-1	Cont-2
Width	<i>m</i>	0.850	2.438	2.438
Length	<i>m</i>	1.000	8.849	12.034
Height	<i>m</i>	1.530	3.500	3.500
Volume	<i>m</i> ³	1.30	65.10	102.68

Figure 69: Three-dimensional representation of a generic 20 MW electrolyser plant

Figure 70: Two-dimensional layout of the generic 20 MW electrolyser plant

26.2.2 High-pressure storage area

The gaseous hydrogen is transported via a transmission pipe from the HPP towards the storage facility, which hosts the compressor unit, high-pressure storage vessels, and filling station for off-taker delivery. The underground transmission pipe safety features include flame arresters and check valves and are projected with an optimal diameter of 150 mm, based on hydrogen production rate at full capacity, and corresponding analyses from the techno-economic study in Deliverable 3.1.

The initial planned hydrogen storage capacity is below the lower-tier threshold (5 tonnes) of the SEVESO III Directive (Directive 2012/18/EU). In addition, expansion to 15 tonnes is under consideration to ensure storage of daily production, which may be beneficial in case of malfunction of hydrogen transportation. The latter is assumed by road through multiple element gas containers.

Figure 71: Horizontally mounted pressure vessel

In principle, the impact assessment and techno-economic study is meant to consider two different pressure vessel configurations, in order to assess advantages and disadvantages, also from a safety perspective towards the NPP. The first one (Vessel-1) consists of a traditional large cylindrical vessel with a nominal pressure of 350 bar (see Figure 71), whereas the second one (Vessel-2) consists of a rack of smaller diameter vessels with a nominal pressure up to 350 bar (see Figure 72).

Nevertheless, this report will exclusively focus on the vessel configuration displayed in Figure 71, which consists of a type I steel vessel. The capacity of each vessel is assumed 1000 kg of compressed gaseous hydrogen. Vessel-1 requires a second hydrogen compression stage in order to increase the pressure to fill the multiple element gas container of the largest available capacity (ISO 668) at a reasonable time. The latter consists of type IV composite vessels with a nominal pressure of 500 bar, and hydrogen transport capacity of around 1200 kg. The hydrogen storage area comprises either 5 or 15 pressure vessels. They are assumed horizontally oriented and equipped with pressure relief valves and burst discs. The high-pressure storage area has its own fire detection and mitigation system.

The initial planned storage capacity is below the lower-tier threshold (5 tonnes) of the SEVESO III Directive (Directive 2021/18/EU). A storage capacity of 5 tonnes would represent roughly 4 trucks of the highest capacity (see Figure 73), whereas 15 tonnes would be enough to store the production of an entire day. Based on these assumptions, we can assume 5 tonnes storage capacity as the lower bound, and 15 tonnes storage capacity as the upper bound.

Figure 72: Rack of horizontally mounted pressure vessels

TABELLE 4: AKTUELL VERFÜGBARE TRAILERGRÖßEN UND -KAPAZITÄTEN

Druck- stufe	Containergröße („high cube“)	Gesamtspeicher- volumen (Wasservolumen)	H ₂ Speicherkapazität gesamt	H ₂ Speicherkapazität nutzbar ⁴
[bar]		[m ³]	[kg]	[kg]
200	20 ft.	18,15	271	226
	40 ft.	37,4	558	466
	45 ft.	42,35	632	528
300	20 ft.	18,9	401	352
	30 ft.	29,4	623	549
	40 ft.	39,9	846	745
	45 ft.	45,15	958	843
350	20 ft.	18,15	435	390
	40 ft.	37,4	897	805
	45 ft.	42,35	1016	911
380	20 ft.	18,9	485	437
	30 ft.	29,4	754	680
	40 ft.	39,9	1024	923
	45 ft.	45,15	1159	1045
500	20 ft.	17,15	542	500
	30 ft.	26,95	851	786
	40 ft.	36,4	1150	1061
	45 ft.	40,95	1294	1194

Figure 73: Available trailer size and capacity for hydrogen transport

26.3 Plant Integration Scenarios

The level of plant integration and the distance between the HPP and the NPP are the most critical factors for the licensing of the cogeneration facility. In contrast, the benefits of plant integration are expected to be higher with lesser distances based on onsite solutions, since the needs of the HPP can be covered by interface systems and components from the NPP. The nuclear licensing requirements will be the most severe over the cogeneration facility. It must be proven that the interaction of the

HPP with the NPP does not increase risk significantly for the NPP design basis, and risks to the environment comply with regulatory requirements.

The licensing impact in NPHyCo is foreseen for three different levels of plant integration into the NPP site: (a) HPP integration within the NPP protected area, (b) HPP integration into the NPP sanitary protection zone, and (c) HPP integration offsite of the NPP perimeter. Based on the investigation of the needs of the HPP, several postulated integration scenarios were identified in the project, which are gathered in Table 48. HPP needs may be supplied by the following NPP auxiliary systems:

- Demineralized water system
- Waste water system
- Cooling water system
- Instrument air supply system
- Nitrogen supply system
- Chilled water system (dismissed by NPP staff)

Table 48: Summary of plant coupling scenarios

Onsite solutions	Offsite solutions
Full integration except chilled water, with electricity at normal price (grid)	Integration of cooling water and electricity at normal price
Full integration except chilled water, with electricity at reduced price (home need)	Integration of cooling water and electricity at reduced price
Integration of cooling water and electricity at normal price	Integration of electricity at normal price
Integration of cooling water and electricity at reduced price	Integration of electricity at reduced price
Integration of electricity (only) at reduced price	Zero integration as benchmark, electricity at normal price

The study here presented is based on onsite integration within the NPP site to evaluate the worst-case scenario within the HPP as an external hazard to the NPP. The risk assessment addresses the coupling scenario with shared electricity from the NPP as feedstock for the HPP, whereas all HPP auxiliaries are located within the cogeneration facility site. The HPP is assumed to be operated in base-load mode at full capacity. This represents a conservative condition in terms of higher hydrogen inventory.

27 Identification of Potential Accident Scenarios

27.1 Hydrogen Safety Engineering

Hydrogen is a flammable gas and therewith, plausible hazard events from hydrogen are [18]:

- Fires after low pressure hydrogen releases
- Jet fires from pressurised hydrogen vessels or pipes
- VCE from pressurised hydrogen vessels or pipes
- VCE from liquified hydrogen pools after leaks from liquified hydrogen vessels
- Boiling liquid expanding vapour explosions from liquified hydrogen vessels

Since liquefied hydrogen is not available at the HPP, the latter two hazard events cannot occur there. Fires and jet fires can lead to strong convective heat release but have only effects nearby the HPP without effects on the NPP. Hence, only hydrogen VCE from pressurised vessels or pipes can affect the NPP. In general, a VCE can cause following effects on its surrounding: shock wave effects, thermal effects leading to consequential fires, damage from missiles, damage from ground shocks, crater forming, and injuries to animals or humans [18] (Section 17.31). Of these effects, shock waves and missiles have the largest potential to cause damages to the NPP on large distances. Thus, the following hazard impact assessment focusses on effects from hydrogen VCE shock waves and missiles.

The HIAD 2.0 database provides a summary of hydrogen fatal events within Europe (ref). Chemical and petrochemical industries lead the statistics and comprise the largest share of accidents with 62% of the total. The vast majority of events are initiated by hydrogen systems (75%), most of which led to explosions (35%) closely followed by fires (24%). Some hydrogen VCE in the open atmosphere have been observed [18] (Table 17.30). For example, 90 kg of hydrogen were released in Jackass Flats in 1964 and about 10 kg of hydrogen were involved in a VCE. However, this event did not cause larger damages. Hence, hydrogen VCE can occur and can pose hazards to its surrounding. Following characteristics of hydrogen contribute to its hazardous potential after its release [22]:

- The minimum ignition energy of hydrogen is much lower than for other combustible gases,
- hydrogen explosions are more prone to develop from deflagration (flame speed below speed of sound) to detonation (flame speed above speed of sound) as other gases,
- the flammability range of hydrogen is between 4% and 75% by volume,
- the detonation range of hydrogen is between 11% and 59% by volume,
- The near-stoichiometric hydrogen concentration in air is at 29.5% by volume.

The transition to detonation is facilitated in case of turbulence because it increases the mixing and the flame speed. Favourable conditions for the transition can be either caused by the turbulent outflow of hydrogen from a leak or by repeated obstacles within the hydrogen cloud. The significance of the deflagration-to-detonation transition (DDT) in reactor safety lies on the destructive potential of these fast combustion modes. Parameters such as the combustion expansion ratio σ and the detonation cell size λ are key to characterize the flame propagation regime, in order to evaluate overpressure and structural response of the container or containment [23].

In addition, hydrogen clouds show a different behaviour to other combustible gas clouds. Several references describe the behaviour of hydrogen clouds in the atmosphere [18] (Sec. 17.28.28). They all stress the effects from buoyancy of hydrogen. E.g., it is described in [18] (Sec. 17.28.28) that only the hydrogen outflow over a rather small duration in the order of seconds can contribute to an explosion. Also, drifts of hydrogen clouds are mostly described regarding clouds from liquid hydrogen but not from pressurized hydrogen. Looking at these references, drifts of hydrogen clouds over a longer duration as they occur for hydrocarbon clouds are not expected.

Hydrogen has some particular characteristics compared to other flammable gases, which are relevant for the hazard impact assessment. On the one hand, hydrogen is highly buoyant. Hence, far drifts of hydrogen gas clouds, as they have been observed for natural gas, are not possible. In addition, the formation of hydrogen clouds, a precondition for an explosion, is only to be expected under special conditions, e.g., within confined spaces or after the release of a large amount of hydrogen within a short period of time. On the other hand, hydrogen has a wide range of flammability (see Figure 74) and can be easily ignited. Explosions can lead to high overpressures due to the high flame speed of hydrogen and they have the potential to cause damages over large distances. A comprehensive review of the main features of gaseous and liquified hydrogen, as well as safety considerations of hydrogen production by nuclear power, and storage nearby nuclear facilities is provided in [22].

Figure 74: Shapiro ternary diagram for air-hydrogen-steam mixture

27.2 Hazard Identification at the Hydrogen Facility

This section aims at identifying the most relevant hazard events within the coupled hydrogen facility. For this purpose, HAZID (HAZard IDentification) technique is applied together with system reliability analysis to identify hazardous points within the electrolyser system, and determining potentially contributory initiating events and root causes. By means of ETA the identified initiating events are extended towards potential hazard events through a sequence of possible events. This allows to estimate the frequency of occurrence of the identified outcome events, which in this study comprise: (1) safe condition, (2) jet fire, (3) chemical explosion, and (4) physical explosion. Chemical explosion refers to a hydrogen VCE, whereas physical explosion refers to a PVB. Two different HPP areas are addressed in the impact assessment: the electrolyser facility and the hydrogen buffer tank.

Hazardous points within the electrolyser facility have been identified through the evaluation of the plant component inventory by means of HAZID technique [18], which consists of a qualitative methodology meant for the systematic assessment and identification of hazards and problem areas associated with plant, system, operation, design, and maintenance. HAZID is widely applied in the risk assessment of hydrogen systems [24] [25]. A detailed inventory of balance of stack, balance of plant, and safety-related systems has been developed for this purpose based on public information and proprietary data. Engineering judgement assumptions have been adopted when needed.

In this work, the postulated initiating event in the electrolyser facility is an undetected overpressure, which eventually leads to mechanical failure (fracture and hydrogen leakage) in the hydrogen collector and separator vessel flange. Pressure build-up is assumed after fault operation of a check valve along the gaseous hydrogen flow path. This constitutes one of the common hazards in PEM systems [1]. In this manuscript, only the most credible initiating events are reported, which are based on generic hydrogen-system leak frequencies developed by [2, 3]. Mean leak frequencies are used in the release calculations presented in this section. In addition, equipment reliability data specific to PEM systems have been obtained from [4]. The schematic representation of the gaseous leakage in the electrolyser is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 75: Schematic representation of hazardous events in the electrolyser facility

The identified hydrogen leakage points within the electrolyser facility, corresponding leak sizes, and frequencies are summarized in Table 49. The leakage in the hydrogen collector is assumed in one of the valves downstream of the eight PEM stacks, so that all hydrogen produced in the 10 MW module leaks into the container volume. Hydrogen leakage in the separator vessel is assumed in the upstream piping flange, and tank blowdown is assumed in the gas processing unit. The impact assessment foresees a range of leak sizes of interest comprising small (1 %), medium (10 %), and large breaks (100 %). Very small leakages (< 1 %) are omitted in this study due to the rather negligible contribution to the worst-case scenario or hydrogen explosion. The slow concentration build-up will hardly reach the LFL before the leak can be detected and isolated. This issue may be further investigated within the electrolyser container volume by means of high-fidelity CFD calculations.

Table 49: Initial event locations for hydrogen leaks and their frequencies

Leak location	Leak size	Frequency (1/yr)
Hydrogen collector (check valve)	Small (1 %)	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
	Medium (10 %)	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	Full bore (100 %)	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Separator vessel (pipe flange)	Small (1 %)	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	Medium (10 %)	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
	Full bore (100 %)	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$

The unintended hydrogen release is set as the initiating event inside the electrolyser, and through ETA it has been extended towards all potential hazard events. The leak size influences frequencies of the outcome events, as it affects not only leak frequencies, but also probabilities of intermediate events (e.g., cloud dispersion). The event sequence diagrams for the confined and unconfined hydrogen releases are displayed in Figure 78 and Figure 79, respectively. The initiating event can lead to three different outcomes: (a) safe condition, (b) jet fire, and (c) hydrogen explosion. Safe condition refers to no ignition of the hydrogen-air mixture and thus no risk-significant consequences, whereas jet fire implies immediate ignition at the leak. Hydrogen explosion requires delayed ignition of the hydrogen gas mixture. The frequencies of the outcome events in the event trees are calculated as:

$$f(\text{outcome event}) = f(H_2 \text{ release}) \times \prod_{i=1}^n P_i$$

where $f(H_2 \text{ release})$ is the rate of component leak expressed in events per year, P_i represents the probability of the i th event or branch occurring given the occurrence of the previous events, and n is

the number of events or branches leading to the specific outcome. The hydrogen ignition probabilities are a function of the hydrogen release rate and are gathered in Table 50 [3]. The nominal production capacity of the reference electrolyser container accounts for 0.051 kg/s. A delayed ignition of a hydrogen gas mixture may as well trigger a flash fire. However, given the level of obstacles in the container process unit by the eight stacks and the balance of stack, and the balance of plant in the gas processing unit, upon ignition, flame front acceleration by turbulent mixing is expected, thereby leading to a hydrogen explosion in a deflagration or detonation mode.

Table 50: Default hydrogen ignition probabilities

Release rate (kg/s)	Immediate ignition (-)	Delayed ignition (-)
< 0.125	0.008	0.004
0.125-6.25	0.053	0.027
> 6.25	0.230	0.120

As far as confined hydrogen release is concerned, the container is equipped with redundant leak and flame detectors [3]. Upon leak detection, the water electrolysis reaction is terminated by the control system. In addition, the electrolyser system is automatically shut-down under abnormal operation by the signal from the flow and pressure transmitters. Natural ventilation through the container openings will play a dominant role depending on the wind conditions outside and the leak size, as dispersion effectiveness increases with decreasing leak size. Upon leak detection or abnormal operation, forced ventilation is activated by the control system by means of an electric air fan. In the hypothetical situation that all previous safety systems fail to act on demand, and if any available ignition source is present in the process container unit, it may trigger the combustion of the released hydrogen.

The design of the HPP is based on ATEX zoning depending on the hydrogen inventory and therefore level of explosion risk. Hence, presence of ignition sources is minimized and comprises mostly electrical equipment. As far as unconfined hydrogen release is concerned, redundant leak and flame detectors are also present on site. The main difference to the confined release scenario lays on the dispersion means of the hydrogen-air mixture, which relies on passive atmospheric dispersion. An analysis of the wind conditions in the Rivne site has been performed in this study, obtaining an average wind speed of 15 km/h, which corresponds to a wind force of 3 in the Beaufort scale. Based on the wind features, the authors have agreed on a probability for successful vapour cloud dispersion of 0.8 in this study, regardless of the leak size.

In Figure 78, outcomes VCE-05 and VCE-10 are identified as hydrogen explosions. Successful or failure of leak detection and isolation leads to two main branches. The first branch assumes successful detection, but failure to perform function of the control system and shut-down the electrolyser. Assuming inefficient natural ventilation to disperse the vapor cloud, and failure of the DC motor driving the air fan to provide forced ventilation, hydrogen concentration may rise above the lower flammability and explosive limits. Upon delayed ignition by an arc fault of the DC motor, this sequence of events may escalate into a hydrogen VCE. The second branch assumes failure to detect and isolate the leak, and failure to shut-down the electrolyser system upon abnormal behaviour by the pressure and flow transmitters. Both are assumed to fail to provide signal. Under inefficient natural circulation, a vapour cloud may develop inside the container. Upon delayed ignition, this leads to a hydrogen VCE.

The frequencies of occurrence of all identified outcome events in Figure 78 are summarized in Table 51. Hydrogen dispersion inside the container via natural ventilation is assumed to be effective under small leaks, whereas medium and large breaks will require forced ventilation to keep the hydrogen

concentration below the LFL. Based on the HPP features, natural ventilation is able to provide an air exchange rate of 6. This value is close to the boundary to keep the hydrogen concentration below 25 % of the LFL. Based on these results, the probability for successful vapour cloud dispersion under the 1 % leak is set by the authors as 0.8, whereas for medium and large breaks is set to negligible. This approach explains the differences between Outcomes VCE-05 and VCE-10 regarding small and mid sizes.

Table 51: Frequencies of occurrence for confined hydrogen release

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	1 % (/yr)	10 % (/yr)	100 % (/yr)
Outcome VCE-01	Safe Condition	$6.74 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-02	Safe Condition	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$6.78 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.71 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Outcome VCE-03	Safe Condition	$3.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.57 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.23 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-04	Jet Fire	$6.47 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$9.70 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3.88 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome VCE-05	Chemical Explosion	$3.21 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$4.81 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome VCE-06	Safe Condition	$7.99 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.79 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome VCE-07	Safe Condition	$9.77 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome VCE-08	Safe Condition	$1.80 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$6.75 \cdot 10^{-13}$	$2.70 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Outcome VCE-09	Jet Fire	$3.60 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$5.40 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.16 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Outcome VCE-10	Chemical Explosion	$1.79 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.68 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Outcome VCE-11	Safe Condition	$4.45 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$6.67 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.67 \cdot 10^{-8}$

In Figure 79, outcomes UVCE-04 and UVCE-09 are identified as hydrogen explosions. Leak detection and isolation leads to two main branches. The first branch implies successful leak detection but failure to shut down the electrolyser by the control system, together with non-successful atmospheric dispersion of the hydrogen cloud. Assuming delayed ignition of the vapour cloud, this may escalate into a hydrogen VCE. The second branch implies failure to detect the leak, failure of flow and pressure transmitters to report abnormal operation to the control system, and finally inefficient atmospheric dispersion. Assuming delayed ignition, this may lead to a hydrogen VCE. The frequencies of occurrence of all identified outcome events for the unconfined hydrogen release are summarized in Table 52.

Table 52: Frequencies of occurrence for unconfined hydrogen release

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	1 % (/yr)	10 % (/yr)	100 % (/yr)
Outcome UVCE-01	Safe Condition	$1.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-02	Safe Condition	$3.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-03	Jet Fire	$7.23 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$4.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome UVCE-04	Chemical Explosion	$3.59 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$6.28 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Outcome UVCE-05	Safe Condition	$8.93 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome UVCE-06	Safe Condition	$1.95 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.42 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome UVCE-07	Safe Condition	$3.60 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.30 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.16 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Outcome UVCE-08	Jet Fire	$7.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$4.32 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Outcome UVCE-09	Chemical Explosion	$3.57 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$6.25 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-11}$

Outcome UVCE-10	Safe Condition	$8.89 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$5.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$
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In the buffer tank, the initiating event is an external fire originated by an arc fault in the electrical cabinet within the container electrical unit that extends to the buffer tank area. The fire may likewise be assumed in one of the three transformers. According to [26], the generic fire frequency accounts for $4.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ per year. The corresponding event tree diagram is depicted in Figure 80. Depending on the fire detection and extinguishing success, two main branches are considered in the impact assessment. If the fire is successfully detected and put out by the water sprinkler system, the outcome event will be a safe condition (outcome PVB-01). On the contrary, if the fire system fails to isolate the fire, pressure will increase in the buffer tank leading to the actuation of the spring-loaded safety valves.

The release of hydrogen by the safety valves may escalate into a jet fire (outcome PVB-03) or hydrogen VCE (outcome PVB-04). Given the thermal conditions imposed by the external fire surrounding the buffer tank, a jet fire is much more likely to occur under immediate ignition (despite the results in Table 53). In case of spurious operation of the safety valve, the rupture of the burst disc at a higher pressure set-point may as well lead to a jet fire (outcome PVB-07) or hydrogen VCE (outcome PVB-08). To the authors' knowledge, up-to-date there is not a single event when the burst disc of a pressure vessel has failed to break under overpressure conditions, but several cases of early break due to degraded conditions [27]. In order to escalate into a physical explosion, this study assumes a human error to calibrate the burst disc beyond the maximum allowable working pressure of the vessel.

The calculated frequencies of occurrence are gathered in Table 53. The higher values for jet fire compared to the unintended hydrogen release within the electrolyser are directly related with three factors: (1) the lower frequency of the initiating event, (2) the high reliability of the passive pressure-relief devices, and (3) the higher ignition probabilities due to higher hydrogen release rates. Despite the calculated chemical explosion in the order of 10^{-5} per year, the actual frequency of occurrence is expected to be lower due to the thermal effects of the fire nearby, which will lead to immediate ignition and development of a jet flame. However, the authors have not yet been able to quantify this thermal effect over the delayed ignition probability. The frequency of a physical explosion (outcome PVB-10) is in the order of 10^{-9} per year, mostly due to the high reliability of the pressure-relief devices.

Table 53: Frequencies of occurrence for the buffer tank

Outcome Event	Hazard/Risk	Frequency (1/yr)
Outcome PVB-01	Safe Condition	$4.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Outcome PVB-02	Safe Condition	$3.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Outcome PVB-03	Jet Fire	$4.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-04	Chemical Explosion	$2.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-05	Safe Condition	$8.23 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Outcome PVB-06	Safe Condition	$2.70 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Outcome PVB-07	Jet Fire	$3.58 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome PVB-08	Chemical Explosion	$1.73 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Outcome PVB-09	Safe Condition	$6.22 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Outcome PVB-10	Physical Explosion	$3.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$

To sum up, the cumulative frequencies for jet fire and hydrogen VCE under confined and unconfined releases are depicted in Figure 76 and Figure 77, respectively. The highest frequency for a hydrogen VCE under confined release lies in the range of 10^{-9} per year. This low value is explained by the low frequency of the leak (see Table 49) as well as the flow and pressure transmitters [4]. On the other hand, the highest frequency of occurrence for a hydrogen VCE under unconfined release is in the order of 10^{-7} per year for small leaks, and 10^{-9} per year for mid and large breaks. Main differences between confined and unconfined release scenarios lie on the leak frequencies and atmospheric dispersion instead of forced ventilation. In the buffer tank, the frequency of a chemical explosion lies in the order of 10^{-5} per year, whereas a physical explosion in the order of 10^{-9} per year

Based on the aforementioned results, an external fire nearby the buffer tank is the major risk contribution within the HPP site. According to the USNRC Regulatory Guide 1.91 [28], the applicant or licensee may show that the risk is acceptably low on the basis of low probability of explosions and fires. A demonstration that the rate of exposure to a calculated peak positive incident overpressure of 6.9 kPa is less than 10^{-6} per year when based on conservative assumptions, or 10^{-7} per year when based on realistic assumptions, is deemed as acceptable. The calculated frequencies in this section are based on conservative conditions in terms of high hydrogen inventory and multiple failure of detection and safety systems. In this regard, a chemical explosion in the buffer tank exceeds the threshold of 10^{-6} per year.

In many states, a target frequency of exceedance of 10^{-4} per year or less is used for design basis external events for natural hazards [17]. In addition, a probability of 10^{-7} per reactor-year is used in the design of new facilities as one acceptable limit on the probability value for interacting events with serious radiological consequences, and this is considered a conservative value for the screening probability level if applied to all events of the same type (e.g., explosions). Therefore, probabilistic safety assessment (PSA) of external hazards has to be performed unless it can be shown that the design basis of the plant ensures that the plant can withstand the loads induced by a hazard with 10^{-7} per year frequency. The load characterizations of all identified accident scenarios are evaluated in Section 28. The results should demonstrate that those outcome events do not pose a risk to the NPP structures gathered in Table 44 based on the fragility criterion of 10 kPa.

Figure 76: Cumulative frequency of occurrence for jet fire

Figure 77: Cumulative frequency of occurrence for chemical explosion

Figure 78: Event tree diagram for confined hydrogen release

Figure 79: Event tree diagram for unconfined hydrogen release

Figure 80: Event tree diagram for pressure vessel burst

28 Hydrogen Vapor Cloud Explosion

28.1 Semi-Empirical Model Description

28.1.1 Baker-Strehlow-Tang Model

The Baker-Strehlow-Tang (BST) model is based on the flame Mach number M_f , which is defined by the ratio of the flame velocity in the cloud to the ambient sound velocity [18]. The model uses a set of non-dimensional blast curves to predict the blast load for a given source energy and standoff distance. More concisely, the BST model uses a continuum of numerically determined pressure and impulse curves that are based on the Mach number of the VCE flame front relative to a stationary point of reference (see Figure 81). Blast load duration can be calculated from pressure and impulse.

Contrarily to other widely used blast load models such as the TNT-Equivalency, the main underlying assumption of this model is that the most likely initiating combustion mode upon ignition of a vapour cloud is a deflagration (instead of a detonation), which is well supported by empirical evidence for hydrocarbon and hydrogen fuels. The BST curves are based on a 1-D numerical study to predict blast waves generated at constant velocity and accelerating flames propagating in a spherical geometry.

The BST curves are closer to empirical results than the Baker-Strehlow model, but still conservative in maintaining the slowest blast wave decay among numerical models. The blast curves are labelled by apparent flame speed based on the Mach number M_f of the flame front. The accuracy of the model is however limited by the ability of the user to select an appropriate curve for a particular plant geometry. The BST model was initially developed for external VCEs. Nevertheless, it can also be implemented for the calculation of confined explosions through several recommendations on the flame speed selection (see Figure 82). In this work, this model will be applied for confined VCE.

Experimental and numerical studies have shown that the degree of enclosure confinement and congestion, together with the fuel reactivity, may lead to a deflagration-to-detonation transition (DDT) via flame acceleration. In this regard, hydrogen is a highly reactive fuel, and the degree of congestion within the container process unit displayed in Section 26.2 can be deemed as mid-to-high, due to the presence of PEM stacks and balance-of-stack. According to the recommendations by Pierorazio et al. [18] displayed in Figure 82, a DDT is highly likely to occur under the current HPP geometry.

This study considers the upper-bound volume from Section 26.2 to perform the explosion calculations at stoichiometric conditions. Under this assumption, and assuming that the empty free volume of the container process and gas process units is identical, the obtained results for confined VCE can be likewise used for unconfined VCE. In any case, the foreseen hydrogen mass within the container at stoichiometric conditions accounts for 2.48 kg. The calculations in this study assume that the entire congested volume is filled with a stoichiometric mixture of air and hydrogen.

Figure 6.43. BST positive overpressure vs. distance for various flame speeds.

Figure 6.44. BST positive impulse vs. distance for various flame speeds.

Figure 81: BST positive overpressure and impulse vs. distances [34]

The range of scaled distance for the impulse is low compared to that of the scaled overpressure. Therefore, the scaled impulse has limited values in the calculations presented in the report. The same scaling variables applied in Baker-Strehlow apply to BST model.

In order to assess the blast load impact of deflagrations and detonations (after a DDT), the study covers the whole range of flame speeds shown in Figure 82. The assumed reference velocities to distinguish between deflagration and detonation are as follows: the flame front velocity during a deflagration shows an upper-boundary of 500 m/s, whereas during a detonation the flame front may reach up to 2000 m/s [18]. Based on these parameters, 462 m/s is considered the boundary between a fast deflagration and a detonation from the charts in Figure 81. This approach will allow to compare results against TNT-Equivalency model, which is meant for detonations.

Table 6.13. BST flame speed correlations (flame speed Mach no. M_f)
 (Pierorazio et al. 2004)

Confinement	Reactivity	Congestion		
		High	Medium	Low
2-D	High	DDT	DDT	0.59
	Medium	1.6	0.66	0.47
	Low	0.66	0.47	0.079
2.5-D	High	DDT	DDT	0.47
	Medium	1.0	0.55	0.29
	Low	0.50	0.35	0.053
3-D	High	DDT	DDT	0.36
	Medium	0.50	0.44	0.11
	Low	0.34	0.23	0.026

Figure 82: BST flame speed correlations [34]

28.1.2 TNT-Equivalency Model

The TNT-Equivalency model is one of the most widely used VCE blast load prediction models for military and civil applications due to its easy implementation. The model was initially foreseen for spherical blast loads (free-air burst), however in the meantime it has been extended to hemispherical blast loads (surface burst). The underlying mechanism is as follows: the TNT-Equivalency relates the explosive energy of the “effective charge weight” of the vapour cloud to that of an equivalent weight of TNT according to the following expression [18]:

$$W_{TNT} = \frac{\alpha W_f Q_f}{Q_{TNT}}$$

Where W_f is the mass of fuel involved (kg), Q_f is the heat of combustion of hydrogen (J/kg), Q_{TNT} is the TNT heat of detonation (J/kg), and α is the TNT equivalency (-). The latter can be regarded as a conversion factor by which the available heat of combustion (chemical energy) can be converted into blast (mechanical) energy. At atmospheric conditions, the theoretical maximum thermodynamic efficiency for conversion of chemical energy into mechanical energy in gas explosions is approximately 40 % (upper bound). Empirical evidence has proven that the TNT-Equivalency tends to over-predict nearby pressure effects, whereas it under-predicts pressure effects at long range distances.

The most common blast scaling laws are the ones introduced by Hopkinson-Cranz and Sachs [18]. The idea behind both formulations is that during the detonation of two charges of the same explosive that have similar geometry but different weight and are situated at the same scaled distance from a target surface, similar blast waves are produced at the point of interest as long as they are under the same atmospheric conditions [18]. According to Hopkinson-Cranz scaling law, the dimensional scaled distance Z can be formulated as:

$$Z = \frac{R}{W_{TNT}^{1/3}}$$

Where R is the distance from the detonation source to the point of interest (m). The positive phase pressures, impulses, durations, and other parameters of this shock environment for a spherical TNT explosion are provided in Figure 83 versus the scaled distance Z .

The blast calculations in this work based on the TNT-Equivalency model use two different mathematical expressions to account for lower-bound and upper-bound incident and (normal) reflected overpressures. As an upper-bound expression for the calculation of the peak overpressure, this work uses the Mills correlation [18]:

$$\Delta p = \frac{1772}{Z^3} - \frac{114}{Z^2} + \frac{108}{Z}$$

As a lower-bound, this work uses the correlation developed by Graham & Kinney based on chemical type explosions [18]:

$$\Delta p = p_0 \frac{808 \left[1 + \left(\frac{Z}{4.5} \right)^2 \right]}{\left\{ \left[1 + \left(\frac{Z}{0.048} \right)^2 \right] \left[1 + \left(\frac{Z}{0.32} \right)^2 \right] \left[1 + \left(\frac{Z}{1.35} \right)^2 \right] \right\}^{0.5}}$$

The TNT-Equivalency is applied in this report for confined and unconfined VCE. Based on the work of Eichler and Napadensky [18], an explosion efficiency of 40 % is selected for the study. As far as unconfined VCE is concerned, the explosion efficiency ranges from 1 % to 10 %, being 4 % the average value based on empirical observations. These three values are adopted in the study for the calculations.

Figure 83: Parameters for positive phase of shock spherical wave [18]

28.1.3 Bauwens Overpressure Model

The Bauwens accumulation and overpressure model [29] allows to predict and evaluate the peak overpressure that may be reached by the expansion of the burned gas upon ignition at stoichiometric conditions within the container free volume. This model has been implemented in the impact assessment to obtain the peak overpressure inside the containment and assess the severity of damage nearby the ignition point. In this regard, the calculations in this report assume that all of the released hydrogen above the LFL is consumed during the combustion process. The peak overpressure inside the container can be calculated by means of the following expression:

$$\Delta p = p_0 \left[\left(\left(\frac{V_T + V_{H2}}{V_T} \right) \left(\frac{V_T + V_{stoich}(\sigma - 1)}{V_T} \right) \right)^\gamma - 1 \right]$$

Where p_0 is the ambient pressure (Pa), V_T is the total volume of the container (m^3), V_{H2} is the expanded volume of pure hydrogen following the release (m^3), V_{stoich} is the volume of a stoichiometric mixture of the consumed hydrogen (m^3), σ is the expansion ratio of a stoichiometric hydrogen-air mixture (-).

The key parameter in the above expression is the mixture expansion ratio σ , which represents the ratio of densities of reactants and products. Together with the cell size, λ is used as a safety criterion in nuclear safety, mostly to determine flame speed and combustion mode of the vapour cloud within the containment. This work applies this model to the container configuration shown in Section 26.2 and follows the guidance/recommendations from the OECD/NEA report [23]. Two expansion ratios have been selected for the calculations, which comprise 2.9 for slow flame (lean mixture), and 4.42 for fast flame (rich mixture), both determined at ambient conditions.

28.1.4 TNO Shock Wave Model by Wiekema

The TNO Shock Wave model by Wiekema (shortly Wiekema model) is a composite model for deflagration and detonation of vapor clouds and was developed in 1980 [19] (Sec. 17.28.24). Wiekema derived the deflagration model from a correlation between the temperature-time profile of a shock wave and the energy of the corresponding explosion. In this model, the cloud is assumed to be a hemisphere of unburned gas with a specific volume. The energy of explosion is derived from this volume. Then a characteristic length is specified which leads to the dimensionless distance, overpressure and duration of overpressure as shown in Figure 84. A correlation is given between the dimensionless distance and the dimensionless pressure (see eq. 17.28.62b in Figure 84). The parameter A depends on an assumed flame speed as shown in Figure 84. The detonation model is based on analyses done in 1966, the correlations are shown also in Figure 84. In the following, four ‘explosion classes’ are used to describe the type of explosion:

- Explosion class 1: Deflagration with flame speed of 40 m/s
- Explosion class 2: Deflagration with flame speed of 80 m/s
- Explosion class 3: Deflagration with flame speed of 160 m/s
- Explosion class 4: Detonation

where E_c is the energy of combustion per unit volume (J/m^3) and R_0 is the radius of the initial cloud (m).

A characteristic explosion length L is defined as

$$L = \left(\frac{E_0}{P_0}\right)^{1/2} \quad [17.28.56a]$$

$$= \left(\frac{2}{3}\pi R_0^3 \frac{E_c}{\rho_0}\right)^{1/3} \quad [17.28.56b]$$

where L is the characteristic length (m), and a parameter λ as

$$\lambda = \frac{L}{t_b} \quad [17.28.57]$$

where t_b is the time (s) at which the expansion process is incomplete. A reduced distance \bar{R} , reduced overpressure \bar{P} , reduced time \bar{t} and reduced duration time \bar{T} are then defined as follows :

$$\bar{R} = \frac{R}{L} \quad [17.28.58]$$

$$\bar{P} = \frac{p - p_0}{p_0} \quad [17.28.59]$$

$$\bar{t} = \frac{t}{t_b} \quad [17.28.60]$$

$$\frac{\bar{T}}{L} = \frac{t_+ c_0}{L} \quad [17.28.61]$$

where c_0 is the local velocity of sound (m/s), R is the distance (m) and t_+ is the duration time (s).

The reduced overpressure is taken as inversely proportional to the reduced distance:

$$\bar{P} = \frac{A}{\bar{R}} \quad [17.28.62a]$$

$$= \frac{AL}{R} \quad [17.28.62b]$$

Figure 84: System of equations used in the Wiekema model [18] (Sec. 17.28.24)

The dimensionless overpressure and dimensionless duration of the overpressure phase can be determined with the model. The dimensionless parameters can be transformed to the absolute overpressure p and the duration of overpressure t . From these both output parameters, the impulse i of the positive phase of the shock wave can be determined with the equation $i = 0.5 \cdot p \cdot t$ [18].

28.1.5 Reflected Overpressure Model

The peak reflected overpressure occurs if a blast wave hits a flat surface of a structure in normal direction [18] (Sec. 17.25.1). This quantity is relevant for the forces acting on the structure. The reflected pressure p_r can be determined with $p_r = 2p + (\gamma + 1) \cdot q$ where p is the overpressure, $\gamma = 1.4$ is the ratio of specific heats and $q = \frac{p^2}{2\gamma p_{ambient} + (\gamma - 1)p}$ is the dynamic pressure. There are more complex models available to determine the reflective overpressure, e.g., considering the angle of the impact, but the model presented here is the most conservative.

$$\bar{T} = \frac{R_1}{L} \left(\frac{c_0}{\bar{v}_n} - 1\right) + \frac{3}{7} A \ln\left(\frac{1 + 7R/3AL}{1 + 7R_1/3AL}\right), \quad R > R_1 \quad [17.28.67a]$$

The method involves selecting an assumed flame speed. The set of flame speeds \bar{v}_n quoted are 40, 80 and 160 m/s, and the corresponding values of the parameter A are 2×10^{-2} , 6×10^{-2} and 15×10^{-2} , respectively.

The model just described is applicable to a deflagration. For the case of detonation in a vapour cloud Wiekema utilizes results obtained by Kogarko, Adushkin and Lyamin (1966), from which he obtains the following relations for the reduced overpressure and reduced duration time:

$$\bar{P} = 0.518\bar{R}^{-1.7}, \quad 0.29 < \bar{R} < 1.088 \quad [17.28.68a]$$

$$= 0.2177\bar{R}^{-1}, \quad \bar{R} > 1.088 \quad [17.28.68b]$$

$$\bar{T} = 0.1853\bar{R}^{1/2}, \quad 0.36 < \bar{R} < 12.6 \quad [17.28.69a]$$

$$= 0.20 + 0.0933 \ln(1 + 10.7\bar{R}), \quad \bar{R} > 12.6 \quad [17.28.69b]$$

Since in the detonation work no results are given for \bar{T} for $\bar{R} > 12.6$, Equation 17.28.69b is based on the deflagration work.

28.2 Confined Hydrogen Explosion

28.2.1 Calculation of release rates and concentration build-up

The confined hydrogen release assumes steady leak flow rates. Nevertheless, due to the large pressure differential across the leak cross-section area, critical flow is expected at the very beginning of the transient calculation. Therefore, the leak mass flow rates have been modelled through two different mathematical expressions, which are shown below [18]:

$$\dot{m}_{choked} = C_D A P_1 \sqrt{\frac{\gamma g_c M}{R_g T_1} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1}\right)^{(\gamma+1)/(\gamma-1)}}$$

$$\dot{m}_{steady} = C_D A P_1 \sqrt{\frac{2 g_c M}{R_g T_1} \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} \left[\left(\frac{P_2}{P_1}\right)^{2/\gamma} - \left(\frac{P_2}{P_1}\right)^{(\gamma-1)/\gamma} \right]}$$

Where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate (kg/s), C_D is the discharge coefficient (-), A is the area of the leak (m²), P_1 is the pressure upstream the leak (Pa), P_2 is the pressure downstream the leak (Pa), γ is the heat capacity ratio (-), g_c is the gravitational constant (N.s²/kg.m), M is the molecular weight of the gas (kg/mol), R_g is the ideal gas constant (J/mol.K), and T_1 is the initial upstream temperature of the gas (°K). A $C_D = 0.6$ is adopted for circular holes and $\gamma = 1.4$ for diatomic gases. The assumption of steady leak flow rate is realistic up to medium leak size due to slow system depressurization, while conservative for the full-bore rupture since it does not account for the flow rate decay with depressurization.

The release rates for each leak size are gathered in Table 54 and depicted in Figure 85. The latter includes timings to reach the LFL, lower explosive limit (LEL), and stoichiometric concentration within the container. The overpressure calculations presented in this section assume delayed ignition of the vapor cloud under stoichiometric conditions (29.5 vol.%). This assumption is deemed as conservative in terms of available hydrogen masses for combustion, which account for 1.57 kg for the Cont-1 configuration (lower-bound), and 2.48 kg for the Cont-2 configuration (upper-bound). The evolution of the volumetric concentration fraction inside the two container configurations is depicted in Figure 86. The study assumes gas dispersion and uniform mixture inside the container.

Uniform hydrogen-air mixture is assumed to be driven by the high turbulence within the container enclosure created by the hydrogen jet, together with the degree of obstruction created by the PEM stacks and the balance of stack. Upon ignition, the combustion mode is assumed to start as a slow deflagration. However, flame speed acceleration is expected to occur with subsequent DDT.

The trends displayed in Figure 86 take into account the available volume for both container configurations and neglect the local build-up of rich mixture within the container. Given the level of obstruction and depending on the leak orientation, local hydrogen-air mixture build-up seems to be likely to occur. Such behavior may lead to the development of a hydrogen plume exceeding the LFL, which may ignite earlier than the times gathered in Table 54. With increasing time and delayed ignition, the vapor cloud will tend to accumulate in the ceiling, thereby giving rise to the development of a localized rich mixture due to the high buoyancy of hydrogen.

The results gathered in Table 54 show late times to reach the LFL under the 1 % break scenario, which given the various types of detectors and equipment redundancies allow to exclude a hydrogen VCE. The 10 % break would reach stoichiometric conditions at 270 s and 426 s for the lower-bound and upper-bound container volumes, respectively. This break size is assumed the base case for the

presented study. The calculations are performed at fixed ambient conditions within the container. However, the release of gaseous hydrogen at 35 bar and 80 °C may alter the LFL due to the continuous temperature and pressure increase within the enclosure. The ventilation system must be able to provide an air exchange rate of 12 to cope with the collector full-bore rupture.

Figure 85: Evolution of leak flow rates within the container

Figure 86: Volumetric hydrogen fraction within the container

Table 54: Hydrogen concentration and safety limits within container

Leak size (-)	Release rate (kg/s)	Container volume	Hydrogen concentration		
			LFL	LEL	Stoich.
0.01	$5.83 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Cont-1	> 1 h	-	-
		Cont-2	> 1 h	-	-

0.10	$5.83 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Cont-1	37 s	138 s	270 s
		Cont-2	58 s	217 s	426 s
1.00	$5.11 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Cont-1	5 s	16 s	21 s
		Cont-2	7 s	25 s	49 s

28.2.2 Calculation of blast loading and safety distances

The Bauwens model is applied first to obtain the peak overpressure inside the process container unit by the resulting overpressure from the hydrogen expansion. Results for slow deflagration account for $\Delta p = 5.4 \cdot 10^2$ kPa, whereas $\Delta p = 1.05 \cdot 10^3$ kPa is obtained for a detonation. Those results correspond to the free volume in the stack compartment (Cont-1) with uniform hydrogen-air mixture inside the enclosure. Based on those results, catastrophic failure of the container is expected. These results will vary when applying different mixture expansion ratios. Therefore, a further investigation of the parameters σ and λ applied to our container geometry and release scenario is highly advised.

In order to obtain the normal reflected peak overpressures with the TNT-Equivalency for spherical charge detonations, the correlations of Mills and Kinney are applied as an upper- and lower-bound, respectively. These correlations are widely used in the literature and verified against experimental data. In addition, in order to account for the container volume uncertainties, two different container volumes (therefore vapour cloud hydrogen masses) are imposed in the calculations. This approach allows to obtain the most conservative value of the peak overpressure against distance, to further evaluate the consequences over the NPP structures and components. The (reflected) peak overpressure results versus distances are depicted in Figure 87.

According to the data sheets provided by the Ukrainian State Operator JSC Energoatom, the buildings and structures of Rivne NPP are able to withstand an approximate airborne shock wave with a frontal compression pressure of around 10 kPa. From a safety perspective, more interesting than peak overpressures at the ignition point and subsequent decay with distance, are the approximate distances needed to comply with the safety limit of 10 kPa provided by the NPP. Those are gathered in Table 55, together with the results obtained with the BST model, which will be described later on in this section. The results summarized in Table 55, together with a look up on the relative distances of the NPP structures with respect to the proposed HPP location in the protected area of Rivne NPP will answer the question of whether is possible to integrate the cogeneration facility onsite, and what measures are to be taken to comply with acceptance criteria and safety regulations.

Figure 87: TNT-Equivalency results for confined VCE

The most conservative value obtained with the TNT-Equivalency model by means of the Mills correlation and the upper-bound container volume (102 m^3), points out to a required distance of 65 m to comply with acceptance criterion of 10 kPa, whereas if the overpressure safety limit is halved in order to account for further uncertainties in the calculations, the required distance would increase up to 130 m. Needless to say, that these results are conservative in terms of the hydrogen mass in the vapour cloud available for explosion, and do not take into account the amount of the blast energy absorbed by the container walls and surrounding structures during the shock wave propagation. Those two factors will significantly reduce the required distance to comply with the NPP design safety limits.

Table 55: Minimum separation distances for the confined VCE scenario

Model	Correlation	Volume (m^3)	Peak overpressure	
			5 kPa	10 kPa
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	65	110 m	57 m
		102	130 m	65 m
	Kinney	65	87 m	47 m
		102	102 m	53 m
BST	M = 0.35	102	55 m	28 m
	M = 1.00	102	Out of range	80 m

Besides the TNT-Equivalency, in this work the BST model is implemented to evaluate peak overpressure based on several flame front Mach numbers. In this regard, the calculations have considered all flame speeds from the original BST curves displayed in Figure 81. The peak overpressure against distance is plotted in Figure 88, and the Mach numbers corresponding to deflagrations are labelled as black, whereas those corresponding to deflagrations are labelled in blue.

As it can be observed from Figure 88, all BST curves with Mach number above 0.35, which can be regarded as a slow deflagration (115.5 m/s), tend to converge at a distance of 20 m from the ignition point. Actually, overpressure shows small differences between the curves with increasing distances

(see Figure 81). However, for practical purposes this approach has been adopted in the presented calculations. The hydrogen mass available for combustion corresponds to 2.48 kg (upper-bound). The BST overpressure results versus distance are limited to 100 m by the BST curves displayed in Figure 88. The results show that for a slow deflagration, a distance of 28 m would be required to comply with the 10 kPa safety limit, whereas for fast deflagrations and detonations a distance of 80 m would be required to comply with such value.

Figure 88: BST results for confined and unconfined VCE

The minimum separation distances necessary to comply with the reference limit of 10 kPa account for 65 m according to the TNT-Equivalency, whereas 80 m would be required based on the BST model. Those results are obtained with conservative hydrogen masses available for explosion and neglecting interaction of the blast wave with surrounding HPP structures. A comparison between both models shows higher peak overpressure at the point of ignition with the TNT-Equivalency, whereas pressure decreases faster with distance than with the BST model.

The results from Figure 87 and Figure 88 show a peak overpressure one order of magnitude higher with the TNT-Equivalency at the source of explosion. The main reason behind these observed differences is the very nature of both models, TNT-Equivalence foreseen for detonations, whereas BST foreseen for deflagrations. As far as the positive impulse is concerned, the incident impulse computed by means of Kinney and Graham at 47 m accounts for $3.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kPa s, whereas at 87 m it accounts for $1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kPa s. The impulse at 80 m computed with the BST model accounts for $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kPa s, one order of magnitude higher than TNT-Equivalency.

All applied models in this section show catastrophic failure of the container upon ignition of the hydrogen vapour cloud. At nearby distances, the TNT-Equivalency results are expected to overestimate the overpressure effects, and the BST and Bauwens are assumed to provide more realistic values. In fact, the results with Bauwens show agreement with those depicted in Figure 88 for slow deflagration and detonation.

To conclude this section, it is important to note that with the adopted conservative conditions in terms of available hydrogen masses and combustion at stoichiometric conditions, as well as neglecting the amount of energy loss by the interaction of the pressure/shock wave with the HPP surroundings, the hydrogen explosion would not violate acceptance criterion in the nearby NPP structure, which are the

standby diesel generators at a distance of 95 m (45 m + 50 m). At the explosion source, catastrophic failure is expected according to the calculation results.

28.3 Unconfined Hydrogen Explosion

The unconfined VCE is assumed to take place in the gas processing area located above the container process unit. For the calculation of peak overpressures and positive impulses, the same geometry is assumed as in the container (realistic assumption), however the container volume for the calculation of the stoichiometric mass of hydrogen at combustion neglects all balance-of-plant located there. In other words, the available hydrogen volume at explosion accounts for 2.48 kg (upper-bound), without taking into account the yield factor. In this section, the TNT-Equivalency and Wiekema models are implemented to determine the peak overpressure against distances for various conditions.

Following the guidelines provided in [18], the TNT-Equivalency calculations consider three different yield factors (lower-bound, average, and upper-bound). The obtained results are plotted in Figure 89 by means of the Mills and Kinney correlations, which are described in Section 28.2.2. The minimal safe distances for Rivne NPP are gathered in Table 56. The most conservative results show that a minimum separation distance of 48 m and 82 m would be required to comply with the safety limits of 10 kPa and 5 kPa, respectively. The differences with respect to the results obtained in the confined VCE arise from the explosion yield. The obtained results firstly overestimate the available mass of hydrogen available for combustion, and secondly, they do not take into account effects of atmospheric dispersion, which would significantly reduce the risk of a delayed ignition.

Figure 89: TNT-Equivalency results for unconfined VCE

The results obtained with the Wiekema model for a fast deflagration and a detonation are depicted in Figure 90. Minimum separation distances required to comply with safety limits are gathered in Table 56. The most conservative results for a hydrogen detonation point out to minimum separation distances of 40 m and 60 m to comply with the safety limits of 10 kPa and 5 kPa, respectively. The same boundary conditions mentioned in the paragraph before applying to the Wiekema calculations.

Table 56: Summary of minimum separation distances for the unconfined VCE

Model	Correlation	Yield	5 kPa	10 kPa
TNT-Equivalency	Mills	$\alpha = 0.01$	38 m	17 m
		$\alpha = 0.04$	60 m	30 m
		$\alpha = 0.10$	82 m	48 m
	Kinney	$\alpha = 0.01$	30 m	16 m
		$\alpha = 0.04$	47 m	25 m
		$\alpha = 0.10$	65 m	33 m
Wiekema	Deflagration	-	62 m	31 m
	Detonation	-	60 m	40 m

The positive impulse obtained with Kinney at 33 m and 65 m account for $3.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kPa.s and $1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kPa.s, respectively. The duration of the blast load according to Wiekema accounts for $4.58 \cdot 10^{-2}$ s. The observed differences with respect to the confined VCE, which show lower values in the current section, are directly related to the yield factor.

Figure 90: Wiekema results for unconfined VCE

29 Pressure Vessel Burst and Projectile Calculation

29.1 Semi-Empirical Model Description

29.1.1 Liberated energy of a pressure vessel burst

The mechanical energy of the physical explosion of a non-ideal gas can be obtained combining Brode's expression [18], and the Abel-Noble equation of state for real gases. This approach is meant to improve predictive capability at high-storage pressures by means of the following expression:

$$\Delta E_m = \frac{(p_g - p_s)(V - mb)}{\gamma - 1}$$

Where p_g is the (absolute) pressure in the tank (Pa), p_s is the surrounding pressure (Pa), $b = 7.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (m^3/kg), V is the tank volume (m^3), and m is the gas mass (kg). The equivalent charge weight of TNT can be calculated according to the following expression:

$$W_{TNT} = \frac{\Delta E_m}{Q_{TNT}}$$

29.1.2 Kinetic energy model to predict initial fragment velocity

The initial velocity of a fragment can be calculated by using the following equation [18]:

$$v_i = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot A_{ke} \cdot E_{av}}{M_v}}$$

Where A_{ke} is the fraction of the liberated energy that goes into kinetic energy of the fragments (-), E_{av} is the liberated energy (J), and M_v is the total mass of empty vessel (kg).

The flying range can be calculated according to the following expression:

$$R = 2 \cdot \frac{v_i^2}{g} \cdot \cos(\alpha) \cdot \sin(\alpha)$$

Where α is the angle of departure ($^\circ$), and g is the gravity acceleration constant (m/s^2).

29.1.3 Moore's empirical formula for the initial fragment velocity

The Moore's model is described in the TNO Yellow Book [19]. This model considers fragment mass and shape, together with dynamic forces acting over the flying fragment. The model consists of several equations for

- the initial velocity of fragments in Figure 91, and
- the maximal range of fragments derived from the scaled initial velocity in Figure 92.

This initial velocity can be calculated by using of the following equation:

$$v_i = 1.092 \left[\frac{E_{av} A_M}{M_v} \right]^{0.5} \quad (\text{m/s}) \quad (7.18)$$

where for spherical vessels $A_M = \frac{1}{1 + 3M_c/5M_v}$ (-) (7.19)

and for cylindrical vessels $A_M = \frac{1}{1 + M_c/2M_v}$ (-) (7.20)

Figure 91. Moore's empirical formula for the initial velocity of fragments taken from [19]

$$\bar{R}_f = \frac{\rho_a C_D A_D R_f}{M_f} \quad (-) \quad (7.21)$$

$$\bar{v}_i = \frac{\rho_a C_D A_D v_i^2}{M_f g} \quad (-) \quad (7.22)$$

where

- \bar{R}_f = scaled maximal range [-]
- R_f = maximal range [m]
- \bar{v}_i = scaled initial velocity [-]
- v_i = initial velocity [m/s]
- ρ_a = density of ambient atmosphere [kg/m³]
- C_D = drag coefficient [-]
- C_L = lift coefficient [-]
- A_D = exposed area in plane perpendicular to trajectory [m²]
- A_L = exposed area in plane parallel to trajectory [m²]
- g = gravitational acceleration [m/s²]
- M_f = mass of fragment [kg]

Figure 7.12 Scaled curves for fragment range predictions. ----: solution for no wind resistance, $R_f = v_i^2/g$

Figure 92: Scaled maximal range of fragments taken from [19]

29.1.4 Gel'fand's model to estimate initial fragment velocity

The scaled overpressure is calculated according to [19]:

$$\bar{P}_1 = (p_1 - p_a) V_g / (M_v a_1^2)$$

Where p_1 is the absolute pressure at failure (Pa), p_a is the ambient pressure (Pa), V_g is the volume of gas-filled part of the vessel (m³), M_v is the mass of the vessel (kg), and a_1 is the speed of sound in gas at failure (m/s). Further information about the model can be found in [19]. By estimating \bar{P}_1 (abscissa)

and going into the chart displayed in Figure 93, one can obtain v_i/a_i (ordinate). The range of the flying fragments can be estimated from the expression shown in Section 29.1.1.

Figure 93: Fragment velocity versus scaled pressure for a cylinder [40]

29.2 Pressure Vessel Burst

The hazard event is an external fire in the electrolyser facility or at the high-pressure storage area that leads to a vessel overpressure, assuming failure of the available pressure-relief devices. This approach does not need specific information about the pressure vessels, but only about the energy inside. Calculation results for single pressure vessel burst are gathered in Table 57. The table summarizes results for explosions in the buffer tank and Vessel-1 configuration. A safety factor of 1.25 is applied over the design vessel pressure (p_g) to assume the pressure increase over the maximum allowable working pressure and to obtain justified conservative values. This safety factor accounts for the set-point of the relief-safety valve plus the factor of 1.21 recommended in [19]. An additional factor of 2 is applied in order to account for ground reflection. The safety factor is not applied during the fatal event scenario since all vessels are assumed to burst at once due to e.g., a plane crash.

Based on the results gathered in Table 57, a pressure vessel burst at the buffer tank obtained with the most conservative results (Mills correlation) would not exceed the fragility criterion in the nearest NPP structure. Furthermore, the results applied to a single vessel burst in the high-pressure storage area show that a minimum safe distance of 520 m to the NPP perimeter would be needed to comply with the safety limit of 10 kPa. The obtained results point out the need of mitigation measures deployed on the high-pressure storage area in order to prevent domino effects between storage vessels.

Table 57: Minimal separation distance for single pressure vessels

Configuration	Model	Mass of hydrogen (kg)	Pressure (bar)	5 kPa R (m)	10 kPa R (m)
Buffer tank	Mills	30	35	165	85
	Kinney			130	70
Vessel-1	Mills	1000	350	520	270
	Kinney			420	220

The results gathered in Table 58 correspond to a fatal event in the high-pressure storage area, which

leads to the release of all the energy contained in the storage vessels. With this aim, two different storage amounts of compressed gaseous hydrogen are considered in the calculations. The most conservative results for the lower-tier storage capacity show a necessary distance of 830 m of the high-pressure storage area to the NPP perimeter to comply with the safety limit of 10 kPa, whereas a storage facility with a capacity of 15 tonnes would require a minimum safe distance of 1190 m to comply with such safety limit. An advantage of the high-pressure storage facility is that it can be located according to the safety requirements due to the high degree of freedom.

Table 58: Minimum separation distance for events in the high-pressure area

Configuration	Model	Mass of hydrogen (kg)	5 kPa R (m)	10 kPa R (m)
Vessel-1	Mills	5000	820	420
	Kinney		660	350
Vessel-1	Mills	15000	1180	600
	Kinney		950	500

29.3 Projectile Calculation

According to IAEA SSG-79 [16], explosions are very likely to create secondary hazards, among them projectiles, and those should be considered in the external hazard impact assessment. A pressure vessel burst may lead to fragmentation and projectile ejection. The range of the flying fragments is strongly determined by the angle of departure, mass, and shape of the fragment. The latter are mostly affected by dynamic forces acting upon the fragment during the flight (drag and lift, gravity).

For the missile impact assessment, detailed information about the pressure vessel is needed (e.g., composition, dimensions, mass, etc.). However, as already stated in the report, no specific information about the facilities other than layout distances has been used to perform the safety calculations so far. Therefore, calculations and assumptions are required to estimate a reasonable vessel geometry based on the foreseen hydrogen storage capacity of 30 kg at 35 bars (relative pressure).

The calculations presented in this section apply to the buffer tank exclusively, to assess load impact hazard to nearby NPP structures. The pressure vessel is based on cylindrical shape with hemispherical end caps and made from steel of classification 25CrMo4. Based on the storage pressure of 35 bar and the capacity of 30 kg, and assuming a storage temperature of approximately 25 °C after the purification and drying unit in the electrolyser system, the volume required by the compressed hydrogen accounts for 10.5 m³. Following the guidelines provided by ASME’s Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section VIII Division 1, as well as the DIN EN 13445 standards for pressure vessels, an estimated outer diameter of 1.5 m has been set as initial condition, to comply with a recommended length-to-diameter ratio of approximately 4.34. The main vessel features are gathered in Table 59.

Table 59: Buffer tank main parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
External diameter	D_e	<i>m</i>	1.50
Overall length	L	<i>m</i>	6.50
Length-to-diameter	L/D	–	4.34
Wall thickness	e	<i>mm</i>	5.27
Total mass	M_T	<i>kg</i>	1250

The vessel wall thickness has been obtained by applying the “kesselformel” Equation from DIN EN 13445-3 applied to cylindrical vessels, which accounts for 5.27 mm. The applied equation is:

$$e = \frac{P \cdot D_e}{2 \cdot f \cdot z + P}$$

Where e is the wall thickness (m), P is the vessel design pressure (Pa), D_e is the vessel outer diameter (m), f is the maximum allowable stress for the material (Pa), and z can be defined as the welding joint efficiency (-). Based on the material properties for the steel 25CrMo4, which can be found in DIN EN 13445-2 and by the steel manufacturer Thyssenkrupp, the yield strength f corresponds to 600 MPa, whereas a z factor of 0.85 is used as recommended by the ASME standard.

The fragmentation patterns of cylindrical vessels have been extensively investigated numerically and experimentally and reported recently in several journal publications [30] [31], as well as in process safety handbooks [18, 19]. In particular, the work of [31] provides a comprehensive identification of fragmentation patterns based on the investigation of numerous industrial accidents. Accordingly, the estimated number of fragments after a cylindrical pressure burst due to overpressure, falls in between two to three pieces. In this study, calculations are performed for these two fragmentation patterns. Figure 94 provides the patterns used in the work of [30] for a cylindrical pressure vessel, together with calculated probabilities of fragmentation pattern.

Projectiles and missiles are identified as secondary hazards after an explosion in the IAEA report SSG-79 “Hazards associated with human induced external events in site evaluation for nuclear installations” [16]. To characterize the mechanical load upon impact, relevant source data such as nature of projectile or missile (e.g., mass, initial velocity, and trajectory) are to be considered, together with assumptions regarding maximum credible projectile or missile, and frequency of release.

To fulfill these recommendations, three different models (see Section 29.1) have been applied in this section to generate enough data and to be able to assess uncertainties arising from the models in terms of fragment flying range. A safety factor of 1.25 has been applied to the vessel design pressure upon burst, in order to account for the effects of overpressure by the assumed external fire and failure of the pressure-relief devices (safety valve and burst disc).

Table 2

Comparison of the fragmentation pattern of vessel 27V-16 and the expected fragmentation patterns as proposed by [Gubinelli and Cozzani \(2009a\)](#). $P_{p,i}$ conditional probability of the i -th fragmentation pattern in case of physical explosion. Refer to [Gubinelli and Cozzani \(2009a, 2009b\)](#) for the complete list of ID codes for reference patterns and fragment shapes.

ID	Fragmentation pattern	Description	$P_{p,i}$	Expected fragment shape
CV2		The fracture, likely to start in the axial direction, may turn in the circumferential direction due to stress field changes (bending or stress intensification near connections), or to defects. If the axial crack propagates on the tube-end and stops, a flattened tube-end may be generated.	0.67	<i>Configuration A</i> ($P_{fs} = 0.28$): 2 tube-ends (PTE2) or <i>Configuration B</i> ($P_{fs} = 0.72$): 1 tube-end (PTE2), 1 flattened plate (PL)
CV3		Similar to CV2. Credible if the fracture starts on a pipe connection or if one of the two tube ends impacts on a near object at the moment of the projection.	0.08	1 tube-end (PTE2), 2 parts of tube-end (PTE2 & PTE1)
CV4		Similar to CV2. Credible if the fracture starts on a pipe connection or if one of the two tube ends impact on a near object at the moment of the projection. The axial fractures on the tube-end could arrest originating flattened tube-ends.	0.13	1 tube-end (PTE2), 2 parts of tube-end (PTE1) 1 plate (PL)
CV7		An axial crack may propagate in circumferential direction in zones where a stress concentration (thickness change, supports, pipe connections), defects or weldings are present. It is highly probable that the circumferential cracks are located at the ends. The shell fragment is generally flattened.	0.08	2 tube-ends (PTE2), 1 flattened shell (PL)
CV11		Similar to CV7. The axial fracture on the tube-end may arrest originating a flattened tube-end.	0.04	1 tube-end (PTE2), 2 parts of tube-end (PTE2 & PTE1) 1 flattened shell (PL)
Case-study		The bottom of the 27V-16 tank was cut off just above the welding stringcourse. The cylindrical shell (item 1) was opened along the full length of the generatrix of the cylinder. The upper cover was cut in two halves (item 4 and 3) along the welding stringcourse. The manhole was cut in two halves (main one item 19). (Adapted from: Piccini and Demichela (2006))	–	1 tube-end (PTE2), 2 parts of tube-end (PTE2 & PTE1) 1 flattened shell (PL) 1 manhole cover (PL)

Figure 94: Cylindrical vessel fragmentation patterns based on the work of [30]

The models applied to determine the fragment initial velocity and travel range are: (a) Kinetic energy method, (b) Gel'fand's method, and (c) Moore's method. Further information about these methods is gathered in Section 29.1. The first step in the calculations here presented is determining the fragmentation pattern of the pressure vessel. This section considers two different fragmentation patterns, with the corresponding masses:

3. Two different pieces: tube end (336 kg) plus flattened plate (914 kg).
4. Three pieces: two end caps (143.5 kg) plus the cylindrical plate (963 kg).

An approach to estimate the fragment mass and shape is depicted in Figure 95. This work has followed the recommendations of [30] [31] to estimate fragment shape and masses upon pressure vessel burst.

Table 7.6 Fragment mass and shape, pragmatic approach

Type of vessel	Fragment mass M_f	Fragment shape
Sphere, 2 fragments	$M_v/2$	hemisphere
Sphere, many fragments	M_v/n_f	plates
Cylinder, 2 equal pieces	$M_v/2$	half of tank
Cylinder, 2 unequal pieces	1 piece: M_{cap} other piece: $M_v - M_{cap}$	cap/hemisphere tank with one cap missing
Cylinder, 3 unequal pieces	2 pieces: M_{cap} other: $(M_v - 2M_{cap})$	cap/hemisphere plate
Cylinder, many pieces	2 pieces: M_{cap} rest: $(M_v - 2M_{cap})/(n_f - 2)$	cap/hemisphere strip

Figure 95: Fragment mass and shape taken from [19]

The results obtained with the kinetic energy model are summarized in Table 60. The results provide the required fragment departure angle to reach any of the nearby NPP structures according to the data provided by Rivne NPP. The results are expressed in terms of the fraction of released energy that goes into kinetic energy of the fragments. In the literature, recommendation for the percentage of energy to fragments ranges from 5 % to 20 % [19]. This model does not account for fragment mass or shape, but it only provides the flying range for an average fragment generated upon vessel burst. Therefore, it neglects important dynamic effects such as drag and lift and is expected to overestimate the fragment flying range.

Table 60: Required fragment departure angle to reach the buildings

Nearest NPP structures	Explosion energy to fragments			
	5 %	10 %	20 %	40 %
Initial velocities	95 m/s	134 m/s	190 m/s	268 m/s
Standby DGs	3°	1.5°	> 0.5°	> 0.5°
Cooling Tower	6°	3°	1.5°	1°
Turbine Building	16.5°	8°	4°	2°
Open Switchgear	-	29°	12.5°	6°

The Interface-Questionnaire for NPHyCo provided by JSC Energoatom regarding Rivne NPP provides neither acceptance criteria nor design requirements for resistance of structures and buildings against projectiles. Therefore, this section evaluates hazard assessment based exclusively on distances of the flying fragments after the explosion. According to IAEA SRS-87 "Safety aspects of nuclear power plants in human induced external events: assessment of structures" [32], missiles or projectiles causing mechanical impacts are broadly classified into two categories: (i) hard missiles; and (ii) soft missiles. The categorization is based on the missile's deformability with respect to the deformability of the impacted object. The fragments originated from the pressure burst can be assumed as soft missiles when impacting continuous reinforced concrete walls, whereas it may be assumed as hard missiles when impacting other NPP structures such as the standby diesel generators. Structural analysis based on specific data of the NPP is advised to be performed as a follow-up of these analyses.

The results from Table 60 show acceptable values for the lowest departure angle, calculated for the energy fraction transferred to the fragments up to 0.2. On the other hand, under the maximum departure angle of 45°, the flying ranges would exhibit significantly high values, whose flying range would exceed the standoff distance to critical NPP structures and buildings. As already mentioned, these results overpredict fragment’s flying range by neglecting dynamic forces (e.g., drag). Nevertheless, they provide valuable information regarding the role of the departure angle upon vessel burst. This stresses the need to develop mitigation measures to control the mechanical failure of the vessel, and therefore keep the departure angle as low as possible.

Besides the simplified kinetic energy model, this section applies the semi-empirical Moore model, which accounts for fragment mass and shape. The results are gathered in Table 61. They provide the initial fragment velocity and maximum flying range based on the fraction of released energy transferred to kinetic energy of the fragments.

Table 61: Fragment velocity and maximum range with Moore’s model

Fragment shape	Explosion energy to fragments			
	20%		10%	
	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)	Velocity (m/s)	Range (m)
Hemispherical cap (tumbling)	145	431	103	323
Hemispherical cap (no tumbling)	145	564	103	324
Cylinder body (edge on)	145	326	103	250

The fragment masses are 143 kg for the hemispherical caps and 963 kg for the cylinder body. The dynamic force coefficients in the calculations are based on those from Figure 96. As observed from Table 61, the initial velocity of the fragments is the same regardless of the fragment shape and mass. It is simply calculated according to the released energy after the pressure vessel burst and a geometric factor relation based on the stored mass of hydrogen and the total mass of the empty vessel. The results obtained with this method are significantly lower than those obtained with the simplified kinetic energy model.

Based on the results summarized in Table 61, the flying fragments upon the most conservative calculations would reach the standby diesel generators, cooling towers, as well as turbine building. The structural response of those buildings and structures needs to be analysed in detail once more specific information about the NPP is available. Nevertheless, as mentioned already, flying fragments are deemed as soft missiles due to the high deformability upon impact. The load impact and structural response of the NPP structure will much depend on the seismic category of them.

Table 7.8 Drag and lift of fragments

Shape	$C_D A_D$	$C_L A_L / C_D A_D$
Plate (tumbling)	$0.585 \times A_{\text{plate}}$	0
Plate (no tumbling, face on)	$1.17 \times A_{\text{plate}}$	0
Plate (no tumbling, edge on)	$0.1 \times A_{\text{plate}}$	0 to 10 ¹⁾
Hemisphere (tumbling)	$0.615 \times \pi/4 \times d_v^2$	0
Hemisphere (no tumbling)	$0.47 \times \pi/4 \times d_v^2$	0
Half a tank (rocketing)	$0.47 \times \pi/4 \times d_v^2$	0
Cylinder (edge on)	$1.20 \times d_v \times L_v$	0
Strips (tumbling)	$0.99 \times A_{\text{strip}}$	0

1) The value depends on the plate's angle. Use the value which gives the maximum fragment range, or calculate a number of possible ranges.

Figure 96: Drag and lift of fragments according to [19]

Finally, the Gel'fand's model applied to a cylindrical pressure vessel with a length to diameter ratio of 5, shows an initial velocity of the flying fragments of 89 m/s, with a minimum fragment flying range of 11 m (0°) and a maximal range of 636 m (45°). The maximum range of Gel'fand's shows agreement with that of Moore, and the same explanations provided above can be applied here.

30 Conclusions and Recommendations

This report has presented the main outcomes from the impact assessment of the integration of a hydrogen cogeneration facility into Rivne NPP in Ukraine. The risk of damage at the NPP site by the worst-case scenario at the HPP, which was identified as a hydrogen explosion, was evaluated by means of frequency estimation obtained through HAZID and ETA methodologies, and deterministic safety calculations by means of selected semi-empirical methods from the process safety.

The external hazard impact assessment has identified four different accident scenarios:

1. Confined hydrogen explosion within the electrolyser container
2. Unconfined hydrogen explosion within the gas processing area
3. Physical explosion in the buffer tank and fragment generation
4. Physical explosion in the high-pressure storage area

The highest frequency for a hydrogen VCE within the electrolyser facility is around 10^{-7} per year for a small leak. According to the calculation results, the small leak size (1 %) is not expected to exceed the LFL before detection and isolation. Therefore, the mid-size break (10 %) is assumed as the most likely event with a frequency of 10^{-9} per year. On the other hand, a hydrogen VCE in the buffer tank has a frequency of 10^{-5} per year. This value lies above the threshold of 10^{-6} per year based on conservative assumptions adopted in the USNRC Regulatory Guide 1.91, and also above the value of 10^{-7} per year that would justify an external event PSA. However, the load characterization shows that the shock wave would not exceed the fragility criterion of the nearby NPP structure.

The deterministic calculations are performed with conservative conditions in terms of available hydrogen mass at combustion and normal reflected peak overpressure. The calculation results show that both confined and unconfined VCEs comply with the proposed safe distances, and do not exceed

the fragility criterion of the nearby NPP structure. A physical explosion in the buffer tank may lead to the generation of fragments with the potential to reach the cooling towers and turbine building. The energy stored in the vessel and reduced fragment mass, together with a 45° departure angle are major contributors to the maximum flying range. Nevertheless, the frequency of occurrence of the physical explosion lies in the range of 10^{-9} per year.

The results applied to the high-pressure area for a catastrophic event (e.g., plane crash), where all the stored hydrogen takes part in the physical explosion shows that this area should be located outside of the NPP perimeter, at a distance of at least 900 m for 5 tonnes of stored hydrogen and 1300 m for 15 tonnes of stored hydrogen. This area can be placed flexibly outside of the NPP perimeter and is not assumed to be a significant risk for the critical NPP structures.

In order to reduce the uncertainties by the buffer tank, the authors propose either to place this small pressure vessel outside of the NPP perimeter, or to perform an external event PSA to analyse its contribution to core damage frequency. Furthermore, in order to reduce the risk of domino effects within the HPP site, deployment of means of protection such as physical barriers (blast walls) between the 10 MW electrolyser containers is highly advised by the authors of this study. The next steps comprise high-fidelity CFD calculations applied to the container under small leak sizes to evaluate local phenomena upon unintended hydrogen release. The outcomes summarized in this study are to be incorporated on a later stage into the NPP level 1 PSA for external events.

Annex 5: Full Report of Subtask 5 – Analysis of the impact of various levels of integration on NPP licensing and license documentation

Deliverable 4.2 subtask 5

Analysis of the impact of various levels of
integration on NPP licensing and license
documentation

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Revisions

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1.A	See Cover Page	All	First Issue, reviewed by NRG

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
DiD	Defence in Depth
DW	Demineralized Water
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
HF	Human Factor
HPP	Hydrogen Production Plant
I&C	Instrumentation & Control
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PIE	Postulated Initiating Event
RCP	Reactor Coolant Pump
SAR	Safety Analysis Report
SSCs	Structures, Systems and Components

Summary

In this part, the impact of the 8 different integration scenarios of an HPP with an NPP on the licensing process are analyzed. For this purpose, the key documents which define relevant requirements for industrial and nuclear installations are first collected. These mainly include:

- IAEA Safety Standards and Recommendations
- WENRA Safety Reference Levels for Existing Reactors
- Directives and other regulations of the European Union

The information contained in these documents is utilized to gain a general overview of the safety standards to be met and the activities required to demonstrate compliance with these standards as part of approval processes. In addition to the documents mentioned, national regulations and standards must always be taken into account in individual cases.

The main subject areas that must be taken into account are then described in detail. This is done first from the perspective of the necessary approvals for the construction and operation of the HPP and then from the perspective of the necessary reviews and updates for the approval of the NPP, which is mainly covered by the Safety Analysis Report (SAR).

The HPP is essentially to be regarded as a chemical facility and, due to the hydrogen produced, harbors the possibility of fire and explosion risks. For both onsite and offsite scenarios, possible effects on the environment (during construction, commissioning and operation) must be examined and, if necessary, remedial measures must be planned. The fundamentally important aspects of licensing law that were considered with regard to the construction and operation of an HPP are as follows:

- **Environmental Impact:** An environmental impact assessment (EIA) must be carried out to minimize potential impacts on local protected plant and animal species as well as on the soil and groundwater. This must include both the construction measures and the operation of the HPP. One possible impact that may result from the construction of the HPP is the impairment of the habitat and possibly of the breeding activities of protected plant and animal species. This may mean that construction work is only permitted at certain times of the year. Care must also be taken to ensure that no substances hazardous to the soil or groundwater. The effort required for offsite scenarios may be expected to be significantly greater, as a completely new EIA may have to be prepared depending on the location of the HPP. Onsite scenarios can be based on the EIA prepared for the construction and operation of the NPP and the preventive measures already taken.
- **External Hazards and Risks/ Emergency Provisions and Response Organization:** According to the Seveso III Directive, the facility can be classified in one of two categories: as a lower-tier establishment (hydrogen quantities between 5 and 50 tons), or as an upper-tier establishment (hydrogen quantities of 50 tons or more). Depending on the category, certain safety analyses and reports as well as internal and external emergency plans are required. Possible interactions with other plants and/or the NPP must be included in these analyses, and necessary measures taken to avoid negative effects. In onsite scenarios, the analyses and emergency plans must be harmonized and coordinated with those of the NPP.
- **Product Safety:** The components and systems used in the HPP must meet the basic requirements of product safety in order to minimize the risk of malfunctions and accidents. This is primarily the responsibility of the manufacturer but should be verified by the operator.

- Occupational Health and Safety:** In principle, the usual occupational health and safety measures for workers in industrial plants must be implemented. In addition to the use of protective equipment and procedures that are appropriate to the hazard potential of individual activities, explosion protection measures and the marking of potentially explosive areas with warning notices must be implemented. For onsite scenarios, radiation protection measures must be taken into account where necessary and appropriate.
- Energy Transmission and Utility Supply Lines:** Depending on the integration scenario, geography, and existing infrastructure at the selected location, it may be necessary to install electric power lines to connect the HPP to the public power grid or to the NPP. In addition, pipelines may be needed to supply the HPP with the required utilities and to transport the hydrogen produced to the consumers. If this is the case, it may be necessary to acquire usage rights for surrounding land, which may involve extensive approval processes including public participation (local communities, associations and private individuals) and can significantly delay the overall project.
- Transport of Dangerous Goods:** If the hydrogen produced is transported by trailer, train or ship, a loading terminal must be built. To do this, the necessary permits from the directive on the domestic transport of dangerous goods must be obtained. In addition, the terminal must be included in all safety-related analyses and possible negative effects must be excluded or minimized as much as possible. The latter aspect is particularly important for onsite scenarios.
- Building Permit:** A building permit is required for the construction of all types of buildings and structures. Plans of the facility to be constructed and the execution of the construction works must be submitted to the competent authority for approval. The authority will check the construction in regular inspections and carries out a final inspection when the work is completed. Other aspects described above (e.g., the performance of an EIA, the possible inclusion of energy transmission and/or utility supply lines, and public participation processes) have a strong influence on both the time frame and the manner of the realization of the project.

These main aspects form the basis of the assessment of the eight integration scenarios with regard to the licensing process for the HPP. The aim of this analysis is to assess the potential expenditures (in terms of time and money) that are likely to arise from the individual constellations of the integration scenarios on a qualitative level. The key points are summarized in table form for each of the integration scenarios. Finally, an overview table compares how the main aspects mentioned are scored, depending on the integration scenario.

Regarding the necessary adjustments to the existing NPP license, the focus is on the Safety Analysis Report (SAR). The SAR contains all key aspects of importance for the safe operation of the NPP. All direct and indirect changes to the technical systems of the NPP, the structure of the operating organization, the activities and procedures resulting from the integration of the HPP must therefore be described and documented in the SAR by the operator.

For the assessment, the basic structure and content of a generic SAR as recommended by the IAEA is first described. Subsequently, for all chapters of the SAR for which it cannot be ruled out from the outset that they will be affected by the integration of the HPP, the potential impact of the integration scenarios is also assessed at a qualitative level. These are:

- Introduction and general considerations
- Site characteristics
- Safety objectives and design rules for structures, systems and components

- Engineered Safety Features
- Instrumentation and Control
- Electrical Power System
- Auxiliary Systems and Civil Structures
- Steam and Power Conversion System
- Radiation Protection
- Conduct of Operations
- Safety Analysis
- Operational Limits and Conditions
- Management for Safety
- Emergency Preparedness and Response
- Environmental Aspects

Some chapters of the SAR are not being addressed, as the influence of integration on them can be assumed to be non-existent. These are:

- Reactor
- Reactor Coolant System and Associated Systems
- Management of Radioactive Waste

Since the NPHyCo project is not yet at a sufficiently advanced stage, detailed information needed for the assessment of other chapters of the SAR is not available at this point. Therefore, the following chapters are not addressed in the assessment:

- Plant Construction and Commissioning
- Human Factors Engineering
- Decommissioning and End of Life Aspects

Other key topics that are not directly part of the SAR, but nevertheless play an important role in safe and successful integration, are also included in the assessment. These are as follows:

- Organizational Aspects
 - Operating Organization
 - Emergency Organization
 - Access and Security Rules
 - Management System
- Emergency Preparedness and Response
- Fire Protection Plans
- Operational Limits, Operating Procedures
- Periodic Safety Review Program

The results of the detailed qualitative analysis of the individual main topics regarding the NPP are also presented in the form of an overview table.

31 Introduction

The production of hydrogen from nuclear power is a complex and regulated process that requires obtaining specific licenses and permits. The licensing aspects of hydrogen production from nuclear power play a critical role in ensuring that this process is conducted in a safe and responsible manner, and that it meets the necessary standards for quality, safety, and environmental protection.

The necessary licensing activities to enable the production of hydrogen from nuclear power can be divided into two main parts:

1. Acquisition of the authorization for the construction and operation of the HPP.
2. Reassessment of the safety of the NPP based on the integration scenario applied, and, if necessary, implementation of additional safety measures.

The amount of work that is necessary to update existing licensing documentation for the NPP and for the additional licensing of the HPP vary depending on the applied integration scenario. This deliverable aims to assess the impact of the integration scenarios for nuclear powered hydrogen cogeneration on the licensing process. For this assessment, first a list of relevant regulations and key topics that need to be addressed in the licensing documentation of the NPP and the HPP was created. This work step was based on the results from D4.1. Out of these key topics, the ones that are affected directly or indirectly by the modifications for each integration scenario are identified. A qualitative estimation of the resulting workload for the NPP operator will be performed.

31.1 Summary of integration scenarios

NPP-HPP integration scenarios are described in Subtask 1 “Identification and description of facility types (NPP/HPP) and operating conditions (derived from levels of integration, Task 1.2)” of Task 4.2. A summary is given below.

Onsite Solutions

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
8. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)

32 Identification of relevant key documents for the licensing process

An analysis of relevant directives, laws and regulations (on EU-level and for selected countries) was performed in D4.1. In the following chapters, lists of relevant key documents, which need to be taken into account in order to successfully complete the licensing process for the integration of an HPP into an already existing NPP, are given.

32.1 Relevant key documents for the licencing process of HPPs

The relevant key documents for the licensing process of HPPs to be addressed are the following.

- [R.1] Directive [2012/18/EU](#) (Seveso) [33]
- [R.2] Regulation [\(EU\) 2023/988](#) (General Product Safety Regulation) and related European Regulations [34]
- [R.3] Directive [2008/68/EC](#) (only relevant if H2 is transported via car, train or ship) [35]
- [R.4] Directive [89/391/EEC](#) (Occupational Health and Safety) [36]
- [R.5] Directive [2010/75/EU](#) (industrial emissions) [37]
- [R.6] Regulation [\(EU\) 453/2010](#) (REACH) [38]
- [R.7] Directive [2011/92/EU](#) (environmental impact assessment) [39]
- [R.8] Directive [2008/1/EC](#) (integrated pollution prevention and control) [40]
- [R.9] Directive [2004/35/CE](#) (prevention and remedying of environmental damage) [41]

The relevant content of these documents shall be described and the impact of the integration scenarios on the aspects covered by these will be discussed and qualitatively assessed in the respective subchapters of chapter 33.

32.2 Relevant key documents for the licencing process of NPPs

The Licensing process of an integrated plant combining a hydrogen production plant with a nuclear power plant (NPP) is complex and requires comprehensive documentation to ensure and demonstrate safety, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency. It involves a comprehensive review and approval process. Several key documents are essential for the licensing process to ensure that all safety, regulatory, and operational standards are met. These documents address the design, construction, operation, and decommissioning of the integrated plant, and must comply with both nuclear and hydrogen safety regulations. Thorough preparation and submission of these documents are crucial for obtaining the necessary licenses and approvals to operate the integrated plant.

The key documents for licensing an integrated plant (HPP integrated within an NPP) are here after listed:

- a. Safety Assessment Report (SAR): this document provides a detailed analysis of the plant's safety features, accident scenarios, and risk assessments. This document is presented in detail in Section 34.4.
- b. Environmental Impact Assessment report (EIA) providing the assessment of the environmental impacts of the integrated plant, including the evaluation of emissions, effluents, and ecological effects. This document provides also mitigation measures, monitoring plans, and public consultation outcomes.
- c. Design and Construction Plan: detailed plans for the design and construction of the integrated plant are required including engineering drawings, specifications, construction schedules, and quality assurance plans.
- d. Operational Safety Plan: this document provides procedures and protocols for the safe operation of the integrated plant including standard operating procedures, safety protocols, emergency response plans, and maintenance schedules.
- e. Risk Management Plan: this document provides the Risk assessments associated with the integrated plant including the identification of risks, the risk's mitigation strategies and contingency plans.

- f. Emergency Preparedness and Response Plan provides strategies and procedures for responding to emergencies involving the integrated plant. This plan includes the Emergency drills, the coordination with local authorities, and communication plans.
- g. Cybersecurity Plan: this document describes measures to protect the integrated plant's control systems from cyber threats including security protocols, monitoring systems, and response strategies.
- h. Quality Assurance Program, this ensures that all aspects of the integrated plant meet the required quality standards including quality control procedures, audit plans, and compliance checks.
- i. Decommissioning Plan: this document provides the plan for the safe decommissioning and dismantling of the integrated plant at the end of its operational life. This includes the decommissioning procedures, waste management plans, and site restoration plans.
- j. Regulatory Compliance Documentation provides the evidence of compliance with all relevant regulations and standards.
- k. Public Consultation Report provides a summary of public consultations and stakeholder engagement activities. It contains the feedback from the public, responses to concerns, and plans for ongoing stakeholder engagement.
- l. Hydrogen Safety Case: this document provides a detailed analysis of the safety considerations specific to hydrogen production, storage, and use: it includes also a description of hydrogen leak detection systems, explosion prevention measures, and safety protocols.

Additionally, compliance with relevant international and national standards is essential. The relevant international guidelines and standards for the licensing process of NPPs to be addressed are listed in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden..**

32.2.1 Relevant key documents for the drafting of the NPP's Safety Analysis Report

The relevant key documents for the drafting of the NPP's SAR to be addressed are listed in the Appendix.

The recommended contents of each of the chapters of the SAR are provided in Section 3, in Appendix I and in Appendix II of IAEA Specific Safety Guide No SSG-61 [6]. The Annex provides the typical table of contents of an SAR. Appendix I is useful to identify the information to be included in each chapter of the SAR issued for different stages of the licensing process of the NPP. The licensing stages to which Annex I refers are the following:

- Site permit: Initial SAR
- Construction permit: Preliminary SAR (PSAR)
- Commissioning- Preoperational SAR; POSAR
- Operational permit: final SAR

Since the integration of an HPP in an NPP shall involve an existing NPP, it could be managed as a "modification of plant", depending on the level of integration.

Furthermore to issue the SAR, Requirement 20 of IAEA General Safety Requirements No. GSR Part 4 (Rev. 1) [42] is also taken into account as it provides indications on the objectives, scope, level of detail and on the updating of the SAR.

In particular, the SAR shall provide the evidence that the facility is compliant with the fundamental safety principles; when the final site shall be chosen, the SAR shall be updated and the compliance with the safety requirements as established in national laws and regulations shall be given (activity out of scope of this deliverable). Furthermore, the SAR shall provide

- a. A justification for the selection of the anticipated operational occurrences and accident conditions considered in the analysis;
- b. An overview and necessary details of data, the modelling, the computer codes and the assumptions made;
- c. Criteria used for the evaluation of the modelling results;
- d. Conclusions on the acceptability of the level of safety achieved and the identification of necessary improvements and additional measures.

A qualitative analysis of the corresponding impacts on a typical NPP Safety Assessment Report, deriving from the NPP+HPP integration scenarios has been carried out in Section 34.4. The levels of integration of an HPP into an NPP have been presented according to the integration scenarios discussed and validated with NPHyCO project partners here after listed. The share between NPP and HPP of systems/users (electricity, demineralized water, service water for non safety related components cooling) and the full integration of an HPP plant into an NPP have been also included.

32.2.2 Relevant NPHYCO documents used as input for the qualitative analysis of impacts of integration scenarios on Safety Assessment Report

Results from other tasks of the NPHyCo project are used as an additional key source of information. These and other Input documents used are also listed in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden..**

33 Description and discussion of licensing requirements for the construction of an HPP

The production of hydrogen is subject to a significant number of requirements in various fields, which can be found in EU Directives and also national laws. The majority of these requirements are not specific to the production of hydrogen, but generally applicable for industrial plants, especially in the chemical industry.

33.1 Environmental impact

The execution of an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for industrial facilities serves the purpose of evaluating the potential environmental consequences of proposed industrial projects before they are carried out. The EIA aims to ensure that decision-makers consider environmental impacts alongside economic and social factors, promoting sustainable development. By systematically examining the effects on air and water quality, biodiversity, soil health, and human health, EIAs help identify potential risks and mitigation strategies to minimize negative impacts.

An EIA is required both for the construction of the HPP itself and for the construction of energy transmission lines. The greater the number of transmission lines and the greater the distance to be bridged, the greater the effort may be, depending on the local conditions.

An EIA must also be carried out for the approval of the construction and operation of an NPP. For onsite scenarios, it can therefore be assumed that either comparatively little effort will be required for an additional EIA for the integration of the HPP, since many or possibly all relevant aspects have

already been assessed and preventive measures implemented in the NPP’s initial licensing process, or that only the existing EIA of the NPP will have to be revised.

33.1.1 Conservation and protection of wild flora and fauna

The Birds and Habitats Directives [43] [44] [45] set out the overall legal framework for protecting and managing Natura 2000 sites.

Essentially, all European bird species, amphibians, reptiles and all bat species as well as their habitats and breeding places are subject to species protection regulations. The planning application must therefore contain information on protected animal species and their habitats that occur on the property and its surroundings. Only in this way can precautions be taken in good time (e.g. construction time control or creation of replacement habitats). Responsibility for the completeness and accuracy of the information lies with the applicant or architect.

The completed species protection documents must be submitted to the responsible nature conservation authority together with the building permit application. The contained information is used for an initial assessment of possible adverse effects on protected animals or their habitats. A precise description of the construction project helps to ensure that the application is examined quickly.

Depending on the number and type of resident species, the necessary adjustment of construction times to their breeding periods can lead to a considerable restriction of the time windows available for construction activities. In addition to the effort and expenses for the EIA, this can result in a significant extension of the project. The material, time and organizational costs increase with the construction area, especially if a new electricity transmission line or a pipeline needs to be built. Therefore, from a licensing perspective, a close integration between NPP and HPP and, if possible, the utilization of rededicated natural gas pipelines for the supply of consumers with the produced hydrogen are the most favorable option. If the construction of new pipelines cannot be avoided, the routing should be adapted to known habitats of protected species. A joint parallel route with existing natural gas pipelines can be advantageous.

33.1.2 Industrial emissions and their environmental impact

A facility for the production of hydrogen via electrolysis is included by the [Directive 2010/75/EU](#) on industrial emissions only if its production capacity exceeds 50 tons of hydrogen per day [46]. The directive deals with the emissions of the production company, and the protection of soil and groundwater. Based on this directive, certain requirements must be met when applying to the competent authority for a permit for the construction of an HPP.

It is necessary to ensure that the operation of an installation does not lead to a deterioration of the quality of soil and groundwater. One focus here is on so-called "water-polluting substances", which can contaminate surface water, groundwater and therefore also drinking water, particularly through carelessness or technical failure of systems. Input materials used in electrolyzers are also hazardous to water. These include, for example, the ion exchange resins used for water treatment, acids and alkalis, cooling fluids in the cooling circuits, hydraulic oils and the oils used in transformers. Also, the direct or indirect discharge of cooling and wastewater plays a role.

Permit conditions therefore usually include appropriate measures to prevent emissions to soil and groundwater (e.g., leakage detection, construction of a floor pan) and regular surveillance of those measures to avoid leaks, spills, incidents, or accidents occurring during the use of equipment and during storage. To ensure that the operation of an installation does not deteriorate the quality of soil

and groundwater, it is necessary to establish, through a baseline report, the state of soil and groundwater contamination. This baseline report should include a description of the following:

- the installation and its activities;
- the raw and auxiliary materials, other substances and the energy used in or generated by the installation;
- the sources of emissions from the installation;
- the conditions of the site of the installation;
- where applicable, a baseline report;
- the nature and quantities of foreseeable emissions from the installation into each medium as well as identification of significant effects of the emissions on the environment;
- the proposed technology and other techniques for preventing or, where this is not possible, reducing emissions from the installation;
- measures for the prevention, preparation for re-use, recycling and recovery of waste generated by the installation;
- further measures planned to comply with the general principles of the basic obligations of the operator as provided for in General principles of the operator's obligations;
- measures planned to monitor emissions into the environment;
- the main alternatives to the proposed technology, techniques and measures studied by the applicant in outline.

An application for a permit shall also include a non-technical summary.

Annex II of the **Directive 2010/75/EU** on industrial emissions [46] contains a basic list of substances that pollute air and water. All substances that can or will be released during operation of the HPP must be compared with this table. Input materials used in electrolyzers include, for example:

- The ion exchange resins used for water treatment,
- acids and alkalis,
- cooling fluids in the cooling circuits,
- hydraulic oils,
- the oils used in transformers,
- wastewater (concentrated solution).

The **REACH Regulation EU 453/2010** [38] deals with requirements for the compilation of safety data sheets of dangerous substances and gases. The safety data sheets contain requirements for storage, protection when working with these substances, and protection of the environment. For example: https://produkte.linde-gas.at/sdb_konform/H2_10021694EN.pdf.

The datasheet must be prepared by the equipment manufacturer. It is not necessary to prepare this document for licensing of the HPP, but it is necessary for production and transport.

Directive 2011/92/EU [39] on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment determines, that for chemical and other facilities an environmental impact assessment (EIA) must be conducted and documented in an environmental impact assessment report. The HPP is treated as an integrated chemical plant, namely a plant to produce substances on an industrial scale by chemical transformation, with several units which are linked and functionally interconnected, and which are designed to produce basic inorganic chemicals.

The environmental impact assessment report shall include the information outlined in Annex IV of the Directive:

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1. A description of the project, including in particular a description of the physical characteristics of the whole project and the land-use requirements during the construction and operational phases, a description of the main characteristics of the production processes, for instance the nature and quantity of the materials used, and an estimate, by type and quantity, of expected residues and emissions (water, air and soil pollution, noise, vibration, light, heat, radiation, etc.) resulting from the operation of the proposed project.
2. An outline of the main alternatives studied by the developer and an indication of the main reasons for this choice, taking into account the environmental effects.
3. A description of the aspects of the environment likely to be significantly affected by the proposed project, including, in particular, population, fauna, flora, soil, water, air, climatic factors, material assets, including the architectural and archaeological heritage, landscape and the interrelationship between the above factors.
4. A description (this description should cover the direct effects and any indirect, secondary, cumulative, short, medium and long-term, permanent and temporary, positive and negative effects of the project) of the likely significant effects of the proposed project on the environment resulting from the existence of the project, the use of natural resources, and the emission of pollutants, the creation of nuisances and the elimination of waste.
5. The description by the developer of the forecasting methods used to assess the effects on the environment referred to in point 4.
6. A description of the measures envisaged to prevent, reduce and where possible offset any significant adverse effects on the environment.
7. A non-technical summary of the information provided under headings 1 to 6.
8. An indication of any difficulties (technical deficiencies or lack of know-how) encountered by the developer in compiling the required information.

Member States are obliged to inform the public as part of the environmental decision-making procedures on the following matters:

- the request for development consent;
- the fact that the project is subject to an environmental impact assessment procedure and, where relevant, the fact that significant effects on the environment in another Member State are likely;
- details of the competent authorities responsible for taking the decision, those from which relevant information can be obtained, those to which comments or questions can be submitted, and details of the time schedule for transmitting comments or questions;
- the nature of possible decisions or, where there is one, the draft decision;
- an indication of the availability of the information gathered pursuant to Article 5;
- an indication of the times and places at which, and the means by which, the relevant information will be made available;
- details of the arrangements for public participation.

Directive [2008/1/EC](#) concerning integrated pollution prevention and control [40] lays down measures designed to prevent or, where that is not practicable, to reduce emissions in the air, water and land from the abovementioned activities, including measures concerning waste, in order to achieve a high level of protection of the environment taken as a whole. On the basis of this directive, a permit application must be submitted, and a permit issued by the Member State confirming the principles of environmental protection.

General principles included in this directive are:

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- Application of the best available techniques for preventive measures against pollution;
- Avoidance of waste production, or where waste is produced, recovery or disposal of waste while avoiding or reducing any impact on the environment;
- Efficient use of energy;
- Necessary measures to prevent accidents and to limit their consequences;
- Necessary measures to avoid any pollution risk and return the site of operation to a satisfactory state upon definitive cessation.

Member States may provide for a single procedure in order to fulfil the requirements of **Directive 2011/92/EU** and **Directive 2008/1/EC**.

Directive 2004/35/CE on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage [41] determines, that in accordance with the 'polluter pays' principle, an operator who causes environmental damage or creates an imminent threat of such damage, should in principle bear the costs of the necessary preventive or remedial measures.

Based on this directive, there could be an obligation to establish some precautionary measures to prevent the risk of environmental damage when a project is being approved. The competent authority may at any time:

- a) require the operator to provide information on any imminent threat of environmental damage or suspected imminent threat;
- b) require the operator to take the necessary preventive measures;
- c) give instructions to the operator to be followed on the necessary preventive measures to be taken; or
- d) itself take the necessary preventive measures.

Carrying out the above assessments and submitting the approval documents and associated reports in accordance with the EU directives mentioned in this section are always mandatory when an industrial plant is constructed. Closer integration of the HPP with the NPP can offer the advantage, that existing documentation and preventive measures that are already implemented at the NPP can also be used and only need to be supplemented selectively.

33.2 External Hazards and Risks, Emergency provisions and response organization

Directive 2012/18/EU (Seveso III Directive) [33] aims to minimize the risk and consequences of major accidents and of domino effects, that may emanate from industrial plants handling hazardous substances. As a safety measure, it is necessary for land-use or other relevant policies applied in the Member States to ensure appropriate distances between industrial facilities and their surroundings and, where existing establishments are concerned, to implement, if necessary, additional technical measures so that the risk to persons or the environment is maintained at an acceptable level.

Therefore, depending on the integration scenario and the local circumstances of the NPP site, the location of the HPP and its distance to residential areas, areas of substantial public use, the environment, or other industrial plants (e.g. chemical industry) is to be evaluated. As outlined in Article 7 of the Seveso III Directive [33], the operator must send a notification containing the following information to the competent authority:

- the name or business name and full address of the operator of the establishment concerned;

- the registered office of the operator with its full address;
- the name and function of the person in charge of the establishment;
- information enabling identification of the dangerous substances and the category of substances which are or may be present, including a complete list of properties (physical, chemical, flammability);
- the quantity and physical form of the dangerous substance concerned;
- the activity or proposed activity of the installation or storage facility;
- information on the immediate surroundings of the plant and the factors likely to cause a major accident or to aggravate its consequences, including available data on neighbouring plants, other establishments outside the scope of this Directive, areas and development activities that could cause or increase the risk of a major accident and domino effects or exacerbate their consequences.

The notification or its update is to be sent within a reasonable time prior to the start of construction or operation, or prior to a modification leading to a change in the inventory of dangerous substances.

One of the biggest risks to be assessed will be the potential of affecting the safety of the NPP in the event of a hydrogen explosion in the HPP and hydrogen storage areas. The possibility of such a threat to the safety of the NPP must be assessed, particularly for onsite scenarios, and preventive measures taken if necessary. Due to the distance of 3 km to the NPP, no risk for the NPP's safety in the event of a hydrogen explosion in the HPP and hydrogen storage areas can be assumed for offsite scenarios. A detailed example risk assessment for explosion incidents in the HPP including estimates of safety distances has been carried out in subtask 4.

Potentially dangerous substances, which may be handled at an HPP, are hydrogen and, if an alkaline electrolysis is chosen, potassium hydroxide. According to Annex I of [Regulation \(EC\) No 1272/2008](#) [47] the named substances belong to the following categories:

- hydrogen:
 - flammable gas, category 1
 - pressurized gas
- potassium hydroxide:
 - acute toxicity, category 4
 - skin corrosion, category 1A

The Seveso III Directive distinguishes between '**lower-tier establishments**' and '**upper-tier establishments**', for which different requirements apply. The classification of an establishment into one of these two groups depends on the maximum amount of hazardous substances that can be expected to be handled there:

- '**lower-tier establishments**' are referred to as establishments where dangerous substances are present in quantities equal to or in excess of the quantities listed in Column 2 of Part 1 or in Column 2 of Part 2 of Annex I, but less than the quantities listed in Column 3 of Part 1 or in Column 3 of Part 2 of Annex I, where applicable using the summation rule laid down in note 4 to Annex I;
- '**upper-tier establishments**' are referred to as establishments where dangerous substances are present in quantities equal to or in excess of the quantities listed in Column 3 of Part 1 or in Column 3 of Part 2 of Annex I, where applicable using the summation rule laid down in note 4 to Annex I.

As potassium hydroxide has no assigned qualifying quantity in Annex I of the Seveso III Directive (and may not be handled at all, depending on the electrolyzer technology used), the amount of hydrogen stored at the HPP is decisive. The decisive factor here is not whether the hydrogen is permanently present in this quantity, but the storage capacity of the system, which serves as a basis for a worst-case scenario evaluation.

The classification of the HPP as a **lower-tier establishment** applies for plants with the capacity to store **hydrogen quantities between 5 and 50 tons**, while they will be classified as an **upper-tier establishment** with the capacity to store **hydrogen quantities of 50 tons or more**.

33.2.1 Lower-tier establishments

According to Article 8 of the Seveso III Directive [33], Member States shall require the operator of a lower-tier establishment to draw up a document in writing setting out the **major-accident prevention policy (MAPP)** and to ensure that it is properly implemented. The MAPP shall include the following main aspects:

- the operator’s overall aims and principles of action,
- the role and responsibility of management,
- the commitment towards continuously improving the control of major-accident hazards, and ensuring a high level of protection;

Furthermore, the MAPP must take into account the main principles set out in **Annex III** of the Seveso III Directive (for more details, see [33]):

- The safety management system shall be proportionate to the hazards, industrial activities and complexity of the organisation in the establishment and be based on assessment of the risks;
- it should include the part of the general management system which includes the organisational structure, responsibilities, practices, procedures, processes and resources for determining and implementing the MAPP;
- The following issues shall be addressed by the safety management system:
 - organisation and personnel
 - identification and evaluation of major hazards
 - operational control
 - management of change
 - planning for emergencies
 - monitoring performance
 - audit and review

33.2.2 Upper-tier establishments

According to Article 10 of the Seveso III Directive [33], Member States shall require the operator of an upper-tier establishment to produce a **safety report**. This safety report is to be prepared in addition to the MAPP.

The safety report shall contain at least the data and information listed in **Annex II** of the Seveso III Directive:

- Information on the management system and on the organisation of the establishment with a view to major-accident prevention. This information shall contain the elements indicated in Annex III;

- a presentation of the environment of the establishment;
- a description of the installation;
- Identification and accidental risks analysis and prevention methods;
- Measures of protection and intervention to limit the consequences of a major accident:

The operator shall **periodically review and where necessary update** the safety report:

- at least every five years;
- following a major accident at its establishment;
- at any other time at the initiative of the operator or at the request of the competent authority, where justified by new facts or by new technological knowledge about safety matters, including knowledge arising from analysis of accidents or, as far as possible, ‘near misses’, and by developments in knowledge concerning the assessment of hazards.

The updated safety report or updated parts thereof shall be sent to the competent authority without delay.

As Article 12 of the Seveso III Directive [33] outlines, operators of upper-tier establishments shall also prepare **internal and external emergency plans**. These plans shall contain the information set out in **Annex IV** of the Seveso III Directive.

The preparation of the MAPP, safety report and internal and external emergency plans may be based on the existing comparable documents of the NPP. However, if the operators of the NPP and HPP are different, independent organizations (this is particularly possible with offsite integration), it may be necessary for the operator of the HPP to prepare these documents in full. In the case of on-site integration, it can be expected that the HPP will be integrated into the emergency plans and safety reports of the NPP (see also chapter 34).

33.3 Product Safety

In order to ensure that only safe and otherwise compliant products find their way on to the single market of the European Union, various harmonization directives have been issued by the European Commission. Among these is a system of EU product rules, which set the levels of public protection objectives of the products concerned as well as the basic safety characteristics that a technical system to be installed must fulfill.

The ‘Blue Guide’ on the implementation of EU product rules [48] is one of the main reference documents explaining how to implement the legislation covered by the EU’s New Legislative Framework (NLF). It can therefore be utilized as an orientation to the product safety rules to be taken into account when setting up an HPP. As the Commission emphasizes, however, the Blue Guide is intended purely as a guidance document – only the text of the Union harmonisation act itself has legal force.

Since an HPP is assembled from numerous parts with different purposes and properties (e.g. pressure vessels & pressure equipment, electrical equipment, machinery, measuring instruments, equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres etc.), it is legally required that the compliance of all parts and the facility as a whole with the relevant EU Directives for product safety is demonstrated in a conformity assessment. EU Directives that are likely to apply to parts and components of the HPP can be:

- Ecodesign requirements for energy-related products (**Directive 2009/125/EC** and all implementing Regulations for specific product groups that have been adopted under this Framework Directive)
- Simple pressure vessels (**Directive 2014/29/EU**)
- Electrical equipment designed for use within certain voltage limits (**Directive 2014/35/EU**)
- Machinery (**Directive 2006/42/EC**)
- Electromagnetic compatibility (**Directive 2014/30/EU**)
- Measuring instruments (**Directive 2014/32/EU**)
- Cableway installations (**Regulation (EU) 2016/424**)
- Radio equipment (**Directive 2014/53/EU**)
- Pressure equipment (**Directive 2014/68/EU**)
- Transportable Pressure equipment (**Directive 2010/35/EU**)
- Equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres (**Directive 2014/34/EU**)
- Personal protective equipment (**Regulation (EU) 2016/425**)

The conformity is to be confirmed in writing with a Declaration of Conformity and the product to be visibly marked with the CE marking followed by the identification number of the notified body, in case that body is involved in the production control phase. The identification number of the notified body shall be affixed by the body itself or, under its instructions, by the manufacturer or his authorised representative.

The manufacturer of the finished product is responsible for the compliance of the complete product with the applicable legislation. Once it reaches the end-user it is no longer considered a new product and the Union harmonisation legislation no longer applies [48]. Therefore, in case the NPP operator commissions a service provider with the construction of the HPP, the conformity assessment of the HPP as a whole or sections of it is within the responsibility of the service provider. For this purpose, the service provider must make sure to only use components and parts, of which the conformity has been confirmed by the manufacturer(s). The NPP operator is responsible to assure, that the service provider demonstrates the product safety of the HPP and its sections. This is essentially done by checking the evidence provided by the service provider in the conformity assessment.

Compliance with product safety requirements is mandatory regardless of the integration scenario selected.

33.4 Occupational Health and Safety

33.4.1 General safety and health of workers

Council directive [89/391/EEC](#) on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work [36] lines out the duty of employers to take measures necessary for the safety and health protection of employees, including external services or persons, in every aspect related to the work.

Basic requirements of prevention are set out in articles 5 to 12. More detailed instructions on the implementation of these basic requirements can usually be found in the technical regulations on occupational safety applicable to the country in question.

Typical hazards that can occur in the HPP can be caused by:

- machinery,

- electrical appliances,
- pressurized pipes and containers or
- explosive atmospheres (mixtures of hydrogen and air).

Compliance with occupational health and safety requirements is mandatory regardless of the integration scenario selected. For onsite scenarios, radiation protection measures must be taken into account where necessary and appropriate.

33.4.2 Safety and health risks from explosive atmospheres

Directive 1999/92/EC [49] lays out minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers potentially at risk from explosive atmospheres.

As a basis, the employer has to perform an assessment of explosion risks. The assessment shall be comprehensive and consider places which are or can be connected via opening to places in which explosive atmospheres may occur. The employer must take necessary measures, so that the work environment allows the work to be performed safely and make use of appropriate technical means to ensure a supervision during the presence of workers in accordance with the risk assessment. Technical and/or organizational measures shall be appropriate to the nature of the operation, and in order of priority in accordance with the following basic principles:

- the **prevention of the formation of explosive atmospheres**, or where the nature of the activity does not allow that,
- the **avoidance of the ignition of explosive atmospheres**, and
- the **mitigation of the detrimental effects of an explosion** to ensure the health and safety of workers.

These measures shall be combined, where necessary, and/or supplemented with measures against the propagation of explosions and shall be reviewed regularly and, in any event, whenever significant changes occur.

Places where explosive atmospheres may occur, must be classified in terms of zones on the basis of the frequency and duration of the occurrence of an explosive atmosphere in accordance with Annex I of the **Directive 1999/92/EC** [49]. The classification serves as a basis for determining the measures to be taken. The minimum requirements for the measures to be taken are outlined in Annex II of the **Directive 1999/92/EC** [49] and contain training of workers, written instructions and permits to work, and explosion protection measures. Places where explosive atmospheres may occur in quantities that endanger the health and safety of workers shall be marked with signs at their points of entry in accordance with Annex III of [49].

Figure 97: Warning sign for places where explosive atmospheres may occur, according to Annex III of [46].

To demonstrate, that an assessment of explosion risks has been conducted and that necessary measures for the protection of workers are being implemented, the employer must draw up an **'explosion protection document'** prior to the commencement of work and keep it up to date. Whenever the workplace, work equipment or organization of the work undergoes significant changes, extensions or conversions, the employer must revise it. The explosion protection document shall demonstrate in particular:

- that the explosion risks have been determined and assessed,
- that adequate measures will be taken for the protection of workers,
- those places which have been classified into zones in accordance with Annex I,
- those places where the minimum requirements set out in Annex II will apply,
- that the workplace and work equipment, including warning devices, are designed, operated and maintained with due regard for safety,
- that in accordance with **Council Directive [89/655/EEC](#)** concerning the minimum safety and health requirements for the use of work equipment by workers at work [50], arrangements have been made for the safe use of work equipment.

Compliance with the requirements regarding safety and health risks from explosive atmospheres is mandatory regardless of the integration scenario selected.

33.4.3 ATEX: Equipment for potentially explosive atmospheres

The **ATEX Products Directive [2014/34/EU](#)** [51] covers equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres. The directive defines the essential health and safety requirements and conformity assessment procedures, which need to be applied before such products are placed on the EU market. Since the main source of danger from the HPP is the risk of fire and explosion, this directive is discussed in more detail.

In the ATEX Products Directive, devices are divided into groups according to the danger of the environment in which they operate. Equipment for the production of hydrogen is categorized in Equipment group II – Equipment category 3. According to the equipment groups/categories, basic health and safety requirements regarding the design and construction of equipment and protective systems are then established in the ATEX Products Directive.

Apart from meeting the conformity criteria to enter the market of the EU (see also chapter 33.3), equipment and protective systems intended for use in areas with potentially explosive atmospheres must be provided legibly and indelibly with the following markings:

- name, registered trade name or registered trade mark, and address of the manufacturer;
- CE marking (see Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 765/2008);
- the specific marking of explosion protection followed by the symbols indicating the equipment-group and category;
- designation of series or type;
- batch or serial number, if any;
- year of construction;
- for equipment-group II, the letter 'G' (concerning explosive atmospheres caused by gases, vapours or mists);
- Furthermore, where necessary, they must also be marked with all information essential to their safe use.

Source: <https://sigma-hse.com/news-insights/atex-equipment-selection/>

Compliance with the ATEX Product Directive's requirements is mandatory regardless of the integration scenario selected.

33.5 Energy transmission and resource supply lines

Land use planning and zoning regulations at the national and local levels govern the permissible uses of land and the allocation of space for various activities, including infrastructure development such as pipelines and electric power lines.

For the transport of liquid or gaseous resources, such as cooling water, demineralized water or hydrogen, pipelines are an option. If the use of pipelines is deemed necessary and useful, there are two possible options. These are either the construction of pipelines or the rededication of existing pipelines. Also, for the supply with electricity, the HPP needs to be connected to the local electricity grid or directly to the NPP, depending on the integration scenario.

The necessity, usefulness and type of realization of pipelines depends on various factors. The circumstances at the NPP site and around it should therefore be taken into account from the planning stage on. Main influencing factors on the required extent of electric power lines and gas pipelines to be constructed can be:

1. **Distance between NPP, HPP, grid connections and hydrogen consumers:** If connecting points to public grids (e.g., electricity, water, wastewater, an extension to the European Hydrogen Backbone in the vicinity) or hydrogen consumers (e.g. steelworks, chemical industry) are far away, this could mean that a pipeline or electric power line must have a considerable length to reach them. If they are located in different directions, this could further increase the complexity of the authorization process and the construction. An off-taker analysis is included in **D2.1**.
2. **Availability of routes:** The availability of suitable routes for pipeline and electric power line construction could affect their length. This could be the case due to the presence of protected natural habitats, settlements, agricultural areas or other industrial facilities.
3. **Topography and terrain:** The terrain that must be crossed can affect the required length. If the terrain is mountainous or difficult to traverse (e.g., due mountains and valleys, flowing and standing water, forests), this could increase the length and expenditure of resources.
4. **Regulatory requirements:** It is possible that there are regulatory requirements that could affect the design and construction of the energy line and increase the length of the pipeline. These could be environmental regulations, safety requirements or land use regulations.

A new construction of pipelines and electric power lines is not desirable from a licensing point of view, since the planning and approval process, including public participation, can complicate the overall process and extend its time frame significantly.

In addition to specific regulations governing energy infrastructure, such as grid connection codes and environmental impact assessments, the construction of gas pipelines and electric power lines must comply with relevant EU legislation on energy, environmental protection, health and safety, and other relevant areas. This may include directives and regulations related to renewable energy, energy efficiency, emissions reduction, land use planning, protection of natural habitats, and regulations aimed at protecting cultural heritage sites and archaeological remains. Developers may need to conduct archaeological surveys and assessments to identify and mitigate potential impacts on cultural heritage assets located within or near the project area.

Public consultation and stakeholder engagement are important aspects of the authorization process. Developers are often required to engage with local communities, landowners, environmental groups, and other stakeholders to gather feedback, address concerns, and ensure that the project takes into account local land use considerations and community interests. In cases where land acquisition or easements across private property are required, developers must comply with regulations governing land expropriation, compensation, and landowner rights. Legal frameworks vary by country, but typically, developers are required to negotiate agreements with affected landowners and provide fair compensation for land use rights or property impacts. This part of the approval process can consume a considerable amount of time and financial resources.

The co-location of gas pipelines and electric power lines in shared rights-of-way is desirable from a licensing point of view. However, co-location of energy transmission systems may result in potential hazards (e.g. electrical interference and fire hazards) which arise from the physical proximity of these energy infrastructure and which should be considered and addressed within the development and authorization process [52] [53].

This aspect depends on the prevailing infrastructural conditions and economic considerations at the selected location but is not significantly influenced by the integration scenarios.

33.6 Transport of dangerous goods

As an alternative to transportation via pipeline, the hydrogen produced can also be delivered to end customers by trailer, rail or inland waterways.

Directive 2008/68/EC on the inland transport of dangerous goods [35] defines common rules for the safe and secure transport of dangerous goods within and between EU countries by road, rail or inland waterway. It also covers aspects such as loading and unloading, the transfer to and from another mode of transport, as well as the stops in the course of the transport process. It extends the application of international rules to national transport of dangerous goods.

The Directive covers the following international rules:

- The European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road, concluded at Geneva on 30 September 1957, as amended (**ADR**);
- the Regulations concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Rail, appearing as Appendix C to the Convention concerning International Carriage by Rail (COTIF) concluded at Vilnius on 3 June 1999, as amended (**RID**);
- the European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Inland Waterways, concluded at Geneva on 26 May 2000, as amended (**ADN**).

Member States are entitled to regulate the transport of dangerous goods and to set down specific requirements for the national and international transport of dangerous goods within their own territory with regard to the transport of dangerous goods by vehicles, wagons or inland waterway vessels not covered by this directive.

In principle, the relevant requirements laid down by the aforementioned international rules and by individual Member States must be complied with if the hydrogen produced is to be transported by road, rail or water.

This aspect depends on the prevailing infrastructural conditions and economic considerations at the selected location but is not significantly influenced by the integration scenarios.

33.7 Building Permit

Generally, all building works which are planned as part of the project will require a building permit. A building permit needs to be applied for with the responsible municipality. The general characteristics of the building control system in member states of the European Union are similar [54].

A request for a building permit will generally need to comply with:

- a. zoning plan and certain other rules for the municipality;
- b. central and local technical building regulations;
- c. rules on building aesthetics.

The exact requirements that need to be met can vary, depending on the country and municipality. If the requirements under b and c are not met, the permit will be refused. If the request does not meet the requirements under a (e.g., in case of the HPP being placed close to a residential area or on agricultural land), then the request may be qualified as a request for a permit to deviate from the zoning plan. The municipality is free to determine policy and there is no obligation on it to comply with this request. A proactive and open exchange of information with the approval authority is recommended in order to avoid ambiguities both in advance and during the implementation of the construction measures.

Designs of the structures to be built within the project must be prepared, described, and submitted to the responsible authority. The responsible authority scrutinises its compliance with zoning demands and building regulations. In order to effectively scrutinise the design, drawings and calculations as well as a description of the stages of the construction work should be included in the documents submitted by the operator. Generally, construction works can start after the building permit has been granted by the building authorities. Depending on the country, there may be exemptions to this rule. For instance, the conduction of preparatory works such as excavation and peripheral contention of the soil until the level of the lower floor or piling of a building's foundations may be conducted before the building permit has been officially granted [54]. This should, however, always be clarified with the licensing authority first.

In several EU countries, the applicant, the contractor or the building surveyor must notify the building authority of his intention to start the construction work. Usually, the notification must state who is responsible for the construction work (building surveyor) and who is executing it (contractor). If the work is interrupted for a long period, a notification should also be presented [54].

In all EU countries, a building permit expires if construction work is not started within a certain period or is not completed within a certain time from the date the permit was granted. An application to extend the period to start or to complete the construction work can be submitted to the building authority. Beyond a certain limit, a new building permit must be applied for [54].

During construction, site inspections guarantee that the structure is built according to design and that it complies with the building regulations. Once construction is complete, a final check is conducted and a completion certificate or a use permit is issued.

33.8 Assessment of the impact of Integration Scenarios on the licensing of the HPP

Based on the regulatory requirements described in the previous sections, a qualitative assessment of the impact of each of the selected integration scenarios on the various licensing aspects concerning the HPP is presented below in tabular form.

33.8.1 Onsite Scenarios

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing environmental impact assessment for the NPP must be checked and supplemented with potential additional information on HPP but should already cover the most important aspects due to high safety standards for NPP's.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events) - Need for an integrated approach for the assessment of risks and accident scenarios. - Possibility to create synergies by using existing analyses for the NPP while performing the risk analysis.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HPP is integrated into the NPP as an auxiliary facility. - Need for integration of HPP personnel and processes into the NPP's existing emergency provisions and response organization.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Occupational Health and Safety rules and measures apply.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Necessity to consider radiological risks into occupational health and safety plan for HPP workers.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of existing NPP infrastructure (with minor modifications such as pipe connections, shut-off valves, instrumentation, etc.) for supply and disposal of media (demi water, cooling water, wastewater). - Need for construction of pipeline for chilled water supply of the HPP (mostly or entirely on NPP site perimeter). - Potential need for the construction of electricity lines outside of the NPP site perimeter for grid connection of the HPP. - Potential need for use of pipelines for transport of produced hydrogen (not influenced by the integration scenario itself but the overall circumstances at the site).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Truck loading and transportation or laying of a hydrogen pipeline must be included in risk analyses and emergency precautions (must not have a negative impact on the safe operation of the NPP)
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General need for obtaining a building permit for the structures required (HPP, storage, ...). - Local conditions of the NPP site must be taken into account during construction planning and execution. - Construction activities must not have a negative impact on the safety of the NPP. - As the NPP is an industrial plant, no nature conservation obstacles are to be expected during the construction work.

2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing environmental impact assessment for the NPP must be checked and supplemented with potential additional information on HPP but should already cover the most important aspects due to high safety standards for NPP's.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events) - Need for an integrated approach for the assessment of risks and accident scenarios. - Possibility to create synergies by using existing analyses for the NPP while performing the risk analysis.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HPP is integrated into the NPP as an auxiliary facility. - Need for integration of HPP personnel and processes into the NPP's existing emergency provisions and response organization.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Occupational Health and Safety rules and measures apply. - Necessity to consider radiological risks into occupational health and safety plan for HPP workers.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of existing NPP infrastructure (with minor modifications such as pipe connections, shut-off valves, instrumentation, etc.) for supply and disposal of media (demi water, cooling water, wastewater disposal). - Need for construction of pipeline for chilled water supply of the HPP (mostly or entirely on NPP site perimeter). - No need for the construction of electricity lines outside of the NPP site perimeter. - Potential need for use of pipelines for transport of produced hydrogen (not influenced by the integration scenario itself but the overall circumstances at the site).

Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Truck loading and transportation or laying of a hydrogen pipeline must be included in risk analyses and emergency precautions (must not have a negative impact on the safe operation of the NPP)
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General need for obtaining a building permit for the structures required (HPP, storage, ...). - Local conditions of the NPP site must be taken into account during construction planning and execution. - Construction activities must not have a negative impact on the safety of the NPP. - As the NPP is an industrial plant, no nature conservation obstacles are to be expected during the construction work.

3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing environmental impact assessment for the NPP must be checked and supplemented with potential additional information on HPP but should already cover the most important aspects due to high safety standards for NPP's.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events) - Need for an integrated approach for the assessment of risks and accident scenarios. - Possibility to create synergies by using existing analyses for the NPP while performing the risk analysis.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HPP is integrated into the NPP as an auxiliary facility. - Need for integration of HPP personnel and processes into the NPP's existing emergency provisions and response organization.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Occupational Health and Safety rules and measures apply. - Necessity to consider radiological risks into occupational health and safety plan for HPP workers.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of existing NPP infrastructure (with minor modifications such as pipe connections, shut-off valves, instrumentation, etc.) for cooling water supply of HPP. - Need for construction of pipelines (demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) to supply the HPP (mostly or entirely on NPP site perimeter). - No need for the construction of electricity lines outside of the NPP site perimeter. - Potential need for use of pipelines for transport of produced hydrogen (not influenced by the integration scenario itself but the overall circumstances at the site).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Truck loading and transportation or laying of a hydrogen pipeline must be included in risk analyses and emergency precautions (must not have a negative impact on the safe operation of the NPP)
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General need for obtaining a building permit for the structures required (HPP, storage, ...). - Local conditions of the NPP site must be taken into account during construction planning and execution. - Construction activities must not have a negative impact on the safety of the NPP. - As the NPP is an industrial plant, no nature conservation obstacles are to be expected during the construction work.

4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing environmental impact assessment for the NPP must be checked and supplemented with potential additional information on HPP but should already cover the most important aspects due to high safety standards for NPP's.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events) - Need for an integrated approach for the assessment of risks and accident scenarios. - Possibility to create synergies by using existing analyses for the NPP while performing the risk analysis.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HPP is integrated into the NPP as an auxiliary facility. - Need for integration of HPP personnel and processes into the NPP's existing emergency provisions and response organization.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Occupational Health and Safety rules and measures apply. - Necessity to consider radiological risks into occupational health and safety plan for HPP workers.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for use of existing NPP infrastructure (with minor modifications such as pipe connections, shut-off valves, instrumentation, etc.) for supply and disposal of media (demi water, cooling water, wastewater). - Need for construction of pipelines (demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) of the HPP (mostly or entirely on NPP site perimeter). - No need for the construction of electricity lines outside of the NPP site perimeter. - Potential need for use of pipelines for transport of produced hydrogen (not influenced by the integration scenario itself but the overall circumstances at the site).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Truck loading and transportation or laying of a hydrogen pipeline must be included in risk analyses and emergency precautions (must not have a negative impact on the safe operation of the NPP)
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General need for obtaining a building permit for the structures required (HPP, storage, ...). - Local conditions of the NPP site must be taken into account during construction planning and execution. - Construction activities must not have a negative impact on the safety of the NPP. - As the NPP is an industrial plant, no nature conservation obstacles are to be expected during the construction work.

33.8.2 Offsite Scenarios

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines etc. (depending on the local circumstances). - Need for a new, independent EIA; no possibility to base the impact assessment on existing analyses for the NPP.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HPP is treated as a standalone chemical plant in risk analysis. - No possibility to base the risk analysis on existing analyses for the NPP, but also no need for an integrated approach.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of independent emergency provisions and plans for the HPP.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for construction of pipeline for transport of cooling water from NPP's water intake to the HPP and back. - Need for construction of pipelines for media supply (demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) of the HPP. - Need for a connecting power line to the electric grid. - Use of common corridor for all constructions relevant for land use recommendable (if safe and practical).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines, connection to electricity grid etc. - Outcome of Environmental Impact Assessment will likely demand preventive measures (e.g., excavation and installation of a floor pan). - Nature conservation issues can limit and delay the construction project (construction activities only possible seasonally due to breeding periods)

6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines etc. (depending on the local circumstances). - Need for a new, independent EIA; no possibility to base the impact assessment on existing analyses for the NPP.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events). - HPP is treated as a standalone chemical plant in risk analysis. - No possibility to base the risk analysis on existing analyses for the NPP, but also no need for an integrated approach.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of independent emergency provisions and plans for the HPP.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for construction of pipeline for transport of cooling water from NPP's water intake to the HPP and back. - Need for construction of pipelines for media supply (demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) of the HPP. - Need for a connecting power line to the NPP. - Use of common corridor for all constructions relevant for land use recommendable (if safe and practical).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines, connection to electricity grid etc. - Outcome of Environmental Impact Assessment will likely demand preventive measures (e.g., excavation and installation of a floor pan).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature conservation issues can limit and delay the construction project (construction activities only possible seasonally due to breeding periods)
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7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines etc. (depending on the local circumstances). - Need for a new, independent EIA; no possibility to base the impact assessment on existing analyses for the NPP.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events). - HPP is treated as a standalone chemical plant in risk analysis. - No possibility to base the risk analysis on existing analyses for the NPP, but also no need for an integrated approach.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of independent emergency provisions and plans for the HPP.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for construction of pipelines for media supply (cooling water, demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) of the HPP. - Need for a connecting power line to the NPP. - Use of common corridor for all constructions relevant for land use recommendable (if safe and practical).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines, connection to electricity grid etc. - Outcome of Environmental Impact Assessment will likely demand preventive measures (e.g., excavation and installation of a floor pan). - Nature conservation issues can limit and delay the construction project (construction activities only possible seasonally due to breeding periods)

8. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)

Licensing aspect	Brief description of the impact on the HPP licensing
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines etc. (depending on the local circumstances). - Need for a new, independent EIA; no possibility to base the impact assessment on existing analyses for the NPP.
External Hazards and Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No interference between NPP and HPP (initiating events). - HPP is treated as a standalone chemical plant in risk analysis. - No possibility to base the risk analysis on existing analyses for the NPP, but also no need for an integrated approach.
Emergency Provisions and Response Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of independent emergency provisions and plans for the HPP.
Product Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact by choice of integration scenario.
Occupational Health and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Energy transmission and media supply lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for construction of pipelines for media supply (cooling water, demi water, chilled water, wastewater disposal) of the HPP.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for a connecting power line to the electric grid. - Use of common corridor for all constructions relevant for land use recommendable (if safe and practical).
Transport of dangerous goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No specific impact.
Building Permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for more extended assessment due to construction of auxiliary systems, pipelines, connection to electricity grid etc. - Outcome of Environmental Impact Assessment will likely demand preventive measures (e.g., excavation and installation of a floor pan). - Nature conservation issues can limit and delay the construction project (construction activities only possible seasonally due to breeding periods)

33.9 Main Findings

To summarize the above sections, the application of each integration scenario provides pro and contra arguments. These must be weighed against each other depending on the individual case. The most relevant aspects are listed below.

- Product safety rules are independent from the integration scenarios and therefore are not an influencing factor.
- The construction of the HPP at a larger distance from the NPP avoids the need to consider possible effects of the HPP's operation on the safe operation of the NPP.
- The construction of electric power lines and pipelines over large distances can lead to extensive licensing processes, on the one hand, due to the obtaining of land use rights with the involvement of local landowners, municipalities and associations, on the other hand of EIAs. These can significantly delay the start and progress of construction work.
- A closer integration of the HPP at the NPP site requires more extensive considerations regarding interference and possible effects of the HPP's operation on the safe operation of the NPP (e.g., in the MAPP and/or safety report for the HPP).
- A closer integration requires a revision of existing NPP licensing documentation (see chapter 34) and integrated internal and external emergency procedures.
- A closer integration mostly avoids the need for the construction of electric power lines and supply pipelines for the HPP, which may be necessary when choosing an offsite integration scenario.
- A closer integration mostly avoids the need for extensive EIAs, since these have already been conducted within the construction and Periodic Safety Reviews of the NPP.
- When choosing an onsite integration scenario, certain existing assessments, reports and licenses for the NPP (protection of wild flora and fauna, environmental impact assessment, industrial emissions etc.) can serve as templates for the documents needed for the licensing of the HPP. If the competent authorities agree to it, the HPP may even be integrated in existing licenses as a modification of the NPP.
- Methods and measures for ensuring the occupational health and safety of workers at the NPP can be used as a basis for the HPP (i.e., the HPP gets integrated both technically and organizationally)

With regard to the approval procedures required for the construction and operation of the HPP, it can be concluded that offsite scenarios will require more time and overall expenses. This is not exclusively dependent on the chosen integration scenario itself (especially with regard to the construction of power lines and pipelines), but also on individual local conditions such as geography, existing

infrastructure, ownership of land and local flora and fauna. A holistic analysis of local conditions and national legal regulations is therefore of great importance.

However, the interim conclusion can be drawn that by choosing a closer integration (i.e. construction of the HPP on the site of the NPP), the need to carry out land use procedures (including public participation) and EIAs (with the potential consequence of a delay of construction activities for nature conservation reasons) can be avoided. In this way, the total expense can be limited.

33.10 Impact of the integration scenarios on the licensing requirements to be fulfilled

The table below shows a comprehensive overview of the impact each integration scenario has on the specific licensing subjects. The qualitative assessment of the impact of the integration scenarios is included in the annex.

Onsite Solutions

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
 6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
 7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
 8. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)
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Table 62: Qualitative overview of the impact of the integration scenarios on the licensing requirements for the HPP

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Environmental Impact	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
External Hazards and Risks	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency provisions and response organization	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Product Safety	No Specific Impact							
Occupational Health and Safety	LOW							
Energy transmission lines	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH
Transport of dangerous goods	LOW							
Building Permit	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM

34 Description and discussion of the licensing requirements for the modification of an NPP

The case of installing a new HPP sharing resources from an existing NPP will be treated as a design modification of the NPP, that requires a safety assessment. The assessment requires a systematic evaluation of all features of the facility and all activities relevant to safety. This means that regardless of what integration scenario is chosen, a comprehensive evaluation of the effect on all safety relevant features and activities needs to be performed. The extent of the evaluation will strongly depend on the actual changes, firstly to structures, systems & components, and secondly to the operating organization, procedures and activities at the NPP site.

34.1 Structure of a generic Safety Analysis Report for NPPs

In **Council Directive [2009/71/Euratom](#)** [55] and its amendment **[2014/87/Euratom](#)** [56], it is required from an applicant for an operating license for an NPP to demonstrate nuclear safety, and to regularly assess and verify, and continuously improve it, as far as reasonably achievable, in a systematic and verifiable manner. This shall include verification of the physical barriers and licence holder's administrative procedures of protection that would have to fail before workers and the general public would be significantly affected by ionizing radiations. This is typically achieved by the preparation of a Safety Analysis Report by the licensee, which must then be submitted to the regulatory authority.

The SAR summarizes all relevant aspects which need to be analysed to effectively assess the safety of an NPP and the activities carried out at the NPP site. This includes the technical safety of structures, systems & components, the safe operation, accident & emergency procedures, and plant security. The content of the SAR may be divided or combined into different documents. Recommendations regarding the content and structure of a generic SAR are given by the IAEA in the [Specific Safety Guide No. 12 "Licensing Process for Nuclear Installations"](#) [5] and [Specific Safety Guide No. 61 "Format and Content of the Safety Analysis Report for Nuclear Power Plants"](#) [6]. A comprehensive list of the main topics to be addressed in an SAR is presented in the table below.

Not all the listed aspects are affected by the integration of an HPP into an existing NPP. It is the licensee's task to evaluate, which aspects are affected and how.

Based on the assessment of the necessity and safety significance of plant modifications resulting from the integration scenarios in subtask 2 of D4.2, a generic assessment will be performed and discussed in the following sections.

Table 63: Main topics of a generic SAR and their general content, based on [5] and [6].

Main topic	
Overall planning of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A draft project plan• A site evaluation report• Reports on the use of cooling sources and discharges into the environment• Technical specifications, including all operational limits and conditions• References to and benchmarks against other relevant nuclear installations
Licensing process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The strategic plan for the licensing process

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public inquiry strategy plans and reports
Technical design and construction of the plant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A descriptive construction report A report on the management and organization of the design and construction project A report on the acquisition programme (list of SSCs and their origin, details of the manufacturing process for SSCs important to safety) Technical design documents Fire protection plans Physical protection plans
Plant operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General operating rules Modification rules (may be included in the general operating rules) Plans relating to the operating organization and its management system for all licensing steps Commissioning programmes and reports
Plant security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General site protection plans Access rules
Management of nuclear material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plans for accounting and control of nuclear material Reports on radioactive waste and spent fuel management
Management of personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and qualification plans for operations personnel Proof of trustworthiness of all staff who will be engaged in responsible or sensitive positions
Maintenance and ageing management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Details of the maintenance programme and the periodic testing programme Ageing management plans
Continuous improvement of safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A plan for collecting and applying feedback on operating experience Plans for evaluating and improving safety performance Reports on periodic safety reviews or other safety reviews
Accident and emergency management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operating procedures for accident management Emergency preparedness and response plans
Radiation protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports and manuals on the radiation protection programme

34.2 List of documents to be submitted by the NPP operator

According to the IAEA SSG-12 [5], all the following documents should in general be updated as appropriate and submitted to the regulatory body during the licensing process. The content of some of these documents overlaps with the documents required for the HPP, especially when an onsite integration is chosen. The content of these documents may be divided or combined into different documents, possibly also with the documents required for the HPP.

- 1) A descriptive construction report on the changes to the existing systems of the NPP (including a quality manual), which consists of a description of the fundamental elements including basic information on the nuclear installation, the process and technologies used, justification of related activities and provisions for decommissioning;
- 2) References to and benchmarks against other relevant nuclear installations, including those in other States, if any, and a summary of the most significant differences between the installations with regard to the extension of the NPP by an HPP;
- 3) A draft plan for the extension project, including phases and anticipated schedule (including technical research and development, if necessary), a prior economic study regarding the necessary financial investments and the expected costs;
- 4) An updated site evaluation report, which may include a report on the environmental radiation monitoring programme and all or some of the elements described in paras 3.3–3.11 of SSG-12 dealing with the site evaluation;
- 5) Reports on the use of cooling sources and discharges into the environment, and a report on the environmental impact assessment (if the cooling sources are shared with the HPP);
- 6) Public inquiry strategy plans and reports according to each state’s framework and practice;
- 7) A report on the management and organization of the Extension project, including responsibilities and a list of contractors;
- 8) A report on the acquisition programme, including a list of the structures, systems and components and their origin, and, as applicable, details of the manufacturing process for structures, systems and components important to safety;
- 9) The strategic plan for the licensing process, including the set of requirements, guides, codes and standards to comply with;
- 10) An updated safety analysis report before authorization to begin construction of the Extension, which may include updated information on site evaluation, the design basis, nuclear and radiation safety, deterministic analyses and complementary probabilistic safety

assessment;

- 11) Updated plans relating to the operating organization and its management system for all licensing steps taking into account the extension by an HPP;
- 12) Technical design documents regarding the extension by an HPP;
- 13) Updated Physical protection plans prepared using design related threat analyses, and especially interfaces with safety measures;
- 14) Updated Fire protection plans including the extension by the HPP;
- 15) Updated Training and qualification plans for operations personnel;
- 16) Updated Proof of trustworthiness of all staff who will be engaged in responsible or sensitive positions;
- 17) Commissioning programmes and reports, including the elements described in paras 3.44–3.55 SSG-12 dealing with the commissioning stage of shared systems;
- 18) Updated safety analysis report, which may include all or parts of the elements described in paras 3.3–3.100 on the site evaluation, design, construction, commissioning and operation stages and on provisions for decommissioning;
- 19) Updated Ageing management plans;
- 20) Updated general operating rules, including details of all elements described in paras 3.56–3.81 SSG-12 dealing with the operation stage, and operating procedures;
- 21) Updated technical specifications, including all operational limits and conditions (may be included in the general operating rules);
- 22) Updated plan for collecting and applying feedback on operating experience;
- 23) Updated plans for evaluating and improving safety performance;
- 24) Updated operating procedures for accident management;
- 25) Updated emergency preparedness and response plans;
- 26) Updated reports and manuals on the radiation protection programme;
- 27) Modification rules (may be included in the general operating rules);

- 28) Updated details of the maintenance programme and the periodic testing programme of shared systems;
- 29) Updated reports of periodic safety reviews or other safety reviews;
- 30) Updated decommissioning plans and reports, including details of final shutdown, and decommissioning substages, actions and safety analyses.

The content of many of the documents listed above, especially those with a safety significance, is typically part of the SAR (see section 34.4).

34.3 Qualitative assessment of key topics to be addressed and qualitative analysis of impact of the integration of an HPP into an NPP

In this section a number of topics are discussed, which are not directly related to the technical modifications required at the NPP for the integration of the HPP but are nevertheless essential for a safe and successful integration. These are the following:

- Organizational aspects, e.g.
 - operating organization,
 - emergency organization,
 - access and security rules
 - Management system
- Emergency preparedness and response plans
- Fire protection plans
- Operational limits, Operating procedures
- Periodic safety review program

34.3.1 Organizational aspects

In addition to the technical integration of the HPP into the NPP, an integration of the organizational structure and procedures required for the operation of the HPP into the existing organizational structure of the NPP is necessary. This includes the following main provisions:

- The NPP's operating organization,
- accident & emergency plans,
- access and security rules,
- the management system,
- fire protection plans,
- operational limits and operating procedures,
- periodic safety review program.

All offsite integration scenarios include a placement of the HPP at a distance of 3 km from the NPP. It can therefore be assumed for all offsite scenarios that the extent of organizational integration of the HPP is significantly lower than for the onsite scenarios (this will be the case for example regarding emergency plans, fire protection plans and access rules).

A qualitative assessment of the impact of the integration on the aspects listed above is given in the following subsections.

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34.3.1.1 Operating organization

The operating organization of the NPP will have to be partially adapted but will not undergo any major changes due to the integration of an HPP. Similar to individual specialist areas in the operating organization of NPPs (e.g. mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, maintenance and repair, etc.), an additional specialist area responsible for the operation and overall management of the HPP needs to be added. This new specialist area's responsibilities include the following:

- operation of the HPP, i.e.:
 - starting up and shutting down the HPP, with special attention to the availability of the intended source of electricity
 - full-load operation of the HPP
- monitoring of operational and safety-relevant operating parameters
- maintenance and repair (this task may be integrated into the NPP's existing maintenance and repair plans, since the utilization of human resources for HPP related maintenance and repair activities must be taken into account in the overall planning of maintenance activities)
- qualification and training on H2-specific matters (this task may be integrated into the NPP's existing planning and execution of qualification and training)

Since monitoring, maintenance and repair, qualification and training are activities already being carried out at NPPs, the activities named above will not be performed entirely independently at the HPP but will rather be most likely integrated into the existing organizational structures of the NPP. How closely this integration takes place is significantly influenced by the geographical location of the HPP in relation to the NPP.

As required by international standards [57] [58], the licensee shall ensure that the staff is provided with the necessary facilities and working conditions to carry out work in a safe manner. Reliable fulfillment of this requires a certain amount of additional personnel and material resources (such as tools and spare parts) to be provided by the licensee without negatively affecting the performance of safety-related tasks within the NPP.

The overall influence of the integration scenarios mainly lies in the distinction, whether the HPP is placed offsite at a distance of 3 km or onsite. However, the influence of the chosen integration scenario on the operating organization is estimated as relatively low.

34.3.1.2 Emergency organization

As NPPs are plants with a high hazard potential, emergency precautionary measures are in force for plants with an existing operating license. These include a structured and comprehensive emergency organization with clearly defined responsibilities and associated procedures and instructions on how to react and what measures to take in the event of an accident or emergency. This includes accidents within the NPP's design basis as well as beyond design basis accidents and emergency measures.

The HPP must be integrated into plant specific Emergency Operating Procedures (EOPs), Severe Accident Management Guidelines (SAMGs), and offsite measures in case of a nuclear or radiological emergency. The possibility of an accident at the HPP, the hydrogen storage, a possible trailer loading station, or a hydrogen pipeline acting as an initiating event or aggravating accident scenarios at the NPP must be considered. Appropriate procedures must be provided for the execution of preventive and mitigating measures. Any negative impact of the HPP's presence on the safety of the NPP and its personnel must be excluded or reduced to an acceptable level.

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For this aspect, the difference in influence between onsite and offsite scenarios is considered to be greater. Onsite integration requires the HPP to be closely integrated into the emergency procedures of the NPP, whereas if the HPP is located 3 km away, the plants are largely independent of each other.

34.3.1.3 Access and security rules

In all onsite integration scenarios, personnel involved in the operation, maintenance or repair of the HPP must undergo the same security checks and procedures as all other persons working on the NPP site. In reality, there may not be a strict separation between maintenance personnel for the HPP and other conventional parts of the NPP, so that a simple application of the existing access regulations is sufficient without additional effort. Prior to employment, HPP personnel must undergo the usual personal background check as a preventive measure against sabotage.

As access to radiological monitoring or control areas is not required for work on the HPP, the access to such areas is not to be granted to HPP personnel. In all offsite integration scenarios, the HPP personnel’s access to the NPP site is not necessary for performance of all HPP related tasks.

In addition to the potential hazards of initiating events in the HPP on the safe operation of the NPP, the potential effects on safety equipment must also be analyzed and, if necessary, measures taken to prevent or mitigate them. This must include the possibility of an external attack on the HPP or its storage tanks, especially for onsite scenarios.

34.3.1.4 Management system

The general characteristics of the management system, such as the management’s commitment to safety, leadership and management for safety, continuous measurement, assessment, and improvement of the management system, fostering a culture for safety etc. are not affected by the addition of another operational consumer. Also, the management system’s overall structure and its processes will not be affected. Processes like quality management, staffing, personnel qualification and training, maintenance management will have to include the HPP. With regard to the staffing, qualification and training, this will demand the inclusion of personnel with knowledge and experience regarding the specific properties of hydrogen (explosion limits, ignition temperature, invisible flame etc.).

Especially when demineralized water and cooling water are shared between the NPP and the HPP, existing processes (e.g. staffing, maintenance planning, assignment of chemistry programme) may need to be reviewed and, if necessary, modified according to the needs that arise from the integration. However, these reviews and process modifications can be expected to be of minor overall significance.

A process for management of change must be developed and implemented in the management system, if it does not yet exist in the management system. This process must be examined with regard to its suitability for effectively managing the technical and organizational changes required in the context of system integration, reviewing and determining their potential and actual effects and tracking them in the long term in order to prevent negative developments at an early stage.

The difference in the influence of the integration scenarios on the management system is viewed in such a way that closer integration tends to require more adjustments to the management system. Overall, however, the necessary changes will be of a small scale.

34.3.2 Emergency preparedness and response plans

In general, the operating organization shall develop an emergency plan and shall establish the necessary organizational structure with assigned responsibilities for managing an emergency and shall contribute to the development of off-site emergency procedures.

As comprehensive emergency precautions and measures have already been developed by the operator and approved by the supervisory authority as part of the approval of the NPP, there is no need to set up a new structure. However, the HPP must be integrated into the existing structures and emergency plans, and these must be updated where integration requires it. The extent to which the emergency plans required for the approval of the HPP in accordance with the Seveso III Directive can be reconciled with those of the NPP must also be agreed with the competent authority.

For all offsite scenarios, no significant changes to the emergency preparedness and response plans of the NPP will generally be necessary. If the operation of the HPP falls within the responsibility of the operating organization of the NPP, it is obliged to prepare emergency scenarios for the HPP. For this purpose, reference can be made to the MAPP drawn up as part of the approval in accordance with the Seveso III Directive and the safety report as well as the internal and external emergency plans to be drawn up (see chapter 33.2).

For all onsite scenarios, the HPP must be integrated into all emergency procedures due to the short distance between the NPP and HPP. This includes the consideration of possible initiating events that may emanate from the HPP, as well as the consideration of the HPP's safe shut down and, if necessary, personnel evacuation in case of an emergency at the NPP. Possible initiating events caused by the HPP (see D2.2) are:

1. Confined Vapor Cloud Explosion (VCE) within a HPP container and its effects to the outside.
2. Unconfined VCE in the gas processing unit and its effects to the outside.
3. Burst explosion after catastrophic release of hydrogen from all vessels of a tank system (trailer or storage) due to unspecified external forces.
4. Catastrophic release from the hydrogen pipeline at the HPP due to unspecified external forces.

As stated further above, the difference in influence between onsite and offsite scenarios is considered to be significant with regard to emergency preparedness and response plans. Onsite integration requires the HPP to be closely integrated into the emergency procedures of the NPP, whereas if the HPP is located 3 km away, the plants are largely independent of each other.

34.3.3 Fire protection plans

In case of an onsite integration of the HPP, the NPP's existing fire protection plans must be updated accordingly. This requires the inclusion of the possible initiating events listed in section 34.3.2.

The possibility of fires caused by the above-mentioned initiating events that may arise from the HPP itself or from handling the produced hydrogen need to be included in an appropriate way in the existing fire protection plans.

Most likely the NPP's analyses of external impact scenarios (especially plane crash) already cover the possible impact of a worst-case scenario with hydrogen.

Also, the possible impact of outbreak of fire on the plant premises on the HPP must be analyzed and countermeasures such as protection of the HPP from external fires and an immediate shutdown of the HPP when a fire breaks out must be put into place.

In case of an offsite integration of the HPP, no need for changes of the NPP's existing fire protection plans are to be expected.

34.3.4 Operational limits, operating procedures

In accordance with [6], this section's considerations regarding operational limits relate to the following aspects:

- Safety limits;
- Safety systems settings;
- Limits and conditions for normal operation;
- Surveillance and testing requirements;
- Action statements for deviations from normal operation

Since no changes to the safety systems of the NPP are required for the integration of an HPP into the NPP, no adjustments to safety limits, safety system settings or other safety parameters are necessary. The HPP should be integrated into existing probabilistic safety assessments (PSA) and the results of the updated PSA used as justification for any adjustments to the operating regulations. However, the general operation of the NPP is also not to be expected to be significantly changed by the integration of the HPP.

If the NPP was previously operated in load-following mode, this will no longer take place after the integration of the HPP. With the exception of scheduled plant shutdowns or reactor scrams, the NPP will be constantly operated at full load.

If the HPP draws cooling water from the intake building of the NPP and therefore a lower volume flow is available to the NPP, it is possible that temperature limits for the cooling water drawn from the ultimate heat sink will have to be adjusted. At high summer temperatures, it may be necessary to shut down the NPP at a lower cooling water temperature due to the extraction of part of the cooling water by the HPP.

Requirements for monitoring and testing are not affected by the integration of an HPP, nor are action statements for deviations from normal operation. The HPP merely represents an additional operational power consumer and, if necessary for safety reasons, would have to be switched off in the event of malfunctions of the NPP. Monitoring of important operating parameters of the HPP must be integrated into the control room of the NPP in order to be able to carry out switching operations from there.

As described in section 34.3.1.1, in the case of onsite integration, the systems and components of the HPP must be integrated into the maintenance and servicing program and procedures of the NPP.

In the case of offsite integration, the systems and components of the HPP must also be integrated into the operator's maintenance and servicing program. Due to the distance, a more independent implementation at the HPP site is recommended. In addition, it would be necessary to monitor relevant operating parameters and carry out daily plant walk-downs directly at the HPP site. This may slightly increase the personnel requirements compared to onsite integration.

In some cases, essential administrative aspects, such as the minimum shift composition and the frequency of internal reviews, may also be covered by the OLCs. The reporting requirements for operational events and the administrative requirements, together with a demonstration of how these requirements are met, should be reviewed and updated if necessary.

34.3.5 Periodic safety review program

Routine reviews of nuclear power plant operation (including reviews of modifications to hardware and procedures, significant events, operating experience, plant management and personnel competence) and special reviews following major events of safety significance are the primary means of ensuring safety. In addition, some States have initiated systematic safety reassessments, termed periodic safety review (PSR), to assess the cumulative effects of plant ageing and plant modifications, operating experience, technical developments and siting aspects. A PSR includes an assessment of plant design and operation against applicable current safety standards and operating practices, and has the objective of ensuring a high level of safety throughout the plant’s operating lifetime. It is complementary to the routine and special safety reviews conducted at nuclear power plants and does not replace them.

PSR is a comprehensive safety review of all important aspects of safety, carried out at regular intervals, typically every ten years. The European framework actually requires that “the licence holder under the regulatory control of the competent regulatory authority, re-assesses systematically and regularly, at least every 10 years, the safety of the nuclear installation as laid down in Article 6(c)” of the **Directive 2009/71/EURATOM** [55]. In addition, a PSR may be used in support of the decision making process for licence renewal or long term operation, or for restart of a nuclear power plant following a prolonged shutdown.

In principle, it is to be expected that all aspects of the SAR which are estimated to be affected by the integration of an HPP into an NPP in the following chapters will also have to be reviewed and, if necessary, updated as part of the PSR. However, no effects on the basic procedure or time frame for the periodic safety review are to be expected. The additional effort arising from the inclusion of all relevant aspects connected with the HPP’s integration will, in relation to the overall effort for the preparation of a PSR, be of moderate extent.

34.3.6 Main Findings

To summarize the above sections, the application of close onsite integration scenarios naturally leads to a greater need to adapt organizational structures, procedures and processes of the NPP than is the case for offsite integration scenarios. No significant differences are to be expected within the 4 onsite and 4 offsite scenarios with regard to the key topics considered in the previous sections. The most relevant aspects are listed below.

- The overall operating organization will be impacted by the integration of an HPP in some general areas such as monitoring, maintenance and repair, qualification and training. Additional expenses for material and personnel resources are to be expected.
- For offsite scenarios, the activities in these areas will be less closely interwoven with those in the NPP than for onsite scenarios.
- For onsite scenarios, access and security rules need to be applied to any additional personnel required for the HPP’s operation in an appropriate way. The application of the existing access regulations is sufficient.

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- For offsite scenarios, access and security rules with regard to the NPP's safety play a negligible role.
- Due to the close proximity, the need for a sophisticated integration of the HPP's personnel and operational procedures into the NPP's emergency organization and preparedness and response plans is far greater for onsite scenarios. Compliance with the documents to be submitted as part of the approval of the HPP in accordance with the Seveso III Directive should be discussed with the competent authority.
- For onsite scenarios, the HPP and the potential hazards it poses must be included in the NPP's fire protection plans.
- For offsite scenarios, emergency preparedness and response plans as well as fire protection plans do not need to include the HPP in great detail, since the distance of 3 km serves as a protection.
- Regarding the operational limits and operating procedures, closer attention should be paid to the integration of the HPP onsite scenarios than for offsite scenarios.
- The aspects above will all need to be implemented into an updated version of the management system, which will for the reasons stated require greater effort for onsite scenarios. In this case, the importance of effective management of change is particularly high in order to assess the appropriateness and effectiveness of the changes made and to be able to counteract any negative developments at an early stage.
- The NPP's periodic safety review program will need to include the HPP in accordance with the closeness of its integration.

34.3.7 Comprehensive qualitative assessment of the impact of integration scenarios on organizational aspects

Onsite Solutions

1. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. Onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP.
3. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid.
4. Onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only, with electricity as a load of the NPP.

Offsite Solutions

(3 km distance as a starting point)

5. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity from the grid.
 6. Offsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water (elaboration of break-even distance for cooling water integration) with electricity as a load of the NPP
 7. Offsite solution with integration of electricity only, as a load of the NPP
 8. Offsite solution with zero integration as benchmark (i.e. electricity from the grid)
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Table 64: Qualitative overview of the impact of the integration scenarios on the licensing requirements for the NPP

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Operating organization	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency organization	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Access and security rules	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Management system	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Emergency preparedness and response	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Fire protection plans	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Operational limits, operating procedures	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Periodic safety review program	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

34.4 Qualitative assessment of the impacts of the integration of HPP into a NPP on a typical NPP Safety Analysis Report

This section identifies the main sections of a typical NPP Safety Analysis Report that may be impacted by NPP+HPP integration scenarios. Furthermore, a qualitative analysis of the corresponding impact on the concerned sections of the SAR is also provided.

As provided in [6], the SAR shall consist of the following chapters:

- Chapter 1: Introduction and general considerations;
- Chapter 2: Site characteristics;
- Chapter 3: Safety objectives and design rules for structures, systems and components;
- Chapter 4: Reactor;
- Chapter 5: Reactor coolant system and associated systems;
- Chapter 6: Engineered safety features;
- Chapter 7: Instrumentation and control;
- Chapter 8: Electrical power;
- Chapter 9: Auxiliary systems and civil structures;
- Chapter 10: Steam and power conversion systems;
- Chapter 11: Management of radioactive waste;
- Chapter 12: Radiation protection;
- Chapter 13: Conduct of operations;
- Chapter 14: Plant construction and commissioning;
- Chapter 15: Safety analysis;
- Chapter 16: Operational limits and conditions for safe operation;
- Chapter 17: Management for safety;
- Chapter 18: Human factors engineering;
- Chapter 19: Emergency preparedness and response;
- Chapter 20: Environmental aspects;
- Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of life aspects

A qualitative assessment is carried out for the individual chapters as to whether and to what extent the integration impacts their content.

34.4.1 Chapter 1: Introduction and general considerations

The integration of an HPP into an existing NPP implies modifications on this chapter of the SAR. In particular this section provides a general plant description of the HPP integrated into an existing NPP and introduces the different integration scenarios considered in the SAR. Other information, if available, should be included in this chapter: for example, the plant layout, the safety features, drawings (if available), a description of modes of normal operation of the plant and the compliance with applicable regulations, codes and standards should be presented.

For the operation modes the input from Section 5 (Operation Modes) of D1.2 [R.1] has been taken into account.

The levels of integration of an HPP into an NPP have been presented according to the integration scenarios discussed and validated with NPHyCo project partners in a dedicated project meeting. The share between NPP and HPP of systems/users (electricity, demineralized water and service water for

cooling of non safety related components) and the full integration of HPP into a NPP have also been considered.

34.4.1.1 Integration scenarios

The qualitative analysis of the impacts on the SAR was conducted with regard to the integration scenarios here after listed.

Onsite Solutions:

1. On site solution 1: onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. On site solution 2: on site solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP
3. On site solution 3: onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid
4. On site solution 4: onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only with electricity as a load of the NPP

Offsite Solutions (3 km distance as starting point)

5. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 5: Off-site solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid
6. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 6: Off-site solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity as a load of NPP
7. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 7: Off-site solution with integration of electricity only as a load of NPP.
8. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 8: Off-site solution with zero integration as benchmark (electricity from the grid) (Benchmark Scenario)

34.4.1.2 Input

To support the analysis of the impact of the integration scenarios on the SAR, the outcomes of the following subtasks of NPHyCo Work Package 4.2 have been consulted.

- Sub-task #2: Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP (on a technical level)
- Sub-task #3: Development and detailed description of incident/accident scenarios at the HPP and their impact on the safety of the NPP
- Sub-task #4: Detailed assessment of the various incident/accident)

The relevant NPHyCo documents used as input for the qualitative analysis of impacts of integration scenarios on the SAR are listed in Section 32.2.2.

The level of detail and the information provided in Section 34.4 are congruent with the stage of the project and with the available information shared as outcome of the other subtasks of the Work Package; the most complete information should be provided in the preliminary SAR or the final SAR (out of scope of this Deliverable).

34.4.1.3 General description

The qualitative analysis of impact on Safety Assessment Report of the integration of HPP into an existing NPP refers to a generic EU Site (the analysis is not site-specific, where available the output from other NPHyCO Work Packages activities has been considered). Each country typically has its own nuclear regulatory body with specific regulations and requirements for the licensing of NPPs.

These regulations may include provisions for new technologies and processes such as HPPs. It's fundamental to consult the relevant regulatory documents specific to the country where the NPP is located.

This chapter of the SAR typically provides an overview of the NPP project, including its objectives and scope. In the case of coupling with an HPP, this section needs to be updated to reflect the additional facility, the concerned operation modes and the integration scenarios.

According to NPHYCO deliverable D1.2 [R.1], in principle all types of NPPs could provide the needs of an HPP. The integration of an HPP into an NPP can have an impact on the need of installed capacity of demineralized water and cooling water, which may impact the NPP's safety. The selection of the location of a potential HPP could be impacted by the type of NPP. NPP containments and civil structures are designed against airplane crashes or explosion pressure waves or fire to protect systems, structures and components essential for nuclear safety and sensitive targets; these containment structures are different for the types in question (VVER-440, VVER-1000, KONVOI, etc.) and this should have impacts on the possibilities for the selection of the location of a potential HPP. Specific investigations are carried out in the mainframe of WP2 and WP4 (impact analysis) of the NPHyCo Project. At the current stage there is no impact that requires an exclusion of specific scenarios based on NPP type except the integration of a HTSE plant with a BWR reactor. BWRs can supply only steam contaminated by radionuclides as heat source and the interface point is close to the reactor, the technical solution of the integration of an HTSE plant with a BWR plant appears unreasonable. The co-generation of hydrogen is taken into account also in the early stages of design of advanced and new reactor types: for example a possible integration of GenIV+ nuclear power reactor of ALFRED type (Advanced Lead-cooled Fast Reactor European Demonstrator) with high temperature electrolysis of SOEC type has been analyzed by Ansaldo Nucleare [59]. Also, the coupling of Small Modular Reactors (SMR) with hydrogen production facilities has been investigated in EURATOM projects such as Gemini2.0 or TANDEM [60]. [R.22]Further, there is two-to-three-year pilot project FIRST aimed at demonstrating the commercial-scale production of clean hydrogen and ammonia from small modular reactors in Ukraine using solid oxide electrolysis [61]. New power plants and advanced reactor types are not taken into account for the integration scenarios analyzed in the mainframe of the NPHyCo Project.

34.4.1.4 Compliance with regulations

The integration of an HPP with an NPP would imply a thorough reassessment of the "Regulatory Compliance" section of the NPP's SAR. This reassessment is needed to provide evidence that the operations of the integrated plants are compliant with the applicable regulations, standards, and licensing requirements. The following impacts are envisaged:

- Licensing and Permitting: the licensing and permitting requirements associated with the integration of the HPP with the NPP should be analyzed to identify the necessary licenses, permits, and regulatory approvals required for the construction, operation, and decommissioning of the integrated facilities and outlining the procedure for obtaining these approvals.
- Safety Regulations: the SAR would provide compliance evidence with safety regulations governing both nuclear power plants and hydrogen production facilities. This would include adherence to nuclear safety standards, such as those established by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and national regulatory authorities, as well as compliance with hydrogen safety regulations and codes, such as those developed by organizations like the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and EU directives (see section 32.1)

- Environmental Regulations: the compliance with the applicable environmental regulations shall be assessed with particular attention for the regulations governing air and water emissions, waste management, land use, and habitat protection. Environmental impact assessments should be carried out to evaluate potential environmental impacts associated with the integrated facilities and developing mitigation measures to ensure compliance with applicable environmental regulations.
- Radiological Protection Standards: the SAR would need to demonstrate compliance with radiological protection standards to ensure the safety of workers, the public, and the environment. This would include the compliance to dose limits and exposure guidelines established by national regulatory authorities and international bodies such as the IAEA and the International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP).
- Emergency Preparedness and Response: the assessment of regulatory requirements for emergency preparedness and response should be carried out; this includes the development of emergency response plans, communication protocols, and coordination with external emergency response agencies together with the assessment of the compliance with regulatory standards for emergency preparedness established by national regulatory authorities and industry organizations.
- Quality Assurance and Control: the assessment of regulatory requirements for quality assurance and control to ensure the safety and reliability of the integrated facilities is envisaged with the aim to implement quality assurance programs to verify that design, construction, and operational activities meet regulatory requirements and industry standards.
- Public Participation and Stakeholder Engagement: The SAR would need to address regulatory requirements for public participation and stakeholder engagement in the licensing and permitting process for the integrated facilities. This would involve providing opportunities for public review and comment on the SAR and other regulatory documents, as well as engaging with stakeholders to address concerns and incorporate feedback into the decision-making process.

The integration of HPP with a NPP should require a comprehensive assessment of regulatory compliance requirements and the development of strategies to ensure compliance with applicable regulations, standards, and licensing requirements. This would involve addressing licensing and permitting requirements, complying with safety and environmental regulations, adhering to radiological protection standards, implementing emergency preparedness and response measures, ensuring quality assurance and control, and engaging with stakeholders to facilitate the regulatory approval process.

Overall, the impacts on issuing of this chapter of the SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for on-site integration solutions, MEDIUM for all off site integration solutions except the Off-site solution with zero integration (benchmark scenario) for which the impact is expected to be LOW.

34.4.2 Chapter 2: Site characteristics

The integration of an HPP with an NPP has a considerable impact on the "Site Description" section of an NPP's SAR: in particular a detailed assessment is needed with regard to site suitability, space requirements, environmental impacts, infrastructure requirements, geotechnical considerations, security measures, and regulatory compliance. This comprehensive evaluation ensures that the selected site can safely accommodate both nuclear and hydrogen operations while minimizing risks to the surrounding environment, population, and workers.

The suitability of the site for accommodating both facilities is a crucial point of attention. The assessment must consider factors such as available land area, proximity to water resources for the HPP, and access to infrastructure for hydrogen transport and distribution. The identification and evaluation of sites with suitable characteristics for both nuclear and hydrogen operations need to be carried out.

The integration of an HPP into an existing NPP requires a specific assessment of space requirements. In particular it is needed to analyse the footprint of the HPP, the extension of the storage areas for hydrogen, and the associated infrastructure such as pipelines or storage tanks.

Adequate space must be allocated to ensure safe and efficient operation of both the NPP and the hydrogen plant; about this point please consider the outcome from [R.5].

Furthermore, in this chapter the SAR should address also environmental considerations arising from the coupling of the NPP with an HPP. In particular, an assessment of potential impacts on local ecosystems, water resources, and air quality should be carried out also taking into account the evaluation of the compatibility of hydrogen production processes with environmental regulations and site-specific conditions.

The integration requires additional infrastructure beyond what is typical for an NPP: facilities for hydrogen storage, purification and compression together with transportation infrastructure such as pipelines and/or truck loading stations. This chapter should describe the infrastructure needed to operate NPP and HPP.

As per typical SAR for NPPs, also for the integrated NPP/HPP plant a detailed geotechnical assessment in terms of soils composition, seismic risks, flooding risks need to be carried out to ensure the stability of the structures of both NPP and HPP.

Security and access control measures need to be assessed and presented to safeguard both NPP and HPP against potential threats, including unauthorized access, sabotage, or terrorist attacks. Access control measures may need to be enhanced to protect sensitive areas and materials associated with both operations.

The assessment of compliance with regulatory requirements involving the site selection and the land use becomes paramount when coupling an NPP with an HPP. The "Site Description" section should demonstrate adherence to relevant regulations and standards, including those specific to nuclear safety, industrial safety, environmental protection, and land use planning.

In summary, the impacts of the integration of HPP into NPP has a significant impact on the chapter "Site Characteristics" of the SAR; a detailed assessment of site suitability, space requirements, environmental impacts, infrastructure requirements, geotechnical considerations, security measures, and regulatory compliance is needed to ensure that, for the integration scenarios analysed, the selected site can safely accommodate both NPP and HPP minimizing the risks for workers, environment and population. Overall, the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for on-site solutions, LOW for off-site solutions.

34.4.3 Chapter 3: Safety Objectives and Design Rules for Structures, Systems and Components

The integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Safety Objectives and Design Rules for Structures, Systems, and Components (SSCs)" chapter of a typical SAR. This chapter is crucial as it

outlines the fundamental safety principles and specific design requirements necessary to ensure the safe operation of the plant. Here’s a detailed analysis of how this integration impacts the chapter:

1. **Safety Objectives:** The SAR should present safety objectives for both nuclear and hydrogen operations. This includes preventing hydrogen-related incidents such as leaks or explosions while maintaining the primary safety objectives of the nuclear plant. The integration of an HPP into an NPP should imply the necessary enhanced safety margins to account for the combined risks. This involves setting more stringent safety limits and ensuring redundancy in safety systems.
2. **Design Principles and Criteria:** Design criteria must be expanded to include requirements specific to hydrogen production, storage, and distribution. This includes addressing the high flammability and explosiveness of hydrogen.
3. **Integration of Safety Systems:** Safety systems for hydrogen production, such as leak detection, fire suppression, explosion prevention systems, and systems to mitigate the effects of explosions must be integrated with existing nuclear safety systems.
4. **Redundancy and Diversity:** The design rules must ensure increased redundancy for critical systems, considering the additional risks posed by hydrogen production. This includes multiple layers of safety systems involved in management of hydrogen-related hazards. Utilizing diverse systems and technologies to mitigate risks of common cause failure ensures that a failure in one system does not compromise overall safety. This includes using different types of sensors and safety mechanisms for hydrogen-related hazards.
5. **Separation and Independence:** The design must ensure physical and functional separation between nuclear and hydrogen systems. This includes separate control rooms, power supplies, and safety systems. Safety features for hydrogen systems, such as venting and isolation mechanisms, should be independent of nuclear safety features to ensure that a failure in one does not impact the other.
6. **Reliability and Availability:** SSCs must meet high reliability standards due to the added complexity and risk. This includes rigorous testing and maintenance protocols to ensure consistent performance. Ensuring the availability of critical safety systems for both nuclear and hydrogen operations requires robust design and maintenance strategies. This includes having backup systems and spare parts readily available.
7. **Regulatory Compliance:** Compliance with both nuclear and hydrogen safety regulations is necessary. The SAR must outline how the integrated plant meets the regulatory requirements of both domains, including any additional certifications or approvals required. Continuous engagement with regulatory bodies to ensure compliance and address any emerging safety concerns related to the integrated operations is essential.

At this stage of the project, according to the results of [R.5], it is possible to conclude that the following impacts are expected for the drafting of this chapter of the SAR with reference to coupling an HPP with an NPP:

- a reference on the chapter of the SAR of the NPP that describes the three fundamental safety functions (FSF) according to IAEA SSR-2/1 [62] *(i) control of reactivity, (ii) removal of heat from the reactor and from the fuel store, and (iii) confinement of radioactive material, shielding against radiation and control of planned radioactive releases, as well as limitation of accidental radioactive releases*, needs to be included.
- an evaluation of the fundamental safety functions for the integration scenarios should be carried out.
- a list of structures, systems and components that ensure that the safety functions applicable are ensured in normal, degraded and accidental conditions. The assessment will

consider also SSCs performing specific safety functions to be determined for impact analyses on the fundamental safety functions as a result of integration scenarios.

- a demonstration that the fundamental safety functions are not affected by the modifications introduced by the integration scenarios by adopting specific measures (if applicable) should be provided.

An evaluation of the different levels of defense in depth (DiD) needs to be carried out to provide evidence that the DiD levels are not affected by the modifications needed for the integration scenarios. **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** of [R.5] provides the Safety Principles coupled to the different levels of DiD for the different phases of plant life. This table is a useful guide to identify structures, systems, and components relevant for safety that are linked to the DiD layers, and the associated safety principles/topics.

With reference to the integration scenarios, the criteria to identify the SSC relevant for safety the following criteria should be applied:

- if in the accomplishment of a function, the component contributes to accomplishment of a safety function, the component has been defined as element important for the safety.

The criteria adopted to classify the SCCs are below summarized:

Elements are classified into the following classes:

- Class 1: components credited in the safety demonstration process and required to place the plant in a safe state and maintain it in that state;
- Class 2: components used to prevent, detect or limit the consequence of incidents and accidents, but which are not required for placing the facility in a safe state and maintaining it in that state.

With reference to Rivne NPP the following systems have been taken into account in [R.5] for sharing with an HPP:

1. Electricity
2. Demineralized Water
3. Domestic water supply
4. Service water for cooling (non-safety components)
5. Chilled water
6. Household sewage
7. Pressurized air
8. Nitrogen

The sharing of steam has not been considered for Rivne NPP due to the relative low steam temperatures, the input reference document of [R.5] provides indication of modifications of selected shared systems (electric power distribution system, demineralized water and service water for cooling of non-safety components) these have been here after quoted together with the impacts on safety functions and DiD layers.

34.4.3.1 Impact on Safety Functions [R.5]

Sharing of Electric Power Distribution System

As per [R.5], the existing NPP Rivne supplies power through 110 kV outdoor switchgear to local district consumers and to the reserve (backup) transformers of power units 1 and 2 (1RT and 6RT) with an

installed capacity of 40MVA 110kV/6kV. The 110kV outdoor switchgear does not supply power to systems relevant for nuclear safety and doesn't implement any nuclear safety function both in normal and in accident conditions. To supply electricity from the existing NPP Rivne to the HPP, the 110 kV outdoor switchgear needs to be modified by adding a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers at a reserve position (cubicle No8) of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear with the functionality to supply electricity to the HPP. The other functionalities of the 110kV outdoor switchgear are not impacted by this modification. The reliability of the modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear needs to be tested, but the malfunctioning of this switchgear does not impact safety functions of the NPP SSCs. A malfunctioning of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear should imply the loss of electric power at the NPP but no impact on the safety functions is expected: the loss of onsite power is a design basis event for the existing NPP: the reactor is able to proceed safely with shut down (scram) and the core can be cooled by emergency powered systems; the confinement functions (e.g. reactor cooling system, containment system) are ensured. Loss of onsite power is an event for which the plant is designed.

The modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear has no impact on, and is not related to, the (basic) safety functions of the Rivne NPP.

Sharing of Demineralized Water System

As per [R.5], the demineralized water system is designed to produce chemically demineralized water having the function to replenish steam and condensate losses in the primary and secondary circuits. The demineralized water has no cooling function. In case of sharing of demineralized water system, it shall be needed to connect a new pipeline to the pressure header of demineralized water supply pumps. This pipeline shall be equipped with a manual shut-off valve and instrumentation for pressure and water flow rate control; the readings of these instruments shall be on the water treatment operator's panel. This modification on the demineralized water system of the NPP site is configured as an extension of the drainage water system that doesn't change or interfere with the NPP's function. For constant supply of demineralized water to the HPP it is required to install a demineralized water storage tank and booster pumps at the HPP site.

The modification introduced to the demineralized water system due to coupling with the HPP has no impact on the (basic) safety functions of the existing NPP.

Sharing of Service Water System

In the existing NPP the service water system, part of the secondary water loop of the NPP, is dedicated to the cooling of turbine equipment. Heat from the NPP's primary circuit is removed by the secondary loop in the Steam Generator. The heat of the secondary loop is also absorbed by turbine equipment which need to be cooled. However, the service water system dedicated to the turbine equipment is not involved in the safety function related to the cooling of the core. As per [R.5], in case of sharing of the service water system between HPP and NPP the service water system needs to remove more heat than it was originally designed for: an extra heat removal due to HPP needs requires a modification of the heat balance of the cooling water heat removal capacity of the NPP. For these modifications technical and safety justification shall be required to also give evidence that the modified service water system meets the required margins to operate and safety limits; furthermore, all the preferred users /equipment of the service water system shall be identified and specific procedures to manage the service water system for preferred users shall be issued.

The service water system is not involved in the other basic safety functions i.e. reactivity control of the core and confinement of radioactive material.

According to [R.5], with reference to the coupling of Rivne NPP with an HPP, a potential sharing of the service water system of the turbine equipment of unit 3 and 4 with the HPP has been assessed. In this case a modification of the service water system is required for the pressure headers of the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 3 and the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 4. From these pumps, a pipeline is to be extended to the HPP site. It is envisaged that in case of off-site scenarios, using the service water supply from the Turbine Department for HPP needs is complicated due to the length of the piping that should connect NPP and HPP.

The heat balance of the NPP needs to be revised taking into account a further analysis of the HPP's needs. However, the modification has no impact on reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

34.4.3.2 Impact on Defence in Depth

As per [R.5], the sharing of the systems Electric Power Distribution System, Demineralized Water and Service Water System are linked to SSCs in the first level of DiD with reference, respectively, to the supply of electricity for measurement and correction systems, contribution to replenishment of primary and secondary system inventory, cooling of secondary system components. To prevent deviations that may result in the second level of DiD (Anticipated Operational Occurrences), the following provisions should be applied to all SSCs involved: sufficient design margins and conservatism, high reliability of systems and components, adequate training and qualification of personnel, and quality assurance system. For the 4th level of DiD, the modifications introduced by the sharing of the systems bring advantages for example in severe accident conditions the extra demineralized water inventory used in the HPP, or the service water should be used as emergency cooling water.

Electric power distribution system

The modification introduced consists in adding a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers at a reserve position (cubicle No8) of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear with the functionality to supply electricity to the HPP. This modification has no impact on function and configuration of NPP electric systems. The capacity to supply electricity to the systems relevant for safety, involved in the different DiD layers, is not changed.

Demineralized Water System

The modification introduced are related to the connection of a new pipeline to the pressure header of demineralized water supply pumps. This pipeline shall be equipped with a manual shut-off valve and instrumentation for pressure and water flow rate control. This modification has no impact on the DiD layers. A possible advantage for the 4th level of DiD could be the installation of a demineralized water storage tank to continuously supply demineralized water to the HPP: during severe accident conditions the extra water inventory from this demineralized storage tank could be used as emergency cooling water.

Service Water System

The modification has no impact on the DiD layers. A possible advantage for the 4th level of DiD could be connected to the use of service water as emergency cooling water due to extra connection points in case of severe accidents conditions.

To summarize, the integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Safety Objectives and Design Rules for SSCs" chapter of an SAR. This integration requires comprehensive updates to safety

objectives, design principles, redundancy and diversity strategies, separation and independence criteria, reliability and availability standards, and regulatory compliance measures. Addressing these impacts thoroughly ensures that the integrated plant can operate safely and effectively, mitigating the combined risks associated with nuclear and hydrogen production operations.

Overall, the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for on-site solutions, MEDIUM for all off site solutions except for Benchmark scenario for which the impact is expected LOW.

34.4.4 Chapter 4: Reactor

This chapter has not been investigated, treating the reactor itself as a black box for the purpose of this deliverable. So no information on these items has been given: fuel design, nuclear design, thermohydraulic design, design of control, shutdown and monitoring system, reactor control system and core components. For the integration of an HPP into an NPP, the systems shared between HPP and NPP shall be described in another chapter of the SAR.

For a Description of NPP systems that can be coupled with the HPP, the reference document is provided in [R.5] (in particular the Appendix (Chapter 6) provides a description of Rivne NPP Power units (pressurized water reactors)). In particular the description of the Power units with VVER-440 and VVER-1000, the turbine section, the reactor cooling system, the steam generator, the service water supply and the safety systems is provided.

34.4.5 Chapter 5: Reactor Coolant System and Associated Systems

This chapter has not been investigated. Treating the reactor itself as a black box for the purpose of this deliverable, this chapter has not been detailed. So, no information on components of the reactor coolant system and associated systems should be provided.

The description of the reactor cooling system Rivne NPP Power units (pressurized water reactors is provided in Appendix of [R.5].

34.4.6 Chapter 6: Engineered Safety Features

The engineered safety features presented in this chapter are those SSCs that are necessary to fulfil safety functions in the case of design basis accidents, beyond design conditions (including beyond design conditions with core melting) and some anticipated operational occurrences. It should be demonstrated that the engineered safety features are able to mitigate the consequences of accidents, to bring the NPP to a controlled state and, finally, to reach a safe state. This chapter should include information on the possible impacts (if any) deriving from the integration of an HPP in an NPP, on containment and associated systems that are implemented to contain the effects of accidents and to prevent the loss of containment integrity in all plant states, including design extension conditions with core melting.

The on-site integration scenarios have impacts on the "Engineered Safety Features" chapter of a typical SAR. This chapter focuses on the systems designed to mitigate the consequences of accidents and ensure the safety of the plant. Here's a detailed analysis of how the integration impacts this chapter:

1. Safety Feature Integration and Coordination: This chapter should address the integration of hydrogen-specific safety systems added to the existing nuclear safety features. This includes hydrogen leak detection, venting systems, and explosion suppression mechanisms. Coordination between nuclear and hydrogen safety systems is crucial. Integrated safety

protocols must be developed to ensure that systems work together effectively in emergency scenarios.

2. **Hydrogen Detection and Mitigation:** Advanced hydrogen detection systems must be installed to promptly identify hydrogen leaks. These systems should be integrated with the nuclear plant’s alarm and monitoring systems. The SAR should detail mitigation measures such as venting systems to safely dissipate hydrogen, and explosion suppression systems to manage potential ignition events.
3. **Containment Systems:** The integrity of the containment systems must be reassessed to ensure they can handle additional hydrogen-related pressures and potential explosion impacts. Specific measures to control hydrogen accumulation within the containment structures must be implemented. This includes designing venting pathways and recombiners to prevent hydrogen build-up.
4. **Cooling Systems.** The integration might necessitate enhanced cooling capabilities to take into account the HPP’s cooling needs. This involves assessing the cooling requirements and ensuring redundancy in cooling systems.
5. **Heat Removal Systems:** The SAR should evaluate the heat removal systems’ capability to manage combined heat loads from both nuclear and hydrogen operations, especially during accident conditions.
6. **Fire Protection Systems:** Fire protection systems must be upgraded to address the unique fire hazards associated with hydrogen. This includes installing specialized fire suppression systems capable of managing hydrogen fires.
7. **Fire Barriers and Isolation:** The design should include physical barriers and isolation mechanisms to prevent the spread of fire between nuclear and hydrogen facilities.
8. **Emergency Power Systems:** Emergency power systems must be evaluated to ensure they can support both nuclear and hydrogen safety systems during power outages. This includes backup generators and battery systems. Redundant power supplies and independent power circuits for hydrogen safety systems should be established to ensure continuous operation during emergencies.
9. **Instrumentation and Control Systems: integrated Control Systems.** Instrumentation and control systems for hydrogen safety features must be integrated with the plant’s overall control system. This ensures real-time monitoring and coordinated response during emergencies.

The sharing of Electric Power Distribution System, Demineralized Water System and Service Water System (for cooling of non-safety related components) has no impact on the NPP safety functions of reactor cooling system and containment system as from outcomes of [R.4] and [R.5] provided in 34.4.3.1. The sharing of the Service Water System could imply the needed to revise the heat balance of the nuclear power plant taking into account HPP needs. However, the modification has no impact on reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

Overall, the modifications related to the sharing of the identified systems could have a low impact on safety related SSCs. A review of the heat balance of the NPP needs to be performed taking into account HPP needs further analysis in case of sharing service water system. In any case as per [R.5], the applicable Management of Change process, as stated in the NPP Management System, must be followed. It is expected that a limited Safety Case Report shall be needed and minor changes to be made to safety analyses, procedures and technical documents. The overall impact to this chapter of the SAR is considered MEDIUM.

Integrating an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Engineered Safety Features" chapter of the Safety Assessment Report. The primary impacts include the need for combined and coordinated safety systems, enhanced hydrogen detection and mitigation measures, robust containment and cooling systems, upgraded fire protection and ventilation systems, reliable emergency power supplies, integrated control systems. Addressing these aspects ensures that the engineered safety features are capable of managing the unique risks associated with both nuclear and hydrogen operations, thereby maintaining a high level of safety for the integrated plant.

Overall the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the coupling of an NPP with an HPP is expected HIGH for on-site solutions, MEDIUM for all off site solutions except for Benchmark scenario for which the impact is expected LOW

34.4.7 Chapter 7: Instrumentation and Control

This chapter of the safety analysis report should identify the instruments and the associated equipment necessary for operational states and for accident conditions of the integrated plant HPP-NPP. All the important instrumentation and control components — those important to safety and those not important to safety — should be described in this section.

In general, it is expected that the integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Instrumentation and Control" (I&C) chapter of a typical SAR for all the integration scenarios (on-site and off-site) for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged. For example, in the scenarios for which an amount of electricity from the NPP is dedicated to the HPP, the HPP is considered a constant additional consumer; in this case the HPP produces hydrogen at the designed capacity in continuous mode and starting and stopping the HPP depends on the availability of the NPP. This chapter of the SAR is critical as it outlines the systems used to monitor and control the plant's operations, ensuring safety and efficiency. Here's a detailed analysis of how the integration impacts this chapter:

1. System Integration and Interface: The control systems for the HPP must be integrated with the existing NPP control systems. This requires the development of a unified control architecture that can manage both nuclear and hydrogen operations.
2. Interface Design: New interfaces must be designed to allow operators to monitor and control hydrogen production systems alongside nuclear systems. This includes integrating hydrogen-specific controls and displays into the existing control room setup.
3. Instrumentation Requirements. Additional sensors and instruments are required to monitor hydrogen production processes. This includes sensors for hydrogen flow, pressure, temperature, and leak detection.
4. Calibration and Maintenance: The additional instrumentation requires regular calibration and maintenance to ensure accuracy and reliability. Procedures must be updated to include these new components.
5. Safety and Protection Systems: I&C systems must be enhanced to continuously monitor the safety of both nuclear and hydrogen systems. This includes implementing real-time monitoring for hydrogen leaks and integrating these alarms into the plant's safety systems.
6. Automatic Shutdown Systems: The I&C systems should include automatic shutdown capabilities for both nuclear and hydrogen systems in case of detected anomalies or emergencies, ensuring rapid response to potential hazards.
7. Human-Machine Interface (HMI): A unified HMI could be useful to provide operators with a clear and comprehensive view of both nuclear and hydrogen operations. The HMI should be designed to minimize operator workload and reduce the risk of human error. The design of

- the HMI should prioritize usability, ensuring that operators can easily navigate between nuclear and hydrogen system controls and quickly understand the status of both systems.
8. **Communication and Data Integration:** Data from both nuclear and hydrogen systems must be integrated to provide a comprehensive overview of plant operations. This includes real-time data sharing and storage for analysis and decision-making.
 9. **Secure Communication Protocols:** These protocols must be established to ensure reliable and secure data exchange between nuclear and hydrogen control systems, protecting against cyber threats.
 10. **Emergency Response Systems:** The I&C systems must support coordinated emergency response strategies for incidents involving both nuclear and hydrogen systems. This includes integrating emergency alarms, notifications, and response procedures. Regular drills and testing of the integrated emergency response systems are necessary to ensure readiness and effectiveness in managing combined emergencies.
 11. **Redundancy and Reliability:** The I&C systems must have increased redundancy to ensure reliable operation even in the event of component failures. This includes redundant sensors, controllers, and communication paths for both nuclear and hydrogen systems. All components of the I&C systems must meet high reliability standards to prevent failures that could compromise safety or operational efficiency.
 12. **Cybersecurity:** The integration introduces new cybersecurity challenges. Robust cybersecurity measures must be implemented to protect both nuclear and hydrogen control systems from cyber-attacks. Regular cybersecurity audits and updates are necessary to address emerging threats and vulnerabilities, ensuring the ongoing security of the integrated I&C systems.
 13. **Regulatory Compliance:** The integrated I&C systems must comply with both nuclear and hydrogen safety and regulatory standards. This involves documenting how the systems meet all relevant requirements and obtaining necessary approvals.
 14. **Continuous Monitoring and Reporting:** Continuous monitoring and reporting mechanisms should be in place to ensure ongoing compliance with regulatory standards and to provide transparency in plant operations.

Integrating an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Instrumentation and Control" chapter of the Safety Assessment Report. Key impacts include the need for integrated control systems and interfaces, additional instrumentation for hydrogen monitoring, enhanced safety and protection systems, a unified and user-friendly HMI, integrated data and secure communication systems, coordinated emergency response capabilities, increased redundancy and reliability, robust cybersecurity measures, and comprehensive regulatory compliance. Addressing these aspects thoroughly ensures that the integrated plant can operate safely and efficiently, managing the complexities and risks associated with both nuclear and hydrogen production operations.

From the analysis of outcomes of [R.4] and Subtasks 3 in particular, the integration scenarios that involve the sharing of one or more of the following systems: Electric Power Distribution System, Demineralized Water System and Service Water System (for cooling of non-safety related components) has not impact on the NPP Safety functions of reactor cooling system and containment system. The sharing of Service Water System could imply the needed to revise the heat balance of the NPP taking into account HPP needs However, the modification has no impact on reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

Overall, the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for all the integration scenarios (on-site and off-site) for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged, LOW for Benchmark scenario.

34.4.8 Chapter 8: Electrical Power System

This chapter of the SAR should describe the electrical power system necessary to the non-safety loads and to the safety loads during operational states and for accident conditions of the integrated plant HPP-NPP.

In [R.5] a detailed description of the Electrical Power Distribution system with reference to the existing Rivne NPP is given [R.4]; furthermore the electric system of Rivne NPP and the system functioning in case of failures are also described, here after the main outcome is provided and the expected impacts on the electrical power system in case of coupling of NPP with HPP.

Two operating transformers of 25 MVA each, 15.75/6.3-6.3 kV supply power in normal operation mode to the auxiliary consumers. the transformers are connected to generator current lines by blind taps between unit transformers and generator circuit breakers. The 6/0.4 kV operating transformers, which are connected to 6 kV sections of the power unit supply power to the consumers connected to 0.4 kV sections. The rectifier of the unit-wide DC installation, which provides DC power to consumers (including power to inverters, as well as recharging of the unit-wide accumulator battery), is fed by a separate 6/0.4 kV transformer connected to the 6 kV section. In normal operation mode, the battery of the CSP (control and protection system) is recharged from a separate rectifier connected to the 0.4 kV section. The Inverters connected to the DC panel busbars convert DC voltage into three-phase AC 0.4 kV voltage of 50 Hz frequency. In case of loss of AC voltage at the 6 kV section, the rectifier is switched off and the battery enters in the discharge phase and is able to supply the DC load and inverters. In this case the operation mode of consumers of the first reliability group is not interrupted. When AC voltage is restored at the 6 kV section, the rectifier is automatically switched on (in 50-90 seconds), charging the accumulator battery to the voltage is started by the rectifier stabilization voltage setpoint.

In case of coupling of NPP with HPP an estimation of the power necessary for the HPP has been carried out in [R.4]. The power needed for the HPP is assumed to be 45 MW (of which the capacity of the electrolyzer is 30 MW). The power supply consists of a source of direct current, necessary for electrolysis and a source of alternating current, necessary for the equipment. The HPP is normally connected to the medium voltage network (20-30 kV), the compressors need a voltage level of 6 kV, and other equipment need the connection with the 400 V network. Currently, at the Rivne NPP the 110 kV outdoor switchgear that consists of 12 cubicles (CP) has a free cubicle (CP 8-reserve) from which the HPP could be powered.

The expected modification to the existing electrical supply system of Rivne NPP to also feed the HPP have been analyzed in [R.4] and [R.5] and are here after summarized:

- the installation of a 110kV circuit breaker and a 110kV disconnecter on VRP-110kV,
- the installation of a power transmission line with a voltage of 110 kV with a length of 2200m to 2800m,
- the installation of a 63MVA step-down transformer (110kV/20kV/6kV); this transformer can be installed in proximity of the modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear or within the HPP site (in this case it is needed to consider also the HPP power supply line to install in the overall impacts of the modification).

- the supply of complete distribution devices for the voltage of 20, 6, and 0.4 kV for HPP consumers.

Moreover, since the NPP is connected to the grid, in the event of a fault in the direct electricity line from the NPP to the HPP, it should be checked that the line going to the grid is appropriately sized to withstand the total load coming from the NPP (including the power that would normally go to the HPP).

In any case, even if it were not possible to discharge the total load to the network, in the event of a loss of the direct electricity line from the NPP to the HPP (loss due to HPP accidents), specific procedures to be followed in the event of network disconnection should be activated on the NPP, normal procedures that should already be foreseen for the NPP.

Possible consequences of accidents in the electrical part, as well as accidents with the main equipment of the existing power unit of Rivne NPP are assessed in [R.4], a detailed assessment of possible consequences of a failure in the modified electrical system to take into account the HPP power needs should be carried out and the main outcomes provided in this Chapter. The overall impact on this chapter of the SAR is considered MEDIUM for all the scenarios for which the HPP is fed by electricity directly from the NPP, LOW for the other scenarios.

34.4.9 Chapter 9: Auxiliary Systems

This chapter shall provide information about the auxiliary systems essential for the safe shutdown of the integrated plant or for the protection of the public.

34.4.9.1 Demineralized Water System

With reference to the existing Rivne NPP, [R.5] provides the indication of safety functions of the demineralized water system. Document [R.4] provides the description of the existing service water system and of the modification needed in the demineralized water system of the existing NPP in case of sharing of the system between HPP and NPP. The main outcomes of [R.4] and [R.5] are here after provided. The demineralized water system is not a safety related system, however, in the event of abnormal operations and accidents, the system can be used for the replenishment of losses and maintenance of balance of water of the secondary side, turbine room systems and for replenishment of losses and maintenance of water reserves in the emergency feed water tanks of the steam generators. The equipment of demineralized water system is located in the chemical water treatment building of the NPP's Chemical Department. Demineralized water is used for washing of components (evaporator, condenser, degassers, filter), decontamination, and preparation of boric acid solution and decontamination solution. during maintenance activities the system is used for pressure testing and washing of the equipment.

In case of sharing of the demineralized water system between NPP and HPP, minor modifications on the existing system need to be carried out: an additional pipeline with a shut-off valve, a pressure gauge and a flow meter should be installed. All modifications are carried out in the demineralized water pump room. The pipe laying to the HPP is performed in the NPP site and does not require operational control. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valve) is performed by the operating workers of the NPP's demineralized water system. The schemes and operating instructions of the demineralized water system should be modified. The personnel should be trained and given the necessary instructions on control and management of the modified system. Possible additional malfunctions (leaks, valve or instrumentation failures) should be assessed.

34.4.9.2 Service Water System

With reference to the existing Rivne NPP, [R.5] provides the indication of safety functions of the service water system. [R.4] provides the description of the existing service water system and of the modifications needed in case of sharing of the system between HPP and NPP. The main outcomes of [R.4] and [R.5] are here after provided.

As per [R.5], the service water system is a non-safety related system. However, in case of abnormal situations and accidents the service water system can be used for cooling of equipment such as turbine equipment, reactor coolant pumps (RCP) electric motors, unit transformers and for the heat removal from the process condenser.

The service water systems of existing Rivne NPP consist of ducts, storage tanks, pipelines, and cooling towers; they are separated according to power units that they serve. Units 3 and 4 are served by similar but separated service water systems; the systems are redundant (one pump of two is in operation, the second pump is in automatic standby). The system provides cooling water for the equipment of the turbine department and for the electric motors of the RCPs. With the variation of the height of the water sprinkler over the pool it is possible to control the heat removal to the air. The pumps are located in pumping station buildings which are separated from the turbine building on the NPP site.

In case of sharing of the existing NPP's service water system with the HPP the following modifications are needed: additional pipelines with shut-off valves need to be installed within the location of the existing pipelines of the system. New pipelines are needed to connect the existing pipelines of service water of units No. 3 and No. 4 with the HPP site. The installation of 2 new HPP water supply pumps, a gauge and a flow meter are also expected. All modifications are arranged within the NPP site. The laying of pipes to the HPP and water return is carried out on the NPP site (for on-site scenarios) and does not require operational control. The water flow for the HPP is controlled on the HPP site and is not required with NPP personnel. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valves, pumps) are carried out by NPP workers. Diagrams and operating instructions shall be updated. The power supply equipment for the needs of the corresponding NPP unit will also be modified and power supply cables will be extended to the new pump motors. The diagrams and instructions of the Electrical Department and the Automation and Measurement Department must also be changed. Possible additional faults (leaks, failures of valves, pumps or instruments) must be assessed.

The overall impact on this chapter of the SAR is considered HIGH for all integration scenarios (on-site and off-site) for which the sharing of the demineralized water system and/or the service water system is envisaged, LOW for the other scenarios.

34.4.10 Chapter 10: Steam and power conversion system

This chapter of the SAR involves the design of plant steam and power conversion systems. This chapter should provide information about any possible modification introduced by the integrated plant on the design and operation of the steam and power conversion systems with particular emphasis on those that affect the reactor and its safety features or contribute towards the control of radioactive material. The information provided should demonstrate the capability of the integrated plant to function without compromising (directly or indirectly) the safety of the plant, under both steady state and transient situations.

With reference to Rivne NPP VVER-440 and VVER-1000, [R.4] provides for VVER-440 reactor a description of the scheme of the power unit with the description of the circuit to the steam turbine

part, for VVER-1000 a detailed description of the turbine section and steam generator PGV-1000 is given.

34.4.11 Chapter 11: Management of radioactive waste

This chapter of the SAR is out of scope of the activity and shall not be assessed. Low impact of the integration of an HPP into the NPP is expected on the safe management of radioactive waste generated during the lifetime of the plant. In general, the evaluation of waste streams from both the NPP and the HPP and their treatment should be assessed. This would include the assessment of the types and quantities of waste generated, and the outlining strategies for waste minimization, recycling, and proper disposal to minimize environmental impacts and to accommodate the combined operations of the NPP and the HPP.

34.4.12 Chapter 12: Radiation Protection

This chapter of the SAR provides the evaluation of the occupational exposure of the personnel in the NPP during normal operation and accidental conditions. The evaluation of doses to the public is in scope of Chapters 15 and 20.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would imply a thorough reassessment of the "Radiological Protection" section of the NPP's SAR. This section aims to give evidence that the protection of workers, public, and environment from potential radiological hazards associated with the operation of the NPP is ensured in normal and accidental conditions. The reassessment of this section implies the following activities:

- Radiological Hazard Assessment: the comprehensive assessment of the radiological hazards resulting from the integration of an HPP into an NPP implies the evaluation of potential sources of radiological releases, for example the releases consequent to hydrogen-related incidents, as well as the assessment of the pathways through which these releases could propagate and the evaluation of radiological impacts for workers, population and the environment. This would involve the evaluation of the dose levels associated with various scenarios, such as hydrogen leakages or fires, and the demonstration of their compliance with radioprotection objectives and regulatory dose limits.
- Radiation Shielding and Containment analysis: the adequacy of existing radiation shielding and containment measures within the NPP should be checked to prevent the release of radioactive materials in the event of hydrogen-related incidents. This could involve reinforcing containment structures, enhancing ventilation systems to minimize the spread of radioactive contaminants, and implementing additional barriers to mitigate the release of radiation to the environment.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would require a comprehensive reassessment of radiological protection measures to ensure safety of workers, public, and environment in the presence of potential radiological hazards resulting from hydrogen-related incidents. This would involve assessment of radiological hazards and emergency response procedures to effectively manage radiological risks associated with the integrated facilities. The overall impact to this chapter of SAR is considered HIGH for all on site scenarios, LOW for the other scenarios

34.4.13 Chapter 13: Conduct of Operations

This chapter of the SAR should provide a description of the following sub-chapters:

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- Organizational structure of the operating organization,
- Training of the personnel,
- Implementation of the operational safety programme,
- Plant procedures and guidelines.

Integrating an HPP into an NPP introduces several new elements and considerations that need to be addressed in the "Conduct of Operation" chapter of a typical SAR. Here is a detailed analysis of the potential impacts:

1. **Operational Interfaces:** the integration of an HPP will create new operational interfaces between the NPP and the HPP. These include:
 - **Communication protocols:** Clear communication protocols must be established for communication between the NPP control room and the HPP control systems.
 - **Coordination Procedures:** Procedures for coordinated operation, especially during startup, shutdown, or emergency conditions, need to be developed.
 - **Responsibility and Authority:** Defining the responsibilities and authorities of personnel in both plants to ensure seamless operations.
2. **Operational Procedures:** existing operational procedures need to be reviewed and updated to account for the integration of the HPP.
 - **Integration Procedures:** New standard operating procedures for the integrated operation must be created, including those for normal, abnormal, and emergency conditions.
 - **Maintenance Coordination:** Maintenance schedules and procedures for the HPP must be synchronized with those of the NPP to avoid conflicts and ensure safety.
 - **Emergency Operations:** Specific emergency operating procedures addressing potential hydrogen-related incidents must be incorporated.
3. **Safety Management.** The integration will imply a reevaluation of safety management practices with particular attention for safety culture, training programs and safety assessment:
 - **Safety Culture:** Promoting a unified safety culture across both plants, emphasizing the importance of safety in all operations.
 - **Training Programs:** Comprehensive training programs for NPP staff on HPP operations and vice versa, including emergency response training.
 - **Safety Assessments:** Regular safety assessments to evaluate the impact of the HPP on the overall safety of the NPP.
4. **Emergency Preparedness.** Emergency preparedness plans must be enhanced to include scenarios involving the HPP. In particular, the following key elements should be considered:
 - **Risk Assessment:** Detailed risk assessments to identify potential hazards associated with hydrogen production, storage, and utilization.
 - **Emergency Scenarios:** Development of new emergency scenarios, such as hydrogen leaks, fires, or explosions, and conduction of emergency drills.
 - **Coordination with External Agencies:** Ensuring that local emergency services are aware of the HPP and have appropriate response plans in place.

5. **Monitoring and Control Systems:** monitoring and control systems will need to be updated to integrate the HPP. In particular:
 - **Instrumentation:** Installation of additional instrumentation to monitor hydrogen production, storage, and distribution.
 - **Control Room Integration:** Modifications to the control room to accommodate monitoring and control interfaces for the hydrogen plant.
 - **Data Analysis:** Enhanced data analysis capabilities to monitor the integrated system's performance and safety.

6. **Technical Specifications:** the technical specifications will need to be revised to reflect the integrated operations. It will be necessary to define new operational limits and conditions taking into account the integration of the HPP (please refer to Chapter 16 - Section 34.4.16). Adequate safety margins should be adopted to ensure that the integration does not compromise existing safety margins for the NPP. Furthermore, the compliance evidence that all operations comply with regulatory requirements for both nuclear and hydrogen technologies should be given.

7. **Maintenance and Inspection:** Maintenance and inspection regimes will need to be adapted. In particular, the following activities should be carried out:
 - **Integrated Schedule:** Developing an integrated maintenance schedule to minimize downtime and ensure reliability.
 - **Inspection Protocols:** Creating inspection protocols that consider the unique aspects of hydrogen technology, such as hydrogen embrittlement.
 - **Predictive Maintenance:** Utilizing predictive maintenance techniques to identify potential issues before they become critical.

8. **Hazard Analysis:** A comprehensive hazard analysis needs to be conducted for the integrated system to assess the risks, including also those deriving from the interaction between the NPP and HPP systems and the identification of appropriate mitigation strategies including physical barriers, automated shutdown systems, and emergency response plans.

Integrating an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Conduct of Operations" chapter of the SAR. It requires a thorough review and update of operational procedures, safety management practices, emergency preparedness plans, monitoring systems, and maintenance protocols. Ensuring regulatory compliance and addressing potential hazards associated with hydrogen technology are also critical. The integration must be approached systematically to maintain the safety and reliability of both the NPP and the HPP. The impact is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.14 Chapter 14: Plant construction and commissioning

Integrating an HPP into an NPP presents unique challenges and considerations that must be addressed in the "Plant Construction and Commissioning" chapter of a typical SAR for the NPP. This integration affects various aspects, including design, safety, operational procedures, and regulatory compliance. Here's a detailed breakdown of how the chapter would be impacted:

1. **Design Modifications:** The site layout must accommodate both the NPP and the HPP, ensuring adequate space, access routes, and separation distances to prevent potential hazards.

2. **Shared Infrastructure:** Integration may involve shared use of certain infrastructure such as cooling systems, electrical systems, and control rooms. Detailed design plans must highlight these shared systems and ensure their safety and reliability.
3. **Safety Design:** Hydrogen is highly flammable and poses explosion risks. The safety design must incorporate measures to manage hydrogen production, storage, and distribution safely.
4. **Containment and Isolation:** Systems to contain hydrogen leaks and isolate sections in case of an incident need to be designed and integrated into the overall plant safety systems.
5. **Construction Activities:** the construction plan of the HPP must account for the activities carried out within the existing NPP, ensuring that safety and quality standards are maintained throughout the process. The installation of specialized hydrogen production and storage equipment, including electrolyzers, compressors, and storage tanks, must be carefully planned and executed.
6. **Interface Points:** Clear plans for the interface points between the NPP and the HPP shall be identified, detailing how they will be constructed and commissioned.
7. **Commissioning Procedures:** Comprehensive testing procedures shall be developed to ensure that the integrated systems function correctly and safely, including scenarios involving both plants operating simultaneously. The commissioning procedures shall be in compliance with nuclear safety standards as well as hydrogen safety regulations, potentially involving multiple regulatory bodies.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on the "Plant Construction and Commissioning" chapter of a Safety Assessment Report is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario. It requires meticulous planning, design modifications, adherence to stringent safety and regulatory standards. The detailed considerations outlined above ensure that the integrated plant operates safely, efficiently, and in compliance with all relevant regulations.

34.4.15 Chapter 15: Safety Analysis

This chapter of the SAR should provide the results of the safety analyses carried out to give demonstration of the safety of the plant in normal operation and in accident scenarios on the basis of established acceptance criteria presented in Chapter 3 "Safety Objectives and Design Rules for Structures, Systems and Components" (Section 34.4.3). These analyses normally include deterministic safety analyses of normal operation, anticipated operational occurrences, and design basis accidents. The radiological consequences and the technical acceptance criteria relating to the integrity of barriers should be specified in this section for the accident scenarios investigated. The level of detail provided in this chapter should increase as the integrated plant project develops from the siting stage through the construction stage to the commissioning and operation stages.

This section of the SAR is strongly impacted by the integration of an HPP into an NPP. The integration implies significant modifications and expansions to address the potential impacts and safety measures to adopt associated with this integration. In particular, specific safety analyses are envisaged to ensure the safe operation of the NPP and to identify and mitigate potential hazards. With reference to the chapter "Safety Analysis" of the SAR, the expected impacts of the integration are the following:

- **Introduction of new hazards:** The integration of an HPP into an NPP site implies the introduction of specific hazards to analyze in the SAR; taking into account that hydrogen is a highly flammable gas and it can form explosive mixtures with air it is needed to analyze the

potential for hydrogen leakages, accumulation, and ignition both within the HPP and in all the areas where it could migrate to within the NPP.

- Hazards identification and analysis: This section includes the hazards associated with hydrogen production, storage and handling and the interactions between hydrogen related accidents and the operation of the NPP. The safety analysis would involve the development and modelling of various accident scenarios to assess the potential consequences of hydrogen-related incidents on the safety of the NPP. This could include scenarios such as hydrogen leakages, fires, explosions, and their potential impact on critical systems, structures, and components of the NPP.
- An analysis of combined risks is required to evaluate the potential failures or accidental scenarios in one facility that may have impacts on the safety of the other facility, appropriate detection means, and mitigation measures need to be investigated to minimize these risks.
- Assessment of consequences: the safety analysis would assess the consequences of hydrogen-related incidents on the safety functions of the NPP, including the potential for radiological releases, damage to safety-classified equipment, and impacts on workers safety. This would involve the evaluation of the potential pathways through which hydrogen-related hazards could affect the NPP and the quantification of their potential consequences. Probabilistic safety assessment techniques to quantitatively evaluate the likelihood and consequences of hydrogen-related incidents could be carried out. This would involve analyzing fault trees and event trees to assess the overall risk profile of the NPP in the context of its integration with the HPP.
- Impact on structural integrity: The integration of the HPP has implications to the structural integrity of NPP buildings associated to the expected accidental scenarios which could occur in the HPP; furthermore, the hydrogen embrittlement of materials could necessitate additional analysis to ensure the integrity of critical structures.
- Safety measures and mitigation measures: Specific safety measures and mitigation means could be implemented to reduce the risks associated with hydrogen-related hazards. This could include design modifications, operational procedures, emergency response protocols, and personnel training programs to enhance the safety of the NPP in the presence of an HPP.
- Modification of safety classified systems: Specific analysis could be required to evaluate the suitability of existing safety systems within the NPP in mitigating the effects of hydrogen-related incidents. This would include the assessment of the effectiveness of ventilation systems, fire suppression systems, emergency shutdown procedures, and other safety measures in controlling and mitigating hydrogen hazards. The integration of an HPP into an NPP may imply modifications to the list of safety classified systems: for example, systems to detect H₂ leakages and modifications to fire suppression systems are envisaged.

34.4.15.1 Impact on Risks

According to [R.5], the modifications to the shared systems imply the need to evaluate specific risks due to failure of the modified system or interference with other systems.

With reference to the sharing of the electric power distribution system, the following additional risks are envisaged as per [R.5]: the slight (/negligible) increase of fire probability (e.g. ignition frequency) due to extra heat and number of the extra electronic components or due to extra interferences among electronic systems and the slight (/negligible) increase of loss of onsite power probability due to interference with other electric power systems and/or failure of the implemented 110 kV switchgear in cell 8 and the connected electronic components of the HPP.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels during operation.

The sharing of the demineralized water system implies the following additional risks: the slight (/negligible) increase of flooding probability due to leakage or break of piping or tanks and the slight (/negligible) increase of failure probability of the replenish system to the primary and secondary circuit due to extension of the existing system with components and structures.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels during operation.

The sharing of the service water system implies the following additional risks: the slight (/negligible) increase of flooding probability due to leakage or break of piping or tanks and the slight (/negligible) increase of failure probability of turbine equipment cooling system due to extension of the existing system with components and structures.

The modification does not result in an increase in radiation levels during operation.

34.4.15.2 Impacts on Safety Assessment

The safety assessment related to the existing NPP needs to be revised considering the coupling of NPP and HPP in accordance with the accident scenarios. The safety assessment aims to identify potential incident-accident events, causes of postulated events, potential consequences and the following levels of defense in depth implemented in the plant:

- prevention of deviations,
- detection and correction of deviations and malfunctions,
- accident control and intervention of safety systems,
- reduction of the consequences of accidents for the environment,
- mitigation of radiological consequences of significant releases of radioactive materials (off-site emergency response).

The safety demonstration aims to demonstrate that the safety functions applicable to the integration scenarios analyzed are ensured. For each event the following information is provided:

- Causes/origin of the risk,
- Consequences,
- Prevention,
- Controls/detection,
- Mitigation means.

A preliminary list of events to be assessed is here after provided:

- Reactivity and power distribution anomalies,
- Decrease/increase in primary heat transport system inventory,
- Decrease/ Increase in heat removal by secondary system,
- Decrease in primary heat transport system flow rate,
- Radioactive release from a sub-system or a component,
- Malfunction/Loss of support/auxiliary systems,
- External explosion,
- External Fire,
- Loss of Electrical Power Supply,
- Steam line break (in case of sharing steam from steam generator),
- Secondary loop instabilities (in case of sharing steam from SG,
- Earthquake,
- Load Drop,

- External Flooding,
- Extreme Natural Events,
- Internal Fire,
- Internal Explosion,
- Internal Flooding,
- Combinations of hazards i.e.: internal fire+ Internal explosion, water table + External flooding, internal fire + internal flooding, earthquake and internal fire.

Document [R.6] provides the assessment of some accidental scenarios occurring inside the HPP. In particular, the effects of confined explosion in the PEM stack container, whereas unconfined explosion in the gas processing unit, and buffer tank burst in storage areas have been evaluated. The NPP buildings and structures are assumed to withstand an approximate airborne shock wave with a frontal compression pressure of around 10 kPa. This represents the main safety limit for this study. In addition, results are assessed against the lower safety limit of 6.9 kPa established by the US NRC ¹. According to document [R.6], the assessment of a hydrogen explosion after vessel blowdown in the gas processing unit shows that a safe distance of around 95 m to the nearby NPP structure is needed. The calculation results highlight that the hydrogen buffer tank would not be located onsite of the NPP unless mitigation measures such as reinforced concrete blast walls would be deployed to surround the vessel: in fact, a safety distance of 1350 m is required for the Storage area (15t) to respect the safety limit of 6.9 kPa established by the US NRC for NPP buildings and structures.

After having assessed all the applicable events, a final list of SSCs relevant for the safety shall be issued as provided in [R.5], the integration scenarios have an impact on the SSCs, new risks could be introduced. The evaluation of risks shall take into account both nuclear/radiological aspects and conventional risks. It is expected that the coupling of HPP and NPP can result in added risks, for example the extra pipework, or NPP and HPP sharing the service water system or demineralized water system which could imply added flooding risk (increase of leakage/break frequency). Therefore, the existing risk evaluation of the NPP should be revised if modifications have impact on the different process parts causing changes in the final safety assessment. It is expected that the different existing risk levels for the different areas are not (significantly) affected by the modifications if appropriate measures are taken (if applicable). About the conventional risks, these shall be evaluated taking into account the outcome from Work Package 4.1.

Preliminary information about the systems should be shared between NPP and HPP and the expected impact on safety functions for the integrated plant are provided in [R.5]; in particular the quoted document takes as reference the Rivne NPP located in Ukraine (a pressurized nuclear reactor of the series VVER-440), but the main conclusions involving the impacts on NPP safety functions can be extended to other existing NPPs based on the PWR technology. The integration of an NPP based on the BWR technology with an HPP has been excluded because the technical solution of the integration of an HTSE plant with a BWR plant appears unreasonable (BWRs could supply only steam contaminated by radionuclides as heat source and a tie-in point is close to the reactor).

¹ Please consider that in France, Arrêté du 29 September 2005 provides overpressure limits lower than 69 mbar for the effects on some structures - 20 hPa or mbar, threshold for significant destruction of windows,- 50 hPa or mbar, threshold for light damage to structures. For serious damage to structures the overpressure limit is 140 hPa or mbar

About the accident events above listed, [R.5] suggests that the sharing of the identified systems (electric power distribution system, demineralized water and service water for cooling of non-safety components) has impacts on the following specific postulated initiating events:

For the sharing of the electric power distribution system, the following postulated initiating events (PIEs) have been identified: Loss of electrical power supplies, internal fires (ignition frequency) and Electro-Magnetic Interference (EMI) from equipment on site.

In case of sharing of demineralized water system and service water system, internal flooding has been identified as PIE. Overall, the modifications related to the sharing of the identified systems could have a low impact on safety related SSCs. A review of the heat balance of the NPP needs to be performed taking into account HPP needs in case of sharing of the service water system. Furthermore, the consequences of interruption of integrated system for NPP due to accidents occurring in the HPP should be evaluated. The overall impact is considered MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more of systems is envisaged. In any case as per [R.5], the applicable Management of Change process as stated in the NPP Management System, must be followed. It is expected that a limited Safety Case Report shall be needed and minor changes to be made to safety analyses, procedures and technical documents.

The expected impact of the integration of an HPP into an NPP site on Chapter 15 of the SAR for on-site integration scenarios is considered HIGH. The integration of a HPP with a NPP would imply a comprehensive reassessment of the design basis for the NPP, with a focus on the identification and mitigation of the risks associated with hydrogen production. This would require close collaboration between the operators of both facilities and the integration of hydrogen safety considerations into all aspects of the NPP's design, operation, and emergency response planning. A safety analysis shall be developed to identify, assess, and mitigate the additional hazards introduced by the integrated plant with the aim to protect workers, public, and the environment from the potential consequences of hydrogen-related accidents and to ensure that the nuclear safety functions applicable to the NPP are ensured in normal, abnormal and accident conditions. The impact of the benchmark scenario is expected to be LOW.

34.4.16 Chapter 16: Operational limits and conditions for safe operation

With reference to the integration an HPP into an NPP, specific provisions for training programs procedures need to be developed to ensure that personnel are adequately prepared to safely operate and maintain both the NPP and the HPP. This would involve training on hydrogen safety procedures, emergency response protocols, and the identification and mitigation of hydrogen-related hazards. The safe operating envelope for the integrated plant should be also defined. The safe Operating Envelope defines the boundary within which the facility can be operated safely without any risk to workers, the public or the environment. A set of "Limits and Condition" should be defined also, these limits and conditions identify the boundary of safe operation. With the term "limit" it is intended the maximum justifiable safe state of operations. The limits are parameters (such as temperature or mass limits). Conditions describe the situations necessary to keep operations within the safe operating envelope.

Operating Conditions

According to NPHyCo Deliverable 1.2 [R.1], two possible operation modes have been identified for the HPP integrated into a NPP:

- Continuous operation: in this mode, the HPP is permanently operated at the designed capacity and an amount of electricity from the NPP is permanently dedicated to the hydrogen production; starting and stopping of the NPP has an impact on the operation of the HPP (HPP starts and stops with the NPP).
- Flexible operation: in this operational mode, the production of hydrogen at the HPP is not constant but varies during the day depending on the achievable revenue or on grid balancing services (for example, the amount of hydrogen production will vary during the day and night time or depending on the availability of regenerative electricity from solar or wind power; on the same day, the HPP may start and stop frequently, these frequent HPP starts and stops have impacts on the NPP due to the frequent load disconnections.

The operating conditions based on the hydrogen production strategy are provided in [R.3].

In particular, different modes of operation are presented and assessed from the point of view of their impact on design, license and cost of installation and operation. The modes of operation assessed in [R.3] are the following:

- d) Continuous production: according to this mode, the HPP produces hydrogen at the designed capacity in continuous mode. In this case an amount of electricity from the NPP is dedicated to the HPP considered as a constant additional consumer. Starting and stopping the HPP depends on the availability of the NPP. In case of outage of the NPP or in the event of electricity production from the NPP that is less than the amount required to power the HPP, the HPP needs to be stopped. The HPP as an additional consumer within the NPP has impacts on the operational licences of the NPP. Furthermore, in all H2 production methods, it implies new power transformers that can be upstream or downstream of the NPP generator transformer, depending on the size of the HPP.
As provided in [R.3], the change on the plant systems due to the sharing of some systems between NPP and HPP needs to be treated as design modification of the NPP. The following changes are expected and discussed in [R.3]:
 - a. Changes in the operating conditions of the integrated system,
 - b. Alignment changes (for example, starting an additional pump) needed to manage the new consumption and flows,
 - c. New components in the NPP system (new pumps, for example).
- e) Production based on opportunity prices: in this case the hydrogen production varies within the range no H2 production-design capacity depending on the achievable revenue: This implies ageing of H2 components due to cycling; depending on the integration scenarios frequent starts and stops of this additional consumer could also have an impact on the NPP due to the frequent load disconnections.

As provided in [R.3], due to the variable demand of the HPP the following actions could be required:

- a) review the control loops of integrated systems,
 - b) update maintenance plans and expected lifetime of equipment affected, for example the lifetime of turbines could be affected by the frequent change of the operating point.
- Production based on grid balancing services: in this case the NPP operator is requested to participate in electricity markets that provide balancing services to the grid. In this case the electricity supplied to the grid should change with a required ramp to follow the demand curve. For this reason, the HPP as a load of the NPP should be working at around 50% of its capacity to be able to increase or decrease its electricity consumption when required by the electricity market.

Due to the variable demand of the HPP it would be required to:

- a) review the control loops of integrated systems and
- b) update maintenance plans and expected lifetime of equipment affected.

The table provided in Section 3.4 of document [R.3] summarizes the different operating conditions cases considering the level of integration, the hydrogen production strategy and the HPP technology.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on the "Operational limits and conditions for safe operation" chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.17 Chapter 17: Management for safety

Chapter 17 should describe the overall management of all safety related activities. The information provided in this chapter should cover establishing, assessing, sustaining and continuously improving effective leadership and management for safety.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has impacts on the "Management for Safety" chapter of a typical SAR. This chapter focuses on the organizational, administrative, and procedural aspects required to maintain and enhance safety. Here's a detailed analysis of the impact:

1. **Organizational Structure and Responsibilities:** The integration of hydrogen production within an NPP necessitates the development of an integrated management system that covers both nuclear and hydrogen plant operations. This includes defining clear roles and responsibilities for managing the additional risks and operational complexities. Furthermore, enhanced coordination and communication mechanisms between nuclear and hydrogen plant management teams are essential to ensure safety operations.
2. **Safety Culture:** Promoting a unified safety culture that encompasses both nuclear and hydrogen operations is critical. This involves training personnel on the safety philosophies and practices specific to both types of facilities.
3. **Safety Attitudes and Behaviors:** The SAR must outline initiatives to instill a safety-first attitude among all staff, with a particular emphasis on the unique hazards associated with hydrogen production (e.g., flammability, explosiveness).
4. **Training and Competence:** Training programs must be expanded to cover the operation, maintenance, and safety procedures specific to hydrogen production facilities.
5. **Continuous Competency Development:** Ongoing competency development programs are necessary to ensure that personnel are well-versed in both nuclear and hydrogen safety practices.
6. **Integrated Emergency Plans:** Emergency preparedness and response plans must be updated to account for the presence of hydrogen facilities. This includes planning for potential hydrogen-related incidents (e.g., leaks, explosions) in addition to nuclear emergencies.
7. **Dual Regulatory Frameworks:** Compliance with regulatory requirements for both nuclear and hydrogen production facilities is essential. The SAR should outline the specific regulatory obligations for each and how they are being met.
8. **Regular Audits and Inspections:** The SAR must detail the schedule and scope of regular audits and inspections to ensure ongoing compliance with safety standards for both types of operations.
9. **Incident Reporting and Analysis:** An integrated incident reporting system that captures safety incidents from both nuclear and hydrogen operations should be established.

10. Root Cause Analysis: The SAR should describe the processes for conducting root cause analyses of incidents, ensuring that lessons learned are applied across both types of facilities.
11. Safety Review and Continuous Improvement: Regular safety reviews that encompass both nuclear and hydrogen operations should be conducted to identify and address potential safety issues.
12. Continuous Improvement Programs: The SAR should highlight continuous improvement programs aimed at enhancing safety across the integrated plant, incorporating feedback from safety reviews, incident reports, and regulatory audits.
13. Stakeholder Engagement: Engaging with stakeholders (e.g., regulatory bodies, local communities, employees) about the safety measures and management practices for both nuclear and hydrogen facilities is crucial.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has significant implications for the "Management for Safety" chapter of a SAR. This integration necessitates comprehensive updates to the organizational structure, safety culture, risk management practices, training programs, emergency preparedness plans, safety documentation, regulatory compliance measures, incident reporting systems, safety review processes, and stakeholder engagement strategies. Addressing these impacts thoroughly ensures that safety is maintained and enhanced across the combined facilities, mitigating the unique risks associated with hydrogen production while preserving the stringent safety standards required for nuclear operations.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on the "Management for Safety" chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.18 Chapter 18: Human Factors Engineering

Human & Organizational Factors should be incorporated into the design of the integrated plant. Specific requirements for Human Factors Engineering throughout the life cycle of the integrated plant should be defined. The compliance evidence with these requirements should be given in order to ensure that the following objectives are met:

- Human errors (in terms of frequency and consequences) are minimized.
- Human reliability shall be maximized, all the tasks that shall be carried out by workers shall be assessed in order to evaluate the human reliability to the safe operation of the integrated plant.
- Hazards that could compromise the health of personnel and that could present impacts for the population and the environment shall be minimized.
- The arrangement of control room will consider human factor engineering for the safe and efficient operations of the systems.
- The design shall minimize costs associated with human resources (numbers of workers per task, time to carry out safely operations and maintenance activities).
- The Return of Experience deriving from the operation of similar systems/plant where incidents/accidents have occurred or, where that system is subject to poor operational or maintenance performance shall be taken into account.

The compliance evidence with several essential health and safety requirements relating to the design and construction of machinery or related products, listed in annex III of Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2023 shall be provided. In particular the following requirements are related to Human and Organization Factors (*Principles of safety integration, Lighting, Design of machinery or a related product to facilitate its handling, Ergonomics, Operating positions, Protection against corruption, control systems, protection against*

mechanical hazards, *Required characteristics of guards and protective devices, Risks due to other causes, 1.6. Maintenance*)

The compliance evidence with the applicable essential health and safety requirements related to the design and construction of machinery listed in Annex III of the Regulation (EU) 2023/1230, shall be provided within a specific document "Assessment of conformity with the Essential Health and Safety requirements as per Annex III of Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 ". The assessment shall consider specific HF requirements from legislation of the Site where the integrated plant shall be constructed.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Human Factors Engineering" chapter of a typical SAR. This chapter focuses on optimizing the interaction between humans and the technological systems they operate, ensuring safety, efficiency, and reliability. Here's a detailed analysis of the impact:

1. **Interface Design and Usability:** The control room must be redesigned or expanded to incorporate the monitoring and control systems for the HPP. This includes integrating new displays, controls, and alarms specific to hydrogen production. New Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs) must be designed to be intuitive and user-friendly, ensuring that operators can easily manage both nuclear and hydrogen systems without confusion or overload.
2. **Workload and Staffing:** Operators will face an increased workload due to the additional responsibilities of managing hydrogen production. This necessitates a thorough workload analysis to prevent operator fatigue and ensure optimal performance. The integration may require additional staffing or cross-training of existing staff to handle the dual responsibilities, ensuring that there are enough qualified personnel to manage both systems effectively.
3. **Training and Qualification:** Comprehensive training programs must be developed to cover the operational, maintenance, and safety aspects of the hydrogen plant. This includes understanding the unique properties and hazards of hydrogen. Operators and maintenance personnel must meet new qualification standards that encompass both nuclear and hydrogen plant operations, ensuring they possess the necessary skills and knowledge.
4. **Procedure Development Integrated Procedures:** New and updated procedures must be developed to reflect the integrated operations. This includes normal operations, maintenance, and emergency procedures that account for both nuclear and hydrogen systems. All new and revised procedures must be validated to ensure they are effective and practical, involving operators in the development and testing phases.
5. **Human Error Analysis and Prevention:** The potential for human error increases with the added complexity of integrating hydrogen production. A detailed human error analysis is required to identify potential error points and develop mitigation strategies. Error prevention strategies, such as automation of routine tasks, clear labeling, and fail-safes should be implemented to minimize the risk of human error.
6. **Communication and Coordination:** Clear and effective communication channels must be established between nuclear and hydrogen plant teams to ensure coordination and information flow. Enhanced coordination between different teams (e.g., operators, maintenance, safety) is necessary to manage the integrated operations efficiently. This includes joint training sessions and regular coordination meetings.
7. **Ergonomics and Physical Work Environment:** The physical work environment, including control rooms and maintenance areas, must be ergonomically designed to accommodate the needs of operators managing both systems. This includes appropriate seating, lighting, and control layouts.

8. Environmental Factors: Factors such as temperature, noise, and ventilation must be considered to ensure a comfortable and safe working environment, especially in areas where hydrogen production equipment is located.
9. Human Factors Integration in Design: Human factors considerations must be integrated into the design and modification processes of both the nuclear and hydrogen systems. This involves conducting human factors design reviews and usability testing.
10. Operator Involvement: Operators and maintenance personnel should be actively involved in the design process to provide insights and feedback, ensuring that the systems are user-centric and meet operational needs.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has impacts on the "Human Factors Engineering" chapter of a Safety Assessment Report. The changes required include redesigning control rooms and interfaces, addressing increased workload and staffing needs, developing comprehensive training programs, creating integrated procedures, conducting human error analyses, promoting a unified safety culture, establishing effective communication and coordination mechanisms, ensuring ergonomic design, and integrating human factors into the design process. Addressing these aspects thoroughly ensures that the human element in managing the combined facilities is optimized for safety, efficiency, and reliability.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on the "Human Factors Engineering" chapter of a Safety Assessment Report is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.19 Chapter 19. Emergency preparedness and response

The safety analysis presented in Chapter 15 of the SAR would also evaluate the emergency preparedness and response capabilities of the NPP in the event of hydrogen-related incidents. It is envisaged to carry out a specific assessment of the adequacy of emergency response procedures, communication protocols, and the availability of resources and personnel to effectively manage hydrogen-related emergencies.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP requires changes to emergency response procedures: in particular, an updating of emergency response procedures outlined in the "Radiological Protection" section is needed to account for the potential radiological consequences of hydrogen-related incidents. Specific procedures need to be adopted to manage the hydrogen related accidents (for example H₂ leakages and fire). These procedures need to be integrated in the overall emergency response plan for the NPP.

Specific response protocols for radiological emergencies triggered by hydrogen leakages, fires, or explosions shall be developed and the availability of resources and workers to effectively manage such incidents shall be ensured.

Communication strategies for informing and educating the public about the radiological risks associated with the operation of the integrated facilities shall be outlined. Clear and transparent information about the potential radiological hazards, emergency response procedures, and protective measures in place to ensure public safety shall be provided.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would imply a significant reassessment of the "Emergency Planning and Response" section of the NPP's SAR. This section outlines the protocols, procedures,

and resources in place to manage and mitigate emergencies that could occur during the operation of the NPP. The expected impacts on this section are the following:

1. **Scenario Development and Analysis:** New emergency scenarios specific to the integration of an HPP into the NPP shall be investigated. This would involve the assessment of potential accidents such as hydrogen leakages, fires, explosions, and their potential impact on the safety and operability of the integrated facilities.
2. **Emergency Response Protocols:** The safety report would outline specific emergency response protocols tailored to address hydrogen-related incidents. This would include procedures for rapidly detecting and responding to hydrogen leakages, initiating shutdown sequences, and implementing measures to mitigate the consequences of hydrogen-related emergencies.
3. **Coordination with External Agencies:** Integration with an HPP would require enhanced coordination with external agencies responsible for emergency response, such as local fire departments, hazmat teams, and regulatory authorities. The safety report would detail the communication protocols, mutual aid agreements, and joint training exercises established to facilitate effective collaboration during emergencies.
4. **Personnel Training and Preparedness:** The safety report would outline training programs and preparedness measures to ensure that personnel are adequately trained to respond to hydrogen-related emergencies. This would include training on hydrogen safety procedures, emergency response protocols, and the operation of specialized equipment for managing hydrogen-related incidents.
5. **Public Alerting and Communication:** The safety report would address public alerting and communication strategies to inform and educate the public about hydrogen-related emergencies. This would involve developing clear and concise communication protocols for issuing alerts, providing evacuation instructions, and disseminating accurate information to minimize public confusion and ensure public safety.
6. **Resource Management and Contingency Planning:** The safety report would assess the availability of resources, such as personnel, equipment, and supplies, to effectively manage hydrogen-related emergencies. This would include developing contingency plans for securing additional resources if needed and establishing procedures for prioritizing resource allocation during emergencies to ensure the most critical needs are addressed first.
7. **Drills and Exercises:** The safety report would outline the schedule and scope of emergency drills and exercises conducted to test and validate the effectiveness of emergency response plans and procedures. This would include tabletop exercises, functional drills, and full-scale simulations involving both NPP and HPP personnel, as well as external emergency response agencies.
8. **Lessons Learned and Continuous Improvement:** The safety report would include mechanisms for capturing and incorporating lessons learned from past emergencies and drills to continuously improve emergency response capabilities. This would involve conducting post-emergency debriefings, analyzing response performance, and implementing corrective actions to address any identified deficiencies.

Integrating an HPP into an NPP would require a comprehensive reassessment and enhancement of emergency planning and response measures to effectively manage the unique hazards associated with hydrogen-related incidents. This would involve developing tailored emergency response protocols, enhancing coordination with external agencies, ensuring personnel readiness through training and drills, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement to enhance overall emergency preparedness and response capabilities.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on this chapter of a generic SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.20 Chapter 20: Environmental Aspects

This Chapter shall provide a brief qualitative description of the approach to assess the impact on the environment of the integrated plant (for operational states as well as for all accident conditions) and decommissioning of the plant, taking into account a generic EU site for the integrated HPP-NPP plant.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would significantly impact the "Environmental Impact Assessment" developed in support of the SAR. A specific evaluation of the potential environmental impacts associated with the operation of the integrated plant should be carried out, the measures to mitigate adverse effects on the environment should be defined. In particular, the impact is expected in terms of:

- Emissions and Discharges: an assessment of the potential emissions and discharges associated with the operation of the HPP, including emissions of greenhouse gases, air pollutants, and wastewater discharges should be carried out. This would involve the evaluation of emissions and discharges from both the NPP and the HPP and the evaluation of their potential impacts on air quality, water quality, and ecosystems.
- Hydrogen Production Process: it is envisaged a detailed analysis of the environmental impacts associated with the hydrogen production process, including the energy sources used, the efficiency of the production process, and the generation of by-products or waste streams. This would include the assessment of the potential for emissions of greenhouse gases, such as carbon dioxide, during hydrogen production and the evaluation of strategies to minimize or offset these emissions.
- Water Usage and Management: The safety report would evaluate the water usage requirements of the integrated facilities, including both the NPP and the HPP, and assess the potential impacts on local water resources. This would involve quantifying water consumption, evaluating the potential for water withdrawals to impact aquatic ecosystems or water availability for other users, and outlining measures to minimize water usage and mitigate impacts on water resources.
- Land use and Habitat Impact: The safety report would assess the potential impacts of the integrated facilities on land use and habitats, including the footprint of the facilities, land disturbance during construction, and habitat fragmentation. This would involve conducting surveys to identify sensitive habitats and species potentially affected by the project and developing mitigation measures to minimize impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services.
- Waste Management: The safety report would evaluate the generation of waste streams from both the NPP and the HPP and assess their potential impacts on the environment. This would include assessing the types and quantities of waste generated, evaluating the potential for hazardous or radioactive waste, and outlining strategies for waste minimization, recycling, and proper disposal to minimize environmental impacts.
- Regulatory compliance and permitting: The safety report would outline the regulatory requirements and permitting processes associated with the integration of the HPP with the NPP, including environmental impact assessments, permits for air and water emissions, and compliance with relevant environmental regulations. This would involve identifying applicable regulatory requirements, conducting environmental impact assessments to demonstrate compliance, and obtaining necessary permits and approvals from regulatory agencies.

- Overall, integrating an HPP with an NPP would require a comprehensive environmental impact assessment to evaluate and mitigate potential environmental impacts associated with the operation of the integrated facilities. This would involve assessing emissions and discharges, evaluating water usage and management, minimizing impacts on land use and habitats, managing waste generation and disposal, contributing to climate change mitigation efforts, and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and permitting processes.

The impact of the integration of an HPP into an NPP on this chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; LOW for the off-site scenario.

34.4.21 Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of Life Aspects

The integration of an HPP into an NPP affects the "Decommissioning and End of Life Aspects" chapter of a typical SAR in several significant ways. Here's a detailed analysis:

1. **Extended Operational Life and Decommissioning Timeline:** The integration of an HPP may extend the operational life of the NPP due to the additional role of hydrogen production. This extension influences the timeline for decommissioning activities.
2. **Planning and Coordination:** A coordinated decommissioning plan must account for both the nuclear and hydrogen components, potentially complicating the scheduling and phasing of decommissioning activities.
3. **Additional Infrastructure and Facilities.** The HPP adds new infrastructure, such as electrolysis units, storage tanks, and distribution pipelines. These structures need to be dismantled safely at the end of life. The SAR must include detailed plans for decommissioning these additional facilities, including specific methodologies for dismantling hydrogen production equipment.
4. **Safety and Hazard Analysis:** Hydrogen production introduces additional hazards (e.g., flammability, explosiveness) that must be considered in the safety analysis. This complexity impacts the decommissioning process. The SAR must provide a comprehensive risk assessment covering the decommissioning of hydrogen-related facilities, addressing potential accidents, and mitigation strategies.
5. **Regulatory and Compliance Requirements:** The integration of hydrogen production may necessitate compliance with additional regulations specific to chemical plants, affecting the overall decommissioning strategy. New permits and regulatory approvals may be required for the decommissioning of hydrogen-related components, impacting timelines and processes outlined in the SAR.
6. **Waste Management and Disposal:** The decommissioning process will generate various waste streams, including nuclear, chemical, and mixed waste from the hydrogen plant. These need classification and handling according to regulatory standards. The SAR must detail disposal pathways for all waste types, including specific procedures for handling and disposing of hydrogen production materials and equipment.
7. **Cost Estimation:** The integration of an HPP will alter the cost estimates for decommissioning. The SAR must provide updated financial assessments, including the additional costs for decommissioning of the HPP.
8. **Environmental Impact Assessment:** The environmental impact assessment must consider the cumulative effects of decommissioning both the NPP and the HPP, including potential contamination and environmental hazards.
9. **Human Resources and Expertise:** Decommissioning of a combined NPP and HPP requires a workforce with expertise in both nuclear and chemical plant decommissioning.

10. Site Restoration: The SAR must address the restoration of the site to its original state or another designated end-use.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Decommissioning and End of Life Aspects" chapter of a Safety Assessment Report. The SAR must be updated to include detailed plans for the extended operational life, additional infrastructure, complex hazard analysis, regulatory compliance, waste management, environmental impacts, specialized workforce requirements, and legacy management. Each of these aspects introduces new challenges and considerations that must be meticulously addressed to ensure a safe and compliant decommissioning process.

The impact of the integration of an HPP into an NPP on this chapter of a Safety Assessment Report is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios; LOW for the off-site scenarios.

34.4.22 Comprehensive Qualitative Assessment of integration scenarios on Safety Assessment Report- Executive Summary

The licensing process involving the integration of an HPP into an existing NPP is complex and requires comprehensive documentation to ensure safety and regulatory compliance; the Safety Assessment Report (SAR) is a key document to obtain the necessary license and approvals to operate the integrated plant.

A qualitative analysis of the corresponding impacts on a typical SAR, deriving from the NPP+HPP integration scenarios has been carried out. The levels of integration of an HPP into an NPP have been presented according to the integration scenarios discussed and validated with NPHyCo project partners here after listed. The sharing of systems/users (electricity, demineralized water, service water for non-safety related components cooling) between NPP and HPP and the full integration of an HPP into an NPP have been also included.

Onsite Solutions:

1. On site solution 1: onsite solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity from the grid
2. On site solution 2: on site solution with full integration except chilled water with electricity as a load of the NPP
3. On site solution 3: onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid
4. On site solution 4: onsite solution with integration of electricity and cooling water only with electricity as a load of the NPP

Offsite Solutions (3 km distance as starting point)

5. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 5: Off-site solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity from the grid
6. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 6: Off-site solution with integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity as a load of NPP
7. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 7: Off-site solution(s) with integration of electricity only as a load of NPP.
8. Offsite solution (3 km distance) 8: Off-site solution with zero integration as benchmark (electricity from the grid) (Benchmark Scenario)

To support the analysis of the impact on Safety Assessment Report of the integration scenarios, the outcomes of the following subtasks of NPHyCo Work Package 4.2 have been consulted.

- Sub-task #2: Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP (on a technical level)
- Sub-task #3: Safety Case Approach NPP-HPP integration and Example of Rivne NPP
- Sub-task #4: Detailed assessment of the various incident/accident scenarios

The relevant NPHyCO documents used as input for the qualitative analysis of the impact of the integration scenarios on a generic SAR are listed in Section 32.2.2. Table 65 shows a comprehensive overview of the impact of the integration scenarios on a generic SAR.

34.4.22.1 Impacts on Chapter 1: introduction and general considerations

This chapter typically provides an overview of the NPP project, including its objectives and scope. In the case of coupling with an HPP, this section needs to be updated to reflect the additional facility, the concerned operation modes and the integration scenarios.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP should require a comprehensive assessment of regulatory compliance requirements and the development of strategies to ensure compliance with applicable regulations, standards, and licensing requirements. This would involve addressing licensing and permitting requirements, complying with safety and environmental regulations, adhering to radiological protection standards, implementing emergency preparedness and response measures, ensuring quality assurance and control, and engaging with stakeholders to facilitate the regulatory approval process. Overall, the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for on-site integration solutions, MEDIUM for all off-site integration solutions except the Off-site solution with zero integration (benchmark scenario) for which the impact is expected LOW.

34.4.22.2 Impacts on Chapter 2: Site characteristics

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has a considerable impact on the "Site Description" chapter of an NPP's SAR: in particular, a detailed assessment is necessary with regard to site suitability, space requirements, environmental impacts, infrastructure requirements, geotechnical considerations, security measures, and regulatory compliance. This comprehensive evaluation ensures that the selected site for the integration scenarios analysed can safely accommodate both nuclear and hydrogen operations while minimizing risks to the surrounding environment, population, and workers.

Overall, the impacts on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the coupling of NPP with HPP is expected HIGH for on-site scenarios, LOW for off-site scenarios.

34.4.22.3 Impacts on Chapter 3: Safety objectives and design rules for Structures, Systems and Components

The integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Safety Objectives and Design Rules for SSCs" chapter of the SAR. This integration requires comprehensive updates to safety objectives, design principles, redundancy and diversity strategies, separation and independence criteria, reliability and availability standards, and regulatory compliance measures. Addressing these impacts thoroughly ensures that the integrated plant can operate safely and effectively, mitigating the combined risks associated with nuclear and hydrogen production operations.

At this stage of the project, according to the results of D4.2 Subtask 3 [R.5], it is possible to conclude that the following impacts are expected for the drafting of this chapter of the SAR with reference to the NPP-HPP coupling:

- A reference on the chapter of the SAR that describes the three fundamental safety functions (FSF) according to IAEA SSR-2/1 (i) *control of reactivity*, (ii) *removal of heat from the reactor*

and from the fuel store, and (iii) confinement of radioactive material, shielding against radiation and control of planned radioactive releases, as well as limitation of accidental radioactive releases, needs to be included.

- An evaluation of the fundamental safety functions for the integrated plant scenarios should be carried out.
- A list of structures, systems and components that ensure that the safety functions applicable are ensured in normal, degraded and accidental conditions. The assessment will consider also SSCs performing specific safety functions to be determined for impact analyses on the fundamental safety functions as a result of integration scenarios.
- A demonstration that the Fundamental Safety Functions are not affected by the modifications introduced by the integration scenarios by adopting specific measures (if applicable) should be provided.

Impacts on Safety Functions for the integration scenarios assessed in [R.5]

Electrical Power supply for HPP from NPP

As per outcome of document [R.5], the supply of electricity from the existing NPP Rivne to the HPP implies modifications to the 110kV outdoor switchgear: this components does not supply power to systems relevant for nuclear safety and doesn't implement any nuclear safety function both in normal and in accidental conditions. The modification consists in adding a high-voltage circuit breaker with disconnecter and measuring transformers at a reserve position (cubicle No8) of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear that shall be dedicated to supply electricity to the HPP. The reliability of the modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear needs to be tested, but the malfunctioning of this switchgear does not impact the safety functions of the NPP's SSCs. A malfunctioning of the 110 kV outdoor switchgear should imply the loss of electric power at the NPP but no impact on the safety functions is expected: the loss of onsite Power is a design basis event for the existing NPP: the reactor is able to proceed safely with shut down (scram) and the core can be cooled by emergency powered systems; the confinement functions (e.g. reactor cooling system, containment system) are ensured. Loss of onsite power is an event for which the plant is designed.

The modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear has no impact on, and is not related to, the(basic) safety functions of the Rivne NPP.

Sharing of Demineralized Water System

As per outcomes of document [R.5], the demineralized water system is designed to produce chemically demineralized water having the function to replenish steam and condensate losses in the primary and secondary circuits. The demineralized water has no cooling function. In case of sharing of the demineralized water system, the connection of a new pipeline to the pressure header of the demineralized water supply pumps will be necessary. This pipeline shall be equipped with a manual shut-off valve and instrumentation for pressure and water flow rate control; the readings of these instruments shall be on the water treatment operator's panel. This modification on the demineralized water system of the NPP site is configured as an extension of the drainage water system that doesn't change or interfere with the NPP's function. For constant supply of demineralized water to the HPP it is required to install a demineralized water storage tank and booster pumps at the HPP site.

The modification introduced to the demineralized water system due to coupling with the HPP has no impact on the (basic) safety functions of the existing NPP.

Sharing of Service Water System

In the existing NPP the service water system, part of the secondary water loop of the NPP, is dedicated to the cooling of turbine equipment. Heat from the NPP's primary circuit is removed by the secondary loop in the steam generators. The heat of the secondary loop is also absorbed by turbine equipment which needs to be cooled. However, the service water system dedicated to the turbine equipment is not involved in the safety function related to the cooling of the core. As per [R.5] In case of sharing of the service water system between HPP and NPP plant, the service water system needs to remove more heat than it was originally designed for: an extra heat removal due to the HPP's needs requires a modification of the heat balance of the cooling water heat removal capacity of the NPP. For these modifications technical and safety justifications shall be required to give also evidence that the modified service water system meets the required margins to operate and safety limits; furthermore, all the preferred users /equipment of the service water system shall be identified and specific procedures to manage the service water system for preferred users shall be issued.

The service water system is not involved in the other basic safety functions, i.e. reactivity control of the core and confinement of radioactive material.

According to [R.5], with reference to the coupling of Rivne NPP with an HPP, a potential sharing of the service water system of the turbine equipment of unit 3 and 4 with the HPP has been assessed. In this case a modification of the service water system is required for the pressure headers of the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 3 and the cooling water pumps of the turbine department of unit 4. From these pumps, a pipeline is to be extended to the HPP site. It is envisaged that in case of off-site scenarios, using the service water supply from the Turbine Department for the HPP's needs is complicated due to the length of the piping that should connect NPP and HPP.

The heat balance of the NPP needs to be revised taking into account a further analysis of the HPP's needs. However, the modification has no impact on reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

Impacts on Defence in Depth (DiD)

As per [R.5], the sharing of the systems Electric Power Distribution System, Demineralized Water System and Service Water System are linked to SSCs in the first level of DiD with reference, respectively, to the supply of electricity for measurement and correction systems, contribution to replenishment of primary and secondary system inventory, and cooling of secondary system components. To prevent deviations that may result in the second level of DiD (Anticipated Operational Occurrences), the following provisions should be applied to all SSCs involved: sufficient design margins and conservatism, high reliability of systems and components, adequate training and qualification of personnel, and quality assurance system. The sharing of the service water system and the demineralized water system introduces possible advantages for the 4th level of DiD : in severe accident conditions the extra demineralized water inventory used in the HPP or the service water can be used as emergency cooling water.

Overall, the impact on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the NPP-HPP coupling is expected HIGH for on- site solutions, MEDIUM for all off site solutions except for Benchmark scenario for which the impact is expected LOW.

34.4.22.4 Impacts on Chapter 6 Engineered Safety features

The on- site integration scenarios have HIGH impacts on the "Engineered Safety Features" chapter of a typical SAR. This chapter focuses on the systems designed to mitigate the consequences of accidents and to ensure the safety of the plant. The sharing of the Electric Power Distribution System, the Demineralized Water System and the Service Water System (for cooling of non-safety related

components) has not impacts on the NPP Safety functions of the reactor cooling system and the containment system as from outcomes of Sub-task#2 and Subtasks 3 provided in 34.4.3.1. The sharing of the Service Water System could imply the need to revise the heat balance of the NPP taking into account the HPP's needs. However, the modification has no impact on reactivity control and confinement of radioactive material.

The modifications related to the sharing of the identified systems could have a low impact on safety related SSCs. A review of the heat balance of the NPP needs to be revised taking into account HPP needs further analysis in case of sharing service water system. In any case as per [R.5]the applicable Management of Change process as stated in the NPP's Management System, must be followed. It is expected that a limited Safety Case Report shall be needed and minor changes to be made to safety analyses, procedures and technical documents. The overall impact onf this chapter of the SAR is considered MEDIUM.

Overall, the impact on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the NPP-HPP coupling is expected HIGH for on-site solutions, MEDIUM for all off site solutions except for the Benchmark scenario for which the impact is expected LOW.

34.4.22.5 Impacts on Chapter 7: Instrumentation and Control

In general, it is expected that the integration of an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Instrumentation and Control" (I&C) chapter of a typical Safety Assessment Report (SAR) for all the integration scenarios (on- site and off-site) for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged. For example, for scenarios for which an amount of electricity from NPP is dedicated to HPP, the hydrogen production plant is considered as a constant additional consumer); in this case the HPP produces hydrogen at the designed capacity in continuous mode and the starting and the stopping of the HPP depends on the availability of the NPP. This chapter of the SAR is critical as it outlines the systems used to monitor and control the plant's operations, ensuring safety and efficiency. Key impacts include the need for integrated control systems and interfaces, additional instrumentation for hydrogen monitoring, enhanced safety and protection systems, a unified and user-friendly HMI, integrated data and secure communication systems, coordinated emergency response capabilities, increased redundancy and reliability, robust cybersecurity measures, and comprehensive regulatory compliance. Addressing these aspects thoroughly ensures that the integrated plant can operate safely and efficiently, managing the complexities and risks associated with both nuclear and hydrogen production operations.

Overall, the impact on issuing of this Chapter of the SAR with reference to the NPP-HPP coupling is expected HIGH for all the integration scenarios (on-site and off-site) for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged, LOW for the Benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.6 Impacts on Chapter 8: Electrical Power System

This chapter of the SAR should describe the electrical power system necessary to the non-safety loads and to the safety loads during operational states and for accident conditions of the integrated plant.

In [R.5] a detailed description of the Electrical Power Distribution System with reference to the existing Rivne NPP is given [R.4]; furthermore the electric system of Rivne NPP and the system functioning in case of failures are also described, here after the main outcome is provided and the expected impacts on the electrical power system in case of coupling of NPP with HPP.

In case of coupling of NPP with HPP an estimation of the power necessary for the HPP has been carried out in [R.4]. The power needed for the HPP is assumed to be 45 MW (of which the capacity of the electrolyzer is 30 MW). The power supply consists of a source of direct current, necessary for

electrolysis and a source of alternating current, necessary for the equipment. The HPP is normally connected to the medium voltage network (20-30 kV), the compressors need a voltage level of 6 kV, and other equipment need the connection with 400 V network. Currently, at the Rivne NPP the 110 kV outdoor switchgear that consists of 12 cubicles (CP) has a free cubicle (CP 8-reserve) from which the HPP could be powered.

The expected modifications to the existing electrical supply system of Rivne NPP to feed also the HPP have been analyzed in [R.5] and [R.4] and are here after summarized:

- The installation of a 110kV circuit breaker and 110kV disconnector on VRP-110kV.
- The installation of a power transmission line with a voltage of 110 kV with a length of 2200m to 2800m.
- The installation of a 63MVA step-down transformer (110kV/20kV/6kV); this transformer can be installed in proximity of the modified 110 kV outdoor switchgear or within the HPP site (in this case it is necessary to consider also the HPP's power supply line to install in the overall impacts on the modification.
- The supply of complete distribution devices for the voltage of 20, 6, and 0.4 kV for HPP consumers.

Moreover, since the NPP is connected to the grid, in the event of a fault in the direct electricity line from NPP to HPP, it should be checked that the line going to the grid is appropriately sized to withstand the total load coming from the NPP (including the power that would normally go to the HPP).

In any case, even if it were not possible to discharge the total load to the network, in the event of a loss of the direct electricity line from NPP going to HPP (loss due to HPP accidents), specific procedures to be followed in the event of network disconnection (procedures that should already be in place) should be activated at the NPP.

Possible consequences of accidents in the electrical part, as well as accidents with the main equipment of the existing power unit of Rivne NPP are assessed in [R.4], a detailed assessment of possible consequence of failure in the modified electrical system to take into account the HPP's power needs should be carried out and the main outcomes provided in this chapter. The overall impact to this chapter of the SAR is considered MEDIUM for all the scenarios for which the HPP is fed directly by electricity from the NPP, LOW for the other scenarios.

34.4.22.7 Impacts on Chapter 9: Auxiliary Systems

With reference to the existing Rivne NPP, document [R.5] provides the indication of safety functions of the Demineralized Water System. Document [R.4] provides the description of the existing service water system and of the modifications needed in the demineralized water system of the existing NPP in case of sharing of the system between HPP and NPP. The main outcomes of documents [R.5] and [R.4] are here after provided. The demineralized water system is not a safety related system. However, in the event of abnormal operations and accidents, the system can be used for the Replenishment of losses and maintenance of balance of water of the secondary side, turbine room systems and for replenishment of losses and maintenance of water reserves in the emergency feed water tanks of the Steam generator. The equipment of the Demineralized Water System is located in the chemical water treatment building of the NPP Chemical Department. Demineralized water is used for washing of components (evaporator, condenser degassers, filters), decontamination, preparation of boric acid solution and decontamination solution. during maintenance activities the system is used for pressure testing and washing of the equipment.

In case of sharing of the demineralized water system between NPP and HPP, minor modifications on the existing system need to be carried out: an additional pipeline with a shut-off valve, a pressure gauge and a flow meter should be installed. All modifications are carried out in the demineralized water pump room. The pipe laying to the HPP is performed in the NPP site and does not require operational control. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valve) is performed by the operating workers of the NPP's demineralized water system. The schemes and operating instructions of the DW system should be modified. The personnel should be trained and given the necessary instructions on control and management of the modified system. Possible additional malfunctions (leaks, valve or instrumentation failures) should be assessed.

With reference to the existing Rivne NPP, document [R.4] provides the description of the existing service water system and of the modifications needed in the service water system of the existing NPP in case of sharing of the system between NPP and HPP. As per document [R.5], the service water system is a non-safety related system. However, in case of abnormal situations and accidents the service water system can be used for cooling of equipment such as turbine equipment, reactor coolant pumps (RCP) electric motors, unit transformer and for the heat removal from the process condenser.

As per document [R.4], in case of sharing of the existing NPP's service water system with the HPP, the following modifications are needed: Additional pipelines with shut-off valves shall be installed within the location of the existing pipelines of the system. New pipelines are needed to connect the existing pipelines of service water of units No. 3 and No. 4 with the HPP site. It is also expected the installation of 2 new HPP water supply pumps, a gauge and a flow meter also have to be installed. All modifications are arranged within the NPP site. The laying of pipes to the HPP and water return is carried out on the NPP site (for on-site scenarios) and does not require operational control. Control of water flow for the HPP is performed on the HPP site and is not required with NPP personnel. Pressure checking and control of the modified part of the system (valves, pumps) are carried out by NPP workers. Diagrams and operating instructions shall be updated. The power supply equipment for the needs of the corresponding Unit will also be modified and power supply cables will be extended to the new pump motors. The diagrams and instructions of the Electrical Department and the Automation and Measurement Department must also be changed. Possible additional faults (leaks, failures of valves, pumps, or instruments) must be assessed.

The overall impact on this chapter of the SAR is considered HIGH for all integration scenarios (on site and off site) for which the sharing of the demineralized water system and/or the service water system is envisaged, LOW for the other scenarios.

34.4.22.8 Impacts on Chapter 12: Radiation Protection

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would imply a thorough reassessment of the "Radiological Protection" section of the NPP's SAR. This section aims to give evidence that the protection of workers, public, and environment from potential radiological hazards associated with the operation of the NPP is ensured in normal and accidental conditions. The reassessment of this section implies the following activities:

The integration would require a comprehensive reassessment of radiological protection measures to ensure safety of workers, public, and environment in the presence of potential radiological hazards resulting from hydrogen-related incidents. This would involve assessment of radiological hazards and emergency response procedures to effectively manage radiological risks associated with the integrated facilities. The overall impact on this chapter of the SAR is considered HIGH for all on-site scenarios, LOW for the other scenarios.

34.4.22.9 Impacts on Chapter 13: Conduct of Operations

Integrating an HPP into an NPP significantly impacts the "Conduct of Operations" chapter of the SAR. It requires a thorough review and update of operational procedures, safety management practices, emergency preparedness plans, monitoring systems, and maintenance protocols. Ensuring regulatory compliance and addressing potential hazards associated with hydrogen technology are also critical. The integration must be approached systematically to maintain the safety and reliability of both the NPP and the HPP. The impact is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.10 Impacts on Chapter 14: Plant Construction and commissioning

Integrating an HPP into an NPP presents unique challenges and considerations that must be addressed in the "Plant Construction and Commissioning" chapter of a typical SAR for the NPP. This integration affects various aspects, including design, safety, operational procedures, and regulatory compliance.

In particular, the site layout must accommodate both the NPP and the HPP, ensuring adequate space, access routes, and separation distances to prevent potential hazards. The Integration of HPP into NPP may involve shared use of certain infrastructure such as cooling systems, electrical systems, and control rooms. Detailed design plans must highlight these shared systems and ensure their safety and reliability. Given that hydrogen is highly flammable and poses explosion risks, the safety design must incorporate measures to manage hydrogen production, storage, and distribution safely. Furthermore, the construction plan of the HPP must account for the activities carried out within the existing NPP, ensuring that safety and quality standards are maintained throughout the process. The installation of specialized hydrogen production and storage equipment, including electrolyzers, compressors, and storage tanks, must be carefully planned and executed. Clear plans for the interface points between the NPP and the HPP shall be identified, detailing how they will be constructed and commissioned. Comprehensive testing procedures shall be developed to ensure that the integrated systems function correctly and safely, including scenarios involving both plants operating simultaneously. The commissioning procedures shall be in compliance with nuclear safety standards as well as hydrogen safety regulations, potentially involving multiple regulatory bodies.

The impact of the NPP-HPP integration on the "Plant Construction and Commissioning" chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.11 Impacts on Chapter 15: Safety Analysis

This section of Safety Assessment Report is strongly impacted by the integration of HPP into a NPP. The integration of HPP into a NPP implies significant modifications and expansions to address the potential impacts and safety measures to adopt associated with this integration. In particular, specific safety analyses are envisaged to ensure the safe operation of the NPP and to identify and mitigate potential hazards.

Document [R.6] provides the assessment of some accidental scenarios occurring inside the HPP. In particular, the effects of confined explosion in the PEM stack container, whereas unconfined explosion in the gas processing unit, and buffer tank burst in storage areas have been evaluated. The NPP buildings and structures are assumed to withstand an approximate airborne shock wave with a frontal

compression pressure of around 10 kPa. This represents the main safety limit for this study. In addition, results are assessed against the lower safety limit of 6.9 kPa established by the US NRC ². According to document [R.6], the assessment of hydrogen explosion after vessel blowdown in the gas processing unit show that a safe distance of around 95 m to the nearest NPP structure is needed.

The calculation results highlight that the buffer tank would not be located onsite of the NPP unless mitigation measures such as reinforced concrete blast walls would be deployed to surround the vessel: in fact, a safety distance of 1350 m is required for the Storage area (15 t) to respect the safety limit of 6.9 kPa established by the US NRC for NPP buildings and structures.

After having assessed all the applicable events, a final list of SSCs relevant for safety shall be issued. As provided in [R.5], the integration scenarios have an impact on the SSCs, new risks could be introduced. The evaluation of risks shall take into account both nuclear/radiological aspects and conventional risks. It is expected that the coupling of HPP and NPP can result in added risks, for example the extra pipework needed in case of sharing the service water system or demineralized water system could imply added flooding risk (increase of leakage/break frequency). Therefore, the existing risk evaluation of the NPP should be revised if modifications have impact on the different process parts causing changes in the final safety assessment. It is expected that the different existing risk levels for the different areas are not (significantly) affected by the modifications if appropriate measures are taken (if applicable). About the conventional risks, these shall be evaluated taking into account the outcome of Work Package 2.1.

Preliminary information about the systems should be shared between NPP and HPP. The expected impact on safety functions for the integrated plant are provided in [R.5]; in particular, the quoted document takes as reference the Rivne NPP located In Ukraine (a pressurized nuclear reactor of the series VVER-440), but the main conclusions involving the impacts on NPP safety functions can be extended to other existing NPPs based on the pressurized water reactor technology. The integration of NPPs based on the BWR reactor technology with an HPP has been excluded because the technical solution of the integration of HTSE plant with a BWR plant appears unreasonable (BWRs could supply only steam contaminated by radionuclides as heat source and a tie-in point is close to the reactor).

About the accidental events above listed, [R.5] suggests that the sharing of the identified systems (electric power distribution system, demineralized water and service water for cooling of non-safety components) has impacts on the following specific postulated initiating events (PIEs):

For the sharing of the Electric Power Distribution system, the following PIEs have been identified: Loss of electrical power supply, internal fires (ignition frequency) and electromagnetic interference (EMI) from equipment on site.

In case of sharing of the Demineralized Water System and the Service Water System, internal flooding has been identified as PIE.

Overall, the modifications related to the sharing of the identified systems could have a low impact on safety related SSCs. A review of the heat balance of the NPP needs to be performed taking into account a further analysis of the HPP's needs in case of sharing service water system. Furthermore, the consequences of interruption of integrated systems for the NPP due to accidents occurring at

² Please consider that In France, Arrêté du 29 September 2005 provides overpressure limits lower than 69 mbar for the effects on some structures - 20 hPa or mbar, threshold for significant destruction of windows,- 50 hPa or mbar, threshold for light damage to structures. For serious damage to structures the overpressure limit is 140 hPa or mbar

the HPP should be evaluated. The overall impact is considered MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged. In any case as per [R.5], the applicable Management of Change process as stated in the NPP's Management System, must be followed. It is expected that a limited Safety Case Report shall be needed and minor changes to be made to safety analyses, procedures and technical documents.

The expected impact of the integration of an HPP into the NPP site on Chapter 15 of the SAR is considered HIGH for on-site integration scenarios. The integration would imply a comprehensive reassessment of the design basis for the NPP, with a focus on the identification and mitigation of the risks associated with hydrogen production. This would require close collaboration between the operators of both facilities and the integration of hydrogen safety considerations into all aspects of the NPP's design, operation, and emergency response planning. A safety analysis shall be developed to identify, assess, and mitigate the additional hazards introduced by the integrated plant with the aim to protect workers, public, and the environment from the potential consequences of hydrogen-related accidents and to ensure that the nuclear safety functions applicable to NPP are ensured in normal, abnormal and accident conditions. The impact of the benchmark scenario is expected LOW.

34.4.22.12 Impacts on Chapter 16: Operational limits and conditions for safe operations

With reference to the integration of an HPP into an HPP, specific provisions for training programs and procedures need to be developed to ensure that personnel are adequately prepared to safely operate and maintain both the NPP and the HPP. This would involve training on hydrogen safety procedures, emergency response protocols, and the identification and mitigation of hydrogen-related hazards. The safe operating envelope for the integrated plant should be also defined. The safe operating envelope defines the boundary within which the facility can be operated safely without any risk to workers, public or the environment. A set of "Limits and Condition" should be defined also, these limits and conditions identify the boundary of safe operation. With the term "limit" it is intended the maximum justifiable safe state of operations. The limits are parameters (such as temperature or mass limits). Conditions describes the situations necessary to keep operations within the safe operating envelope.

According to NPHyCo deliverable D1.2 [R.1], two possible operation modes have been identified for the HPP integrated into an NPP:

- Continuous operation: in this mode the HPP is permanently operated at the designed capacity and an amount of electricity from the NPP is permanently dedicated to the hydrogen production; starting and stopping of the NPP has an impact on the operation of the HPP (HPP starts and stops with the NPP).
- Flexible operation: in this operation mode the production of hydrogen from the HPP is not constant but varies during the day depending on the achievable revenue or on grid balancing services (for example, the amount of hydrogen production will vary during the day and night time or depending on the availability of regenerative electricity from solar or wind power; on the same day the HPP may start and stop frequently, these frequent HPP starts and stops have impacts on the NPP due to the frequent load disconnections.

The operating conditions based on the hydrogen production strategy are provided in [R.3].

The impact of the integration of an HPP into an NPP on the "Operational limits and conditions for safe operation" chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM

for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.13 Impacts on Chapter 17: Management for Safety

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has significant implications for the "Management for Safety" chapter of a SAR. This integration necessitates comprehensive updates to the organizational structure, safety culture, risk management practices, training programs, emergency preparedness plans, safety documentation, regulatory compliance measures, incident reporting systems, safety review processes, and stakeholder engagement strategies. Addressing these impacts thoroughly ensures that safety is maintained and enhanced across the combined facilities, mitigating the unique risks associated with hydrogen production while preserving the stringent safety standards required for nuclear operations.

The impact of NPP-HPP integration on the "Management for Safety" chapter of SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.14 Impacts on Chapter 18: Human Factors Engineering

This chapter focuses on optimizing the interaction between humans and the technological systems they operate, ensuring safety, efficiency, and reliability. Human & Organizational Factors should be incorporated into the design of the integrated plant. Specific requirements for Human Factors Engineering throughout the life cycle of the integrated plant should be defined. The compliance evidence with these requirements should be given in order to ensure that the following objectives are met:

- Human errors (in terms of frequency and consequences) are minimized.
- Human reliability shall be maximized, all the tasks carried out by workers shall be assessed in order to evaluate the human reliability to the safe operation of the integrated plant.
- Hazards that could compromise the health of personnel and that could present impacts for population and environment shall be minimized.
- The arrangement of the control room will consider human factor engineering for the safe and efficient operations of the systems.
- The design shall minimize costs associated with human resources (number of workers per task, time to carry out operations and maintenance activities safely).
- The return of experience deriving from the operation of similar systems/plant where incidents/accidents have occurred or, where that system is subject to poor operational, or maintenance performance shall be taken into account.

The compliance evidence with several essential health and safety requirements relating to the design and construction of machinery or related products, listed in annex III of Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2023 shall be provided.

The compliance evidence with the applicable essential health and safety requirements related to the design and construction of machinery listed in Annex III of the Regulation (EU) 2023/1230, shall be provided within a specific document "Assessment of conformity with the Essential Health and Safety requirements as per Annex III of Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 ". The assessment shall consider specific HF requirements from legislation of the Site where the integrated plant shall be constructed.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP has impacts on the "Human Factors Engineering" chapter of a Safety Assessment Report. The changes required include redesigning control rooms and interfaces, addressing increased workload and staffing needs, developing comprehensive training programs, creating integrated procedures, conducting human error analyses, promoting a unified safety culture, establishing effective communication and coordination mechanisms, ensuring ergonomic

design, and integrating human factors into the design process. Addressing these aspects thoroughly ensures that the human element in managing the combined facilities is optimized for safety, efficiency, and reliability.

The impact of integration on the "Human Factors Engineering" chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.15 Impacts on Chapter 19: Emergency preparedness and response

The safety analysis presented in Chapter 15 of the SAR would also evaluate the emergency preparedness and response capabilities of the NPP in the event of hydrogen-related incidents. It is envisaged to carry out a specific assessment of the adequacy of emergency response procedures, communication protocols, and the availability of resources and personnel to effectively manage hydrogen-related emergencies.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP requires changes to emergency response procedures: in particular an updating of emergency response procedures outlined in the "Radiological Protection" chapter is needed to account for the potential radiological consequences of hydrogen-related incidents. Specific procedures need to be adopted to manage hydrogen related accidents, for example H₂ leakages and fire. These procedures need to be integrated in the overall emergency response plan for the NPP.

Specific response protocols for radiological emergencies triggered by hydrogen leakages, fires, or explosions shall be developed and the availability of resources and workers to effectively manage such incidents shall be ensured.

Communication strategies for informing and educating the public about the radiological risks associated with the operation of the integrated facilities shall be outlined. Clear and transparent information about the potential radiological hazards, emergency response procedures, and protective measures in place to ensure public safety shall be provided.

The integration of an HPP into an NPP would imply a significant reassessment of the "Emergency Planning and Response" section of the NPP's SAR. The integration would require a comprehensive reassessment and enhancement of emergency planning and response measures to effectively manage the unique hazards associated with hydrogen-related incidents. This would involve developing tailored emergency response protocols, enhancing coordination with external agencies, ensuring personnel readiness through training and drills, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement to enhance overall emergency preparedness and response capabilities.

The impact of integration of an HPP into an NPP on this chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios, MEDIUM for off-site scenarios for which the sharing of one or more systems is envisaged and LOW for the benchmark scenario.

34.4.22.16 Impacts on Chapter 20: Environmental Aspects

The NPP-HPP integration would significantly impact the "Environmental Impact Assessment" developed in support of the SAR. A specific evaluation of the potential environmental impacts associated with the operation of the integrated plant should be carried out, the measures to mitigate adverse effects on the environment should be defined. The impact of integration on this chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the onsite integration scenarios, LOW for the off-site scenario.

34.4.22.17 Impacts on Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of Life Aspects

The NPP-HPP significantly impacts the "Decommissioning and End of Life Aspects" chapter of a SAR. The SAR must be updated to include detailed plans for the extended operational life, additional infrastructure, complex hazard analysis, regulatory compliance, waste management, environmental impacts, specialized workforce requirements, and legacy management. Each of these aspects introduces new challenges and considerations that must be meticulously addressed to ensure a safe and compliant decommissioning process.

The impact of integration on this chapter of a SAR is expected HIGH for all the on-site integration scenarios and LOW for the off-site scenarios.

Table 65: Qualitative assessment of the impacts of the integration of HPP into a NPP on a typical Safety Assessment Report

Subject	Onsite Scenarios				Offsite Scenarios			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4	Scenario 5	Scenario 6	Scenario 7	Scenario 8
Chapter 1: introduction and general considerations	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 2: Site Characteristics	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 3: Safety objectives and design rules for structures, systems and components	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 6: Engineered safety features	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 7: Instrumentation and control	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW
Chapter 8: Electrical power	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 9: Auxiliary systems	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW
Chapter 12: Radiation Protection	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 13: Conduct of Operations	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 14: Plant Construction and Commissioning	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 15: Safety Analysis	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 16: Operational Limits and	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW

Conditions for Safe Operation								
Chapter 17: Management for Safety	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 18: Human Factor Engineering	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 19: Emergency Preparedness and Response	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW
Chapter 20: Environmental Aspects	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW
Chapter 21: Decommissioning and end of Life Aspects	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	LOW	LOW	LOW	LOW

35 Conclusions

The purpose of the considerations made in this report is to make a qualitative statement as to which integration scenario for the coupling of an NPP with an HPP is the most preferable one in terms of the effort involved in the legal processes. Economic considerations regarding the investment costs and profitability of the individual scenarios are considered in detail in WP3 of the NPHyCo project and have not been analysed in detail here.

To this end, the issues to be addressed for the approval of the HPP and the associated systems as well as the review and renewal of the existing approval for the NPP based on the Safety Analysis Report were considered. The main difference between the scenarios is, on the one hand, the distance between the two facilities and, on the other hand, the systems shared with each other.

The main findings of this report are listed below:

HPP licensing

- The more independent the HPP is from the NPP, the more systems have to be set up and connected to supply points (e.g. for electric power supply, water for demineralization, cooling water, wastewater disposal).
- If the hydrogen produced is to be transported by pipeline, it will also be necessary to construct longer pipelines to the nearest connection to an existing hydrogen network or to the consumer(s)
- Depending on the local infrastructure and geographical conditions, it may be necessary to lay longer power lines and/or pipelines. In this case, approval procedures with public participation may have to be carried out for the authorization to use privately or publicly owned land.
- An onsite location of the HPP on the NPP's perimeter may offer the opportunity to simplify procedures such as the environmental impact assessment and habitat assessment, as these have already been carried out for the existing NPP.
- However, a closer integration of the HPP with NPP systems requires more extensive considerations regarding risks and possible effects of the HPP's operation on the safe operation of the NPP (e.g., in the MAPP and/or safety report for the HPP).
- When choosing an onsite integration scenario, certain existing assessments, reports and licenses for the NPP (protection of wild flora and fauna, environmental impact assessment, industrial emissions etc.) can serve as basis for procedures/documents needed for the licensing of the HPP. If the competent authorities agree to it, the HPP may even be integrated in existing licenses as a modification of the NPP.

NPP licensing

- A more independent offsite integration largely or completely eliminates the need for the NPP operator to carry out comprehensive analyses of the safety implications of system modifications.
- Close integration of the HPP into the infrastructure of the NPP (i.e. sharing of systems such as the Electric Power Distribution System, the Demineralized Water System, or the Feedwater System) requires consideration of possible safety-related effects (e.g. explosion, internal flooding) and, if necessary, the provision of measures to prevent them.

- Certain aspects, such as the integration of the HPP into operational processes (e.g. operating and maintenance procedures) as well as instrumentation & control technology required for a smooth joint operation of the two facilities, need to be addressed in any integration scenario.
- A closer integration of the HPP requires a revision of existing internal and external emergency procedures of the NPP.

Overall conclusions

- Both onsite and offsite integration scenarios offer advantages and disadvantages from a licensing perspective.
- The advantages and disadvantages are not exclusively dependent on the integration scenario, but also on individual conditions at the plant location, which are not foreseeable within the scope of this project.
- In principle, from a sole licensing point of view, there is a slight tendency for the advantages of onsite location of the HPP to outweigh the disadvantages more than is the case with offsite location. This is due to the possibility of avoiding certain approval procedures (e.g. land use) or making them less extensive (e.g. EIA, protection of wild flora & fauna).
- The main determining factor for the choice of the integration scenario to be applied will therefore most likely be economic factors.

36 Appendix

36.1 International guidelines and standards for the licensing process of NPPs

- [R.1] [Licensing Process for Nuclear Installations, IAEA Safety Standards Series No. SSG-12](#) [5]
- [R.2] [Governmental, Legal and Regulatory Framework for Safety, IAEA General Safety Requirements No. GSR Part 1 \(Rev. 1\)](#) [63]
- [R.3] [Modifications to Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-71](#) [64]
- [R.4] [The Operating Organization for Nuclear Power Plants IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-72](#) [58]
- [R.5] [Periodic Safety Review of Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide SSG-25](#) [65]
- [R.6] [Hydrogen Production Using Nuclear Energy, IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NP-T-4.2](#) [22]
- [R.7] [WENRA Safety Reference Levels for Existing Reactors 2020](#) [57]

36.2 Relevant key documents for the drafting of the NPP's Safety Analysis Report

- [R.10] [Format and Content of the Safety Analysis Report for Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-61](#) [6]
- [R.11] [Safety Assessment for Facilities and Activities IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GSR Part 4 \(Rev. 1\) General Safety Requirements](#) [42]
- [R.12] [Safety of Nuclear Power Plants: Design, IAEA Safety Standards Series No. SSR-2/1 \(Rev. 1\)](#) [62]
- [R.13] [Safety of Nuclear Power Plants: Commissioning and Operation, IAEA Specific Safety Requirements SSR-2/2 \(Rev. 1\)](#) [66]
- [R.14] [Site Evaluation for Nuclear Installations, IAEA Safety Standards Series No. SSR-1](#) [67]
- [R.15] [Design of the Reactor Containment and Associated Systems for Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-53](#) [68]
- [R.16] [Protection against Internal Hazards in the Design of Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-64](#) [69]
- [R.17] [Protection Against Internal and External Hazards in the Operation of Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-77](#) [70]
- [R.18] [External Man-Induced Events in Relation to Nuclear Power Plant Design: A Safety Guide, IAEA Safety Series No. 50-SG-D5 \(Rev. 1\)](#) [71]
- [R.19] [Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency, IAEA General Safety Requirements No. GSR Part 7](#) [72]

Other national guidance and requirements may also have to be taken into account for an individual case assessment.

The main guidances on the content and format of a typical Safety Assessment Report (SAR) followed to develop this section consist of the following IAEA documents:

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- [Format and Content of the Safety Analysis Report for Nuclear Power Plants, IAEA Specific Safety Guide No. SSG-61](#) [6]
- [Safety Assessment for Facilities and Activities IAEA Safety Standards Series No. GSR Part 4 \(Rev. 1\) General Safety Requirements](#) [42]

36.3 Relevant NPHYCO documents used as input for the qualitative analysis of impacts of integration scenarios on Safety Assessment Report

- [R.1] Deliverable D1.2 Scenario definition
- [R.2] WP2.2 Impact Assessment part a: Industrial accidents
- [R.3] WP4.2 Subtask 1 Identification and description of facility types (NPP/HPP) and operating conditions
- [R.4] WP4.2 Subtask 2 Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP
- [R.5] WP4.2 Subtask 3 Safety Case Approach NPP-HPP integration and Example of Rivne NPP
- [R.6] WP4.2 Subtask 4 Detailed Assessment of the incident / accident scenarios

36.4 Other Input documents

- [R.20] EnergyTech. (2023, September 25). US-Ukraine Collaborating on Pilot Using Small Nuclear to Generate Carbon-Free H2 and Ammonia. [61]
- [R.21] M. Constantin, I. Turcu, C. Paunoiu, Al. Toma, D. Diaconu, M. Apostol, M. Nitoi, D. Gugiu, "Lead fast reactor technology and ALFRED Demonstrator development in the context of future markets of energy", EMERG Serie nouă, An V, vol. 12/2019 [59]
- [R.22] Ciftcioglu, M., Genco, F. & Tokuhiko, A. (2022) Optimized Clean Hydrogen Production using Nuclear Small Modular Reactors and Renewable Energy Sources: a Review atw Vol. 68(2022) [60]